

Living with Dementia in Supported Housing in Scotland: Multiple-Case Study Research

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Abstract

Purpose: To understand the experience of living with dementia in supported housing in Scotland, through Stakian, multiple-case study research.

Methodology: A systematic review of qualitative research was first conducted, to understand how living in supported housing influences the lives of people with dementia. One overarching theme, "Maintaining Independence and Autonomy," was developed, composed of three subthemes: "Support and Care," "Social Relationships," and "The Physical Environment." A conceptual framework, drawing from literature on independence, autonomy, personhood, person-centred care, social citizenship, and environmental gerontology, was then developed. The empirical phase included three instrumental case studies on living with dementia in 1) sheltered housing, 2) very sheltered and extra care housing, and 3) perspectives on supported housing as a future choice. Six settings were studied, involving interviews with six people with dementia, six social care professionals, and two family members. Documents and photographs were also gathered. Individual case studies were analysed using description, direct interpretation, and categorical aggregation, culminating in a cross-case analysis.

Findings: Three cross-case themes were developed: "Views of Supported Housing," "The Ideal Candidate," and "Too Far Gone." Key findings highlight limitations in providing support and care for people with dementia in supported housing, due to resource constraints, poor dementia awareness, and suboptimal environmental design. To continue living in supported housing, people with dementia must possess a series of "ideal" characteristics, such as independence and environmental familiarity. The study also highlights the limited housing options for people with dementia in Scotland, especially for those who are ineligible for social housing or reluctant to live in housing for older adults.

Conclusion: While supported housing is proposed to facilitate independent living for people with dementia, this is not consistently achieved. Progression of dementia often necessitates a move from these settings, revealing challenges and limitations in supporting individuals with dementia within Scotland's housing landscape.

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Claire, thank you for being you.

Author's Declaration

I, Michael Smith, hereby certify that this thesis has been written by me and has not been submitted for another comparable academic award.

Personal details withheld.

Prelude

My first steps into academia began with a BSc (Hons) in psychology, obtained from the University of Stirling in 2014. I enjoyed exploring clinical and health psychology, along with engaging in research. My undergraduate thesis delved into the impact of binge drinking on memory and executive functioning in university undergraduates, employing an experimental approach and utilising memory and problem-solving tests. Throughout the study, participants spontaneously shared insights into social influences relating to binge drinking behaviours, shedding light on the pressures of alcohol and drug use inherent in university life. It appeared that these pressures were experienced by undergraduate students establishing their identities as independent adults. Recognising the limitations of experimental research in addressing the *why* behind phenomena, I appreciated the importance of capturing the voices of individuals to enrich research findings.

In 2016, I completed a MSc in health psychology at the University of St. Andrews, choosing this path for its acknowledgment of the broader impacts of social, environmental, and psychological factors on health and illness. My interest extended into clinical communication research, with my thesis focussing on how clinician responses in general practice consultations could influence symptom disclosure, perceived clinician empathy, and overall satisfaction. Despite the emphasis on empathy in healthcare, I observed variations in clinicians' communication approaches, often negatively impacting individuals' experiences in healthcare consultations. Clinical placements in various Scottish hospitals, and psychological services, provided insights into the challenges associated with meeting healthcare needs, particularly, resource limitations and funding constraints in psychological services.

I enjoyed the research components of my education. Following graduation, I embarked on a role as a research assistant on the ROADMAP study (<https://www.roadmap-alzheimer.org/>), focussing on Alzheimer's disease. This study aimed to understand the most important outcomes for people living with the condition, their supporters, and healthcare professionals, through literature reviews, surveys, and public involvement consultations. I was drawn to this study for its emphasis on hearing the voices of those affected by Alzheimer's disease. The study found that delaying entry into institutional care, and remaining at home for as long as possible, were important outcomes of Alzheimer's disease, from the perspectives of those involved. However,

it was acknowledged that this was not experienced by many people, who faced unmet housing, health, and social care needs.

Motivated by the importance of housing for people with dementia, and the significance of incorporating the voices of those affected into research, policy, and practice, I aspired to pursue a PhD in the dementia field. This PhD provided an opportunity to conduct research within supported housing environments, to bring the experiences of people with dementia to the fore, and to understand the benefits and challenges of living in such settings. Furthermore, core values of the Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice, which emphasise human rights and the involvement of people with dementia in research, resonated with my worldview. I am privileged to be associated with this centre and hope the findings of this thesis can be used to improve the lives of people with dementia and their family members.

Thesis Structure

This thesis is formed of seven chapters. Chapter One introduces the thesis and builds context regarding housing and dementia in Scotland. Chapter Two presents the findings of a systematic review and thematic synthesis, which was conducted for the first stage of the thesis. Chapter Three provides an overview of theoretical and conceptual perspectives, relating to housing and dementia. A conceptual framework is also presented, which serves to enhance the development of an understanding of the experience of living with dementia in supported housing. Chapter Four presents the philosophical and methodological underpinnings of the empirical phase of the thesis, with an in-depth exploration of case study research. Chapter Five discusses the research design and methods of the empirical study. Chapter Six presents the findings from the individual case studies that were conducted for the empirical component of the thesis, followed by a cross-case analysis. Chapter Seven forms the discussion chapter of the thesis, presenting an interpretation of the research findings, their implications, the strengths, and limitations of the study, in addition to recommendations for research, policy, practice, and education.

Chapter One: Introduction and Context Building

1.1. Introduction to the Thesis and Chapter One

The dementia policy imperative in Scotland states that people with dementia should be enabled to live safely at home, or in a homely setting, for as long as they and their families wish (Scottish Government, 2010; Scottish Government, 2013; Scottish Government, 2017b; Scottish Government, 2023a). Research has shown that remaining at home is the preferred option for people living with dementia (Evans *et al.*, 2019a; Tochel *et al.*, 2019), linked to feelings of connectedness, attachment, familiarity, and control (Redwood, Eley and Gaughan, 2016). However, many community-dwelling people with dementia experience unmet housing, health, and social care needs, such as access to appropriate care, and safety issues in the home (Black *et al.*, 2013; Black *et al.*, 2019; Morrisby, Joosten and Ciccarelli, 2019). These unmet needs mean that people with dementia, in Scotland, can experience increased hospitalisations and premature care home admissions, with 62% of Scotland's care home population living with dementia (Brown *et al.*, 2017; National Records of Scotland, 2023; Public Health Scotland, 2022). It is important to develop an understanding of different housing models in Scotland, which might mitigate these negative outcomes and enable people with dementia to continue living at home, should they wish.

Coinciding with the development of Scotland's third national dementia strategy (Scottish Government, 2017b), a report was published in 2017, focussing on housing and dementia in Scotland (Brown *et al.*, 2017). The authors document a series of recommendations in relation to the provision of housing and care for people living with dementia. Such recommendations have been influential, and continue to inform government reports and housing frameworks in the United Kingdom and Scotland (All Party Parliamentary Group on Housing and Care for Older People, 2021; Dementia Services Development Centre, 2022; Healthcare Improvement Scotland, Chartered Institute of Housing Scotland and Alzheimer Scotland, 2019). The report acknowledges the potential for supported housing to be a positive housing choice for people living with dementia, due to the integration of housing and social care services in these settings. However, the authors state that it is unclear if supported housing can fully meet the needs of people living with dementia. To address this, Brown *et al.* (2017) suggest that more research is needed to understand the experience of living

with dementia in supported housing, from the perspectives of people living with the condition. Hence, this study was conceptualised.

The remainder of this chapter aims to develop context regarding research, policy, and practice, of relevance to dementia and supported housing. It will focus, primarily, on the Scottish context, but will draw learnings from wider literature. The chapter begins by discussing dementia and ageing, presenting figures, prevalence, causes and treatments, culminating in the acknowledgement that dementia is a public health priority. The primary reason for this is to demonstrate that, at present, dementia is an incurable, neurodegenerative syndrome, meaning that individuals develop complex needs that impact all facets of their lives. The chapter then turns its focus to the living arrangements of people with dementia, providing a critique of the housing and dementia policy imperative in Scotland. The final section discusses supported housing and dementia, and why this research study is necessary, emphasising the importance of hearing the voices of people living with dementia in research.

1.2. Ageing and Dementia

1.2.1. Facts and Figures

The World Health Organization defines dementia as a syndrome, caused by a variety of diseases or injuries, that impact brain functioning (World Health Organization, 2023b). Dementia is typically chronic or progressive and associated with deterioration to a range of cognitive, functional, emotional, and physical health outcomes (Alzheimer's Research UK, 2021; American Psychiatric Association, 2013). There are many types of dementia, each with their own distinct pathologies and symptomologies. The most common are dementia caused by Alzheimer's disease (50 – 75% of cases), vascular dementia (up to 20% of cases), dementia with Lewy bodies (10 – 15% of cases) and frontotemporal dementia (2% of cases) (Livingston *et al.*, 2017; Livingston *et al.*, 2020). It is possible to have more than one of these conditions at the same time, referred to as mixed dementia (Alzheimer's Research UK, 2021). Strikingly, over the last decade, dementia has been the leading cause of death in Scotland, and the rest of the United Kingdom (Alzheimer's Society, 2023).

Given its progressive nature, those living with the condition are often described as having mild, moderate, or advanced dementia, as assessed by clinical measurement tools (Folstein, Folstein and McHugh, 1975; Hughes

et al., 1982; Reisberg, 1988; Reisberg *et al.*, 1982). Each individual experiences the condition differently, due to their unique characteristics and personal life experiences (Kitwood, 1997; Kitwood and Brooker, 2019). However, the progressive nature of dementia means that individuals develop increased needs over time (Janssen *et al.*, 2020; Tochel *et al.*, 2019). For example, in the earlier stages of the condition, a person with dementia may experience some memory loss, or require support with household chores (Janssen *et al.*, 2020). As dementia and its symptoms progress, individuals develop complex needs, such as increased dependency on support with eating or drinking, communication, and personal care (Alzheimer's Research UK, 2021; Brown, Tolson and Ritchie, 2020). In the advanced stage of the condition, and towards the end of life, individuals can often become nonverbal, immobile, and in need of 24-hour care (Brown, Tolson and Ritchie, 2020). The time living with dementia varies greatly for each person due to age, comorbidities, and dementia type, though life expectancy following a diagnosis typically ranges from five to ten years, with some individuals living for up to 20 years (Alzheimer's Society, 2021).

It should be acknowledged that although people with dementia are living with neurodegenerative health conditions, these individuals should not simply be defined by their diagnoses (Kitwood, 1997; Kitwood and Brooker, 2019). People with dementia can, and should be supported to, contribute to civic life in any way possible, through the provision of support and care that meets their needs (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010; Birt *et al.*, 2017; Brannelly, 2011; O'Connor *et al.*, 2022; Swinton, 2021).

1.2.2. Worldwide Prevalence

Figures from the Global Burden of Disease Study (GBD) estimate that in 2019, 57.4 million people were living with dementia worldwide, with this figure projected to rise to 152.8 million by 2050 (GBD 2019 Dementia Forecasting Collaborators, 2022). The largest percentage increase in cases will occur in low- and middle-income countries, due to improved life expectancy, population size, and exposure to risk factors (GBD 2019 Dementia Forecasting Collaborators, 2022; Livingston *et al.*, 2020).

Dementia primarily impacts those aged 65 and over, with this age group accounting for 91% - 95% of dementia cases (Prince *et al.*, 2015; World Health Organization, 2017). By 2050, it is expected that 22% of the world's population will be aged 60 and over, compared to 12% in 2015 (World Health Organization, 2022). As

discussed previously, this demographic change will largely account for the increase in dementia cases predicted worldwide by 2050 (GBD 2019 Dementia Forecasting Collaborators, 2022). However, a systematic review and meta-analysis conducted in 2019 estimated that 3.9 million of those living with dementia worldwide (7% of 2019 cases) were aged 64 or younger (GBD 2019 Dementia Forecasting Collaborators, 2022; Hendriks *et al.*, 2021). Hence, contrary to common stereotypes, dementia is not only experienced by those of older age and does not simply occur due to ageing (Low and Purwaningrum, 2020).

1.2.3. Prevalence in Scotland

Alzheimer Scotland and the Scottish Government estimate that over 90,000 people are living with dementia in Scotland (Alzheimer Scotland, 2019b; Scottish Government, 2023a), with this figure predicted to rise to 164,000 by 2036 (Public Health Scotland, 2020). However, it is estimated that only two-thirds of people with dementia in the United Kingdom have a formal diagnosis, meaning that this figure is likely much higher (Ford *et al.*, 2019). The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on dementia diagnoses in Scotland should also be acknowledged. It is estimated that thousands more people are living with undiagnosed dementia in Scotland, due to disruptions caused by COVID-19 infection control practices, and the associated backlog of diagnostic testing (Alzheimer Scotland, 2020). This is important to consider, as it means that thousands of people living with dementia in Scotland do not have access to the health and social care services that they require. Again, this demonstrates the scale of the impact of dementia on Scotland's people.

1.2.4. Causes and Treatments

The public health response to dementia has focussed on prevention, emphasising the importance of improving health education, increasing physical activity, reducing smoking, and combating air pollution (Livingston *et al.*, 2020; World Health Organization, 2017). This is because 40% of dementia cases are believed to be preventable, with the Lancet Commission listing 12 modifiable risk-factors that can decrease the likelihood of developing dementia (Livingston *et al.*, 2020). These include health behaviours, such as smoking or alcohol consumption, health conditions, such as diabetes, hypertension or traumatic brain injury, and socio-environmental factors, like air pollution or access to healthy foods (Livingston *et al.*, 2020).

Conditions like Alzheimer's disease and frontotemporal dementia are also linked to a build-up of various proteins in the brain, such as amyloid- β and tau, which form plaques or neurofibrillary tangles, causing neuronal death (Alzheimer's Research UK, 2021; Livingston *et al.*, 2020). Dementia drug development in recent years has focussed mainly on disease modification, targeting molecules like amyloid- β and tau (Cummings *et al.*, 2023). For example, in 2021, of the 152 trials assessing new therapies for Alzheimer's disease, 82.5% focussed on disease modification, 10.3% focussed on cognitive enhancement, and 7.1% focussed on reducing neuropsychiatric symptoms (Cummings *et al.*, 2021). Positive pharmaceutical advancements have been seen in recent years, giving hope that treatments will be developed that can slow the progression of dementia (Cummings *et al.*, 2023; U.S. Food and Drug Administration, 2021). However, there currently exists no readily available, disease-modifying treatment for dementia in many countries, including the United Kingdom (Cummings *et al.*, 2023; Mahase, 2021).

Given the incurable and progressive nature of dementia, supporting those living with the condition relies on the provision of health and social care, a combination of pharmaceutical, environmental, and psychosocial interventions, and palliative or end-of-life care (World Health Organization, 2017). As such, focussing only on prevention and cure does not allow for the development of an in-depth understanding of the experience of actively living with the condition, which is central to this study. Dementia organisations, such as Alzheimer Europe, have stressed the importance of including people living with dementia in qualitative research, to give voice to those living with the condition (Alzheimer Europe, 2019; Diaz *et al.*, 2021; Georges *et al.*, 2022). Hearing these voices can help researchers understand the pertinent issues that impact the lives of people with dementia, which can be used to inform future directions for research, policy goals, and practice guidelines.

1.2.5. Dementia as a Public Health Priority

To summarise the previous sections, dementia is an incurable, progressive health condition that can impact individuals at any stage of adult life, with some individuals living with the condition for up to 20 years following diagnosis (Alzheimer's Society, 2021). As such, in 2012, the World Health Organization declared that tackling dementia is a public health priority (World Health Organization, 2012). Subsequently, the World Health

Organization released a global action plan for the public health response to dementia, for the period of 2017 – 2025 (World Health Organization, 2017). The global action plan is grounded by seven principles, emphasising human rights, empowerment, and engagement for people with dementia and their families; evidence-based practice and universal health and social care coverage; focus on dementia prevention and cure; equity; and the need for multisector, integrated collaboration to implement the plan, involving health and social care, education, employment, justice, and housing (World Health Organization, 2017).

From these stemmed seven action areas. One of which was to ensure that 75% of the 194 World Health Organization member states have a new or updated national dementia plan by 2025 (World Health Organization, 2017; World Health Organization, 2023a). To monitor the implementation of the global action plan, the World Health Organization developed the Global Dementia Observatory (World Health Organization, 2023c). At the time of writing, 50, primarily high income, out of the 194 World Health Organization member states have a national dementia plan (World Health Organization, 2023d), with the organisation stating that the world is still failing to address the dementia challenge (World Health Organization, 2021).

Dementia has been a public health priority in Scotland since 2007 (Public Health Scotland, 2020), with the Scottish Government publishing four national dementia strategies since 2010 (Scottish Government, 2010; Scottish Government, 2013; Scottish Government, 2017b; Scottish Government, 2023a). Highlights of these dementia strategies, since implemented in the real-world, include the provision of one-year of post-diagnostic support for people diagnosed with dementia in Scotland, based on Alzheimer Scotland's Five-Pillars Model of Post-Diagnostic Support (Alzheimer Scotland, 2011). The model emphasises the importance of planning for future decision making; supporting community connections; understanding the illness and managing symptoms; peer support; and planning for future care (Alzheimer Scotland, 2011).

The Eight-Pillars Model of Community Support was then developed, which outlines an integrated and evidence-based approach to support community-dwelling people living with dementia throughout the moderate and advanced stages of the condition, discussing personal support, community connections, therapeutic intervention, and more (Alzheimer Scotland, 2012). The Eight-Pillars Model also outlines the

involvement of a Dementia Practice Coordinator, who leads the care, treatment and support for the person living with dementia and their family members (Alzheimer Scotland, 2012).

In 2015, Alzheimer Scotland also developed the Advanced Dementia Practice Model, which focusses on the advanced stage of the condition and end-of-life. This model adds to the Eight-Pillars Model, introducing an Advanced Dementia Specialist Team, including a consultant geriatrician, allied health professionals, district nurses, a psychiatrist and psychologist, and a palliative care specialist (Alzheimer Scotland, 2015).

Further developments include the Transforming Specialist Dementia Hospital Care report (Alzheimer Scotland, 2018), discussing how to improve the quality of support for those receiving specialist dementia care, and the Connecting People, Connecting Support report (Alzheimer Scotland, 2017), aimed at shaping the way that allied health professionals support people living with dementia. In addition, the Standards of Care for Dementia in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2011d) and the Promoting Excellence Framework (Scottish Government, 2011c) were published, to help people with dementia and their families understand their rights, to ensure they receive the support they require, and to detail the skills and knowledge that health and social care professionals should have when supporting those living with dementia. Together, the national dementia strategies, and associated developments from Alzheimer Scotland, have permeated through health and social care policy and practice in Scotland, to varying degrees, and have shaped the way support and care is delivered to those living with dementia.

Stemming from the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (United Nations, 2006), the Cross-Party Group in the Scottish Parliament developed the Charter of Rights for People with Dementia and their Carers in Scotland (Cross-Party Group in the Scottish Parliament on Alzheimer's, 2009). This was developed to tackle the social, cultural, and economic barriers faced by those living with dementia in Scotland and is underpinned by the PANEL approach to human-rights (Scottish Human Rights Commission, 2022). This emphasises the rights of everyone to; participate in decisions which affect their human rights; accountability of those responsible for the respect, protection, and fulfilment of human rights; non-discrimination and equality; empowerment to know their rights and how to claim them; legality in all decisions through an explicit link with human rights legal standards in all processes and outcome

measurements (Cross-Party Group in the Scottish Parliament on Alzheimer's, 2009). Again, a human-rights based approach permeates throughout Scotland's national dementia strategies, models and standards of care, and the promoting excellence framework, with the clear message that those living with dementia have the same rights as any other citizen (Alzheimer Scotland, 2012).

However, despite being a world leader regarding dementia policy and the provision of health and social care, there is still much more to be done to meet the needs of all people living with dementia in Scotland. For example, a recent independent review of adult social care in Scotland, conducted by Feeley, noted several areas requiring urgent attention (Feeley, 2021). One of which is to ensure that individuals with dementia can live in a home or a homely setting for as long as they wish, a human right (Feeley, 2021). However, in many situations, as Feeley notes, individuals with dementia are left little choice when deciding where to live, with the default option being a care home in the event of a move (Feeley, 2021). The report also notes that access to dementia services is not equal throughout Scotland. Of note, the provision of one-year of post-diagnostic support (Feeley, 2021). Public Health Scotland noted that only 43.4% of those newly diagnosed with dementia in Scotland were referred for post-diagnostic support in 2018 – 2019, with only 75.1% of those referred receiving one year of support (Public Health Scotland, 2021).

Furthermore, there are significant health inequalities regarding dementia care provision in Scotland. Alzheimer Scotland's Fair Dementia Care campaign states that people with advanced dementia do not have equal access to the expert health and nursing care services that they need (Alzheimer Scotland, 2019a). This means that those living with advanced dementia in Scotland are often disproportionately subject to social care charges for health and nursing care needs, which are otherwise free of charge (Alzheimer Scotland, 2019a). Like the World Health Organization's global action plan on dementia, which emphasises the need for integration between health and social care, education, employment, justice, and housing services (World Health Organization, 2017), the independent review of adult social care, and the Fair Dementia Care campaign, call for the integration of health and social care services to tackle these issues (Alzheimer Scotland, 2019a; Feeley, 2021). Central to these plans for integration, in dementia strategies, and in discussions

surrounding human-rights, lies housing. Hence, an important consideration is the living arrangements of people with dementia.

1.3. Living Arrangements

1.3.1. Figures

Most people living with dementia reside in their own homes in the community, with figures ranging from 60% in the United Kingdom, 70% in Australia, 80% in the United States of America, and 93% in Canada (Osborne, 2020). A 2017 report, focussing on housing and dementia in Scotland, estimated that 73% of people with dementia live in their own homes in Scotland, with roughly 20,000 living alone (Brown *et al.*, 2017). Comparatively, a 2019 report stated that roughly 20,000 people living with dementia resided in care homes in Scotland in 2016, constituting 20% - 30% of total dementia cases, depending on prevalence figures used (Burton *et al.*, 2019). Research stresses the importance of living at home for people with dementia, linked to feelings of connection, permanency, familiarity, expression, and autonomy, amidst the uncertainty posed by the condition (Aminzadeh *et al.*, 2009; Aminzadeh *et al.*, 2010; Redwood, Eley and Gaughan, 2016). A recent systematic review found that living independently at home, and delaying entry into residential care, was the preferred option for people living with dementia (Tochel *et al.*, 2019). The desire for many people living with dementia to remain at home highlights the importance of access to appropriate housing, health, and social care for this population. Again, the key role of housing features in global dementia initiatives (World Health Organization, 2017), Alzheimer's Disease International's World Alzheimer's Report (Fleming, Zeisel and Bennett, 2020), and indeed, Scotland's most recent national dementia strategy (Scottish Government, 2023a). Despite this, research suggests that many people living with dementia in the community experience unmet housing, health, and social care needs (Black *et al.*, 2013; Black *et al.*, 2019; Morrisby, Joosten and Ciccarelli, 2018; Morrisby, Joosten and Ciccarelli, 2019). Others question whether enough appropriate housing options exist for people of older age and those living with dementia in Scotland (Brown *et al.*, 2017; Fyfe and Hutchison, 2020; Harding *et al.*, 2018). Living alone with dementia has also been linked to social isolation and loneliness (Alzheimer's Society, 2013), a higher rate of hospitalisations and care home admissions (Soto *et al.*, 2015), and an increased rate of cognitive decline (Grande *et al.*, 2018). This is an important consideration

given that some 20,000 community dwelling people living with dementia live alone (Brown *et al.*, 2017). More recently, the All Party Parliamentary Group on Housing and Care for Older People, and the independent review of adult social care in Scotland, acknowledged that more needs to be done to meet the housing needs of people with dementia, to make the policy ideals of access to appropriate housing, health, and social care a reality for more people living with dementia. Therefore, it is important to consider the housing and dementia policy context in Scotland, to determine how the country aims to address these issues.

1.3.2. Scottish Housing Policy

Regarding housing and dementia strategies and policies in Scotland, housing featured minimally in Scotland's first national dementia strategy (Scottish Government, 2010). By the second national dementia strategy, commitment five focussed on taking action to provide safe and supportive home environments for people living with dementia, with adaptations and assistive technologies to enhance independence and quality of life (Scottish Government, 2013). The third national dementia strategy maintained its commitment to housing, with commitment 12 focussing on implementing actions from the Age, Home and Community: A Strategy for Housing for Scotland's Older People: 2012 – 21 report, again, emphasising the need to enable those living with dementia to live independently and safely at home for as long as possible (Scottish Government, 2011b; Scottish Government, 2017b). Age, Home, and Community has been the major housing policy relating to older people living in Scotland over the last decade, with three updated strategy documents being produced since its inception (Scottish Government, 2011b; Scottish Government, 2017a; Scottish Government, 2018). Since then, the most recent housing policy was released in 2021, titled Housing to 2040 (Scottish Government, 2019; Scottish Government, 2021).

It can be argued that there is little synergy between housing and dementia policies in Scotland. For example, Housing to 2040 makes no reference to Age, Home, and Community, or to people living with dementia, and progress made over the last decade is unclear (Scottish Government, 2011b; Scottish Government, 2021). To illustrate, the original Age, Home, and Community document states that a "holistic approach" is required regarding the provision of support and care to older people living at home, with an action point being the improved integration between housing, health, and social care (Scottish Government, 2011a). However, 10

years later, an action point in Housing to 2040 is to work with “...health and social care and housing services, service commissioners, delivery organisations and older and disabled people to embed a person-centred approach, that aligns housing support with social care services...” (Scottish Government, 2021, p. 57). Hence, it is unclear how much has changed regarding the integration of health, social care, and housing over the last 10 years.

Age, Home, and Community also acknowledges the need to “...achieve simpler, fairer and more effective delivery of [home] adaptations...” for older people and those with disabling health conditions, due to the significant backlog (Scottish Government, 2011a). Additionally, action 20 of Housing to 2040 was to “...streamline and accelerate the adaptations system...” (Scottish Government, 2021, p. 63). In the 2010 – 2012 Scottish House Condition survey, when Age, Home, and Community was first published, 73,000 homes occupied by a person with a disabling condition were waiting for home adaptations (Scottish Government, 2023c). In the most recent Scottish House Condition Survey data (2017 - 2019), this figure increased to 82,000 (Scottish Government, 2023b). Other Scottish Government statistics show that 71% (513,000) of homes occupied by those aged 65 and over in Scotland have some level of disrepair, with 25% (194,000) requiring urgent repair (Scottish Government, 2023b). It is unclear how the delivery of home adaptations will be accelerated or streamlined moving forward.

Age, Home, and Community also states that a priority for government was to build affordable and sustainable housing that encourages “...mobility in the housing system and enables downsizing for those that wish it” (Scottish Government, 2011a, p. 6). However, Housing to 2040 still acknowledges that much more needs to be done to address the housing needs of those living with disabling conditions in Scotland, with over 10,000 individuals living with disabilities waiting for appropriate housing (Scottish Government, 2021). Relatedly, Age, Home and Community acknowledged that in 2011 - 2012, the number of specialist housing dwellings available in Scotland, such as sheltered, retirement, very sheltered or extra care housing (collectively, supported housing) failed to meet demand (Scottish Government, 2011a). The document states that to meet supported housing demand, and to accommodate choice, we “...need a range of different types of services

that are flexible and enable older people to choose the options, which reflect their individual lifestyles and are best for them” (Scottish Government, 2011a, p. 19).

In 2011, of the 2.5 million dwellings in Scotland, there were 22,071 supported housing dwellings, including medium dependency, sheltered, and very sheltered housing (Scottish Government, 2018b; Scottish Government, 2019a). The most recent figures show that in 2022, there were 2.7 million dwellings in Scotland, with supported housing and similar settings accounting for 1% (roughly 27,000 dwellings) of total housing stock (National Statistics, 2023; Scottish Government, 2021). Additionally, in 2017, the London School of Economics conducted an assessment to determine the projected demand of supported housing between 2015 and 2030 in England, Scotland, and Wales (Wittenberg and Hu, 2017). They note that, based on population projections and supported housing demand, some 59,000 supported housing developments were required to meet demand in 2015 in Scotland. By 2030, this figure will rise to 73,000 (Wittenberg and Hu, 2017). Given that provision of supported housing has declined substantially over the last two decades, it is unlikely that this target will be met (Scottish Government, 2022).

To add, Age, Home and Community acknowledged that a caveat to achieving the outlined aims of the strategy was the Great Recession, occurring between 2008 and 2009 in the United Kingdom, resulting in decreased public funding (Scottish Government, 2011a, p. 1). However, the United Kingdom has since faced a worse recession, largely due to the COVID-19 pandemic (Moreira and Hick, 2021), further impacting the Scottish Government’s ability to achieve their ambitious housing goals.

In sum, there is growing evidence that people living with dementia would welcome positive housing choices in later life. This includes an opportunity to move, if they wish, to more appropriate housing (Brown *et al.*, 2017). However, there is a clear need for in-depth research focussing on various housing models and their ability to facilitate independence and access to appropriate support and care for people living with dementia, reflecting the Scottish policy imperative. This study focusses on one housing option, supported housing. It has been suggested that supported housing can facilitate independent living for people with dementia, by integrating housing with additional support or care services (Brown *et al.*, 2017). Others state that living in supported housing can ameliorate the issues raised in the previous sections. For example, by enabling people

with dementia to continue living in their own homes, reducing loneliness, and improving access to health and social care (Twyford, 2018). However, the benefits and challenges of living with dementia in supported housing in Scotland are not fully understood, particularly from the perspectives of those living with the condition (Brown *et al.*, 2017). Hence, to give more context to the overall study, the next section provides information regarding what supported housing delivers as a service.

1.3.3. Supported Housing and Dementia

In the United Kingdom, supported housing is defined as “...any housing scheme where housing is provided alongside care, support, or supervision to help people live as independently as possible in the community” (Department for Work and Pensions and Department for Communities and Local Government, 2016). In Scotland, and in the context of housing for people of older age, supported housing relates to settings that offer a low level of support, like sheltered or retirement housing, through to settings offering a higher level of support and, sometimes, direct care, like very sheltered or extra care housing (Care Information Scotland, 2020). Supported housing settings differ in size and structure, including shared housing environments, blocks of flats, and individual bungalows or houses. These settings aim to facilitate independent living, with residents classified as tenants or homeowners by law (Brown *et al.*, 2017; Care Information Scotland, 2020).

Other typical features include staff presence, such as wardens, support workers, or care providers; self-contained home environments; access to emergency alarm systems or pull chords; shared and communal spaces; organisation of social activities, and; provision of meals (Beach, 2018; Care Information Scotland, 2020; Howe, Jones and Tilse, 2013). Most supported housing dwellings are rented through the social housing sector in Scotland, though figures indicate that roughly 10% of supported housing stock is privately provided (Brown *et al.*, 2017).

The total proportion of people living with dementia in supported housing in Scotland is unclear. Figures from the Alzheimer’s Society suggest that 8.1% of all individuals living in extra care housing, in the United Kingdom, have dementia (Alzheimer’s Society, 2014). Though, the authors state that this figure should be interpreted with caution, and these statistics are predominantly based on the English housing market (Alzheimer’s Society, 2014). More recently, the Housing and Dementia Research Consortium stated that 16% of those living

in extra care housing in the United Kingdom have dementia, with a further 7% living without a diagnosis (Barrett, 2020; Barrett, 2021). Again, these figures focus primarily on England, and do not reflect settings offering a lower level of support, such as sheltered or retirement housing. These figures compare to 47.8% to 50.3% of care home residents in Scotland, with a further 6.9% to 7.3% of care home residents considered to have dementia without a formal diagnosis (Burton *et al.*, 2019). It should be noted that figures for supported housing will vary considerably based on the housing model, the availability of care, and housing provider policies.

Supported housing has been described as an appropriate housing choice for people living with dementia. There is some evidence to suggest that supported housing can improve quality of life, increase independence and autonomy, combat social isolation, reduce hospitalisations, and defer entry into residential care for people living with dementia (Brooker *et al.*, 2011; Dutton, 2009; Holland *et al.*, 2015; Twyford, 2016). However, other research suggests that these positive outcomes are not always experienced (Dutton 2009; Verbeek *et al.*, 2019). A report on housing and dementia in Scotland noted that there is a dearth of evidence that adequately considers the perspectives of people living with dementia in supported housing environments (Brown *et al.*, 2017). Developing an in-depth understanding of the experience of living with dementia in supported housing in Scotland will provide much needed information about the potential of this model to facilitate access to health and social care, to promote social relationships and community connections, and to provide a dementia-friendly environment that promotes the independence and wellbeing of those living with dementia.

1.4. Chapter One Summary

This chapter begins developing an understanding of ageing and dementia, and the typical living arrangements of people living with dementia. As discussed, dementia is an incurable health condition, experienced by millions worldwide, and is a public health priority. Those living with the condition often have complex health and social care needs, and most individuals living with the condition live in their own homes in the community. Living at home has been described as the preferred living arrangement for this population.

Receipt of appropriate housing, health, and social care to meet these complex needs are human rights. However, many people living with dementia in the community experience unmet housing, health, and social care needs. An influential document acknowledged these issues (Brown *et al.*, 2017), stating that one potential solution is supported housing. There is some suggestion that supported housing can meet the needs of people living with dementia, by integrating housing, health, and social care, whilst enabling these individuals to live in their own, self-contained home in the community. However, the report acknowledges that research relating to supported housing and dementia is lacking, particularly in Scotland, and there is a limited understanding of the experiences of people living with dementia in the supported housing literature. As such, this study was conceptualised, with the overall aim of developing an in-depth understanding of the experience of living with dementia in supported housing in Scotland. Having developed an overview of the housing and dementia context in Scotland, Chapter Two focusses on a systematic review and thematic synthesis, which was undertaken for the first part of this study.

Chapter Two: Systematic Review and Thematic Synthesis

2.1. Introduction to Chapter Two

As discussed in Chapter One, it has been proposed that supported housing is an appropriate housing choice for people living with dementia, due to the integration of housing and social care within these settings (Brown *et al.*, 2017). However, the experience of living with dementia in supported housing in Scotland is not fully understood. There is a need for research that gathers the perspectives of people living with dementia in these settings (Brown *et al.*, 2017). Resultantly, the overall aim of this thesis is to develop an in-depth understanding of the experience of living with dementia in supported housing in Scotland. To inform the development of the objectives for the empirical stage of this thesis, a systematic review and thematic synthesis of qualitative research was first conducted.

The emphasis on understanding perspectives and experiences, in the recommendations proposed by Brown *et al.* (2017), informed the decision to focus on qualitative research in this review. Indeed, the importance of hearing the voice of people living with dementia, in research, has been described as essential for understanding the pertinent issues that impact the lives of people with dementia (Alzheimer Europe, 2019). In turn, these perspectives can influence future directions for research, policy goals, and practice guidelines. Scoping exercises showed that no systematic review had been conducted, which focussed on the experience of living with dementia in supported housing. As such, this was a clear gap in the evidence base that could be addressed in this thesis.

Systematic reviews have been described as the most time-consuming review approach (Brennan *et al.*, 2020). This is due to the extensive methodological steps involved (through registering review protocols, the development of detailed search strategies, processes of critical appraisal, data extraction, and the resultant evidence synthesis), and the comprehensiveness of such steps (Brennan *et al.*, 2020). These comprehensive steps aim to ensure that all relevant publications are identified, increasing the rigour of the evidence synthesis (Brennan *et al.*, 2020; Grant and Booth, 2009). Other literature review approaches, such as scoping or rapid reviews, have been described as lacking clear methodological steps, with an increased risk of missing relevant

articles, impacting rigour (Brennan *et al.*, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic created significant disruption throughout this research study, in relation to conducting applied research, due to infection control guidelines. However, this presented an opportunity to turn the focus of the research to the completion of a rigorous systematic review.

There are multiple approaches to systematic review that can be applied to qualitative evidence synthesis, such as meta-ethnography, meta-synthesis, and narrative synthesis (Seers, 2015). These approaches were considered prior to conducting the review. However, a critique of these approaches is that they lack formal instructions regarding the analytical steps of extracting the relevant text from research articles, and synthesising the uncovered evidence (Thomas and Harden, 2008). In this regard, the thematic synthesis approach of Thomas and Harden (2008) was followed, given that clear analytical steps are documented. In accordance with guidelines for conducting rigorous systematic reviews (Tacconelli, 2010), the thematic synthesis approach emphasises the importance of developing an audit trail of decisions and interpretations made throughout the research process (Thomas and Harden, 2008). This enables the reader to discern where the evidence that informs the synthesis has come from, enhancing rigour. Additionally, rigour is also developed by presenting textual information from the reviewed articles, to support any interpretations made by the researcher, enabling the reader to determine the soundness of these interpretations (Thomas and Harden, 2008). In sum, this rigorous approach utilises people's perspectives shared in research, to develop an evidence-informed synthesis that can be used to highlight research gaps and develop policy and practice recommendations (Thomas and Harden, 2008). As this thesis emphasises the importance of hearing the perspectives of people living with dementia in supported housing, the thematic synthesis approach was deemed most suitable.

The systematic review has been published in the journal of Health and Social Care in the Community, shown in Appendix 1. It is worth noting that the publication has been cited 10 times at the time of writing this thesis, demonstrating its value to the wider evidence base relating to supported housing and dementia. The review was conducted in collaboration with the PhD researcher's supervisory team, in addition to Dr Constantina

Papadopoulou, who was involved in the study given her extensive expertise in the conducting of systematic reviews. The full reference for this publication is as follows:

Smith, M., Brown, M., Ritchie, L., Papadopoulou, C. and Tolson, D. (2022) 'Living with dementia in supported housing: A systematic review and thematic synthesis of qualitative research', *Health and Social Care in the Community*, 30(3), pp. e589-e604.

The remainder of this chapter presents the review's abstract, followed by a brief introduction to the review and its research question. The systematic review steps are then outlined, including details relating to searches, critical appraisal, and data synthesis. Following this, the findings of the thematic synthesis are presented. The review culminates in a discussion of the uncovered evidence.

2.2. Abstract

Supported housing has been highlighted as a potential way to facilitate independent living for people with dementia by integrating housing with support or care services. However, the benefits and challenges of living with dementia in supported housing are not fully understood. This systematic review and thematic synthesis sought to understand how living in supported housing influences the lives of people with dementia, from the perspectives of people with dementia, their supporters, health, and social care professionals. Seven databases were searched for qualitative research, date range: 1st January 2000 – 31st July 2021. Eleven published articles were included in the thematic synthesis. One core theme was generated, Maintaining Independence and Autonomy, divided into three subthemes – Support and Care, Social Relationships, and the Physical Environment. Factors like person-centred care, social interaction, and good environmental design contributed to the maintenance of independence and autonomy. Barriers like low staff ratios, stigma, and limited access to the community led to a loss of independence and autonomy – often leading to people with dementia being referred or managed out of the settings. Although the articles acknowledged the importance of maintaining independence and autonomy for people with dementia, it appeared that supported housing settings often lacked the resources and facilities to make this a reality. More high-quality research is needed, particularly from the perspectives of people with dementia and their supporters, to understand if supported

housing can delay care home admission, promote independence and autonomy, and facilitate social networks and community connections for this population.

2.3. Introduction

As discussed in Chapter One, most people with dementia live in their own homes in the community, with figures ranging from 60% in the United Kingdom, 70% in Australia, 80% in the United States of America, and 93% in Canada (Osborne, 2020). Living independently, remaining at home, and delaying entry into residential care is the preferred option for people with dementia (Tochel *et al.*, 2019).

The dementia policy imperative reflects this by highlighting the importance of enabling people with dementia to live independently at home or in a homely setting for as long as they wish (Alzheimer Europe, 2018; World Health Organization, 2017), though achieving this “...requires appropriate housing options in the community, in combination with home and social care...” (Fleming *et al.*, 2020, p. 15). However, research suggests that many community-dwelling people with dementia experience unmet health and social care needs (Morrisby, Joosten and Ciccarelli, 2018), while others question if enough appropriate housing options exist for this population (Brown *et al.*, 2017; Harding *et al.*, 2018). As stated in Chapter One, there is a need for research to assess housing options for people with dementia and their ability to facilitate independent living, with this thesis focussing on supported housing.

Research stresses the importance of synthesising personal stories and lived experiences to gain a comprehensive and multifaceted understanding of living with dementia (Górska, Forsyth and Maciver, 2018; O'Rourke *et al.*, 2015). However, scoping searches of PROSPERO, the Cochrane Library, and the Joanna Briggs Institute review repositories indicate that there has yet to be a rigorous systematic review focussing on the experience of living with dementia in supported housing. Considering the policy imperative on access to housing for people with dementia, the importance of enabling independent living for this population, and the potential of supported housing to facilitate this, this review can enhance our understanding of this housing option. By thematically synthesising an international body of qualitative research, this review aimed to answer the question:

How does living in supported housing influence the lives of people with dementia, from the perspectives of people living with dementia, their supporters, health, and social care professionals?

2.4. Methods

The systematic review protocol was registered on PROSPERO (ID CRD42020176816). The review adhered to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) (Moher *et al.*, 2009) and the Centre for Reviews and Dissemination (CRD) guidance for undertaking reviews in health care (Tacconelli, 2010).

2.4.1. Search Strategy

All search strategies are provided in Appendix 2 of the supplementary material for this thesis. This systematic review thematically synthesised findings from peer-reviewed qualitative research, including mixed methods research with a qualitative component. The search strategy was first developed for MEDLINE (EBSCOhost), then adapted for CINAHL Complete (EBSCOhost), Health Source: Nursing / Academic Edition (EBSCOhost), APA PsycArticles (EBSCOhost), Psychology and Behavioral Sciences Collection (EBSCOhost), SocINDEX (EBSCOhost), and Social Care Institute for Excellence: Social Care Online (<https://www.scie-socialcareonline.org.uk>).

Each search in EBSCOhost was conducted individually to account for differences in search functions for each database. Search terms related to supported housing and comparative housing models, study methodologies and methods, dementia and its major subtypes, and a range of symptoms, experiences, and outcomes of dementia. The search strategy was informed by previous housing reviews (Croucher, Hicks and Jackson, 2006; Dutton, 2009; Howe, Jones and Tilse, 2013; O'Malley and Croucher, 2005), core or priority dementia-related outcomes lists (Janssen *et al.*, 2020; Reilly *et al.*, 2020; Webster *et al.*, 2017a; Webster *et al.*, 2017b), and elements of the lived experience of dementia (Górska, Forsyth and Maciver, 2018). The search was balanced for sensitivity and specificity and incorporated subject headings / indexing terms specific to each database (e.g., Medical Subject Headings, CINAHL Subject Headings, APA Thesaurus of Psychological Index Terms), synonyms, and differences in spellings, in accordance with CRD guidelines (Tacconelli, 2010). Articles written in English from all countries were included.

The date range of the searches was limited to 1st January 2000 – 31st July 2021, including articles that were available as pre-prints or were forthcoming at the time of the search. Although published and unpublished articles have reviewed literature relating to housing and dementia prior to the year 2009 (e.g., Dutton, 2009; O'Malley and Croucher, 2005), qualitative research, published from 2000 – 2009, was not discussed in these reviews. This may be due to the omission of search terms like “assisted living”, “independent living”, or “extra care” (O'Malley and Croucher, 2005), or the specified inclusion criteria of the review (Dutton, 2009). It is also unclear how search strategies were input into each database, or if subject headings and indexing terms were used in accordance with CRD guidelines, which may have impacted the number of references uncovered (Tacconelli, 2010). As such, the specified date range was selected to provide an overview of the most up-to-date qualitative research, whilst documenting a replicable search strategy and robust critical appraisal of relevant research.

The authors of any relevant, unpublished research were contacted to determine if their findings had been published in a peer-reviewed journal. The reference lists of any relevant articles were also hand-searched, to uncover literature not identified in the databases.

2.4.2. Selection Criteria and Screening

Drawing on comparative reviews of international housing models for older people and previous literature reviews on supported housing (Croucher, Hicks and Jackson, 2006; Dutton, 2009; O'Malley and Croucher, 2005), a broad definition of supported housing was used. In this review, supported housing was defined as any form of housing for older people, where housing is provided alongside support or care to promote independent living. This included settings offering a low level of support (e.g., sheltered housing, retirement housing, independent living), and settings offering a higher level of support and care (e.g., very-sheltered housing, extra care housing, housing with care, assisted living). Settings described as “care homes”, “nursing homes”, “locked”, “secure” or “institutional” were not included. This was to ensure that the included settings operationally focussed on the provision of housing, rather than the provision of health care. Further inclusion and exclusion criteria (Table 1) were developed in accordance with the Study, Participants, Phenomenon of Interest, Outcomes (SPIO) framework (Richardson *et al.*, 1995).

All peer-reviewed articles meeting the review criteria were included. This meant that if a subsection of the research related to dementia, it would be included, provided the findings could be extracted from the article and differentiated from other participant groups. EndNote X8 (Clarivate Analytics, 2018) was used for reference management. Covidence software (Veritas Health Innovation, 2019) facilitated screening. All titles / abstracts / full texts were screened by the PhD researcher, and a second member of the review team.

2.4.3. Quality Appraisal

For each article, methodological quality was assessed using the ten items of the Critical Appraisal Skills Program (CASP) Qualitative Checklist (Critical Appraisal Skills Programme, 2018). Each article was given a score ranging from 0 – 10 based on satisfaction of each criterion. A score of 0 (denoting “No”) was given if the article did not meet the criterion. A score of 0.5 was given if the article provided evidence of relevance to the criterion, though not in sufficient detail to determine if the criterion was satisfied (denoting “Can’t Tell”). A score of 1 was given if the article satisfied the criterion (denoting “Yes”). In line with the thematic synthesis process, no articles were excluded based on quality, but rather, quality issues were outlined as part of the thematic synthesis (Thomas and Harden, 2008). A sensitivity analysis was conducted, in line with the thematic synthesis approach, to determine the contribution of each article to the overall synthesis and the potential impact of methodological quality on the review findings (Thomas and Harden, 2008). The PhD researcher conducted all appraisals, with content agreed at supervisory meetings.

Table 1: Outline of inclusion and exclusion criteria, following the SPIO framework (Richardson *et al.*, 1995).

Inclusion	Exclusion
Study Design	
Qualitative research. Mixed methods research with an extractable qualitative component.	Quantitative research. Commentaries, discussion, or opinion pieces. Literature reviews. Intervention studies.
Population	
People with dementia: All subtypes, living in supported housing.	People living in care or nursing homes (including small-scale, homelike dementia care settings and nursing homes), or those living in “ordinary” housing.
Supporters: Family members, friends (including other residents), and unpaid caregivers of people living with dementia in supported housing.	People with learning disabilities or severe mental illness and dementia.

Health and social care professionals: Paid caregivers, support workers, managers, primary care nurses, community mental health nurses, allied health professionals, general practitioners, and other health and social care professionals who provide support or care to people living with dementia in supported housing.	People with mild cognitive impairment. Building planners / architects / policy makers, or individuals with no direct role in the everyday functioning of a supported housing setting.
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Phenomenon of Interest

How living in supported housing influences the lives of people with dementia, from the perspectives of the populations of interest.	Views regarding the prospect of moving into a supported housing setting.
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Outcomes (Findings)

Experiential accounts, related specifically to living in supported housing with a diagnosis of dementia.	Quantitative analysis. Commentaries, opinion, or discussion pieces. Evidence syntheses in literature reviews.
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2.4.4. Data Extraction and Synthesis

A data extraction form was developed, available in Appendix 3 of this thesis. Data extraction was conducted by the PhD researcher, with content agreed at supervisory meetings.

Data synthesis utilised the thematic synthesis approach (Thomas and Harden, 2008). Thematic synthesis enables researchers “...to stay 'close' to the results of the primary studies, synthesising them in a transparent way, and facilitating the explicit production of new concepts...”, and can be used to inform policy, practice, and directions for future research (Thomas and Harden, 2008). It draws from elements of meta-ethnography and grounded theory and is philosophically underpinned by critical realism (Barnett-Page and Thomas, 2009). It is characterised by three analytical processes: coding text, development of descriptive themes, and generating analytical themes, conducted as follows in the present review.

Coding Text: The qualitative data and the authors’ second level interpretations were extracted from the results section of each article and stored in an NVivo 12 Pro database (QSR International Pty Ltd, 2020). In some instances, unique findings were reported in the discussion sections of the articles, which were extracted. Free coding of the findings was conducted line-by-line. Articles with the highest methodological quality and the largest amount of relevant data were coded first, followed by the remaining articles. New and

existing codes were developed throughout the analytical process. Coding was conducted by the PhD researcher, with the coding framework refined at subsequent supervisory meetings.

Development of Descriptive Themes: All codes were then arranged and visualised hierarchically using NVivo 12 Pro software, forming the basis of the descriptive themes. Visualising codes promoted rigorous synthesis and enabled the researcher to group codes into meaningful themes, capturing the content of the included articles. These themes were discussed at supervisory team meetings.

Generating Analytical Themes: The descriptive themes were then expanded into analytical themes. The previous steps were rooted in the original findings of the included articles. This step aimed to transcend the content of the individual articles, generating new concepts and understandings from the evidence base. This process was cyclical and conducted within the supervisory team until all descriptive themes were synthesised. These analytical themes, together with illustrative participant quotes and authors' interpretations, are reported in the results section.

2.5. Results

2.5.1. Searches

Figure 1 shows the output of the database searches and screening phases. Based on title / abstract screening of the 3,914 unique records identified in the searches, there was 95% agreement regarding inclusion and exclusion decisions, meaning that conflicts arose for 198 articles. This corresponded to a Cohen's kappa statistic of 0.52, denoting a moderate level of inter-rater reliability (Cohen, 1960). Conflicts were resolved within supervisory team meetings. Of the 153 full texts screened, 11 articles were included in the thematic synthesis.

2.5.2. Study Characteristics

Characteristics of the 11 included articles are shown in Table 2. The articles were based on eight research studies. Two articles were based on a research study conducted in assisted living settings in Missouri, United States of America (Aud, 2002; Aud, 2004). Two articles were based on The Provision of Social Care in Extra Care Housing study (ECHO), conducted in England, United Kingdom (Cameron, Johnson Eleanor and Evans,

2020; Evans *et al.*, 2020). Two articles were based on the Technology-Enriched Supported Accommodation study, conducted in Northern Ireland, United Kingdom (Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2021). The five remaining studies were conducted in England in retirement housing (O'Malley *et al.*, 2018), extra care housing (Evans *et al.*, 2019b; Evans and Means, 2006), a mixture of supported housing settings (Barrett, Evans and Pritchard-Wilkes, 2020), and supportive seniors' housing in Western Canada (Stewart-Archer *et al.*, 2016). Studies were described as exploratory, longitudinal, or mixed methods. Articles that reported details of analysis used thematic analysis or presented their findings as themes. From articles that explicitly reported participant numbers, views were gathered from 21 people with dementia, 28 supporters, and 77 health and social care professionals.

2.5.3. Quality Appraisal and Sensitivity Analysis

CASP Qualitative Checklist (Critical Appraisal Skills Programme, 2018) scores are shown in Table 2, with a more detailed breakdown provided in Appendix 4 of this thesis. The most common quality issues were - not discussing the relationship between the researcher(s) and the research participants and providing limited information on data collection methods. Other common issues related to limited descriptions of recruitment, ethical considerations, and data analysis. The least common quality issues related to providing clear study aims, the appropriateness of qualitative research to address these aims, and discussion of how valuable the research is, with all articles providing a clear statement of findings. Similar trends have been reported in systematic reviews of qualitative dementia research; however, authors suggest that a clear statement of findings is the most important quality indicator for qualitative data synthesis (e.g., O'Rourke *et al.*, 2015).

Figure 1: PRISMA Flow Diagram (Moher *et al.*, 2009) showing citation numbers in each stage of the screening process.

Table 2: Summary of study characteristics.

Article; Location	Study Aim(s)	Research Design; Data Collection; Analysis	Relevant Participants	Relevant Setting(s)	CASP Score
Aud (2002); Missouri, USA ¹	To understand the reasons why people with dementia are discharged from assisted living settings to skilled nursing facilities, focussing on behaviour-environment interactions.	Exploratory qualitative. Ethnographic-style interviews, 45 – 90 minutes. Open coding with findings reported as themes.	14 assisted living administrators.	14 assisted living sites; Housing between 24 and 136 people; 7 not-for-profit, 7 for-profit.	5.5
Aud (2004); Missouri, USA ¹	To understand the reasons why people with dementia are discharged from assisted living settings to skilled nursing facilities, focussing on behaviour.	Exploratory qualitative. Ethnographic-style interviews, 45 – 90 minutes. Open coding with findings reported as themes.	14 assisted living administrators.	14 assisted living sites; Housing between 24 and 136 people; 7 not-for-profit, 7 for-profit.	6.5
Barrett <i>et al.</i> (2020); England, UK	To explore the causes, implications, impact, and outcomes of walking with purpose on the lives of people with dementia.	Mixed methods with qualitative case study component. Structured interviews. Thematic analysis.	3 family members, 8 housing managers.	3 extra care housing and 3 retirement housing sites.	6
Cameron, Johnson, and Evans (2020); England, UK ²	To explore tenants' perceptions and experiences of living in extra care housing, and to consider the advantages and disadvantages of this model.	Longitudinal qualitative. Interviews conducted 4 times over a 20-month period. Thematic analysis.	Study included 51 people living in extra care housing, 7 housing managers, 20 formal caregivers; total number of people with dementia not reported.	4 extra care housing sites, 1 of which dementia specific.	6.5
Evans <i>et al.</i> (2020); England, UK ²	To explore how extra care housing can respond to the	Longitudinal qualitative.	Study included 51 people living in extra care housing, 7 housing managers, 20	4 extra care housing sites, 1 of which dementia specific.	7.5

Article; Location	Study Aim(s)	Research Design; Data Collection; Analysis	Relevant Participants	Relevant Setting(s)	CASP Score
	changing social care needs of people with dementia.	Interviews conducted 4 times over a 20-month period. Thematic analysis.	formal caregivers; total number of people with dementia not reported.		
Evans <i>et al.</i> (2019); England, UK	To explore opportunities, benefits, barriers, and enablers to interaction with nature for people with dementia.	Mixed methods. Qualitative case study component. Interviews. Thematic analysis.	7 people with dementia, 3 housing managers, 4 other staff members including care assistants and activity coordinators.	3 extra care housing sites.	5.5
Evans and Means (2006); England, UK	To understand professional perceptions and practices regarding risk and the desire of people with dementia to remain independent in extra care housing.	Longitudinal, mixed methods with qualitative case study component. Study was conducted over 3 – 5 years, during which, periodic interviews were conducted at 6 case study sites. No information on analysis.	The study involved people with dementia, other tenants, relatives, and health/housing/social care managers; Participant numbers not reported.	6 extra care housing sites.	6
O'Malley <i>et al.</i> (2018); England, UK	To explore wayfinding experiences of older adults with memory difficulties living in a communal retirement development and explore their design preferences.	Exploratory qualitative. Semi-structured interviews. Thematic analysis.	2 people with dementia; Article included 13 people living with memory difficulties, but only two had a dementia diagnosis.	1 retirement housing site; 42 apartments.	10
Rondon-Sulbaran <i>et al.</i> (2020); Northern Ireland, UK ³	To explore informal caregivers' perceptions of technology-enriched supported accommodation for people with dementia and their perceptions of their relatives' experience of	Exploratory qualitative. Semi-structured interviews, 40 – 60 minutes. Thematic analysis.	25 family members, including 11 daughters, 6 sons, 3 wives, 1 friend, 1 granddaughter, 1 niece, 1 sister, 1 sister-in-law.	9 technology-enriched supported accommodation sites; Housing between 12 and 61 people.	10

Article; Location	Study Aim(s)	Research Design; Data Collection; Analysis	Relevant Participants	Relevant Setting(s)	CASP Score
	the move and of life in the scheme.				
Rondon-Sulbaran <i>et al.</i> (2021); Northern Ireland, UK ³	To explore the extent to which person-centred care practices are evident in technology-enriched supported accommodation, and how this can be facilitated using assistive technology.	Exploratory qualitative Semi-structured interviews, 40 – 60 minutes. Thematic analysis.	21 staff members, including 13 support workers, 2 senior support workers, 3 managers, 2 activity coordinators, and 1 team leader.	9 technology-enriched supported accommodation sites; Housing between 12 and 61 people.	10
Stewart-Archer <i>et al.</i> (2016); Western Canada	To define quality of life as characterised by people with dementia.	Mixed methods with qualitative interview component. Semi-structured interviews. Thematic content analysis.	12 people with dementia.	9 supportive seniors' housing sites.	10

Note: Superscripts 1, 2, 3 indicate that articles were based on the same study

A sensitivity analysis was conducted to determine the contribution of each article to the overall synthesis, considering issues of methodological quality (Thomas and Harden, 2008). Contribution to the synthesis appeared to be determined by a trade-off between two factors; 1) high methodological quality, and 2) the amount of data and themes reported of relevance to the review question. Articles with high methodological quality that reported a large amount of data contributed most to the synthesis (Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2021). Articles with lower methodological quality that reported a large amount of data also contributed meaningfully to the synthesis, though to a lesser extent (Aud, 2002; Aud 2004; Barrett *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2019; Evans and Means, 2006). This was largely because the data analysis and reported themes were less developed, a phenomenon consistent with previous thematic syntheses (Thomas and Harden, 2008). Articles reporting a small amount of data (e.g., where people with dementia were a subgroup of the total sample) contributed least to the synthesis, regardless of methodological quality (Cameron, Johnson, and Evans, 2020; O'Malley *et al.*, 2018; Stewart-Archer *et al.*, 2016). These articles still contributed meaningfully to the synthesis, as their participants included people with dementia (O'Malley *et al.*, 2018; Stewart-Archer *et al.*, 2016) and their supporters (Cameron, Johnson, and Evans, 2020), with a limited amount of data available for these participant groups in the included articles.

2.5.4. Thematic Synthesis

The thematic synthesis generated one overarching theme, Maintaining Independence and Autonomy. This was divided into three subthemes – Support and Care, Social Relationships, and The Physical Environment. To illustrate how the overarching theme and subthemes were developed, and to provide further context to the findings, Table 3 shows example codes, data extracts, codes assigned to each extract, and the articles contributing to each theme.

2.5.5. Overarching Theme: Maintaining Independence and Autonomy

All articles, and participant groups, discussed the importance of “independence”, “control”, “freedom”, “choice”, “autonomy”, or “self-determination” for people with dementia in supported housing. “Promoting”, “maximising”, or “supporting” independence and autonomy was highlighted as a central goal of supported housing (Aud, 2002; Aud, 2004; Evans *et al.*, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020), described as the underlying

“philosophy”, “ethos”, or “ideal” of the settings (Aud, 2002; Evans *et al.*, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020). In the context of the included articles, independence focussed more on supporting people with dementia to “do things” for themselves, related to activities of daily living like self-care, shopping, and household management (Aud, 2002; Aud, 2004; Evans *et al.*, 2020; Evans and Means, 2006; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2021; Stewart-Archer *et al.*, 2016). Terms like autonomy, control, choice, and self-determination focussed on the freedom of choosing how, where, and who people with dementia spent their time with, in addition to choosing the level of support required to live independently (Barrett *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2020; Evans and Means, 2006; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2021; Stewart-Archer *et al.*, 2016).

Despite this, articles frequently described barriers to maintaining independence and autonomy, suggesting that these “ideals” are not always evident in practice (Evans *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2019; Stewart-Archer *et al.*, 2016). The three subthemes of Support and Care, Social Relationships, and The Physical Environment, highlight barriers and facilitators to maintaining the independence and autonomy of people with dementia living in supported housing, and form the remainder of the thematic synthesis.

2.5.5.1. Subtheme One: Support and Care

With regard to providing support or care for people with dementia, adopting a person-centred approach was outlined as key to ensuring that the individual can remain in the supported housing setting for as long as possible (Cameron, Johnson, and Evans, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2020; Evans and Means, 2006; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2021). A flexible, person-centred approach was described as essential for enabling people with dementia to maintain their independence and autonomy, discussed by the following care manager working in extra care housing:

Table 3: Illustrating the thematic synthesis process, showing the theme / subthemes, example codes, example data extracts and codes assigned to these, and a breakdown of contributing articles / participant groups.

Overarching Theme	Example Codes	Example Data Extracts / Code(s) Assigned	Articles / Participant Groups Contributing to Theme
Maintaining Independence and Autonomy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Independence • Autonomy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Choice ○ Control ○ Self-Determination • As an ethos / philosophy / ideal of supported housing • Loss of independence / autonomy 	<p>"I ran a good household, raised 8 kids well. What did I do to let them think I can't look after myself? I didn't even get to choose 1 photo, or hang 1 picture here now. I don't need help with anything, but everything is done for you. Everything." (Person with dementia, supportive seniors' housing; Stewart-Archer <i>et al.</i>, 2016, p. 1724). – choice, loss of independence / autonomy</p>	<p><u>People with Dementia</u> (Evans <i>et al.</i>, 2020; Evans <i>et al.</i>, 2019; Evans & Means, 2006; O'Malley <i>et al.</i>, 2018; Stewart-Archer <i>et al.</i>, 2016)</p>
		<p>"They've got a bit of their own independence you know their own room, they can make their breakfast and their tea and their cups of tea when they want it and they can come down to the lounge for stimulation or they can go upstairs and just be themselves." (Family member, extra care housing; Evans & Means, 2006, p. 79). – independence, autonomy</p>	<p><u>Supporters</u> (Cameron, Johnson, & Evans, 2020; Evans & Means, 2006; Rondon-Sulbaran <i>et al.</i>, 2021)</p>
		<p>"...our ethos is more basically trying to promote as much independence with them as possible. So, being more, us standing back and giving them by that to promote, for them to be able to do the things for themselves, to try and keep their minds stimulated." (Formal caregiver, technology-enriched supported accommodation; Rondon-Sulbaran <i>et al.</i>, 2020,</p>	<p><u>Health and Social Care Professionals</u> (Aud, 2002; Aud 2004; Barrett <i>et al.</i>, 2020; Evans <i>et al.</i>, 2020; Evans <i>et al.</i>, 2019; Evans & Means, 2006; Rondon-Sulbaran <i>et al.</i>, 2020)</p>

p. 2297). – as an ethos / philosophy / ideal of supported housing, independence

Subtheme 1	Example Codes	Example Data Extracts / Code(s) Assigned	Articles / Participant Groups Contributing to Subtheme
Support and Care	<p>Facilitators of independence and autonomy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Person-centred support / care • Staff training • Good staff ratios • Good dementia understanding / awareness <p>Barriers to independence and autonomy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of funding • Cost of care • Inadequate staff ratios • Lack of dementia understanding and awareness • Support / care need vs limited availability • Risk averse support / care approaches 	<p>“Well for (a) start off you’re still yourself and that’s what I like, you know, they’re not coming round and saying you’ve gotta... they don’t, but if you ask them anything you want them to do they’ll do it.” (Person with dementia, extra care housing; Evans <i>et al.</i>, 2020, p. 1496). – person-centred support / care</p> <p>“I don’t think there could be a business formula with dementia... [To] care successfully for people that are suffering from dementia requires a slightly different cost approach from the containment that you have in a nursing home facility where people are confined in rooms or beds and there’s a ratio of one to ten or one to 15. Here you’ve got maybe somebody that is in need to go downtown to get to do a message and that stimulus is very important to them and that opportunity for them to get out and engage with the community and have that independence...” (Family member, technology-enriched supported accommodation; Rondon-Sulbaran <i>et al.</i>, 2021, p. 19). – person-centred support / care, good staff ratios</p> <p>“If you’ve got someone with dementia yeah, we will promote independence and I think that’s what we need to focus to promote it, but it’s not that “Oh if she’s here let’s expect her to be independent”</p>	<p><u>People with Dementia</u> (Evans <i>et al.</i>, 2020; Evans & Means, 2006; Stewart-Archer <i>et al.</i>, 2016)</p> <p><u>Supporters</u> (Cameron, Johnson, & Evans, 2020; Evans & Means, 2006; Rondon-Sulbaran <i>et al.</i>, 2021)</p> <p><u>Health and Social Care Professionals</u> (Aud, 2002; Aud 2004; Barrett <i>et al.</i>, 2020; Evans <i>et al.</i>, 2020; Evans <i>et al.</i>, 2019; Evans & Means, 2006; Rondon-Sulbaran <i>et al.</i>, 2020)</p>

		because that's not how it works. They sometimes can do only small things – let them do those small things, if they cannot do the big ones help them and let's see how we go." – (Formal caregiver, extra care housing; Evans <i>et al.</i> , 2020, p. 1497). - person-centred support / care	
Subtheme 2	Example Codes	Example Data Extracts / Code(s) Assigned	Articles / Participant Groups Contributing to Subtheme
Social Relationships	<p>Facilitators of independence and autonomy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relationships with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Family / friends ○ Other residents ○ Staff • Involvement in social activities <p>Barriers to independence and autonomy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social isolation / loneliness • Stigma / prejudice from other residents • Lack of funding / staff to organise activities • Deteriorating health 	<p>"I used to go and meet up with four friends of a Wednesday and have a coffee and hour in town when I was capable, and I used to have – that's with four of my friends – and then another couple of my neighbours we used to have a taxi once or twice a week and go into town regularly and do our shopping. And I miss that." (Person with dementia, extra care housing; Evans <i>et al.</i>, 2020, p. 1500). – relationships with family / friends, social isolation / loneliness, deteriorating health</p> <p>Equally, the social aspect of the facility in terms of activities and encouragement of social life (outside and within the facility) and relationships was also praised by the participants: "But then she's made friends here, too. Which is good, because if she was at home she wouldn't have any of that." (Family member, technology-enriched supported accommodation; Rondon-Sulbaran <i>et al.</i>, 2021, p. 21). – relationships with other family / friends / other residents, involvement in social activities</p> <p>Pressures on staff time were identified by several interviewees as a barrier to supporting connections with nature... one extra care</p>	<p><u>People with Dementia</u> (Evans <i>et al.</i>, 2020; Evans <i>et al.</i>, 2019)</p> <p><u>Supporters</u> (Cameron, Johnson, & Evans, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran <i>et al.</i>, 2021)</p> <p><u>Health and Social Care Professionals</u> (Aud, 2002; Aud 2004; Barrett <i>et al.</i>, 2020; Evans <i>et al.</i>, 2020; Evans <i>et al.</i>, 2019; Rondon-Sulbaran <i>et al.</i>, 2020)</p>

		housing manager had no dedicated activity staff and a lack of time and funding for care staff to support nature-based activities. (Housing manager, extra care housing; Evans <i>et al.</i> , 2019, p. 148). – lack of funding / staff to organise activities	
Subtheme 3	Example Codes	Example Data Extracts / Code(s) Assigned	Articles / Participant Groups Contributing to Subtheme
The Physical Environment	<p>Facilitators of independence and autonomy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dementia friendly design <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Signage ○ Colour contrast ○ Space • Good location within the community • Assistive technology <p>Barriers to independence and autonomy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large buildings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Navigation difficulties • Small communal or dining areas • Small flats / apartments • Poor location within the community • Lack of access to amenities • Lack of funding / training regarding assistive technology 	<p>The location of a scheme, for example, can restrict opportunities for autonomous activity: “Yes, and try to walk up to the local Co-Op or something like that, but I don’t know how far it is. Well, it’s not far up the road. I’ve been in the car and seen it but I don’t just know quite how long it would take me so I’m a bit nervous about risking going up there.” (Person with dementia, extra care housing; Evans <i>et al.</i>, 2020, p. 1498). – poor location within the community, lack of access to amenities</p> <p>“...the apartments are well spaced out, they are not cramped and there are good grounds outside... It’s within a housing estate... It’s just like a wee oasis in the middle of it all.” (Family member, technology-enriched supported accommodation; Rondon-Sulbaran <i>et al.</i>, 2021, p. 19). – space, good location within the community</p> <p>“You know, even their push buttons in bathrooms and stuff, they’re right beside the toilet and they know to press that so I think it gives them confidence as well to live independently as much as they can, that they can go in and use the toilet by themselves... We</p>	<p><u>People with Dementia</u> (Evans <i>et al.</i>, 2020; O’Malley <i>et al.</i>, 2018)</p> <p><u>Supporters</u> (Rondon-Sulbaran <i>et al.</i>, 2021)</p> <p><u>Health and Social Care Professionals</u> (Aud, 2002; Aud 2004; Barrett <i>et al.</i>, 2020; Evans <i>et al.</i>, 2019; Evans & Means, 2006; Rondon-Sulbaran <i>et al.</i>, 2020)</p>

don't have to be there all the time... it's about them being able to do the things without us constantly following them." – Formal caregiver, technology-enriched supported accommodation; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020, p. 2302). – assistive technology

“Extra care for people living with dementia is a great concept. It’s a great way to keep people living independently for that little bit longer, if possible. However, it really does come with its challenges to be able to be flexible like we need to be to support people with dementia. I will say that the team, the care and support workers, are really good in that they know their clients so well. If they do go to somebody who that particular day doesn’t want to go to bed, they’re very good at working together to say, ‘Gertrude is looking like she wants to go to bed in the communal room. Let’s swap this with Gertrude. Let’s move Isabella to her time.’” (Evans *et al.*, 2020, p. 1501).

However, articles highlighted the need for specific staff training to support person-centred care (Cameron, Johnson, and Evans, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2020; Evans and Means, 2006; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020). In situations where training was provided, health and social care staff reported attending training sessions on person-centred dementia care approaches and learning from senior staff and other colleagues (Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020).

Although there was evidence that person-centred care could facilitate the maintenance of independence and autonomy for people with dementia, articles highlighted barriers to delivering adequate and meaningful person-centred care. These included low staff ratios, lack of appropriate funding, a lack of training or understanding of dementia, and costs of delivering care (Aud, 2002; Aud 2004; Cameron, Johnson, and Evans, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2019; Evans and Means, 2006; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020). Issues with staff ratios were discussed by a family member of a person with dementia living in technology-enriched supported accommodation:

“I know there are times where they’re short staffed and they don’t have the time, really, and stuff like that. I think there have been problems when they don’t have the full squad in.” (Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2021, p. 20).

Lack of understanding and training, negative attitudes towards people with dementia, and funding pressures also lead to people with dementia being managed or referred out of supported housing settings, according to the literature (Aud, 2002; Aud 2004; Evans *et al.*, 2020; Evans and Means, 2006). In the article by Aud

(2002), an administrator spoke of managing the support people with dementia received by charging people for additional support with activities of daily living:

“So mainly for the dependent people sometimes like we’ll do eye drops or we’ll do dressings for them for a limited period of time and you know there’s a time factor there. And sometimes we don’t charge and sometimes we do charge them. The main thing, main reason we charge is to try to limit. Not that we want to make money, but to try to limit.” (Aud, 2002, p. 74).

In many instances, it appeared that an over-emphasis on being able to live independently with minimal support, rather than meeting the increasing needs of people with dementia to maximise their independence and autonomy, led to many reports of people with dementia moving into residential care or nursing home settings (Aud, 2002; Aud 2004; Cameron, Johnson, and Evans, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2020; Evans and Means, 2006).

The literature suggests that barriers to person-centred care often result in a risk-averse approach to supporting people with dementia, which is in contrast with the rights-based approaches to housing, support and care emphasised in policy (Aud, 2002; Aud 2004; Barrett *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2020; Evans and Means, 2006). This often related to finding a “balance” between safety and independence, with safety issues relating to falls, misuse of household items, or becoming lost when leaving the settings (Aud, 2002; Aud 2004; Barrett *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2020; Evans and Means, 2006). Articles acknowledged the importance of independence and autonomy, yet an overemphasis on ensuring the safety of people with dementia and minimising risk often led to restrictions on independence and autonomy (Barrett *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2020; Evans and Means, 2006; Stewart-Archer *et al.*, 2016), as discussed by the following person living with dementia in supportive seniors’ housing:

“I want to do more. Not allowed to do much by neither staff nor family. They do it all for you... right down to doing your laundry and putting my photos where they want them. I did this all for years and years.” (Stewart-Archer *et al.*, 2016, p. 1722).

It was suggested that instances of “risky” or “unsafe” behaviours were often rare occurrences (Barrett *et al.*, 2020; Evans and Means, 2006), with risk-averse approaches informed by “anxiety” experienced by health and social care professionals (Evans and Means, 2006). A person-centred approach to managing risk was emphasised as a facilitator of independence and autonomy (Evans and Means, 2006; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020), though settings often lacked appropriate policies or training to implement this in practice (Barrett *et al.*, 2020; Evans and Means, 2006).

There was some evidence to suggest that people with dementia could defer entry into residential care in supported housing settings that utilised a flexible, person-centred approach with a good staffing ratio and dementia-specific training. However, the literature highlights that where person-centred care was not facilitated in the settings, the ideals of maintaining independence and autonomy could not be delivered.

2.5.5.2. Subtheme Two: Social Relationships

The literature emphasised the importance of facilitating relationships between people with dementia and their family members or friends, other residents, and health and social care staff working within the settings. Facilitating relationships, providing opportunities for social interaction, and promoting choice regarding who people with dementia spend their time with, was linked to maintaining independence and autonomy.

Family members and health and social care professionals believed that the supported housing model had advantages over residential care settings, by facilitating familial relationships and enabling family members to adopt caregiving responsibilities (Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2021). Adopting caregiving responsibilities was valued by health and social care staff, as this alleviated pressure caused by low staffing ratios and helped ensure the needs of the person with dementia were met (Aud, 2002; Aud 2004; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020).

In some instances, supported housing was viewed as having fewer restrictions on independence and autonomy, e.g., not operating with highly structured mealtimes or care plans, which might be evident in residential care (Evans *et al.*, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2021). In this context, supported housing was described as a facilitator of family involvement and inclusivity (Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2021). However, apparent barriers to maintaining family

relationships related to the small size of some flats, meaning that family members could not stay overnight in the setting, contributing to feelings of loneliness and isolation (Evans *et al.*, 2020).

Relationships between people with dementia and other residents focussed mainly on engagement in social activities, which provided opportunities for social interaction (Cameron, Johnson, and Evans, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2019; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2021). Activities involved walking, outdoor fayres, tapestry, dominoes, bingo, and mindfulness, art, and music groups (Evans *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2019; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2021). The development of positive relationships with other residents was discussed by people with dementia (Evans *et al.*, 2020), and supporters and health and social care professionals believed that providing opportunities for independent and autonomous engagement in social activities limited social isolation (Evans *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2019; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2021). A person with dementia living in extra care housing discusses their involvement in social activities:

“Yes, we play dominoes and bingo and [pause] I’m doing some tapestry at the moment and knitting squares for a blanket. Yes, yeah. And that was one of the things I really wanted to come for, to join in with the activities.” (Evans *et al.*, 2020, p. 1499).

One article reported that in settings with “good dementia awareness”, other residents would take an active role in supporting people with dementia, e.g., helping them return to their flat if they become lost (Barrett *et al.*, 2020). Though in other instances, residents who did not have dementia held stigmatising or prejudiced views towards those living with dementia, linked to poor understanding or awareness of the condition (Cameron, Johnson, and Evans, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2020), outlined in the following authors’ interpretation.

“Our findings also suggest that despite increasing awareness of dementia, there is still considerable stigma and prejudice amongst other residents. There was some evidence of a lack of understanding about dementia on the part of residents across all four schemes that took part in the study” (Evans *et al.*, 2020, pp. 1498-1499).

This meant that, in some instances, residents without dementia reported not interacting with or speaking to people with dementia, which contributed to social isolation and fewer opportunities for social interaction (Cameron, Johnson, and Evans, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2020). Other barriers to forming social relationships with other residents related to people with dementia becoming isolated in their flat due to poor physical health or limited staff capacity to run activity groups (Evans *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2019). This contributed to limited opportunities for independent and autonomous engagement in the settings (Evans *et al.*, 2020).

Relationships between people with dementia and health and social care staff were often functionally driven, focussed on the provision of support or care and meeting the needs of people with dementia (Aud, 2002; Barrett *et al.*, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2021). However, health and social care staff reported engaging in informal chatting and spending time with people with dementia, in more socially driven interactions, outlined in the following quote from a formal caregiver:

“...there’s the support and the girls, the staff go in and out for a short space of time and do what they need to do. And then if they want to have a chat or sit down, they’ll sit and have a chat with you, but if they don’t, then just go out again.” (Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020, p. 2297).

This was linked to the flexible, person-centred approach to care that some supported housing settings offered, meaning that social relationships could be developed rather than always focussing on the functional aspects of support or care provision (Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020). However, barriers to forming these relationships related to an over-emphasis on “task-oriented” duties and low staff ratios, which limited opportunities for social interaction (Evans *et al.*, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020).

2.5.5.3. Subtheme Three: The Physical Environment

The internal and external physical environments of the supported housing settings and their location within the local community were described as either barriers or facilitators to maintaining the independence and autonomy of people with dementia.

Throughout, design of the interior of the supported housing settings was discussed (Barrett *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2019; O'Malley *et al.*, 2018; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*,

2021). An evident barrier to independence and autonomy was the overall size of the supported housing settings, with larger settings having similar corridors on all floors requiring the use of lifts or stairs to reach higher levels, which created navigation difficulties (O'Malley *et al.*, 2018), outlined in the following quote from a person living with dementia:

“I really think that was badly designed because they do have a long way to come, you know two lifts to have to use. Or two flights of stairs or whatever but not for me because as I say I’m well placed.” (O’Malley *et al.*, 2018, p. 1803).

Strategies to aid independent navigation included hanging familiar photographs at the end of corridors, use of signage, colour contrast, spacious flats and corridors, with frequent seating areas throughout communal areas (Barrett *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2020; O'Malley *et al.*, 2018; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2021). These features are indicative of dementia-friendly design guidelines, however, possible barriers to their implementation related to the prospect of making the setting look “institutional” or unappealing to potential residents and funding limitations (Evans *et al.*, 2020).

Additionally, small communal and dining areas were an evident barrier to social interaction and engagement in social activities (Evans *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2019). In one dementia-specific setting, small dining areas meant that mealtimes had to be staggered due to a lack of seating, meaning that many residents could not eat together (Evans *et al.*, 2020). The dementia-specific setting also had no access to a café, hairdresser, or shop on-site, whereas the non-dementia-specific settings did – again, linked to reduced opportunities for social interaction and independent or autonomous engagement in activities (Evans *et al.*, 2020).

As supported housing aims to promote an open, independent environment, the immediate external environment of the settings (gardens, patios, outdoor communal areas), and the physical location of the settings within the wider community (links to shops, closeness to roads, connections to nature), were frequently discussed (Aud, 2002; Aud 2004; Barrett *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2019). A good location enabled people with dementia to engage independently with their local community, discussed in the following quote from a formal caregiver:

“Some of the tenants just go out shopping, they go to church, they do everything that they would’ve done in their own home; but they’re assessed to see how safe they are on the road. That’s an important assessment because you don’t want to, this is not, you know, this is just supported housing, so we want them to enjoy life and not to be feeling enclosed” (Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020, p. 2298).

In other instances, the physical location of the setting was a barrier to engaging with the local community. This was largely due to limited access to amenities and the proximity to busy roads, leading to a loss of independence and autonomy (Aud, 2004; Barrett *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2020).

Assistive technologies, when used in a non-restrictive, unobtrusive way, could also facilitate independence and privacy (Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020), potentially combating the “risk-averse” approaches to support and care discussed previously. Assistive technologies included alarm systems, sensors, lifestyle monitoring devices, CCTV, mobile phones, and telecare (Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020). When used positively, the assistive technology alerted staff to falls or accidents within the home, whilst enabling the resident to live otherwise independently, highlighted in the following authors’ interpretation:

“...assistive technology enabled formal carers to monitor the execution of simple tasks like making cups of tea or cooking snacks, so that accidents could be prevented while still allowing the person to do things for themselves when they wanted” (Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020, p. 2301).

Use of assistive technology varied throughout the literature, with low uptake and ineffectual use linked to lack of staff knowledge and funding (Barrett *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2020; Evans and Means, 2006).

2.6. Discussion

Drawing from an international evidence base, the present systematic review and thematic synthesis aimed to understand how living in supported housing influences the lives of people with dementia, from the perspectives of people with dementia, their supporters, health, and social care professionals. One overarching theme was generated, Maintaining Independence and Autonomy, divided into three subthemes – Support and Care, Social Relationships, and the Physical Environment.

The reviewed literature included multiple supported housing types, including extra care housing, assisted living, supported accommodation, etc. However, the common aim of these settings was to promote the independence and autonomy of the residents. In previous literature, supported housing has been described as a potential way to support people with dementia to live independently in the community for longer (Brooker *et al.*, 2011; Brown *et al.*, 2017; Dutton, 2009; Fleming *et al.*, 2020; Twyford, 2016). However, the evidence presented in this systematic review shows that a diagnosis of dementia may become a barrier to living independently and autonomously in supported housing, with people referred out of the settings as their condition progressed and care needs increased. A lack of resources, including low staff numbers, limited / no staff training in dementia and dementia care, and limitations in the physical environment appeared to be the main reasons for this. Similar findings have been reported in previous reviews, discussion papers (e.g., Dutton, 2009; Dutton, 2010), and in quantitative research conducted in supported housing settings (e.g., Brooker, Argyle, and Clancy, 2009; Twyford, 2016; Verbeek *et al.*, 2019). These studies questioned if supported housing settings have the resources to support or care for people with dementia beyond the milder stages of the condition.

The international dementia policy imperative emphasises that people with dementia should be enabled to live independently at home or in a homely setting for as long as they wish (Alzheimer Europe, 2018), with access to appropriate housing, health, and social care defined as a human right for people with dementia (United Nations, 2006; World Health Organization, 2015; World Health Organization, 2017). This review suggests that even in housing settings offering integrated support and care, these policy ideals may not reflect the experience of supported housing residents living with dementia. To meet these policy ideals, it is imperative that housing organisations are provided with adequate funding and resources so that support and care can be configured in a way that meets the complex and changing needs of people with dementia.

2.6.1. Limitations in the Evidence Base

An aim of this review was to explore the experience of living in supported housing from the perspectives of people with dementia and their supporters. However, the research reviewed does not adequately present the voice of these groups, with most articles presenting the views of health and social care staff. People with

dementia and their supporters were often a subsample of the participants in the included articles, meaning that the amount of relevant data extracted was often limited. Of note, there was limited evidence regarding what independence and autonomy meant from the perspectives of people with dementia and their supporters, with most data on these concepts collected from health and social care professionals. There was also limited evidence from people with dementia on the care or support received within the settings, their engagement in the social aspects of the settings, and their perspectives on the environmental design. There was limited evidence on the perspectives of people with dementia living in dementia-specific supported housing and settings offering a low level of support, such as sheltered or retirement housing. Future research should explore ways to involve people with dementia and their supporters to express their views.

A further limitation in the evidence base was the overall sparsity of research in the area. Only eleven articles were identified for inclusion in the systematic review. The included articles were conducted in the United Kingdom and North America, meaning that the findings are reflective of those living in these regions. Additionally, segmented publication was evident in articles based on the ECHO study, with five articles uncovered in the systematic search based on the same data (Cameron *et al.*, 2019; Cameron, Johnson and Evans, 2020; Cameron *et al.*, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2020; Johnson *et al.*, 2020). This could potentially distort the findings of the review (Šupak Smolčić, 2013), but effort was made to include the articles of greatest relevance to dementia.

2.6.2. Methodological Limitations

Initially, the review aimed to include unpublished literature. Throughout the review process, it was evident that unpublished reports did not document formal research processes and lacked sufficient detail regarding methodology, recruitment, data collection, and analysis. Given the limited volume and quality of some of the included peer-reviewed articles, the PhD researcher opted to exclude unpublished research from the thematic synthesis to limit any additional review bias. Instead, authors of the unpublished articles were contacted to determine if their findings had been published in a peer-reviewed journal. The review only included articles written in English, meaning that some articles of relevance to the review may have been missed.

2.6.3. Implications and Conclusions

As dementia progresses, it is inevitable that the individual's care and support needs will change (Brown *et al.*, 2020). In terms of housing and support, there is a need to respond to these changes to prevent unnecessary moves out of settings deemed appropriate. Although literature suggests that supported housing can be a suitable housing option for people with dementia (e.g., Fleming *et al.*, 2020), the findings of this review suggest that we are failing to meet the needs of many people living with dementia in supported housing settings.

Future research on supported housing should strive to include the perspectives of people with dementia and their supporters, to better understand how supported housing can facilitate access to health and social care, promote social relationships and community connections, and provide dementia-friendly environments that promote the independence, autonomy, and wellbeing of those living with dementia.

2.7. Chapter Two Summary

This thesis acknowledges the proposition that supported housing can be a positive housing choice for people with dementia, given the integration of housing and social care in these settings (Brown *et al.*, 2017). Despite this, the experience of living with dementia in supported housing is not fully understood, particularly from the perspectives of people living with the condition. To inform the development of the objectives of the empirical stage of this thesis, this chapter sought to provide a rigorous review and critique of the current evidence base relating to the experience of living with dementia in supported housing. The review shows that although supported housing has been highlighted as an appropriate housing model for people with dementia, this is not always evidenced in practice. In many instances, settings appeared to lack the resources to adequately meet the needs of people with dementia, often resulting in a move to a care or nursing home. Methodological limitations were also outlined in the literature, relating to poor descriptions of methodologies and methods. There was also limited application of theory in the research, and no research has been conducted in Scotland at the time of writing. Having developed a fuller understanding of the qualitative evidence base relating to the experience of living with dementia in supported housing, from the perspectives of people living with the condition, their supporters, and health and social care professionals, the aim and

objectives for this research were developed. Chapter Three will provide an overview of the aim and objectives, together with an in-depth discussion of theoretical and conceptual literature that can help inform interpretations made throughout the empirical stage of the thesis.

Chapter Three: Theoretical and Conceptual Perspectives

3.1. Introduction to Chapter Three

Drawing from the literature discussed in Chapters One and Two, the purpose of Chapter Three is to first present the aim and objectives of the empirical component of this thesis. The theoretical underpinnings that have influenced the research, relating to the aim and objectives under study, are then outlined. Finally, based on this theoretical literature, a conceptual framework is presented. The conceptual framework seeks to support and structure the analytical process, contributing to the development of theory in the context of living with dementia in supported housing. It should be noted that the role of theory in this study is not to test or assess how accurate a theory is at describing phenomena. Rather, this research will take an inductive approach, with theory used as “lenses” to support the interpretation of findings and advance our understanding of the experience of living with dementia in supported housing.

Barriers and facilitators that influence the maintenance of independence and autonomy, for people living with dementia in supported housing, are outlined in Chapter Two. To illustrate, factors like the provision of person-centred care, creating opportunities for social interactions, and the application of dementia-friendly design principles in supported housing settings, acted as facilitators of independence and autonomy. However, low staff ratios, the stigmatising views of other tenants or homeowners, and limited staff training on dementia, acted as barriers to independence and autonomy. These barriers and facilitators were conceptualised within an overarching theme, Maintaining Independence and Autonomy, made of three subthemes: 1) Support and Care, 2) Social Relationships, and 3) The Physical Environment.

As concluded in Chapter Two, the experiences of those living with dementia in supported housing, relating to independence and autonomy and the above subthemes, are poorly understood in the literature. Further gaps were outlined. For example, no peer-reviewed, published research has focussed on dementia and supported housing in Scotland, and there is limited research that compares the experiences of those living in different models of supported housing. An additional limitation of the literature is that there is minimal application of theory, either through theoretical or conceptual frameworks, that can contribute to our

understanding of findings and the experience of living with dementia in supported housing (Miles, Huberman and Saldaña, 2018).

Failure to apply theory means that the interpretation of findings can be limited. This is because theory can help researchers, and others, understand or explain why phenomena may occur (Reeves *et al.*, 2008). For example, it has been established that the experience of living with dementia in supported housing is influenced by many things, relating to policy, practice, and wider societal issues. In Chapter Two, the reviewed literature showed that many people with dementia are moved from their homes in supported housing, due to issues like limited resources, poor environmental design, and a lack of dementia awareness. Hence, applying theories can help develop an understanding of the ways we can improve environmental design, dementia awareness, and the best ways to deliver support and care for people living with dementia.

The findings of the systematic review in Chapter Two helped inform the development of the central aim of the empirical study. This chapter will explore theoretical perspectives and presents the conceptual framework underpinning the thesis. Such a conceptual framework supports the research to be bounded and focussed, concentrating on what is most important regarding the topics of study. This framing is important in the context of multiple-case study research, which can include large data sets giving rise to data overload, limiting comparability (Miles, Huberman and Saldaña, 2018). In this regard, the conceptual framework has been abstracted from wider literature relating to housing and dementia, of relevance to the findings outlined in Chapter Two.

3.2. Problem Statement and Aim

Chapter Two demonstrates that the benefits and challenges of living with dementia in supported housing are not fully understood, particularly from the perspectives of those living with the condition. Hence, this study's aim is:

To develop an in-depth understanding of the experience of living with dementia in supported housing in Scotland.

This will provide much needed information about the potential of supported housing to facilitate access to health and social care, to promote social relationships and community connections, and to provide dementia-friendly environments that promote the independence and autonomy of those living with dementia.

3.3. Objectives

The aim will be met through the following objectives:

Objective one: To understand how support or care is delivered in supported housing settings to meet the needs of people living with dementia.

Objective two: To understand how living in supported housing impacts social relationships and community connections for people living with dementia.

Objective three: To understand how the physical environments of supported housing settings enable people living with dementia to maintain their independence.

Objective four: To understand perspectives on supported housing as a future housing choice for people living with dementia.

3.4. Theoretical Perspectives

The systematic review in Chapter Two identified key concepts, relating to supported housing and dementia, which will be explored in greater detail throughout this thesis. The review highlighted a lack of theoretical understanding regarding these concepts. Hence, this led to the development of an exploratory conceptual framework, which will be detailed within this chapter. This framework aims to enhance interpretations and develop a theoretical basis for future research, without making claims of causality. The conceptual framework is grounded in theoretical literature, discussed in Sections 3.4.1 - 3.4.4. (summarised in Figure 2). It emphasises independence and autonomy, defined as functional independence and self-determination, respectively (Smith *et al.*, 2022). These concepts were added to the framework as the underlying goal of supported housing is to support people to maintain their independence and autonomy (Smith *et al.*, 2022). The framework also incorporates concepts from person-centred care models and Kitwood's theory of personhood, to understand how person-centred support and care are delivered in these contexts (Kitwood,

1997; Kitwood and Brooker, 2019; McCormack and McCance, 2006; McCormack et al., 2010; McCormack and McCance, 2017). This is because person-centred care has been described as essential for ensuring that people with dementia can continue living in supported housing (Smith *et al.*, 2022). Expanding on personhood, concepts from social citizenship theory are incorporated to understand the societal and political influences on individuals living with dementia in supported housing (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010). As people living in supported housing are classed as independent citizens, living in self-contained homes, this is an important consideration (Smith *et al.*, 2022). Social citizenship theory allows for a greater understanding of how people with dementia experience the social aspects of supported housing, in addition to wider societal, political, and community-based influences (Smith *et al.*, 2023). Finally, the framework considers environmental concepts, based on Lawton's environmental press-competence model and subsequent works (Lawton and Nahemow, 1973; Wahl, Iwarsson, and Oswald, 2012), suggesting that interactions between person-environment resources affect identity, wellbeing, and autonomy. Although it has been acknowledged that the environment has a key role in enabling people to live independently in supported housing, the physical environments of supported housing settings have not been examined in detail within the current research evidence base (Smith *et al.*, 2022). Overall, the conceptual framework contends that the above concepts and theories contribute to the likelihood that a person with dementia can continue living in supported housing, which will be explored in detail throughout this thesis. This chapter now discusses the theories that contributed to the development of the conceptual framework, before presenting the conceptual framework in Section 3.5.

3.4.1. Independence and Autonomy

The overarching theme developed in Chapter Two relates to the maintenance of independence and autonomy, often cited as the underlying aim or goal of supported housing services. In this regard, independence meant supporting people with dementia to do things for themselves around their home, with an emphasis on activities of daily living. Autonomy focussed on choice, control, and self-determination, emphasising the importance of enabling people with dementia to choose how, where, or with whom to spend their time.

Figure 2: An overview of the study's aim, topics of study, and related theories, discussed throughout this Chapter. The theories that will be discussed relate to personhood (Kitwood, 1997; Kitwood and Brooker, 2019), person-centred support and care (McCormack and McCance, 2006; McCormack *et al.*, 2010; McCormack and McCance, 2017), social citizenship (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010), the environmental press-competence model (Lawton and Nahemow, 1973), and the integrative framework of ageing well (Wahl, Iwarsson and Oswald, 2012). As the concept of independence and autonomy permeates through all topics of study, definitions of independence and autonomy will be developed.

Resultantly, independence and autonomy permeated through all the findings and related subthemes. For example, functional independence in the home, regarding receiving support and care, engaging in independent social activity, and independently navigating the settings and local communities. Although the promotion of independence and autonomy was viewed positively, those living with dementia were often managed or referred out of settings as their needs increased. There often appeared to be an overemphasis on being able to live independently with minimal support, as opposed to meeting the needs of individuals to maximise their independence and autonomy. As these concepts are central to the overall research study, it is first necessary to discuss how these concepts will be defined, with reference to relevant literature.

3.4.1.1. Defining Independence

Regarding independence, broader dementia research and practice often focusses on assessing the extent to which individuals can independently conduct activities of daily living. These range from activities such as grooming, dressing, or eating, often referred to as basic activities of daily living (Barros *et al.*, 2023; Giebel *et*

al., 2014; Katz, 1983), through to more instrumental or complex activities of daily living, like managing finances, shopping, and using transport (Lawton and Brody, 1969; Mao *et al.*, 2018; Sikkes *et al.*, 2012; Sikkes *et al.*, 2013). Hence, basic activities of daily living relate to the skills required to meet basic human needs, whereas instrumental activities of daily living relate to activities that enable individuals to live independently at home and in the community (Mlinac and Feng, 2016). As a person with dementia's condition progresses, there is often an increased need for support and care to conduct such activities (Janssen *et al.*, 2020). To varying degrees, the underlying goal of supported housing is to provide help with activities of daily living, to enable people to live independently at home and interact with their local community (Irving-Clarke, 2019). Hence, conceptualising independence in a way that reflects an individual's ability to conduct activities of daily living, like washing, cooking, or interacting with the local community, can help with the development of an understanding of the experience of living with dementia in supported housing.

Independence is important to consider for several reasons. Within the Scottish context, the Charter of Rights for people with dementia and their carers states that such individuals have the right to live as independently as possible in the community, with appropriate access to support and care services to accommodate this (Cross-Party Group in the Scottish Parliament on Alzheimer's, 2009). Indeed, discussion on human rights and independent living permeates through Scotland's most recent dementia and housing strategies (Scottish Government, 2021; Scottish Government, 2023). At a wider level, the United Nations state that access to housing, health, and social care are human rights (United Nations, 2006). Resultantly, Goal 11 of the United Nation's Sustainable Development Goals states that housing environments should be inclusive and safe (United Nations, 2023).

However, drawing from the evidence discussed in Chapter Two, the extent to which supported housing services have the resources to meet the needs of people with dementia is unclear. Enabling independent living, with access to appropriate support and care, does not appear to be a reality for all people with dementia living in supported housing. This, therefore, is an infringement of these individual's human rights. The purpose of discussing human rights here is to acknowledge the importance of independence in the

context of dementia and supported housing. Human rights will be discussed and conceptualised further when discussing social citizenship in Section 3.4.3.1.

Evidently, assessment tools for independence (e.g., Katz, 1983; Lawton and Brody, 1969) are dated, and do not capture a broad range of activities, or the subjective, context dependent nature of what it means to be independent. The present research study will facilitate the development of a greater understanding of what it means to live independently with dementia in supported housing, and the conditions that support or hinder this. As much of the supported housing literature describes independence in relation to activities of daily living, in the present study, independence is defined as an individual's ability to conduct the activities required to meet basic human needs, in addition to more complex activities that enable individuals to live independently at home and engage with the community.

3.4.1.2. Defining Autonomy

Although linked to independence, discussions surrounding autonomy often move beyond the task-oriented, functional view of conducting activities, to having the choice and control over where, when, and with whom these activities are conducted (de Waal, 2014). Chapter Two demonstrates that, in some instances, factors like the provision of flexible, person-centred care, family relationships, and a good location in the community, could maximise autonomy. This was because individuals could choose when they received support and care throughout the day, with greater opportunities for social and community engagement. Though, this was not always evident, with many people living with dementia experiencing a loss of autonomy due to a lack of resources and limited staff training regarding dementia.

Although not linked directly to supported housing, other research involving people with dementia has sought to define the meaning of autonomy for this population. For example, a Q-methodology study involving people with dementia, their family caregivers, and health professionals described three factors that were indicative of autonomy for people with dementia (Wolfe *et al.*, 2021). For this sample, autonomy reflected shared decision making and self-expression, being supported by family to make decisions, and having opportunities for social interaction (Wolfe *et al.*, 2021). Although there is some overlap with the findings outlined in Chapter Two, how these concepts manifest in the context of supported housing is unclear. That

is, should an individual wish, how can they be supported to make decisions and express themselves, maintain relationships with family, or engage in social interactions within supported housing settings? It may be stated that such questions have an added layer of complexity in the context of supported housing, with settings being shared with other tenants or homeowners, and places of work for housing, health, and social care professionals. This study allows for such phenomena to be explored.

Regarding policy and strategy, the Scottish Charter of Rights for people with dementia and their carers reiterates that autonomy is a human right, defined as the freedom to make one's own choices (Cross-Party Group in the Scottish Parliament on Alzheimer's, 2009). The charter states that autonomy should be enhanced with appropriate access to supports, legal services, and care. Again, the Scottish Government's recent housing and dementia strategies discuss human rights, autonomy, and choice throughout, regarding where an individual wants to live and the support or care they wish to receive (Scottish Government, 2021; Scottish Government, 2023). Although this is acknowledged, equal access to services is not evident throughout Scotland, with many people with dementia having little choice regarding access to appropriate housing, support, and care (Feeley, 2021; Public Health Scotland, 2020).

A further consideration here is the impact that dementia can have on decision making abilities. Dementia can impact the retaining of information, judgement, mood, and language use, among other functions, that can impact autonomy (de Waal, 2014). In such instances, individuals can be assessed as lacking capacity, that is, the ability to process, understand, and retain information to inform decision making (Curtice and Exworthy, 2010). Individuals should be supported to make decisions where possible, or, supported with advance care planning in accordance with legislation, for example, the Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act 2000. However, the literature discussed in Chapter Two notes that individuals with dementia can experience a lack of choice and control in supported housing, for example, regarding the decoration of their home or involvement in support or care related decisions. This may be a byproduct of a wider societal stigma relating to dementia, viewing individuals with dementia as being incapable of making decisions for themselves (Bosco *et al.*, 2019a). Poor dementia awareness, stigma, and prejudice were outlined as barriers to autonomy for people living with dementia in supported housing in Chapter Two.

Hence, the present study views autonomy as the making of self-determined choices, and having control over where, when and with whom to spend one's time. It also views autonomy as a fundamental human right, particularly regarding accessing appropriate housing, health, and social care, that enables individuals to live independently and autonomously in the community for as long as they wish. This is a key consideration in the context of supported housing, which seeks to support individuals to live independently and autonomously and contribute to civic life (Irving-Clarke, 2019). The present research study will facilitate the development of a greater understanding of what it means to live autonomously with dementia in supported housing and explore the conditions that support or hinder this.

3.4.2. Support and Care

Supported housing research, discussed in Chapter Two, emphasises the importance of the provision of person-centred support and care for people living with dementia. The benefits of person-centredness relate to its consideration of the needs of the individual, with supports provided flexibly, and the opportunity to increase support or care if needed. However, this was not always evident in practice, due to low staff ratios, limited dementia-focussed training and awareness, and resource limitations. A major limitation of much of the literature was simply stating that person-centred support and care should be provided in supported housing, without providing much evidence or guidance of what this would look like in practice.

Articles with the greatest depth of discussion surrounding person-centredness and supported housing (Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2021) applied McCormack and colleague's person-centred practice framework to their analyses (McCormack and McCance, 2006; McCormack *et al.*, 2010; McCormack and McCance, 2017). The framework notes that; external factors (e.g., health and social care policy); carer attributes (e.g., competence and interpersonal skills); the care environment (e.g., the physical environment and decision-making systems), and; the process of care delivery (e.g., through caring activities that consider the care recipients' beliefs and values), contribute to positive person-centred outcomes, like good care experiences and enhanced wellbeing (McCormack and McCance, 2017). Although such areas are important considerations in supported housing settings, it may be stated that they hold more relevance in the context of caring or nursing environments.

Supported housing services offer differing levels of support and care, influenced by the supported housing model. For example, those living in extra care housing will likely receive a higher level of care than those living in sheltered or retirement housing (Beach, 2018). Further, those living with dementia in supported housing are homeowners or tenants living in the community, and not always recipients of support or care. Nor are these individuals required to disclose information about their diagnoses. Although it is important to meet increased support or care needs, as required, the provision of care is not the only consideration. Chapter Two acknowledges other areas of support that are important in supported housing settings, for example, when decorating the home, with gardening, repairs, and domestic chores, or the conducting of safety checks for kitchen appliances.

Of relevance to dementia is literature concerning personhood, which had a significant impact on the development of such person-centred care models. Kitwood's seminal work on personhood and dementia defines personhood as a standing or status attributed to an individual, that is contextually defined by social structures and relationships (Kitwood, 1997). This work sought to move away from social perceptions of dementia that focussed predominantly on the dementia diagnosis, concerning an individual's cognitive abilities and how productive they can be in society (Swinton, 2021). Indeed, such values are ingrained in Western culture, with value often placed on cognitive abilities and productivity over other attributes (Swinton, 2021). Individuals like Kitwood contend that what it means to be a person stretches beyond this, with changes to cognitive functioning or other abilities not signifying a loss of personhood (Kitwood, 1997).

As noted, Kitwood believes that personhood is bestowed on an individual by others, emphasising a relational aspect to the concept. With the right conditions and relationships in place, those living with dementia can lead lives that are laden with their own values, meaning, purpose, and dignity (Swinton, 2021). Hence, person-centred dementia care focusses on the values, meaning, and purpose that an individual attributes to their life and caters support and care to reflect these, rather than simply concentrating on task-oriented, medicalised practice (Kitwood, 1997). However, much like the ideals discussed in policy and practice, that are not always experienced by people with dementia (e.g., the promotion of independence and autonomy in supported housing), those living with dementia can lose their personhood. The relational focus of person-

centred care means that those living with dementia can be subject to stigma or being denied the opportunity for choice and control, due to the values held by others and society (Swinton, 2021). Some of the literature discussed in Chapter Two noted that those living with dementia could be subject to stigmatising views held by other tenants or homeowners living in supported housing settings or were subject to risk-averse care practices because of poor dementia awareness and understanding.

Regardless, Kitwood's work on shifting the narrative from seeing the condition, to seeing the person, has continued to evolve through various person-centred dementia care models. For example, Brooker, colleague of Kitwood, proposed a number of components of person-centred care, with indicators that support integration of these components in practice (Brooker, 2007; Kitwood and Brooker, 2019). Such components (and indicators) are, 1) valuing care providers (e.g., by supporting staff development), 2) individualised care (e.g., by incorporating individuals' preferences and routines in care), 3) perspective of the person with dementia (e.g., by being empathetic), and 4) social environment (e.g., being respectful and creating a sense of community) (Brooker, 2007). Indeed, the application of person-centred care in various environments, including extra care housing, has shown improvements to outcomes like quality of life for people living with dementia (Brooker *et al.*, 2011; Kim and Park, 2017). However, reiterating previous discussion in relation to McCormack and colleagues' person-centred practice framework, it may be argued that living with dementia in supported housing has unique considerations, and instead, such models apply more to care or nursing environments, or those living with a higher level of need.

It has been noted that those living with dementia in supported housing are tenants or homeowners who live in the community, and not always recipients of support or care (Brown *et al.*, 2017). Although having access to support and care, when needed, is key to enabling people with dementia to live in supported housing for longer, shown in Chapter Two, discussions of person-centred care, in relation to personhood, concentrate more on the provision of direct care. However, this may not be of relevance to the person with dementia living in supported housing, who lives life as an independent citizen, partaking in hobbies, looking after their self-contained home, travelling, going shopping, and engaging with their local community. Hence, building on the supported housing literature discussed in Chapter Two, the present study will be cognizant of key

components of personhood and person-centred care (Kitwood, 1997; Kitwood and Brooker, 2019; McCormack and McCance, 2006; McCormack *et al.*, 2010; McCormack and McCance, 2017), and how they manifest in supported housing settings. However, by also acknowledging that those living with dementia in supported housing are citizens, who manage their own homes and engage with their local community, there is more to consider. In this regard, this chapter will now discuss social citizenship theory.

3.4.3. Social Relationships and Community Connections

Chapter Two noted that the maintenance of social relationships with family members or friends, other tenants, or homeowners, and with housing, health, and social care professionals, could enhance the independence and autonomy of those living with dementia in supported housing. Further, the location of the setting within the local community was key to enhancing the likelihood that those living with dementia could engage with their local community. However, the literature noted that barriers like limited staff awareness or understanding of dementia, stigma, and poor physical health and mobility, could contribute to social isolation and loneliness, thus impacting independence and autonomy. Although the literature acknowledged the importance of social relationships and access to the community, discussion was often surface level. For example, there was no in-depth discussion of how those living with dementia engaged with their local community, and discussion of social relationships with family members, friends, and other tenants or homeowners typically focussed on the organisation of social activities by staff members. Hence, building on aspects of personhood and person-centred approaches to support and care, it is important to understand how those living with dementia in supported housing can maintain or develop social relationships and community connections, and remain as active social citizens.

3.4.3.1. Social Citizenship

The work of Bartlett, O'Connor and colleagues (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2007; Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010) has brought discussion of social citizenship and dementia to the fore. Their work sought to add a greater layer of depth to discussions of personhood and person-centred care in dementia, that often focus on immediate caring contexts, without wider considerations of the political and social structures that impact the lives of those living with dementia (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2007). Hence, social citizenship is underpinned by

the human right to freedom from discrimination and having opportunities to grow as an individual, participating in civic life as far as possible. It is concerned with justice, social positions, upholding personhood, and human rights, acknowledging that those living with dementia are citizens who can shape events, both within personal contexts and at a broader societal level (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010; O'Connor *et al.*, 2022). Although the importance of personhood and person-centred care is acknowledged in the supported housing literature, it is important to also consider the wider societal impacts that may accompany living in a self-contained home in the community. To reiterate, not all those living with dementia in supported housing are recipients of support and care, though it may be likely that their needs for support and care will increase. Hence, for this research, it is helpful to consider the provision of support and care in supported housing through personhood and person-centred perspectives and consider social relationships and community connections through a social citizenship perspective.

Bartlett and O'Connor (2010) present a continuum of concepts that are central to social citizenship theory. This continuum takes Kitwood's (1997) concepts of person-centred care, which outline the main psychological needs of people living with dementia, extending these to concepts that are of relevance to social citizenship. Although central to many people's experiences of living with dementia, the aim is to extend these concepts beyond only focussing on the provision of care, to viewing those living with dementia as social citizens. The continuum is outlined below in Figure 3, followed by a discussion of such concepts and their relevancy to the present study.

Figure 3: The continuum of concepts of social citizenship, extending Kitwood's (1997) framework for dementia care, to concepts that emphasise agency, rights, and competency, in keeping with social citizenship. Adapted from Bartlett and O'Connor (2010), p. 40.

3.4.3.1.1. From Comfort to Growth

Kitwood (1997) views comfort as the experience of human tenderness and warmth, in addition to feeling physically and emotionally secure, safe from harm or threat. In addition, social citizenship emphasises the

importance of having opportunities to grow, recognising a person's inner hopes, desires, and capacity to contribute to everyday life (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010; O'Connor *et al.*, 2022). The emphasis is not only on the experience of comfort and security, as discussed by Kitwood (1997). To illustrate, growth can occur through developing relationships, or involvement in social groups. The concept aims to move away from the narrative of loss and despair that might accompany a diagnosis of dementia. As demonstrated in Chapter Two, concepts like safety, security, and familiarity are key considerations in supported housing settings for people living with dementia. However, it was also evident that community engagement, access to amenities and nature, and involvement in social activities, both within and outside of the settings, were important. Hence, social citizenship theory can facilitate an exploration of factors like comfort and security in supported housing settings, whilst also acknowledging growth and contributions to everyday life, reflecting an individuals' desires.

3.4.3.1.2. From Identity to Social Positions

Discussions about identity, in the context of dementia, have often focussed on a loss of self, with debate around whether those living with dementia can retain a sense of identity as their condition progresses (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010; O'Connor *et al.*, 2022). Kitwood (1997) challenged these discussions, viewing the loss of identity as a hazard of poor support or care, rather than an inevitability of living with dementia.

Adding to this, social citizenship posits that identity is fluid, not fixed (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010; O'Connor *et al.*, 2022). Identity can often be viewed as a fixed set of characteristics, with changes to these characteristics symbolising a loss of self or identity. However, the concept of social positions recognises that people have multiple identities that can change. For example, mother, church member, supported housing resident, while also acknowledging power dynamics and status. Although Chapter Two outlined the importance of social relationships and community connections in supported housing, there is limited discussion in the research literature regarding the development of new, or evolution of existing relationships, or changes to social positions that may occur when living with dementia in supported housing. As stated previously, supported housing settings are places of work, often containing communal and shared areas, in addition to self-contained dwellings. Hence, social and power dynamics in such settings, and how they

manifest, warrants further study. To illustrate, Chapter Two notes that those living with dementia in supported housing settings could experience stigma from others, risk-averse care practices, and management or referrals out of settings, due to their dementia diagnosis. However, they could also experience positives through, for example, involvement in social activities. This study will provide further learnings regarding the promotion of identity and the manifestation of social positions in the context of living with dementia in supported housing.

3.4.3.1.3. From Occupation to Purpose

Kitwood (1997) places emphasis on occupation and involvement in organised activities, like cooking classes or reminiscence sessions, in his discussion surrounding person-centred care. There is a focus on the therapeutic or psychological value of being involved in such activities. However, a focus on simply doing activities may not always represent what is important to the individual. Social citizenship focusses on the meaning and purpose of life, emphasising the importance of understanding what has meaning and purpose to the individual (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010; O'Connor *et al.*, 2022). Although involvement in organised activities is an important aspect of living with dementia in supported housing (Smith *et al.*, 2022), social citizenship emphasises involvement in everyday activities, for example, shopping, going to the library, or partaking in other community-based activities (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010). Given that supported housing emphasises the promotion of independence, autonomy, and living in the community, these considerations are important. Chapter Two noted that a benefit of supported housing was that the provision of support and care or the scheduling of mealtimes was not highly regimented. This meant that those living in the settings could come and go as they pleased and be visited by family or friends at any time. Though, it was also evident that those living with dementia could face limited choice and control, regarding what to eat, the decoration of their homes, or could be limited by the setting's poor location in the community, contributing to social isolation. This study will allow for a greater understanding of the involvement of people with dementia in activities within supported housing settings, in addition to involvement in everyday or community-based activities that have meaning and purpose for the individual.

3.4.3.1.4. From Inclusion to Participation

According to Bartlett and O'Connor (2010), inclusion, in the context of person-centred dementia care, has typically focused on involvement in care decisions. In this regard, inclusivity can often mean being a presence when care decisions are made, rather than actively participating in such decisions. Participation relates more to continued working, learning, and acting following a diagnosis of dementia. It emphasises more than just inclusion, rather, the human right to participate in life in whatever way possible, central to living as an active social citizen. The concept focusses on agency and control, and raises discourse with regard to capacity issues, that can risk exclusion from participating in society (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010' O'Connor *et al.*, 2022). In more recent conceptualisations of citizenship in dementia, participation has been closely linked to agency and autonomy, where agency is related to the process of acting, and autonomy is linked to the status of being an independent citizen (O'Connor *et al.*, 2022). In this regard, promoting social citizenship involves the preservation and maintenance of people with dementia's abilities, and their capacity to act, for as long as possible, whilst acknowledging that an individual's needs and abilities may change through the progression of their dementia (O'Connor *et al.*, 2022).

In Chapter Two, it was evident that factors like resource limitations, and poor dementia awareness or understanding, could contribute to risk-averse care practices, and, ultimately, people with dementia being managed or referred out of supported housing settings to receive care elsewhere. Here, there was often an overemphasis on being able to live independently, as opposed to increasing support or care provision to enable individuals to live independently and autonomously as their needs increase. Although the human right to accessing appropriate support and care and housing, and involvement in care decisions, is espoused in Scottish housing and dementia policy, strategy, and wider human rights literature (Cross-Party Group in the Scottish Parliament on Alzheimer's, 2009; Scottish Government, 2021; Scottish Government, 2023a; United Nations, 2006), it appears that those living in supported housing may face limitations regarding the support or care received, risking exclusion from such settings. Hence, through a social citizenship lens, this research can enhance our understanding of the ways in which those living with dementia can participate in life within supported housing settings, in addition to society more widely, and the conditions that support or hinder this.

3.4.3.1.5. From Attachment to Solidarity

In the context of person-centred care, attachment is viewed as an emotional bond with someone or something (Kitwood, 1997). It explains actions and experiences in emotional terms, for example, psychological connectedness. Social citizenship theory posits that attachment to someone or thing risks placing power with that someone or thing, rather than with the person with dementia (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010). In this regard, solidarity focusses on broader socio-political connectedness, community responsibilities, and connectedness to other people with dementia, rather than only focussing on emotional connectedness (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010; O'Connor *et al.*, 2022). In the context of research literature, oriented towards the experience of living with dementia in supported housing, both concepts of attachment and solidarity are largely unexplored. For example, psychological connectedness to a particular location, or staying within a community that is familiar to the individual with dementia, is not readily discussed. Though, it is acknowledged that limitations regarding choice and demand for supported housing means that many individuals cannot live in settings of their pleasing (Scottish Government, 2021). Further, regarding solidarity, Chapter Two noted that in settings that promoted dementia awareness, other tenants and homeowners living within the settings would support those living with dementia if they became lost. Though, it was more readily reported that those living with dementia were subject to stigmatising views. Connectedness and solidarity within the community is linked to active social citizenship (O'Connor *et al.*, 2022), hence, the present study will allow for the development of a greater understanding of these concepts, and how they manifest for people living with dementia in supported housing.

3.4.3.1.6. From Love to Freedom from Discrimination

Kitwood (1997) describes love as feelings of being cared for, cherished, and respected. Social citizenship acknowledges the risk that love might be displayed as dependence. For example, in care environments where carers can have more power, with the rights of the person with dementia being curtailed (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010). Rather, the social citizenship approach emphasises freedom from societal and interpersonal discrimination in all aspects of life. This feeds directly into discussions surrounding human rights, stigma, choice, and control that are evident throughout this section. This study will allow for an

exploration of feelings of love and respect, but also an unpacking of issues regarding stigma, and an unequal distribution of power that may be evident in such settings.

In sum, rather than refuting work focussing on personhood and person-centred care, social citizenship compliments such theories, cognizant of wider societal structures, social relationships, power, agency, and autonomy. Personhood and person-centred care models offer insight into the provision of support and care in supported housing settings, while social citizenship focusses more on relational dynamics and involvement of those living with dementia, both within supported housing settings and the local community. A further consideration, however, is the immediate physical environments of the supported housing settings and the potential impact they may have on the lives of people with dementia, their family members or friends, and housing, health, and social care staff.

3.4.4. The Physical Environment

Chapter Two outlined that the internal and external physical environments of supported housing settings could act as barriers or facilitators of independence and autonomy for those living with dementia. In this regard, the overall size and design of settings could hinder independence and autonomy. For example, some settings were viewed as difficult to navigate, and others had small dining and communal areas, which limited opportunities for social engagement. In some settings, assistive technologies could enhance privacy for those living in the settings, as they negated the need for frequent check-ins. However, assistive technologies were not implemented in all settings, due to resource limitations and a lack of training regarding their use. Further, Chapter Two demonstrated that navigation or orientation difficulties, linked to “wandering” or walking with purpose, could lead to those living with dementia being managed or referred out of settings. The extent to which this was caused by poor design was not explored in detail in the supported housing literature, and no formal theories relating to ageing and the environment were applied in any of the studies outlined in Chapter Two. Theories, particularly those developed by, and emanating from, the work of Lawton and colleagues, posit that poorly designed environments can create difficulties with adaptation or familiarisation, and impact the quality of life and psychological wellbeing of older people and those living with dementia. Hence, to expand on this area of the supported housing and dementia literature, this study will draw on such theories.

3.4.4.1. Environmental Press-Competence Model

The Environmental Press-Competence Model (Lawton and Nahemow, 1973) contends that physical and social environmental demands (environmental press) interact with an individual's competency to meet such demands, influencing how well the individual adapts to their environment. Competence is influenced by an individual's biological health, sensation and perception, motor behaviour, and cognition (Lawton, 1983). Lawton (1983) structured such competencies into a hierarchy, ranging from organ, cellular, and functional health, through to higher order competencies relating to time use and social behaviour, such as creativity, nurturance, or intimacy. In this regard, an individual with low competencies, occupying an environment with strong physical and social demands, may experience negative affect and maladaptive behaviour. In the same regard, an individual with high competence, occupying an environment with weak physical and social demands, can also experience negative affect and maladaptive behaviour. Hence, balancing competencies and environmental press can lead to positive affect, provide comfort, or maximise performance potential (Lawton and Nahemow, 1973). Ultimately, improvements to environmental quality can enhance behavioural competence. Lawton states that purpose-built housing for older people should incorporate social and physical design features that improve competence, for example, avoiding the development of multi-storey housing schemes that are difficult to navigate, or increasing activity by housing individuals of similar ages near one another (Lawton, 1983).

Relatedly, Lawton drew from wider literature to document environmental barriers and facilitators, referred to as outcomes, that impact the quality of life of people living with Alzheimer's disease (Lawton, 2001). This study focussed on nursing home environments. Nonetheless, there is considerable overlap with previous discussions on supported housing, outlining the importance of, for example, the promotion of autonomy, individuality, relationships, safety and security, and functional competence (independence) for people with Alzheimer's disease (Lawton, 2001). Such outcomes can be improved through architecture, environmental psychology, and interior design, with design features being assessed using dementia-oriented environmental assessment tools (Lawton *et al.*, 2000; Lawton, 2001).

Although some of Lawton's discussion on good dementia design and adaptations is dated, such as the placing of mirrors over doors to prevent people living with dementia from leaving buildings (Lawton, 2001), he nonetheless drove forward research that acknowledges the impact that the physical environment has on those living with dementia. From this work has stemmed assessments of dementia-friendly design in supported housing environments, focussing on social interactions and activity, wellbeing, eating and drinking, mobility, continence and hygiene, orientation, and safety and security (The King's Fund, 2020). As such, the present study will allow for an exploration of how such design principles are implemented and experienced in supported housing settings by people living with dementia, their family members or friends, and members of housing, health, and social care staff.

3.4.4.2. Integrative Framework of Aging Well

Central to theories like the environmental press-competence model (Lawton and Nahemow, 1973) is the nature of the relationship between a person and their environment. For example, Lawton and Nahemow (1973) believe that person-environment interactions can be measured, whereby personal competencies interact with objective environmental characteristics to determine functioning. However, such thinking does not address the subjective nature of person-environment exchanges, with experiences influenced by factors like personal meaning, attachment, and identity (Wahl, Iwarsson and Oswald, 2012). Indeed, Lawton later discussed the role that perceived quality of life had with regard to person-environment interactions, psychological wellbeing, competence, and an individual's perception of living "the good life" (Lawton, 1983).

The Integrative Framework of Ageing Well as Person-Environment Interchange (Figure 4) sought to expand on the work of Lawton, stating that experience-driven belonging and behaviour-driven agency influence person-environment interchanges, which impact the ability to age well (Wahl, Iwarsson and Oswald, 2012).

In this regard, belonging relates to place attachment, identity, the meaning of home, and familiarity, and how these influence an individual's affective, cognitive, behavioural, and social bonds with their environment, which can develop over time (Wahl, Iwarsson and Oswald, 2012). Agency relates to goal-directed behaviour and having control over the physical environment, relating to the ability to change environments to meet needs, through adapting, retrofitting, and creating places (Wahl, Iwarsson and Oswald, 2012).

Personal (e.g., cognitive functioning, affective functioning, personality traits) and environmental (e.g., housing adaptations) resources, have a direct impact on belonging and agency (Wahl, Iwarsson and Oswald, 2012). For example, if an individual’s cognitive or functional needs are not met through environmental resources, such as retrofitting or adaptations, this can impact agency, hence, autonomy, meaning that the environment is no longer the right fit for the individual (Wahl, Iwarsson and Oswald, 2012). Or, if an individual moves to an unfamiliar environment in which they have no bonds or attachment to, then this can impact feelings of belonging, and hence, identity (Wahl, Iwarsson and Oswald, 2012).

In the context of the supported housing literature discussed in Chapter Two, this framework is highly relevant. For example, resource limitations often meant that the needs of those living with dementia in the settings could not be met, ultimately leading to risk-averse care practices being adopted, a loss of independence and autonomy, and an increased likelihood of being managed or referred out of the settings. In this regard, this study will allow for the development of a deeper understanding of how personal and environmental needs are met in supported housing settings, through the provision of personal and environmental resources. The framework also supports the development of a deeper understanding of belonging regarding place attachment, familiarity, and subjective experiences of these, which are not discussed in depth in the supported housing and dementia research literature.

Figure 4: An integrative framework of ageing well as person-environment interchange. Adapted from Wahl, Iwarsson and Oswald (2012), p. 308.

3.5. Conceptual Framework

Drawing on the theories discussed in this chapter, a conceptual framework is shown in Figure 5. The goal of the framework is to evolve our understanding of the experience of living with dementia in supported housing, based on experiences that are unique to each individual case study, their related contexts and participants, and any comparisons that can be drawn. For example, it may be expected that the provision of support and care will be greater in extra care housing settings when compared to sheltered housing settings. In turn, the level of care need of the individual might impact their experience of independence and autonomy, and their ability to interact with the local community. In settings that can accommodate a higher level of need, those living with dementia might be better supported to interact with their local community, and experience factors associated with social citizenship. In this regard, the framework suggests that a person living with dementia can be enabled to live in supported housing through: 1) the provision of person-centred support and care that reflects an individual's personhood, physical, and psychological needs, 2) the experience of social citizenship through factors like participation in society and freedom from discrimination, 3) a physical environment that can be adapted to reflect an individual's competence, belonging, and agency through person-environment resources, and 4) an environment that supports individuals to live independently and autonomously in the community, reflecting their human rights. The framework will support a deeper understanding of the objectives of the study, and what can be learned regarding the experience of living with dementia in supported housing.

3.6. Chapter Three Summary

This chapter sought to demonstrate how the systematic review, conducted in Chapter Two, highlighted gaps in the literature that informed the development of the aim for this study. To address this aim, four objectives are outlined. Key concepts are noted in these objectives, relating to, 1) independence and autonomy, 2) support and care, 3) social relationships and community connections, and 4) the physical environment. The remainder of the chapter sought to outline theoretical perspectives that can contribute to our understanding of these concepts, which, together, were incorporated into a conceptual framework for this research (Figure 5). The use of this framework will not be deductive, and this study does not seek to test or assess theories

for their applicability in practice. Rather, the framework will serve as a theoretical lens to support the development of a richer understanding of the experience of living with dementia in supported housing in Scotland.

Figure 5: Conceptual framework, incorporating elements of the theory discussed in this chapter that can be explored further throughout the research process.

Hence, this chapter suggests that understanding of the provision of support and care in supported housing settings, for people living with dementia, can be enhanced by considering data through personhood and person-centred lenses (Kitwood, 1997; Kitwood and Brooker, 2019; McCormack and McCance, 2017). Extending beyond this, wider social relationships, community, and societal connections can be understood through a social citizenship lens, that expands on elements of personhood and person-centred care, focussing more on the societal contributions that those living with dementia can make as independent and

autonomous citizens (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010; O'Connor *et al.*, 2022). Finally, focussing on the immediate physical environments of supported housing settings, theories such as the environmental press-competence model (Lawton and Nahemow, 1973), and the integrative framework of ageing well as person-environment interchange (Wahl, Iwarsson and Oswald, 2012), can enhance our understanding of how the physical environments of supported housing settings can impact the lives of those living with dementia.

Specifically, such theories can enhance understanding regarding the importance of attachment, familiarity, and belonging in supported housing settings, in addition to the provision of resources that can address personal (e.g., cognitive, or functional) and environmental (e.g., home adaptations) needs in supported housing. Drawing on the theoretical perspectives outlined in this chapter, Chapter Four will seek to present the philosophical underpinnings of this research, outlining how this philosophical positioning also informed the development of the study's aim, objectives, and methodological choices, focussing on social constructionism. Reflecting this philosophical positioning, Chapter Four will also outline the study's methodological underpinnings, with an in-depth, critical exploration of case study research, and how rigour was upheld throughout the research process.

Chapter Four: Philosophical and Methodological Perspectives

4.1. Introduction to Chapter Four

In this chapter, the philosophical underpinnings of the research are discussed, outlining how they have shaped the study's aim, objectives, and methodological choices, focussing on social constructionism. Reflecting this philosophical positioning, the methodological underpinnings of the research are then outlined, with an in-depth, critical exploration of case study research, and how rigour will be upheld throughout the research process. Finally, ethical issues are discussed in the context of research involving people living with dementia, their family members, and housing, health, and social care professionals.

Chapter Three states that the aim of the present study is to develop an in-depth understanding of the experience of living with dementia in supported housing. The previous three chapters have asserted that the experience of living with dementia can be impacted by an array of personal, social, environmental, and societal factors. These may be better understood through the application of theories and models, like personhood and social citizenship. Reflective of the researcher's worldview of science and knowledge generation, this research asserts that understanding individuals' experiences or perspectives, and accessing information about the world, is largely mediated through language, discourse, and social interaction. This perspective, regarding the sharing and generation of knowledge, underpins social constructionism, which will be discussed in greater detail throughout this chapter.

4.2. Philosophical Perspectives

Before discussing social constructionism in greater detail, it is first helpful to provide an overview of the different philosophical paradigms that were considered in this thesis, focussing largely on positivism, critical realism, and constructivism. Positivism is the belief that an objective reality exists independently of whether it is observed (ontology) (Lincoln, Lynham and Guba, 2018). Our understanding of this objective reality is informed by designing experiments and generating observable evidence, with the goal of developing universal laws (epistemology) (Lincoln, Lynham and Guba, 2018; Park, Konge and Artino, 2020). However, this thesis utilises a qualitative methodology, aimed at developing a deeper understanding of the experience of

living with dementia in supported housing. The study is cognizant of social influences and acknowledges the subjective nature of human experiences. Positivistic research relies on the use of quantitative methods, and, often, does not focus on social contexts and subjectivity (Park, Konge and Artino, 2020). Therefore, this philosophical worldview does not align with the aim and objectives of this research, or the researcher's worldview.

Realist paradigms were also considered, most notably, critical realism (Bhaskar, 1975; Bhaskar, 1979; Easton, 2010; Fletcher, 2017; Taylor, 2018; Taylor, 2020). Critical realists believe that an objective world exists independently of whether it is observed (realist ontology) (Bhaskar, 1975; Bhaskar, 1979). However, they also believe that our understanding of the world is informed by subjective interpretations that influence how it is perceived and experienced (relativist epistemology) (Bhaskar, 1975; Bhaskar, 1979). The emphasis on subjective interpretations here is important, as this thesis acknowledges subjectivity regarding the experience of living with dementia in supported housing. However, critical realist research typically utilises quantitative and qualitative methods, like surveys and interviews (Bhaskar, 1975; Bhaskar, 1979). Such research focusses heavily on causality, with the endpoint of critical realist research being the development of causal mechanisms. Causal mechanisms are described as the underlying forces or processes that generate observable patterns in the empirical world (Bhaskar, 1975; Bhaskar, 1979). However, this is a qualitative thesis, and not concerned with causality. Although understanding the factors that might impact the experience of living with dementia in supported housing is important, the goal of this study is not to develop and test causal processes, but to understand the experience of living with dementia in supported housing.

The relativist epistemology of critical realism resonated with the researcher's worldview. Hence, constructivism was also considered. Constructivism contends that there exists no single reality or truth (relativist ontology), and that our knowledge of the world is constructed internally (subjectivist epistemology) (Lincoln, Lynham and Guba, 2018; Taylor, 2018). Indeed, this worldview is shared by key players in qualitative case study research, given their emphasis on understanding multiple perspectives on a given phenomenon (Yazan, 2015). However, constructivism, in the traditional sense, emphasises that knowledge is constructed at the individual level, typically through cognitive processes (Piaget, 1969). Others have acknowledged the

potential pitfalls of this way of thinking, as it fails to acknowledge the social processes that are inherent in knowledge generation (Vygotsky, 1978). In this regard, social constructivism was formed (Vygotsky, 1978). This is important, as this thesis acknowledges the role of social interaction and its impact on the experience of living with dementia in supported housing. Importantly, social constructivism focusses more on the psychological or cognitive mechanisms of knowledge generation (Gergen, 1985; Gergen, 2001; Vygotsky, 1978). Although this may be important in relation to education and cognitive development, with these theories stemming from pedagogical psychology, there are wider societal, cultural, and historical influences regarding the construction of knowledge, which should also be considered (Gergen, 1985). This is particularly relevant in the context of dementia. This thesis has contended that it is not helpful to understand the experience of living with dementia by focussing only on the cognitive impacts associated with the condition (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010; Kitwood, 1997). It is also important to consider wider societal, political, and cultural impacts on the experience of living with dementia, and how these wider impacts can influence the development of social constructions of dementia. For example, the previous chapters have shown that people with dementia can be stigmatised as a result of their condition, with stigmatising views likely influenced by poor dementia awareness or perspectives on dementia that emphasise a loss of self and identity (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010). In this regard, social constructionism resonated with the researcher's worldview, and with the aim and objectives of this thesis. Therefore, social constructionism will now be discussed in greater detail.

4.2.1. Social Constructionism

The first key assumption of social constructionism is that knowledge is constructed or made, with the mind actively constructing knowledge, rather than knowledge being discovered or found (Andrews, 2012; Burr and Dick, 2017; Denzin and Lincoln, 2018; Gergen, 1985; Jacobs and Manzi, 2000; Jacobs, Kemeny and Manzi, 2004; Schwandt, 2000; Taylor, 2018). To unpack this, knowledge could be "discovered" or "found" through the designing of an experiment, conducted in a controlled environment, to understand cause and effect relationships between variables. This scientific worldview aims to develop objective truths about the natural world (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018). Social constructionism, however, focusses on the social world of knowledge generation, with the belief that the natural and social worlds are two different things (Burr and Dick, 2017; Gergen, 1985). Social constructionists believe that people's realities are socially defined and influenced by

subjective experiences. They do not deny the existence of a “real” world and believe that the knowledge construction can correspond to something real (Burr and Dick, 2017; Gergen, 1985). For example, social constructionists would not deny that dementia is a real thing that impacts millions of people worldwide. Rather, people’s perspectives and knowledge relating to dementia change based on subjective experiences, contexts, and social worlds. This is important given that people with dementia can be stigmatised or excluded from elements of society due to their condition, resulting from poor dementia awareness and education.

Hence, the second key assumption of social constructionism is that knowledge is constructed through social interaction. Here, it is important to reiterate the differences between social constructionism and (social) constructivism. This is because they are two different paradigms, but often referred to interchangeably. With its roots in developmental and cognitive psychology, constructivism holds the belief that knowledge is constructed at the individual level, focussing on cognitive processes relating to knowledge generation (Kelly, 1955; Piaget, 1969; Vygotsky, 1978). Social constructionism places greater emphasis on the social aspects of knowledge construction, positing that social worlds are developed through social processes and interaction, with less emphasis on the cognitive processes of knowledge generation (Berger and Luckmann, 1966; Denzin and Lincoln, 2018; Gergen, 1985; Gergen, 2001).

From the worldview of a practicing psychologist, for example, constructivism might be helpful when understanding the cognitive-behavioural processes that occur at the individual level. Here, patterns of thought that lead to depressive or anxious feelings, that occur for that individual, can be challenged. However, the individual focus on knowledge construction in constructivism may be unhelpful in the context of research on the experience of living with dementia in supported housing, which is impacted by social, environmental, and wider societal elements. Therefore, in the worldview of science that underpins this research study, it is important to pay attention to the sharing of knowledge between humans, and the ways in which humans organise and coordinate activities together. Discussion in Chapter Three, regarding personhood, social citizenship, and environmental models, suggests that focussing only on cognition is unhelpful in the context of living with dementia. Such thinking risks diluting the experience of living with dementia to a measure of cognitive functioning. Instead, this research, aligned with social constructionism,

acknowledges social factors and contexts, and their impact on the experience of living with dementia in supported housing.

A third key assumption of social constructionism relates to its relativist ontology. That is, there exists multiple, subjective perspectives regarding the nature of reality (Burr and Dick, 2017; Denzin and Lincoln, 2018; Gergen, 1985). These perspectives are influenced by our social interactions, contexts, and the beliefs of others in our immediate social worlds. Again, this is not to say that all interpretations of reality are true or equal, but rather, consensus can be reached regarding the best understanding or explanation for a given phenomenon (Stake, 1995). Throughout this thesis so far, it has been acknowledged that those living with dementia in supported housing can face stigma and limited choice or control over their lived environment. Theories that underpin this research, such as personhood and social citizenship, contend that phenomena like societal stigma, or unethical support or care practices, can emanate from social constructions of dementia (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010; Kitwood, 1997). Kitwood's (1997) description of personhood, as a standing or status bestowed on an individual by others, highlights this point further, acknowledging the social and relational nature of personhood.

Literature has documented the progression of social constructions of dementia through time. First, described in terms of a divine punishment and insanity; through to medicalisation of the condition, and viewing dementia in terms of cognitive attributes and productivity; and finally, to modern perspectives on dementia, like personhood and social citizenship, that place the person first (Bosco *et al.*, 2019a). These social constructions of dementia can be problematic, contributing to stigma, limitations on choice, control, and participation in society, a loss of human rights, and othering those living with the condition (Bosco *et al.*, 2019b; Bosco *et al.*, 2019a). The supported housing and dementia-oriented literature shows that stigma and limited choice are still apparent in these settings. This suggests that negative social constructions of dementia continue to permeate through society, even in settings that purport to increase the independence and autonomy of their residents. Therefore, understanding social constructions of the experience of living with dementia in supported housing can help inform policy and practice, challenge social constructions that are problematic, and highlight positive experiences.

In this regard, a fourth assumption of social constructionism is the view that the construction of knowledge is historically and culturally situated (Berger and Luckmann, 1966). It emphasises the centrality of context, and the view that collective voices can either shift or sustain narrative change (Berger and Luckmann, 1966). Hence, social constructionism contends that all claims of truth and objectivity are made within communities of meaning making (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018). Perceptions of the world, therefore, are impacted by how they are thought or talked about, the consensus reached regarding their nature, how perceptions of the world are explained to others, and the various concepts used to understand these perceptions (Jacobs, Kemeny and Manzi, 2004). Regarding the present study, communities of meaning making may be influenced by, for example, those living with dementia and their immediate social networks, how housing providers operate to support or care for those living with dementia, and wider societal perspectives, policies, or strategies focussing on dementia in Scotland. The emphasis on interactions and subjectivity in social constructionism allows for a deeper understanding of power dynamics, and how narratives, consensus, and explanations of a particular phenomenon can be influenced by those with the most power in society. Regarding dementia, it is apparent that stigmatising narratives are still held by many in society, focussing on loss, medicalisation of the condition, and the exclusion of those living with dementia in civic life. Hence, social constructionism is suited to the study of social phenomena, which supports the development of an understanding of human action, and helps provide meaningful accounts of human behaviour that can shift or sustain narrative change (Jacobs, Kemeny and Manzi, 2004).

Some of the assumptions of social constructionism are presented above. However, it is important to critique this scientific worldview. The main critique relates to its relativist ontology. For example, some relativists believe that nothing in the world can be truly known, and that knowledge of the world does not extend beyond the language we use to describe phenomena (Schwandt, 2000). As such, the argument here is that little can be drawn from social constructionist research, given that those prescribing to stronger forms of relativism believe that all interpretations of reality or a phenomenon have legitimacy and are treated equally (Andrews, 2012). This is problematic, because if all interpretations of reality are treated equally, then all pieces of social constructionist research are simply presentations of an individual's reality. As such, claims

made in the research cannot be refuted or contested. This impacts the advancement of science and knowledge.

It may be argued that such a critique stems from diluting ontological discussions to a debate around realism versus relativism. Where reality is either viewed as existing (realism) or not (strong relativism). This thinking is not helpful, and reflective of a poor understanding of social constructionist literature. For example, Berger and Luckmann (1966) do not deny that neurodegenerative health conditions, like dementia, exist. Rather, it is the way that conditions are named, thought of, treated, or defined that are socially constructed. Society, within communities of meaning making, develop consensus based on these social constructions. This is central to developing an understanding of the experience of living with dementia in supported housing, given that perceptions of dementia can influence stigma, the way individuals are cared for, and whether individuals are excluded from elements of society.

From this scientific worldview, this study's aim of understanding the experience of living with dementia in supported housing in Scotland was developed. The objectives of the study are rooted in personal, social, environmental, and societal phenomena. In this regard, social constructions of the experience of living with dementia in supported housing can be understood, focussing on different models of supported housing as communities of meaning making, with data gathered from multiple perspectives. Complimenting theories like personhood, social citizenship, and the more subjective elements of environmental models of ageing and living with dementia, a social constructionist worldview can inform policy and practice, and evoke narrative change regarding the experience of living with dementia in supported housing.

4.2.2. Social Constructionism and Housing Research

Jacobs, Kemeny, and Manzi (2004) have written an extensive text about the application of social constructionism in housing research, having started discussing this decades before (Kemeny, 1984). Their writings contend that positivist research has been most prominent in housing literature, with the goal of informing or influencing policy (Jacobs, Kemeny and Manzi, 2004). The view was that positivist research carried more policy influence due to the large samples involved, as opposed to the more context-specific nature of social constructionist research (Jacobs, Kemeny and Manzi, 2004). However, large-scale positivist

research, with a broad focus, offers little insight into the social problems that people face in housing contexts, people's experiences, and the intricacies that lie therein (Jacobs, Kemeny and Manzi, 2004).

Their view is that society and social policy is open to change, through discourse and collective action, whilst acknowledging that society is influenced by power struggles. Resultantly, there exists no permanent social facts or truths (Jacobs and Manzi, 2000). Despite this, housing research has largely been informed by pre-conceived idealisations about the nature of good housing research, that typically emphasised positivist epistemologies (Jacobs, Kemeny and Manzi, 2004). This research, inevitably, informs the policy agenda in government. Indeed, as discussed in Chapter One, Scottish housing policy over the last decade has acknowledged social problems and the need to address them, such as poverty, unequal access to housing and care, and the unmet needs of people living with dementia in the community (Scottish Government, 2011b). However, it appears that the primary measure of successful housing policy implementation has focussed on the number of new houses built, whilst simply acknowledging that the same social problems still exist (Scottish Government, 2021). It is unclear if this way of thinking addresses access to housing, health, and social care for people living with dementia, or choice regarding where to live. Fundamentally, this shows the pitfalls of thinking of supported housing provision for people with dementia in terms of quantity, which is only one part of the issue. Through sharing of knowledge and the development of social constructions, that are contextually, historically, and culturally grounded, the experience of living with dementia in supported housing can be better understood.

To conclude this section, Jacobs, Kemeny and Manzi (2004, pp. 18 - 19) state that social problems are often discussed as being givens, or objective conditions, in society. However, when acknowledging power imbalances and the malleable nature of society and social policy, social constructionists view social problems as unjust, immoral, intolerable, and oppressive (Jacobs, Kemeny and Manzi, 2004). For example, if social constructions relating to race, sexual orientation, gender, or dementia are understood, it is often evident that such social groups face discrimination. Such social problems are constructions, influenced by, for example, public opinion or political perspectives (Jacobs, Kemeny and Manzi, 2004). Thus, they are open to change. In this regard, social constructionism provides a platform for this research to develop constructions

of the experience of living with dementia in supported housing, cognizant of the influence of society, social policy, and context on these constructions. Reflective of this philosophical worldview, this chapter now moves on to discuss the study's methodology: The case study approach of Stake (Stake, 1995; Stake, 2006; Stake, 2010).

4.3. Methodological Perspectives

4.3.1. Towards Case Study Research

The ethnographic work of anthropologists in the 19th and early 20th centuries has been described as the origin of case study research, through the establishment of anthropology as a fully-fledged discipline (Harrison *et al.*, 2017). The development of case study research, in more recent history, gained traction in the social sciences throughout the 1960s and 1970s in educational research and evaluation (Harrison *et al.*, 2017; Simons, 2009). At the time, predominant methods of educational evaluation, such as systems analysis, did not adequately demonstrate why some programmes failed, and others succeeded (Simons, 2009). Case study research was effective at addressing this issue. It sought to understand individuals' perspectives and their needs, cognizant of the impact of social and political contexts on the implementation of educational programmes, and, on the interpretation of findings. This gave rise to influential texts, which view case study research as a mode of inquiry suited to understanding educational, and, more broadly, social phenomena (Merriam, 1991; Stake, 1995; Yin, 2017).

This research utilised Stake's (1995; 2006; 2010) methodology, which will be unpacked throughout this chapter, along with the reasons why this methodology was selected. First, it is important to bring in some discussion around why case study research was chosen over other qualitative methodologies, focussing on narrative research, ethnography, phenomenology, and grounded theory.

Narrative research was first explored, due to its focus on the retelling of individuals' stories (Creswell and Poth, 2017). Although it is important to explore the lives of individuals living with dementia, this is not the only consideration in this research. For example, focussing on retelling individuals' stories through interviews might miss wider contextual or societal impacts, and the role of the physical environment on the experience

of living with dementia. Further, this approach does not consider multiple perspectives or viewpoints regarding social issues, which is important in research grounded in social constructionist philosophy.

Second, phenomenology was considered, due to its focus on understanding and describing the lived experience, whilst making use of multiple data collection methods, like interviews, documents, and observations (Creswell and Poth, 2017). This means that phenomenology could be useful in the context of this study, given that it aims to understand the experience of living with dementia in supported housing. However, this approach would, typically, only involve people living with dementia, as the primary focus is the experience of living with the condition, to understand the meaning and language used to describe this experience. This research study is not only focussed on the perspectives of people with dementia, and aims to understand different perspectives, wider societal issues relating to policy and practice, and the impact of the physical environment on the experience of living with dementia in supported housing.

Third, grounded theory was explored. Drawing from a general view of grounded theory, the focus of this approach is the development of a theory that is grounded in data from the field (Creswell and Poth, 2017). The primary method of data collection is the use of interviews, typically involving between 20 and 60 individuals (Creswell and Poth, 2017). Indeed, it might be useful to develop a theory on the best model of supported housing, or the best ways to distribute support and care resources in these settings. However, as with narrative research and phenomenology, this thesis aims to develop learnings from other peoples' perspectives, documents, and photographs, and draw from societal and political contexts. Hence, plurality of methods is key to this research, and hearing multiple perspectives is central to the social constructionist philosophy that underpins this study.

Finally, ethnography was considered, due to its focus on understanding and describing cultures, and the shared patterns of the culture of a group (Creswell and Poth, 2017). This could be useful for describing the cultures that exist within various supported housing settings, relating to support or care provision, or social interactions. However, ethnography primarily uses observation and interview methods, with the researcher occupying a "fly-on-the-wall" position. It is unclear if this would be helpful in the context of living in supported housing. It might be helpful to observe patterns of support or care provision, mealtimes, or social activities.

However, those living in the settings occupy self-contained homes, where they would, likely, spend most of their day. It is unclear how helpful it would be to observe individuals in this capacity. It is also important to consider the societal impact of COVID-19. For example, the potential limit this could have on social interaction and care practices in these settings, and what could be observed. Additionally, the appropriateness of occupying an environment for long hours, while the pandemic is still developing, must be considered. It was felt that this research would benefit from a flexible research approach, given the challenges that will likely be faced throughout the research process.

Having shared some considerations regarding the selection of an appropriate qualitative methodology, the following sections focus on case study research, and why it is best suited to address the aim and objectives of this research study.

4.3.2. Defining Case Study Research

To reiterate, this thesis will follow the case study research approach of Stake (1995; 2006; 2010). Before describing his approach in detail, it is first important to establish what is meant by case study research generally, culminating in a discussion of why Stake's methodology was chosen.

A straightforward definition of case study research is elusive, due to the flexibility associated with this research approach, and its drawing from ethnographic, phenomenological, and grounded theory methods (Stake, 1995). Multiple researchers have developed articles with comparisons of various case study research methodologists, most prominently, the approaches of Stake, Merriam, and Yin (Cleland, MacLeod and Ellaway, 2021; Harrison *et al.*, 2017; Yazan, 2015). These reports each contain detailed tables of the characteristics of case study research, from Stake, Merriam, and Yin's perspectives. For the purposes of this Section, some key features of case study research will be addressed, using Simon's (2009) short-hand definition:

An in-depth exploration from multiple perspectives of the complexity and uniqueness of a particular project, policy, institution, programme, or system in real-life context. It is research-based, inclusive of different methods, and is evidence-based. The primary purpose is to generate in-depth

understanding of a ... programme, policy, institution, or system to generate knowledge and / or inform policy development, professional practice and civil or community action. (Simons, 2009).

This definition is, to a high degree, congruent with the approaches of Stake, Merriam, and Yin, compared in greater detail elsewhere (Cleland, MacLeod and Ellaway, 2021; Harrison *et al.*, 2017; Yazan, 2015). The following sections unpack the main elements of this definition, focussing on 1) multiple perspectives, 2) real-life context, 3) plurality of methods, and 4) informing policy development, professional practice, and civil or community action.

4.3.2.1. Multiple Perspectives

In this study, the inclusion of multiple perspectives, from people living with dementia, their family members or friends, and housing, health, and social care professionals, will add an additional level of understanding regarding the objectives of the present study. For example, it may be assumed, based on previous research conducted in supported housing, that supported housing staff concentrate more on the practicalities of supporting people living with dementia (Rondon-Sulbaran *et al.*, 2020), whereas people living with dementia may disclose the more personal aspects of living in the settings (Evans *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, interviewing, for example, professionals only, would risk the omission of important insights from people living with dementia, their family members, or friends. Developing a holistic understanding of phenomena, through the involvement of local participants from the inside, is a defining feature of qualitative case study research (Miles, Huberman and Saldaña, 2018; Stake, 1995). Inclusion of multiple perspectives, therefore, facilitates the development of a holistic understanding of the experience of living with dementia in supported housing. Further, acknowledgment of multiple perspectives to illuminate our understanding of phenomena is also central to social constructionism and ontological relativism, which underpins this research (Stake, 1995). The philosophical underpinnings and their relationship with Stake's methodology is discussed in Section 4.3.4.1. of this chapter.

4.3.2.2. Real-Life Context

Conducting research within the real-life, or naturalistic, settings in which the phenomenon of study occurs is a central feature of qualitative case study research (Miles, Huberman and Saldaña, 2018; Stake, 1995). Case

study research actively encourages conducting research within naturalistic settings, to enable the researcher to situate findings in context for the reader (Stake, 1995). The real-life supported housing environments involved in this research will be key to addressing the study's aim and objectives. As will be described in greater detail in Chapter Five, the settings will be photographed to understand the extent to which dementia-friendly design principles are implemented in practice, and to develop an understanding of how the physical environment impacts the independence of people living with dementia in the settings. Hence, this adds a level of detail that may not be captured by conducting interviews in a different environment, although, the COVID-19 pandemic might influence the extent to which this can be done.

4.3.2.3. Plurality of Methods

Case study research encourages the use of multiple data collection methods to address the aim and objectives of the research, typically in the form of interviews, observations, focus groups, artefacts, document review, and questionnaires or surveys (Harrison *et al.*, 2017). This, again, emphasises the holistic nature of case study research, with the aim of developing a depth and breadth of understanding regarding the phenomenon of study (Harrison *et al.*, 2017; Merriam, 1991; Stake, 1995; Yin, 2017). The data collection methods used, however, differ based on the case study research methodologist's approach. For example, Stake (1995) and Merriam (1991) emphasise the use of interviews, observations, and document review in case study research, whereas Yin (2017) describes the use of documents, archival records, interviews, direct observations, participant observations and physical artefacts, together with the use of quantitative methods. The present study will utilise interviews (from multiple perspectives), documents, and photographs of the physical environments of supported housing settings, following the approach of Stake (1995). This will provide depth and breadth of knowledge regarding the aim and objectives of the study and enable the situating of findings in the contexts in which they were developed. Methods of analysis also differ based on the methodologist, however, a detailed overview of data analysis methods used in the present study, following Stake's (1995; 2006) multiple case study research approach, will be provided in Chapter Five.

4.3.2.4. Inform Policy Development, Professional Practice, and Civil or Community Action

Chapters Three and Four have outlined the centrality of social citizenship and social constructionism in this research. Social citizenship reflects on the importance of participation in civil and community action for people living with dementia, through solidarity with others, with the goal of creating a society that is free from discrimination (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010). Further, social constructionism emphasises the centrality of interactions and context regarding knowledge generation, and the view that collective voices can either shift or sustain narrative change (Berger and Luckmann, 1966). Case study research compliments such theories and scientific worldviews, with the methodology suited to informing policy, practice, and civil or community action. Social constructions of the experience of living with dementia in supported housing, utilising multiple perspectives, methods, and rooted in real-life settings, can be understood to inform policy and practice, highlighting areas for civil and community action. The next section will describe Stake's methodology in greater detail.

4.3.3. The Case Study Research Approach of Stake

4.3.3.1. What is a Case?

At the broadest level, a case can be defined as anything; a person, an organisation, an event, a decision, an action, a location, or a nation (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018). Stake describes cases as things or entities (Stake, 1995). Cases can either be empirical, that is, cases are real and observable units; or, cases can be theoretical constructs, based entirely on scholarly work (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018). Cases can be located at the micro level (people and interpersonal relationships), the meso level (organisations or institutions), and the macro level (communities or societies) (Miles, Huberman and Saldaña, 2018).

A second fundamental aspect of defining cases is acknowledging that cases have boundaries (Stake, 1995). That is, there is a central focus of the study, and a boundary that defines the edge of the cases, or what will not be studied (Miles, Huberman and Saldaña, 2018). Hence, part of defining a case involves defining its boundary. Regarding this, Stake refers to a case as a bounded system with working parts (Stake, 1995, p. 2). Stake states that people and programmes are clear examples of cases, however, events and processes are viewed as harder to define (Stake, 1995). This is because the boundaries of events and processes are unclear.

Supported housing might be thought of as a programme, in that supported housing providers offer a service, with the aim of supporting individuals to live independently in the community for as long as possible. Further, Stake emphasises the importance of specificity when determining the boundary of a case, referring to cases as specific, complex, functioning things (Stake, 1995). The methods, discussed in Chapter Five, will provide a detailed description of the cases in the present study.

4.3.3.2. Ontology and Epistemology

Regarding epistemology and ontology, the aim of this section is to demonstrate how Stake's worldview of science, and the philosophical underpinnings of his methodology, are consistent, or complimentary, to the present researcher's. Stake's (1995) case study research methodology is epistemologically constructivist, and ontologically relativist. He states that the world we know is largely made of human constructions, with our knowledge constructed through shared experience and learning (Stake, 1995, pp. 99 – 104). Stake believes that the researcher's interpretive role is essential in case study research, as it is through this interpretation that knowledge is shared (Stake, 1995). Reproduction of this knowledge, in the form of case study reports, enables the reader to make their own interpretations of events, judge the soundness of the researcher's interpretations, and apply the findings to their own contexts and experiences. Although these interpretations occur at the individual level, in keeping with a constructivist epistemology (Kelly, 1955; Piaget, 1969), Stake acknowledges the importance of sharing knowledge, situationality, context, and the conducting of naturalistic research. This suggests an acknowledgement of a social element in knowledge construction, akin to social constructionism. Although the interpretation comes from the researcher, the processes of developing these interpretations is through interviewing others, reviewing documents, or analysing imagery. To elaborate and provide context, Stake's perspective on reality is presented below, where he outlines the belief that three realities exist in our world:

One is an external reality capable of stimulating us in simple ways but of which we know nothing other than our interpretations of those stimuli.

The second is a reality formed of those interpretations of simple stimulation, an experiential reality representing external reality so persuasively that we seldom realize our inability to verify it.

The third is a universe of integrated interpretations, our rational reality. (Stake, 1995, p. 100).

Stake believes that developing an understanding of the first reality is impossible. Rather, he suggests that case study research aims to construct a clearer understanding of the second reality, and a more sophisticated understanding of the third (Stake, 1995, p. 100). That is, to develop a construction of reality that can withstand scepticism, scrutiny, and challenge, whilst acknowledging that this construction is one of interpretation (Stake, 1995).

Here, Stake states that he does not believe in a stronger form of relativism, akin to absolutism, which views all perspectives and interpretations of reality as equal (Stake, 1995, p. 102). Rather, the aim of case study research is to arrive at the most credible explanation, whilst providing enough data for the reader to make their own interpretations regarding the credibility and utility of this explanation (Stake, 1995). As stated in Section 4.2, social constructionism posits that our perceptions of the world are impacted by how we think or talk about them, the consensuses we reach regarding their nature, how we explain our perceptions of the world to others, and the various concepts we use to understand these (Jacobs, Kemeny and Manzi, 2004). Thus, there are similarities between Stake's worldview of science and that applied in this study. The main difference is that the present study pays more attention to the social and wider societal aspects of knowledge generation, and how these can influence the experience of living with dementia in supported housing.

Other case study methodologies were considered; however, they did not align with the scientific worldview outlined in this study. Further, the philosophical underpinnings of these methodologies are not developed in detail. For example, Yin (2018) states that his case study research approach is underpinned by a realist perspective, without expanding or discussing which type of realism he refers to, of which there are many (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018). Realism is more closely aligned with a positivist worldview, interested in prediction and control, validity, reliability, and causality (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018). This is at odds with the goals of the present study, which aims to understand the experience of living with dementia in supported housing from multiple perspectives, acknowledging the subjectivity of such experiences.

However, in his most recent text, Yin (2018) also states that his approach can complement a relativist ontology. Again, this is not to reduce ontological discussions to relativism versus realism. Rather, it is to

highlight that Yin is noncommittal in his discussion around philosophy. To illustrate, he simply states that his approach "... appears to be oriented toward a realist perspective" (Yin, 2018). It could be argued that Yin refrains from making committed or detailed descriptions of his worldview of science, to avoid philosophical debate regarding the combining of qualitative and quantitative methods. For example, in some areas of his work, Yin appears to adhere to positivistic traditions, discussing replication, reliability, and validity. In other areas of his work, he states that open-ended interviews are one of the most important methods of data collection in case study research, referring to shared experiences and subjectivity.

This can create problems regarding the integrity and trustworthiness of the research, as it is challenging for researchers to determine if his research approach truly adheres to their worldview of science. For example, if a researcher follows Yin's approach, conducting open-ended interviews, then discusses the quality of this research in terms of reliability, validity, and replication, then their understanding of qualitative research could be questioned. This is not to say that qualitative research cannot prescribe to realism. Rather, his use of open-ended, conversational interviews appears to be at odds with this worldview of science. In realist perspectives, more closely aligned with positivism, qualitative data collection may use highly structured or survey interviews, recruiting a large sample size, in which the researcher embodies a more objective or distant role (Grbich, 2013). Yin's approach appears to move away from this thinking.

Merriam's (1991) case study research approach is epistemologically constructivist. In many ways, her approach is consistent with that of Stake's, including the use of qualitative data collection methods only, and the use of interviews and documents. However, a criticism of Merriam's approach is that she pays little attention to the reader's role in interpretation. Given that situationality and context are important in this study, enabling readers to apply the study's findings to their own contexts and experiences, Stake's approach was deemed more suitable. Research adhering to a constructivist or social constructionist philosophy should be cognizant of the reader's role in interpretation, reflecting a relativist ontology. This is perhaps a minor issue, but the explicit acknowledgement of this in Stake's (1995) writings stresses that his approach is truly reflective of his worldview of science. Further, Merriam's (1991) discussion around quality may also be at

odds with her constructivist worldview, given that quality is discussed in terms of reliability, and internal, and external validity.

In sum, when considering the development of the philosophical positions of Stake, Merriam, and Yin, Stake's position is the most comprehensibly developed and true to the philosophy. His position is also the most closely aligned with the philosophical underpinnings of this research. Hence, a primary reason for adopting this methodology.

4.3.4. Case Study Characteristics and Types

4.3.4.1. Overview

Stake states that his case study research methodology draws from naturalistic, holistic, ethnographic, phenomenological, and biographic research methods (Stake, 1995). He views case study research as flexible, with research processes that can be adapted and developed throughout the course of study, using interviews, observations, and documents as sources of data. Expanding on this, Stake outlines special characteristics of qualitative case study research (Stake, 1995, p. 47). The first is that case study research is holistic. Stake's view on holism is the belief that case study research should focus on "... the entity rather than on its constituent parts." (Stake, 1995, p. 171). That is, through the development of contextuality and situationality, enabling readers to situate findings in the contexts in which they occur through vicarious experience. Stake (1995) states that such contexts can be temporal and spatial, historical, political, economic, cultural, social, and personal.

Chapters Two, Three, and Four have outlined the importance of such contexts regarding understanding the experience of living with dementia in supported housing, which appears to be influenced by an array of personal, social, environmental, and societal factors. At present, the current evidence base relating to supported housing and dementia fails to develop contextuality, meaning that it is challenging to apply findings to other contexts and experiences. Stake emphasises that holistic case study research can be produced through description of contexts, specifying the boundary of the cases, and focussing on the development of an in-depth understanding of each individual case (Stake, 1995, p. 47). This is not to say that comparisons across cases cannot be made. Rather, comparisons of cases should be considerate of the unique

contexts in which each individual case occurs (Stake, 1995; 2006). This will be important when addressing the objectives of this research, particularly when developing an understanding of the experience of living with dementia in different models of supported housing. Context is key to developing this understanding, as models differ based on, for example, their sizes and structure or provision of support and care. Stake's methodology facilitates the holistic development of these rich contexts.

The second special characteristic is that case study research is empirical (Stake, 1995). This is described as research that is field oriented, conducted within the naturalistic settings in which phenomena occur (Stake, 1995). This research will be conducted within supported housing settings, to help situate research, policy, and practice-oriented literature in context, and develop a richer understanding of the contexts under study.

The third special characteristic is that case study research is interpretive (Stake, 1995). Here, Stake states that case study researchers rely more on intuition when collecting and analysing data, with research viewed as a researcher-subject interaction (Stake, 1995, p. 47). Evidently, this is linked to Stake's views on the analysis process as interpretive, emphasising the use of direct interpretation and categorical aggregation throughout (Stake, 1995). Direct interpretation involves the interpretation of a single instance, whereas categorical aggregation relates to grouping several instances and making interpretations about them collectively (Stake, 1995). The goal here is to generate vicarious experiences for the reader, as if they experienced the case study themselves. This facilitates the development of case-based assertions, with credibility and utility of these assertions enhanced by the inclusion of rich descriptions of findings and context. This process is congruent with social constructionism.

The final special characteristic is that case study research is empathic (Stake, 1995, p. 47). Stake describes empathy as "... the knowledge of the plight of another by experiencing it yourself." (Stake, 1995, p. 39). Here, Stake states that empathic research pays attention to actor intentionality, their frames of reference, and values (Stake, 1995, p. 47). Although the research design is planned, case study research is flexible and responsive to change, cognizant of emic issues, or those that emerge throughout the course of the study, a further indicator that the research is empathic (Stake, 1995, p. 47). An empathic understanding can also be developed for the reader, by providing thick description that creates vicarious experience (Stake, 1995, p.

47). Hence, case study research is suited to developing an understanding of the phenomenon under study, and the contexts surrounding the phenomenon. Having outlined the special characteristics of Stake's methodology, it is important to provide an overview of Stake's classification of different types of case studies, namely, intrinsic, instrumental, and collective, or multiple case study, and their application in this research (Stake, 1995; 2006).

4.3.4.2. Intrinsic and Instrumental Case Studies

The focus of case study research is to develop an understanding of some thing or phenomenon. Stake states that case studies are structured by research questions, or issues: those brought in by the researcher (etic issues), and those that develop throughout the case study (emic issues) (Stake, 1995). In intrinsic case studies, the case is viewed as of the highest importance. For example, the case might be an individual living with dementia in supported housing. In an intrinsic case study, the focus here would be on the individual's experiences, seeking to describe the case in detail, with an understanding of issues being secondary to the overall aim of the research (Stake, 1995). In instrumental case studies, developing an understanding of the issues of the case study is more important than developing an understanding of the single case (Stake, 1995). If we take the above example of living with dementia in supported housing, and apply it to the present study, this study seeks to develop an in-depth understanding of the experience of living with dementia in supported housing, focussing on the provision of support and care, social relationships and community connections, the physical environment, and perceptions regarding supported housing as a future housing choice for people living with dementia. Hence, developing an understanding of these instrumental issues, through the involvement of people living with dementia, their family members or friends, and members of supported housing staff, is central to the research, rather than the individual case. Hence, the present study is an instrumental case study research project, involving multiple case studies.

4.3.4.3. Collective and Multiple Case Studies

Stake describes collective case studies as the study of several cases within the same project (Stake, 1995). Later, Stake would refer to these as multiple case studies (Stake, 2006). Stake's view of multiple case study research involves the development of a series of individual case study reports, after which, a cross-case

analysis is conducted to develop an understanding of the “quintain” (Stake, 2006). In the context of multiple case study research, the term, quintain, is used to replace the term, phenomenon. This is because Stake (2006) viewed the term, phenomenon, to be too narrow to capture the wider research targets of multiple case study research. In this study, the quintain would be the experience of living with dementia in supported housing in Scotland. Stake (2006, p. 40) states that a cross-case analysis is conducted to understand the quintain, focussing on commonalities and differences between cases. There may be similarities across cases, however, each individual case study report will likely have unusual or unique features (Stake, 2006). Cross-case analysis, therefore, can further our understanding of the quintain, in general, and how the quintain occurs under different conditions and contexts (Stake, 2006).

The term, quintain, is used, as it refers to a target that is struck in the sport of jousting. Stake uses this as a metaphor, as it is highly unlikely that a jousting rider would ever hit the perfect centre of the quintain. Similarly, it is unlikely that a researcher would ever perfectly capture or describe a phenomenon in its entirety. Rather, reflective of their philosophical worldview, the researcher can present their findings in a way that enables the reader to determine the soundness or appropriateness of these interpretations, towards reaching a consensus about the nature of a phenomenon. Just as a jousting rider gets better at “tilting the quintain” with practice, a researcher develops a better understanding of a phenomenon throughout the case study process.

As discussed previously, Stake (1995; 2006) emphasises that the context, situationality, and uniqueness of each case study is key to our understanding of phenomena, and thus, the quintain. The output of the cross-case analysis will yield cross-case assertions – a summary of the researcher’s key interpretations and claims (Stake, 1995; Stake, 2006). As the present study focusses on experiences of living with dementia in various models of supported housing, with a key focus on situationality and context, Stake’s cross-case analysis approach is suited to address the aim and objectives of the study. This is described in more detail in Chapter Five.

4.3.5. Rigour in Qualitative and Case Study Research

In qualitative research, the researcher is viewed as the main instrument of data collection, which can raise issues with the quality of the collected data, and the rigour, or trustworthiness, of the study (Miles,

Huberman and Saldaña, 2018). Rather than focussing on validity, reliability, and control, accuracy or prediction, the quality of qualitative data is related more to its richness, depth, diversity and complexity (Braun and Clarke, 2019). Quality criteria for naturalistic and social constructionist qualitative studies focus more on trustworthiness and authenticity (Lincoln, 1995; Lincoln, Lynham and Guba, 2018). These criteria move away from traditionally positivist concepts, like validity and reliability (Lincoln, 1995). For example, Guba and Lincoln's (1989) concept of authenticity relates more to hearing the voices (viewpoints) of all individuals involved in the research, the likelihood that the research could evoke social change or empower individuals to act, or if the research generates sufficient knowledge about the experiences of those involved. These criteria are more suited to Stake's case study methodology, concerned with meaning and the understanding of experiences, as opposed to accuracy, precision, and causation (Lincoln, Lynham and Guba, 2018). Further, discussion of the likelihood that qualitative research can evoke social change complements social citizenship and social constructionism, which acknowledge the importance of collective action and shifting or sustaining societal narratives (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010; Denzin and Lincoln, 2018).

Enhancing rigour in qualitative research has been conceptualised as the establishment of methodological integrity (Levitt *et al.*, 2017). Distinct, but drawing on the concepts of trustworthiness and authenticity, Levitt *et al.* (2017) describe methodological integrity as being established when the research design and procedures; 1) support the aim and objectives of the research, 2) respect the researcher's approach to inquiry, reflecting their worldview and the philosophical assumptions of the researcher, 3) tailored to the characteristics of the topics of study and those involved. Here, characteristics that might influence the methodological quality of qualitative research are considered.

Levitt and colleagues (2017) state that methodological integrity is influenced by fidelity and utility. Fidelity is described as the connection that a researcher strives to obtain with the phenomenon under study (Levitt *et al.*, 2017). This can be enhanced by conducting in-depth interviews and rapport building, to develop an understanding of people's covert and internal experiences (Levitt *et al.*, 2017), thus increasing our understanding of the phenomenon. As discussed, Stake's (1995) case study methodology emphasises naturalistic research, empathy, holism, and context, with data collected through in-depth interviewing,

observing, and reviewing documents. Utility is defined as the effectiveness of the research design and methods to address the study's aim and objectives (Levitt *et al.*, 2017).

Other indicators of quality, discussed by Stake, relate to triangulation of data sources and researcher training regarding qualitative methodologies (Stake, 1995). In this regard, Chapters Three and Four have attempted to outline theories and models that can enhance understanding regarding the aim and objectives of the research, the philosophical underpinnings of this research, and the selection of a methodology that complements such a worldview. Chapter Five will discuss the study's methods and the reasoning for selecting these methods to address the study's aim, including how the quality of the research was upheld.

4.3.6. Ethical Considerations

Stake (1995) believes that qualitative researchers have an ethical obligation to minimise misrepresentation and misunderstanding throughout the research process. Reflective of theories like personhood and social citizenship, that discuss the importance of the involvement and participation of people living with dementia in society, including research, this section aims to outline ethical considerations in this research study and how they will be addressed. This study aims to provide a platform for people living with dementia, their supporters, and housing, health, and social care professionals to be meaningfully involved in the research. This study adheres to the University of the West of Scotland's Code of Ethics, with implementation of this code informed by the University of the West of Scotland's guidelines for ethical practice in research and scholarship (University of the West of Scotland, 2020b). The University of the West of Scotland proposes four ethical principles, used to guide research with human participants. Namely, 1) autonomy, veracity, and informed consent; 2) privacy and confidentiality, 3) justice and inclusiveness, and: 4) benefits and harms. The following sections provide a critical interpretation of these key principles.

4.3.6.1. Autonomy, Veracity, and Informed Consent

This principle acknowledges the right of all individuals to determine their own course of action. The present study aims to involve people living with dementia, and family members or friends of people living with dementia, who have the capacity to provide informed consent to participate. In accordance with the Adults

with Incapacity (Scotland) Act 2000, the definition of an adult with incapacity is anyone over the age of 16, deemed incapable of:

- Acting; or
- Making decisions; or
- Communicating decisions; or
- Understanding decisions; or
- Retaining the memory of decisions.

This is an important consideration for two reasons. 1) It is important that vulnerable individuals have protections in place to make sure they are not taken advantage of in research and society, however, 2) it is important to ensure that individuals are not wrongfully excluded from research, due to their condition. For example, living with a diagnosis of dementia does not mean that an individual lacks capacity to provide informed consent (Alzheimer Europe, 2019). Additionally, having incapacity does not mean that an individual cannot be supported to be involved in research (Alzheimer Europe, 2019). As discussed previously, theories like personhood and social citizenship emphasise that people with dementia have the same rights as anyone else in society and should be supported to be involved in research in any way possible (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010; Kitwood, 1997). People who do not have capacity to consent will not be included in the study. Nonetheless, it is important to ensure that the research is designed in a way that supports the involvement of people with dementia, should they wish to be involved.

4.3.6.2. Privacy and Confidentiality

At the practical level, data will be managed in accordance with the Data Protection Act (2018), and the University of the West of Scotland's Data Protection Code of Practice (University of the West of Scotland, 2020). However, there are wider ethical considerations that need to be addressed in the context of research on dementia and supported housing. First and foremost, those living with dementia in supported housing are tenants or homeowners, by law, and have no obligation to disclose their diagnosis to anyone, including supported housing staff. This reflects the human rights of any individual living in the community. This is important, as an individual with dementia may self-identify themselves and wish to be involved in the

research but would not like to disclose their diagnosis to others living or working in the setting. This may be understandable, as previous literature, discussed in Chapter Two, has shown that people with dementia are stigmatised in supported housing settings due to their conditions. Ultimately, an individual's health needs are theirs to disclose and should not define them, first and foremost, as people.

This raises an important, wider, ethical discussion. For example, it is acknowledged that people with dementia often have complex care needs, and it is a human right that individuals receive appropriate health and social care to meet these needs. However, if an individual living with dementia in supported housing opts to not disclose their diagnosis, and subsequently requires support and care, this may have a negative impact on their lives that may have been mitigated by informing staff earlier and making them aware of their condition, impacting access to support and care services. Nonetheless, in the context of research, an individual's right to privacy and confidentiality must be upheld, and appropriate steps put in place to ensure individuals' data remain secure (Alzheimer Europe, 2019; Thoft *et al.*, 2020; Thoft, Ward and Youell, 2021).

Regarding a wider social constructionist viewpoint, this research has a duty to ensure that the experiences of those involved are developed to influence issues that impact their lives, and the lives of other people living with dementia. The role of the researcher, in this regard, is to interpret the findings in a way that, confidentially, reflects the experiences of those involved, but also raises important questions in relation to research, policy, and practice that should be addressed. By challenging the way that dementia is socially constructed in society, this research may be placed to raise issues with dementia awareness in supported housing, or the reforming of support and care delivery in these settings. For example, by addressing societal stigma that might influence the disclosure of a diagnosis, or the restructuring of support and care practices that account for all individuals living with dementia in Scotland, to ensure equal access to support and care services. If at the point of diagnosis, individuals with dementia are accurately documented on an integrated health and social care registry or database, then health and social care could be distributed through these services without the need to disclose a diagnosis to others, if the individual does not wish.

4.3.6.3. Justice and Inclusiveness

Reflective of human rights, personhood, and social citizenship, it is important that the human rights of justice and inclusivity are acknowledged for people with dementia (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010; Kitwood, 1997; United Nations, 2006). Being supported to shape issues that impact our lives is a human right, including through involvement in research (United Nations, 2006; Cross-Party Group in the Scottish Parliament on Alzheimer's, 2009). Hence, it is important that research is designed in a way that supports inclusivity for people with dementia and their family members. For example, by following best practice guidelines relating to research involving people with dementia (Alzheimer Europe, 2019). Within the context of research conducted in supported housing, Chapter Two showed that there is a lack of high-quality evidence that adequately considers the perspectives of those living with dementia. This would suggest that people with dementia are underrepresented in the research.

As discussed in Section 4.2 of this chapter, social constructionist research is important for underrepresented groups. This is because it can highlight areas of discrimination that impact those involved, and address power imbalances that occur in relation to social issues. These social issues can be thought of as social constructions that are open to change. For example, although dementia may be acknowledged as a health condition, the way people think of those living with the condition, or how individuals are supported or cared for, are social constructions. Social constructions that other people with dementia and exclude them from areas of society, like research, need to be challenged. As such, this research holds an important role regarding the inclusion of people with dementia, given that they are currently underrepresented in this field, and can shape issues that impact their lives, with the goal of shaping political, societal, and practice-oriented change.

4.3.6.4. Benefits and Harms

It is important that the designed research limits unnecessary harm and provides demonstrable benefit for people with dementia. This study will be designed to be low-risk, and the researcher's academic supervisors have extensive experience conducting research of this type. This will ensure that appropriate consideration is given to the data collection procedures and their ethical implications. Given that the evidence base relating to living with dementia in supported housing is still in its infancy, and there has yet to be a formal research

study conducted in Scotland at the time of writing, this research will be of significant value to future residents of supported housing.

This is important, because as researchers, we must acknowledge that we hold power in this regard. That is, if research is poorly designed, inaccessible, or harmful, it can limit the involvement of people with dementia in research that influences their lives (Alzheimer Europe, 2019). Additionally, although the study can be designed to limit harm, the importance of the research for the wider dementia and supported housing field must be considered. Chapter Two showed that people with dementia can face a degree of harm in supported housing settings through, for example, stigma and poor support or care practices. Although the research may not have direct benefit to those involved, the findings can be used to address these issues, and inform those working in research, policy, and practice for future benefit. Therefore, it is important that the researcher acknowledges their role as a “gatekeeper” to involvement in research and designs their study in accordance with best practice guidelines.

4.4. Chapter Four Summary

Having reviewed the current evidence base in Chapter Two and outlining the theoretical underpinnings of this research in Chapter Three, the aim of this Chapter was to discuss the philosophical underpinnings of the research, and outline how they shaped the study’s aim, objectives, and methodological choices. Reflecting this philosophical positioning, the methodological underpinnings of the research were then discussed, with a critical exploration of case study research, and a discussion of how rigour will be upheld throughout the research process. Finally, ethical issues were discussed in the context of research involving people living with dementia, their family members, and housing, health, and social care professionals. Chapter Five will provide a detailed overview of the methods involved in this research, the reasoning for selecting specific data collection methods to address the aim of the research, and how the discussed ethical issues will be addressed.

Chapter Five: Research Design and Methods

5.1. Introduction to Chapter Five

Having provided an overview of the methodological and philosophical underpinnings of this research, this chapter provides a detailed overview of the research design and methods. As discussed in Chapter Three, the overall aim of this study is:

To develop an in-depth understanding of the experience of living with dementia in supported housing in Scotland.

The aim will be met through the following objectives:

Objective one: To understand how support or care is delivered in supported housing settings to meet the needs of people living with dementia.

Objective two: To understand how living in supported housing impacts social relationships and community connections for people living with dementia.

Objective three: To understand how the physical environments of supported housing settings enable people living with dementia to maintain their independence.

Objective four: To understand perspectives on supported housing as a future housing choice for people living with dementia.

This chapter first provides an overview of the research design of the empirical stage of this thesis, discussing case selection, study settings, recruitment processes, and participant inclusion criteria. The chapter then discusses the ethical considerations outlined in Chapter Four, with an overview of how the study has been designed to address any ethical concerns, ensuring that participants can contribute meaningfully to the research. Data collection methods are then outlined, with an overview of interview procedures, collation of photographs and documents, and the use of outcome measures intended to provide added descriptive information about the individuals involved in the study. Data analysis processes are then outlined, focussing on analysis of the individual case studies, and a subsequent cross-case analysis.

5.2. Research Design

In terms of research design, this study utilises multiple, instrumental case studies. As will be discussed in greater detail throughout this chapter, three case studies were conducted, relating to the experience of living with dementia in 1) sheltered housing, 2) very sheltered and extra care housing, and 3) perspectives on supported housing as a future housing choice for people living with dementia. Case studies one and two involved sheltered housing, and very sheltered or extra care housing settings, respectively. They involve people living with dementia, family members, and housing, health, and social care professionals. These case studies allowed for the development of an understanding of the experience of living in different models of supported housing, including the presentation of findings that are unique to each individual case study, and comparisons of findings across the case studies. Case study three involves people with dementia only. This case study sought to include perspectives on supported housing as a future housing choice, in acknowledgement of the limited housing options available in Scotland, and the associated challenges when accessing appropriate housing.

5.2.1. Case Selection

With reference to the study of programmes, Stake (2006) states that multiple case study research, involving less than four, or more than ten individual case studies, might limit the development of an understanding of the quintain. This is because less than four case studies would, likely, not generate enough information about the quintain, with over ten case studies providing more information than could be comprehended by a research team (Stake, 2006). Discussion around numbers or sample sizes in qualitative research, particularly research guided by a social constructionist philosophy, is not entirely helpful. Rather, the emphasis is on the richness or quality of the data collected, instead of the number of people interviewed (Maxwell, 2010). Hence, Stake's recommendation for the number of case studies to conduct is based on his subjective experience and not concrete. Nonetheless, it has been used as a guide.

Some changes have been made to recruitment processes in this study since its inception, largely due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The original aim of the study was to conduct up to eight case studies, each centred around an individual living in the four recognised models of supported housing in Scotland, focussing on 1)

shared housing, 2) sheltered housing, 3) very-sheltered or extra care housing, and 4) dementia-specific supported housing. Each case study would be built from the person with dementia, with the focus on them nominating other informants for the case study, such as family members, friends, and housing, health, or social care professionals. However, due to complexities with recruitment, caused by gatekeeper availability and restrictions due to the COVID-19 pandemic, it was clear early on that this approach would not be suitable. Therefore, the decision was made to change the focus of the case studies to be built around the model of supported housing, and perspectives on supported housing as a future housing choice, to allow for more flexibility with the gathering of data and recruitment processes. The next section provides a more detailed overview of the impact of COVID-19 on recruitment and the formation of the case studies.

5.2.1.1. Impact of COVID-19 on Recruitment and Case Study Design

Between March 2021 and July 2021, meetings were held to discuss the research study with professionals in management positions. Individuals from one social care and five housing organisations were involved. These individuals worked within the four recognised supported housing models, outlined above. They expressed interest in the study, and the subsequent ethics application and study protocol were developed to reflect these discussions. At the time, the associated housing settings supported people living with dementia, who met the inclusion criteria for the research. Following ethical approval, the initial push for recruitment, between September 2021 and October 2021, involved following up with contacts from these settings.

Due to the changing nature of the pandemic, three of the housing organisations reported that they no longer supported individuals living with dementia, including contacts from shared housing settings. From the two remaining housing organisations, one manager of a dementia-specific supported housing setting reported that all individuals with dementia, that were living in the setting, had now been assessed as not having capacity. This meant that they could no longer be involved in the research. Contacts from the final housing organisation were positive, and following a meeting, had agreed to distribute study information to housing officers working for the organisation. However, this yielded no participants.

Hence, it became evident that the study would struggle to recruit individuals living in supported housing settings operating as shared housing environments, or dementia-specific supported housing settings. It was

also apparent that recruiting individuals living with dementia in sheltered, very sheltered, and extra care housing would be difficult, given the unprecedented impact of the pandemic. Resultantly, the case studies were restructured, as depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Restructuring of the case studies. Note, the Contemplating Group refers to individuals who have considered, or are considering, moving into supported housing.

Within case studies one and two, the plan was to recruit a person with dementia from each setting, a family member, and a member of housing, health, and social care staff. Due to expected challenges with recruitment, the third case study was conceptualised, together with objective four of this study, which aims to understand perspectives on supported housing as a future housing choice for people with dementia. This case study was structured differently to case studies one and two and involved interviews with people living with dementia only. Although not the original plan, this would provide invaluable information regarding people with dementia's perceptions on supported housing. Furthermore, the flexible approach of Stake's (1995) methodology enables changes like this to be made throughout the research process, as the case studies unfold and new directions for inquiry present themselves (Parlett and Hamilton, 1972; Stake, 1995). This is in recognition of the uncertainty associated with conducting naturalistic or field-oriented research (Stake, 1995).

5.2.2. Recruitment

5.2.2.1. Gatekeeping and Access

Recruitment was conducted in several ways. First, recruitment of people living with dementia in supported housing was facilitated by the involvement of gatekeepers. Gatekeepers were sought from providers of each of the housing types, discussed above. Gatekeepers were the housing or care managers working within the supported housing settings, with additional permissions to conduct the research sought from the relevant housing organisations. Inclusion criteria for individuals living with dementia were provided to the

gatekeepers (Appendix 5). The gatekeepers then identified potential participants who met the inclusion criteria or shared the information with all individuals living in the settings, to account for those that have not disclosed their diagnosis. Following this, a study flyer was provided to the potential participant (Appendix 6), containing information about the study and the researcher's contact details. The individual then contacted the researcher directly to indicate that they would like to be involved. Second, due to expected challenges with recruitment, if no people with dementia in the settings had the capacity to provide informed consent, involvement of family members or friends, and a member of housing, health, or social care professionals, was sought if they expressed interest in the study. Although this was not ideal, the views of family members, friends, and professionals provided invaluable insights regarding living with incapacity and dementia in supported housing. The voices of these individuals would otherwise be missing from the study, as the ethical approval obtained would not allow for adults with incapacity to be involved in the research.

5.2.2.2. Recruitment through Social Media, Newsletters, and Attendance at Events

To extend the study's reach, the study was also shared through social media, newsletters, and through attendance at events relating to supported housing. As such, information about the study was shared through flyers (Appendix 7). The study was shared through the researcher's personal Twitter account, and the Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice Twitter and Facebook accounts.

Additionally, individuals from housing and dementia organisations were contacted, and the flyer was shared through their associated newsletters. The study was shared through the Scottish Government Housing and Dementia Policy Subgroup, the Care Inspectorate, the Scottish Social Services Council, the Chartered Institute of Housing, the Scottish Federation of Housing Associations, Scottish Housing News, the Dementia Services Development Centre, and the Alzheimer Scotland Allied Health Professionals forum, and various housing organisations. The study flyer was sent through associated newsletters or emailed to relevant contacts working in supported housing.

Finally, the researcher attended an event hosted by the Scottish Federation of Housing Associations, and an event attended by representatives from all housing organisations in Inverclyde, to present a study overview. If any individual contacted the researcher for involvement, the gatekeeper method would be followed.

5.2.3. Participants

5.2.3.1. People Living with Dementia

The inclusion criteria for people living with dementia in supported housing were:

- Living with a diagnosis of dementia, and aware of this diagnosis.
- Ability to provide informed consent to participate.
- Living in a supported housing setting in Scotland for a minimum of six months prior to the start of the study.
- Agree to conduct interviews in-person, if COVID-19 infection control guidelines permit, or through telephone or videocall.

The inclusion criteria for people living with dementia in the contemplating case study were:

- Living with a diagnosis of dementia, and aware of this diagnosis.
- Ability to provide informed consent to participate.
- Living in standard housing in the community in Scotland, but were considering, or had considered, a move to supported housing.

Selection of participants with a diagnosis of dementia, and awareness of this diagnosis, aimed to ensure that the findings are of relevance to those living with the condition. This approach was informed through understanding of relevant theories relating to dementia. As discussed in Section 3.2.2., social citizenship theory stresses that those living with dementia are social citizens with equal rights (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010). Perspectives on dementia need to shift from seeing:

... the individual person as a passive care recipient to seeing the person as an active social agent in the broad context of their lifestyle, life course, social networks and community activities. (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010, p. 4).

As such, those living with dementia have equal rights to be actively involved in their community and in society, including involvement in research, to influence issues that directly impact their lives (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010). As the evidence base relating to the experience of living with dementia in supported

housing is presently lacking, actively involving those living with dementia aimed to provide much needed insights about the potential of supported housing to facilitate access to health and social care, to promote social relationships and community connections, and to provide a dementia-friendly environment that promotes the independence of those living with dementia.

Further, including people with dementia that had lived in a supported housing setting for a period of six months or longer aimed to include those that had time to familiarise themselves with the supported housing setting and its surrounding community, and arrange support or care if needed.

5.2.3.2. Family Members or Friends

Family members or friends of people living with dementia were recruited in two ways. Those living with dementia, who were actively involved in the study, were asked to nominate a family member or friend to be interviewed. However, if a family member or friend of a person living with dementia expressed interest about being involved, but their family member was an adult with incapacity, the family member was offered the opportunity to be involved. For family members or friends, the inclusion criteria were:

- Family member or friend of a person living with dementia in supported housing, nominated by the person living with dementia.
 - Or, in instances where a family member or friend contacted the researcher regarding involvement, but their family member was an adult with incapacity, these individuals were offered the opportunity to be involved.
- With knowledge of the person with dementia's current and / or previous living arrangements.
- Ability to provide informed consent to participate.
- Agree to conduct interviews in-person, if COVID-19 infection control guidelines permitted, or through telephone or videocall.

For people with dementia who were actively involved in the research, nominating a family member or friend aimed to involve people that those living with dementia are comfortable with. The choice to involve family members or friends that contacted the researcher directly was made due to challenges with recruitment. Although the study aimed to involve as many people with dementia as possible, involving such individuals

provided invaluable information regarding the experience of living with dementia, and being an adult with incapacity, in supported housing. Regarding the second bullet point, above, having knowledge of the person with dementia's previous or current living arrangements aimed to gather further insights into the person with dementia's life in the setting, with the ability to discuss how this compared to their previous living arrangements, from their perspectives. As the family members or friends nominated by the person living with dementia may have had pre-existing health conditions, only those with the capacity to provide informed consent were included.

5.2.3.3. Housing, Health, and Social Care Professionals

Housing, health, and social care professionals were recruited in three ways. First, those living with dementia who were involved in the study were asked to nominate a member of staff to be interviewed. As above, in instances where a family member or friend wished to be involved, but the person with dementia was an adult with incapacity, these individuals were asked to nominate a member of staff to be interviewed. For professionals working within the supported housing settings, the inclusion criteria were:

- Housing, health, or social care professionals, nominated by the person with dementia.
 - Or, in instances where the person with dementia was an adult with incapacity, the professional was nominated by a family member or friend.
 - In settings where no people living with dementia, family members, or friends expressed interest regarding involvement, and a professional contacted the researcher regarding involvement, the individual will be offered the opportunity to be involved.
- With knowledge of the person with dementia's current and / or previous living arrangements.
- Agree to conduct interviews in-person, if COVID-19 infection control guidelines permitted, or through telephone or videocall.

For people with dementia involved in the study, professionals were nominated by the person living with dementia, to include those they were comfortable with being involved. Again, knowledge of the person with dementia's current or prior living arrangements aimed to gather further insights into the person with

dementia's life within the setting, from their perspectives, and how this compared to their previous living arrangements.

For all interviews, with all participant groups, if COVID-19 guidelines permitted, and if the individual wished, interviews were conducted in-person following relevant safety procedures and guidelines. If COVID-19 guidelines meant that in-person interviews were not possible, interviews were conducted by telephone or videocall. In these situations, individuals were expected to agree to using telephone or video calls to complete the interviews. For videocalls, Microsoft Teams was the primary videoconferencing software used.

5.3. Ethical Considerations

5.3.1. Identifying Participants and Consent

This study adhered to the University of the West of Scotland's Code of Ethics, with implementation of this code informed by the University of the West of Scotland's guidelines for ethical practice in research and scholarship (University of the West of Scotland, 2020b). Ethical approval for this study was obtained on the 23rd of September 2021, reference number: 16527 (Appendix 8). The University of the West of Scotland proposes four ethical principles, used to guide research with human participants. These are 1) Autonomy, Veracity, and Informed Consent; 2) Privacy and Confidentiality; 3) Justice and Inclusiveness; and 4) Benefits and Harms. Discussion of how these principles were adhered to is provided in the following sections.

5.3.1.1. Autonomy, Veracity, and Informed Consent

This principle acknowledges the right of all individuals to determine their own course of action. The present study aimed to involve people living with dementia, and family members or friends of people living with dementia, who had the capacity to provide informed consent to participate. In accordance with the Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act 2000 (Scottish Parliament, 2000), the definition of an adult with incapacity is anyone over the age of 16, deemed incapable of:

- Acting; or
- Making decisions; or
- Communicating decisions; or

- Understanding decisions; or
- Retaining the memory of decisions.

As such, the study included individuals living with dementia, and family members or friends of people living with dementia, who could act on, make, communicate, understand decisions, and retain memory of these decisions. Steps were taken to ensure that individuals could make autonomous and informed choices about taking part in the research. Capacity was presumed on this basis by the researcher and the gatekeepers, in line with Scottish legislation. However, the recruitment procedures were designed to provide evidence that individuals had the capacity to consent, with data collection procedures developed to ensure the safety of those involved. The sections, below, describe the chosen factors that indicated that an individual had the capacity to consent, in addition to recruitment and selection procedures. These sections also describe how the study, and all related documentation, were designed to be inclusive of people living with dementia and their family members or friends.

5.3.1.1.1. Independent Citizens

5.3.1.1.1.1. Living with Dementia in Supported Housing

The act of living with dementia in supported housing was treated as an indicator of capacity. Supported housing settings aim to facilitate independent living, with most residents occupying self-contained rooms, flats, bungalows, or houses. Although some settings offer higher levels of support or care, the overarching aim of supported housing is to enable people to live independently in their own homes, with additional support provided if needed (Care Information Scotland, 2020). As such, people living with dementia in supported housing in Scotland are classified as tenants or homeowners by law (Brown *et al.*, 2017; Care Information Scotland, 2020).

Supported housing settings typically house those in the early or moderate stages of dementia. Those with advanced dementia, requiring a higher level of personal or medical care, are often referred to care or nursing homes (Barrett, 2021; Brooker, Argyle and Clancy, 2009; Dutton, 2010; Twyford, 2016). This was affirmed during conversations with housing and care managers throughout early meetings to discuss the study. It was also highlighted in literature uncovered in the systematic review and thematic synthesis, shown in Chapter

Two (Aud, 2004; Aud, 2002; Evans and Means, 2006; Evans *et al.*, 2020). Research suggests that those living with the early and moderate stages of dementia are most likely to retain their capacity to provide informed consent (Hegde and Ellajosyula, 2016; Karlawish, 2008). Hence, living in supported housing was deemed an indicator of capacity, in the first instance.

5.3.1.1.2. Recruitment and Selection

5.3.1.1.2.1. Self-Selection

Through the involvement of gatekeepers, people living with dementia in supported housing were identified using specified inclusion criteria. An information flyer about the study was provided to people living with dementia by each gatekeeper (Appendix 6). In other instances, the person with dementia may have seen the study flyer (Appendix 7) through social media or a newsletter. The person living with dementia would then contact the researcher directly if they wished to be involved in the research, either by email or telephone, to enhance autonomy and choice regarding taking part. During this communication, the project was discussed in greater detail, any questions about the study were answered, and contact information was gathered. This process of contacting the researcher, having read, considered, and processed the information included in the flyer, acted as another indicator of capacity.

5.3.1.1.2.2. Obtaining Informed Consent

After initial contact, it was expected that the person living with dementia would indicate if they would like to be involved in the study. A more detailed participant information sheet (Appendix 9) and consent form (Appendix 10) was provided to the person living with dementia. This information was provided up to two weeks in advance of our interviews, via email or as a paper copy, to ensure that individuals have the time to read and process the information and ask any further questions (Alzheimer Europe, 2019).

Throughout the duration of data collection, if COVID-19 guidelines permitted, and if the individual wished, interviews were conducted in person. However, interviews could also be conducted via video or telephone call, if restrictions were in place, or if the individual preferred. To facilitate remote interviewing, written, informed consent was gathered through email. The consent form was adapted for electronic use. Written consent through electronic signature was approved by the United Kingdom Health Research Authority, and

the Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency, as a method of obtaining informed consent, prior to the commencement of the study (The Health Research Authority and The Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency, 2018). Consent was either obtained in advance of the interview, or, if the person did not complete the consent form or wished to talk through the form with the researcher, consent was obtained during the interview using a paper copy. In addition to written consent, verbal consent was sought at the start of any interview to seek permission for the interview to be recorded and to ensure that the participant was comfortable taking part.

The process consent method was also adopted during interviews with those living with dementia (Dewing, 2008). Given that the capacity of those living with dementia can fluctuate, the process consent method aimed to ensure that those living with dementia retained their capacity to provide informed consent throughout the research process (Dewing, 2008). As there was a possibility that multiple interviews would be conducted with each individual living with dementia, this is an important consideration. Throughout initial contact with those living with dementia, and throughout interviews, awareness of verbal, non-verbal, and behavioural indicators of reduced capacity were developed (Dewing, 2008). Any indicators of distress, fatigue, or discomfort were considered, and the interview would have been stopped if these indicators were consistently presented. If any issues with capacity were encountered, these would have been discussed with academic supervisors, and the relevant gatekeeper, to determine if it was safe for the individual to be involved. The process consent method had been used successfully in qualitative studies conducted in supported housing settings with people living with dementia, prior to the commencement of this research study, and is an established method of obtaining informed consent (Barrett, Atkinson and Evans, 2016; Cameron *et al.*, 2019; Cameron, Johnson Eleanor and Evans, 2020; Evans *et al.*, 2020; O'Malley *et al.*, 2018).

For family members, friends, or staff, in keeping with the steps outlined previously, participant information sheets (Appendix 9) and consent forms (Appendix 10) were provided in advance of the interviews. Consent was either obtained before the interview by email or as a paper copy, or during the interview prior to data collection. As family members and friends were expected to have capacity to provide written, informed consent, any indication that the person had not read and understood the information provided, or exhibited

distress, fatigue, or discomfort, would have been considered. If the family member or friend demonstrated a loss of capacity, the interview would have been stopped, and the events would be discussed with academic supervisors.

5.3.1.1.3. Inclusive Study Design

5.3.1.1.3.1. Information Provided to Participants

All documentation provided to those involved in the study was designed to be sufficiently detailed, relevant, and accurate, in accordance with the University of the West of Scotland's ethical guidelines (2020b). The development of this study's procedures and the associated ethics application were informed by The Dementia Engagement and Empowerment Project ethics gold standards for dementia research, and the Scottish Dementia Working Group's research sub-group core principles for involving people with dementia in research (The Dementia Empowerment and Engagement Project, 2020; The Scottish Dementia Working Group Research Sub-Group, 2014). Further, all participant information sheets, consent forms, and other documentation provided to those living with dementia and their family members or friends was developed in accordance with guidelines developed by The Dementia Engagement and Empowerment Project on use of dementia-friendly language and written content (The Dementia Engagement and Empowerment Project, 2014; The Dementia Engagement and Empowerment Project, 2013). This aimed to ensure that all written content was accessible to people living with dementia and their family members or friends, to better inform their decision about taking part in the research, and to promote openness about what the research would involve. Additionally, any information provided to people living with dementia during the study was provided up to two weeks in advance of their involvement in the research, to allow time to process information, in accordance with Alzheimer Europe's guidelines for the involvement of people living with dementia in research (Gove *et al.*, 2018).

5.3.1.1.3.2. Selection of Data Collection Methods

Interviews with people living with dementia were developed in accordance with best practice, which emphasises the benefits in conducting multiple, shorter interviews to limit fatigue and enhance the meaningfulness and quality of the interview content (Beuscher and Grando, 2009; Cridland *et al.*, 2016).

5.3.1.2. Privacy and Confidentiality

All data were anonymised and pseudonyms were given to all participants. Only the researcher and their academic supervisors had access to the data. Data were managed in accordance with the Data Protection Act (2018) (U.K. Government, 2018), and the University of the West of Scotland's Data Protection Code of Practice (University of the West of Scotland, 2020a). In accordance with the University of the West of Scotland's Data Retention Schedule for Research, data are to be stored for 10 years, and then destroyed (University of the West of Scotland, 2022). Interview data was anonymised at the point of transcription and audio copies were destroyed once transcription accuracy was confirmed.

In accordance with the University of the West of Scotland's Data Classification Schedule, all research data were stored and backed up on a University of the West of Scotland affiliated, and password protected, Microsoft OneDrive account (University of the West of Scotland, 2021). Consent forms, contact details, and any documentation containing personal details were stored separately from the research data. For interviews conducted in-person, all paper copies of documentation, audio recorders, and cameras were transported securely in a locked car. Paper copies of consent forms and any other documents were scanned immediately, stored on the University of the West of Scotland encrypted hard drive, and backed up on the researcher's University of the West of Scotland affiliated Microsoft OneDrive account. Paper copies were then destroyed. Audio recorded interviews and photographs were transferred immediately to the encrypted hard drive and backed up on the researcher's University of the West of Scotland affiliated Microsoft OneDrive account and deleted from the devices.

5.3.1.3. Justice and Inclusiveness

Interviewed individuals were offered a choice regarding which interview method to use (i.e., in-person, online, or telephone), and interviews were conducted during a time that was convenient for them, in keeping with guidelines for involving people living with dementia in research (The Dementia Empowerment and Engagement Project, 2020; The Scottish Dementia Working Group Research Sub-Group, 2014). The option of remote interviewing promoted inclusivity for people who may not have been able to take part in the research, due to work or family commitments, or those that had concerns regarding the spread of COVID-19.

Within the context of research conducted in supported housing, the systematic review in Chapter Two showed that there is a lack of high-quality evidence that adequately considers the perspectives of those living with dementia. Given that this research focusses on those living with dementia, it adds to our understanding of living with dementia in supported housing, from the perspectives of a currently underrepresented group. Further, all information provided to participants was designed carefully in accordance with dementia-friendly guidelines, and selection of data collection methods aimed to be reflective of best practice, to limit fatigue or burden and promote meaningful engagement in the research.

5.3.1.4. Benefits and Harms

This study was designed to be low-risk, and the researcher's academic supervisors had extensive experience conducting research of this type. This ensured that appropriate consideration was given to the data collection procedures and their ethical implications. Given that the evidence base relating to living with dementia in supported housing was still in its infancy at the time of conducting the research, and there had yet to be a formal research study conducted in Scotland, this research would be of significant value to future residents of supported housing.

During the interviews with those living with dementia, there may have been a possibility that interviewees became upset or distressed. This could have been likely if the individual experienced social isolation or was unhappy in their home environment. Throughout the interviews, if the individual became distressed, the interview would be stopped. The interview would be rearranged if the individual wished, and they would have been provided with details of their local Alzheimer Scotland Resource Centre, and the Alzheimer Scotland helpline, if they required further support.

Further, interview methods with people living with dementia were developed in accordance with best practice in qualitative dementia research. Guidelines produced by the Scottish Dementia Working Group research sub-group (2014) and The Dementia Engagement and Empowerment Project (2013; 2014) stress that interviews with people living with dementia should incorporate breaks and be clearly structured to enhance engagement and enable the person living with dementia to make a meaningful contribution to the research. Individuals were offered breaks and the opportunity to conduct multiple, shorter interviews. Those

involved were also able to conduct the interviews through a method of their choosing, to ensure the interview was conducted in an environment that was comfortable for them. The aim of this approach was to create a supportive environment for the person living with dementia to be involved meaningfully in the research.

Interviews with family members and staff were also low risk. One consideration was that family members may be of older age or may be living with a long-term health condition. Throughout the interviews, participants were offered breaks to limit fatigue, and interviews were conducted using a method of their choice, at a date and time that was suitable for them. Discussing their relative that was living with dementia may have been upsetting. Again, if a family member became distressed or upset during the interview, the interview would have been stopped and rearranged for a later date, if the individual wished.

Another possible consideration was the disclosure of poor support or care practices, or the witnessing or discussion of neglect during any interview or supported housing visit. Should this have been witnessed, or if an individual disclosed information regarding poor care or neglect, either received themselves or relating to another resident within the setting, this would have been discussed with the researcher's academic supervisors in the first instance. A decision would have been made to determine how to proceed.

A further consideration is the possibility that the researcher would test positive for COVID-19, risking spread of the virus to individuals being interviewed. The researcher received all possible doses of the COVID-19 vaccination at the time of the research. Prior to any interviews being conducted in-person, or any visitations to the supported housing sites, a COVID-19 lateral flow test was completed, and the researcher only accessed the premises if the test was negative. All social distancing and infection control measures were adhered to.

For the photographs taken of the physical environment, there were two main considerations: 1) the photographs containing personally identifiable imagery, and 2) the photographs showing imagery that poses a threat to the safety of the person with dementia, or any other residents or professionals working in the settings. To address the first issue, shared or communal areas of the supported housing settings were photographed when they were not in use. This was informed by discussions with the gatekeeper or manager for the specific settings. To illustrate, photographs of corridors were taken when empty, and any images of

dining or communal areas were taken at times other than mealtimes or during social activities, to ensure they were not in use. For photographs taken inside the houses of those living with dementia, photographs that included personally identifiable information were edited to redact this imagery before disseminating.

For the second consideration, above, a plan with the gatekeeper or managers from each of the supported housing settings was developed regarding how to respond if an unsafe environment was witnessed. An unsafe environment, in this instance, would have been one that was deemed to be of immediate risk to the safety of the person living with dementia, other residents, and staff working in the settings - e.g., a potential fire risk. The consent form for those living with dementia (Appendix 10) included a section consenting to the informing of a member of staff if an unsafe environment was observed. If an unsafe environment was observed, the researcher would inform the gatekeeper or manager in the first instance.

As the researcher was working alone, visiting supported housing premises, lone working procedures were followed. Prior to entering any supported housing location, the researcher confirmed this with one of their academic supervisors. Once leaving the setting, the academic supervisors were informed. If the researcher had not contacted their academic supervisor within the specified timeframe, agreed prior to entering the setting, the supervisor would have followed standard procedure.

5.4. Data Collection Methods

Each case study involved interviews with people living with dementia, their family members or friends, and members of housing or care staff working within the settings. Photographs of the physical environments of the supported housing settings were also gathered, in addition to documentation relating to the supported housing setting. For descriptive purposes, outcome measures were used to provide an added layer of information regarding independence, social, and psychological wellbeing. For the contemplating case study, interviews with people living with dementia were conducted.

5.4.1. Interviews with People Living with Dementia in Supported Housing

Interviews involving people living with dementia in supported housing were semi-structured, with a brief interview schedule developed around the objectives of the study: The Home Environment, Social

Relationships and Community Connections, and Support and Care. As Stake states, for qualitative case study research, “The qualitative interviewer should arrive with a short list of issue-oriented questions.” (Stake, 1995, p. 65). In accordance with this, the interview schedules are shown in Appendix 11.

In the first instance, those living with dementia were offered the opportunity to conduct multiple, shorter interviews, focussed on the study’s objectives, as opposed to one longer interview. This method was proposed as it had been described as best practice in research involving people living with dementia, to limit fatigue (e.g., The Scottish Dementia Working Group Research Sub-Group, 2014). However, if the individual preferred, the interview was conducted in one session. All interviews were audio recorded.

5.4.2. Interviews with People Living with Dementia in the Contemplating Case Study

Interviews with those involved in the contemplating case study were also semi-structured and again focussed on the topics developed through the systematic review: The Home Environment, Social Relationships and Community Connections, and Support and Care. However, in these interviews, the focus was on their current living arrangements and perspectives on supported housing as a future housing choice. The interview schedule is provided in Appendix 11. Those involved in the contemplating group were also offered the opportunity to conduct the interviews via videocall, telephone, or in-person. All interviews were audio recorded.

5.4.3. Interviews with Family Members, Friends, and Professionals

Interviews with family members, friends, or professionals working within the supported housing settings were either structured around their relationship with the person with dementia that had nominated them, or involved a more general discussion, should this not be the case. A semi-structured interview guide relating to the topics of The Home Environment, Social Relationships and Community Connections, and Support and Care was developed to explore these concepts in more depth from their perspectives (Appendix 11). Those involved were also offered the opportunity to conduct the interviews via videocall, telephone, or in-person. All interviews were audio recorded.

5.4.4. Photographs

Photographs could have been used in two ways. First, to stimulate discussion and promote the collection of novel data during interviews, a digital camera was offered to each person living with dementia, prior to commencement of data collection. This would only be provided to the participant if they wished, otherwise interviews would adhere to the interview guide. If an individual opted to use the digital camera, the person with dementia would have been asked to take photographs relating to the topic of interview. Prompts would have been given to the person living with dementia about what these photographs might include, e.g., “my favourite space”, “where I like to eat”, “where I like to relax”. These prompts are outlined in the participant information sheet in Appendix 9. The participant would have been asked to share the photographs with the researcher, either through email prior to the interview, or if preferred, shown during the interview. Using photo-elicitation to stimulate conversation with people living with dementia is an established method of data collection (Phillipson and Hammond, 2018).

Second, photographs were taken of the homes of those living in supported housing, and of the supported housing developments. This, largely, aimed to provide contextual information and support the development of vicarious experiences for the reader (Stake, 1995). Further, an extensive assessment of the physical environments of the supported housing developments was not conducted. However, to facilitate the development of descriptions of the physical environments, and the extent to which dementia-friendly design principles are evident in practice, elements of the King’s Fund environmental assessment tool, for use in supported housing environments, were considered (The King's Fund, 2020). The environmental assessment tool is split into seven categories, covering 67 assessment criteria. The categories relate to whether the environment promotes: meaningful interaction and activity, wellbeing, eating and drinking, mobility, continence / personal hygiene, orientation, and safety / security.

Access to the supported housing premises was agreed with relevant managers from the housing organisation / gatekeepers. To limit the amount of time spent in the premises and to facilitate a richer analysis, a camera with in-built 360-degree photograph functionality (Insta360 One X2) was used to take photographs of the main areas of the building, including corridors, communal areas, dining rooms, and with permission, the

home environment of the person with dementia or an unoccupied dwelling with a similar layout to the person with dementia's home.

5.4.5. Outcome Measures and Demographic Information

Measures related to social engagement and independence, psychological wellbeing, and quality of life. The aim was that these measures would be completed by each person with dementia. Selection of measures was informed by recently developed outcomes lists of relevance to dementia. These included outcomes lists that were developed through the Real-world Outcomes of Alzheimer's Disease for better care: Multi-modal data Access Platform (ROADMAP) project (Gallacher *et al.*, 2019; Janssen *et al.*, 2020), a core outcome set developed for use in non-pharmacological, community based (including supported housing) health and social care interventions in dementia (Harding *et al.*, 2020; Reilly *et al.*, 2020), and a core outcome set developed for use in clinical trials in dementia (Webster *et al.*, 2017a; Webster *et al.*, 2017b). Following review of outcome measures, three were selected based on ease of completion and free use. The purpose of using these measures was not to conduct inferential statistical analysis. Rather, they were selected to provide contextual information regarding the person's condition.

The Engagement and Independence in Dementia Questionnaire (EID-Q) (Stoner *et al.*, 2017; Stoner, Orrell and Spector, 2018a) contains 26 items relating to activities of daily living, decision making, activity engagement, support, and reciprocity. Together, the measure aims to assess sense of independence and social engagement.

The Positive Psychology Outcome Measure (PPOM) (Stoner *et al.*, 2017; Stoner, Orrell and Spector, 2018b) contains 16 items relating to hope and resilience. It will be used to provide an overall measure of psychological wellbeing.

Quality of Life in Alzheimer's Disease (QoL-AD) (Logsdon *et al.*, 1999; Logsdon *et al.*, 2002) contains 13 items relating to relationships with friends and family, living arrangements, concerns about finances, physical condition, and mood, providing an overall assessment of life quality.

Additionally, demographic information will be sought from the person living with dementia. This will include information on gender, age, and time living in the supported housing settings.

At this stage, it is important to note that data from the outcome measures will not be presented in the case studies. To provide context, the outcome measures were completed by the first individual with dementia that was involved in the study. After a conversation with this individual, it was noted that the outcome measures were unhelpful and added little to the overall understanding of the aim and objectives of the research. Administration of the outcome measures also disrupted the natural flow of the interview. Hence, the decision was made to not complete the outcome measures with any other individual who was interviewed, in all case studies. Again, the flexible nature of Stake's (1995) case study methodology allows for decisions like this to be made throughout the research process. Although it was initially envisaged that the outcome measures would provide some level of context, on reflection, they were not helpful in the context of this study.

5.4.6. Documents

Documentation from the housing providers was sought throughout the duration of each case study, such as reports from the Care Inspectorate, business plans, annual reviews, housing allocation policies, and brochures from the settings. These were either downloaded from relevant websites or accessed through the housing providers. As stated by Stake (1995; 2006), it is important to develop context within each case study. Within the analysis process, the documents were used to help develop an understanding of the context of each setting. Analysis allowed the key information about each setting to be distilled to provide a rich description of each of the case study settings. For example, the information included in these documents was used when describing the settings, such as the support or care provided within the settings, the organisation of social activities, the provision of meals, and descriptions of the underlying goals or aims of the settings. They also provide other contextual information, such as the number of dwellings within each setting, the amenities available within the developments, and the typical layouts of the dwellings within the settings. The document types collected from each setting will be described in each of the case studies. Due to issues with confidentiality and sharing identifiable information, the content of these documents are not reproduced (i.e.,

through excerpts) within this thesis. This is because the documents sought are accessible to the public, meaning that the content of these documents could be traced back to the involved settings. Hence, only contextual information, that is not identifiable, will be used.

5.5. Data Analysis

5.5.1. Preparation of Data for Analysis

5.5.1.1. Transcription

Audio-recorded interviews were transcribed verbatim and anonymised. Seven interviews were first transcribed by the researcher, facilitated by Trint software (<https://trint.com/>). Due to time pressures, the remaining interviews were transcribed by a professional transcription service. Trint is a version of computer assisted transcription software, which uses automated speech recognition software and natural language processing algorithms to transcribe human utterances into written words (Jenkins, Monaghan and Smith, 2021). Trint allows the transcript and audio-recording to be viewed in one place, with sections of the interview timestamped and hyperlinked to the audio-recording.

This study is not concerned with how people use speech, as in conversation or discourse analysis, where researchers are concerned with paralinguistics, like hesitation, talking speed, or intonation (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018). In line with Stake's (1995) description of qualitative research, this study is more concerned with using the content of the interviews to develop an understanding of human experience. Hence, complex transcription processes, commonly used in conversation or discourse analysis, were not used (Silverman, 1993). However, as Stake's (1995) case study methodology emphasises naturalistic research, it was important to retain some intonation that helps convey meaning in the spoken word (King and Horrocks, 2010). Hence, orthographic transcription, as described by Braun and Clarke, was used (Braun and Clarke, 2013). Orthographic transcription retains some additional, nonverbal information, such as laughter, coughing, and pauses – though, not at the level of other methods of transcription (e.g., Silverman, 1993). As such, this transcription method was deemed suitable for the present study. All anonymised transcripts were uploaded to an NVivo 12 Pro (QSR International Pty Ltd, 2020) database to support data management and the analysis process.

5.5.1.2. Photographs

Throughout the analysis process, identifiable imagery was removed from photographs. Photographs taken using the Insta360 One X2 were edited using the Insta360 Studio 2022. This editing process involved taking still frames from the 360-degree images captured, to show various locations within the supported housing settings. Still frames were deidentified in Microsoft PowerPoint. Edited images were saved as new image files. If photographs were taken by those living with dementia, these would also have been deidentified in Microsoft PowerPoint, and saved as new image files.

For each image, a description was developed based on the guidelines for visual analysis produced by Rose (Rose, 1996). For example, descriptions were informed using a series of prompts, such as: What is being shown? What are the components of the image? Was it one of a series? What do the different components of the image signify? (Skinner *et al.*, 2014, p. 6). Further, components of the King's Fund (2020) environmental assessment tool were considered, focussing on factors like colour, contrast, signage, and lighting. This approach has previously been used in Stakian case study research (Skinner *et al.*, 2014), and is complimentary to the interpretive nature of Stake's approach. The descriptions were uploaded to the NVivo 12 Pro database (QSR International Pty Ltd, 2020), and analysed textually, together with the interview transcripts and documents.

5.5.1.3. Documents

As stated previously, documents were used to provide further context to the case studies. All documents used in this thesis were available to download as PDF files from the housing providers' websites, or from the Care Inspectorate website. As such, the documents were uploaded to the NVivo 12 Pro database (QSR International Pty Ltd, 2020), and were analysed textually, together with the interview transcripts and photograph descriptions. No formal documentary analysis methodology was followed. Rather, the textual information included in these documents was coded in the same way as the transcripts and photograph descriptions. In this regard, the information taken from the documents related to support and care provision, the organisation of social activities, the provision of meals, descriptions of the underlying goals or aims of the

settings, the number of dwellings within each setting, the amenities available within the developments, and the typical layouts of the dwellings within the settings.

5.5.1.4. Outcome Measures

It was intended that the outcome measures would be collated into scores relating to the specific measure, to provide further contextual information regarding people with dementia's perspectives on independence, social interaction, quality of life, and wellbeing. As stated, the decision was made not to complete or report these measures, given that they were deemed to be unhelpful in the context of the overall case studies, and disrupted the natural flow of the interviews.

5.5.2. Analysis of the Individual Case Studies

5.5.2.1. Description of Context

Stake (1995) states that the world we know is largely a human construction, with knowledge constructed through shared experience and learning. In this regard, the sharing of knowledge, in research, is partly based on the researcher's interpretation of events. Additionally, the reader of this thesis will also create their own constructions of knowledge and interpretations regarding what has been shared, in congruence with social constructionism and ontological relativism. Therefore, an important part of reporting case study findings involves providing description to invoke vicarious experiences for the reader (Stake, 1995). In this regard, vicarious experiences help the reader develop experiential understanding of phenomena, based on the interpretation of the researcher (Stake, 1995). These vicarious experiences lead to naturalistic generalisations.

As Stake describes, naturalistic generalisations are conclusions that are developed from 1) personal experiences, or 2) vicarious experiences that are constructed to enable the reader to feel as if they are experiencing events themselves (Stake, 1995, p. 85). The reader then relates these to their own experiences, contexts, and research (Braun and Clarke, 2022). Key to enhancing vicarious experience is the emphasis of time, place, and person when providing description (Stake, 1995). Relatedly, and central to Stake's case study methodology, is the importance of context and situationality, that is, the uniqueness or particularities of a case study, including physical, political, and social contexts (Stake, 1995; Stake, 2006).

As such, the initial step of the analysis of each individual case study involves presenting contextual information. This is in the form of description, using data from interviews, documents, and photographs to situate the case study in context. This description focusses on the supported housing developments, and the individuals involved in the case studies, to provide context and situationality.

This is done through Stake's (1995) analytical approaches of direct interpretation and categorical aggregation. Direct interpretation relates to providing an interpretation of a singular instance, whereas categorical aggregation relates to the aggregation of instances "...until something can be said about them as a class." (Stake, 1995, p. 74). Both approaches utilise codes. Direct interpretation relates to single instances of a code, that are unique to that interview, document, or setting. Categorical aggregation involves grouping coded data into categories or themes, based on commonalities. This does not mean that every piece of data must be summarised or interpreted. The aim is to search for meaning in the data, to develop descriptions that address the issues of the research through interpretation, providing enough information to determine how findings were developed (Stake, 1995).

Stake (1995) utilises descriptive codes in his approach to direct interpretation and categorical aggregation. That is, assigning a single word or phrase to a segment of data to summarise its content. For example, "decorum", "ambiance", or "work ethic" (Stake, 1995, p. 82). This approach to coding has been described as useful for qualitative studies that use multiple data sources (Miles, Huberman and Saldaña, 2018). Contextual information was taken from the interview transcripts, based on discussions with those involved in the case studies. For example, professionals were asked to describe the settings in detail, and to provide information about the services they offered. Contextual information was also extracted from the documentation gathered from the settings, including information relating to support and care provision, the organisation of social activities, the provision of meals, descriptions of the underlying goals or aims of the settings, the number of dwellings within each setting, the amenities available within the developments, and the typical layouts of the dwellings within the settings. The photographs provide an added layer of contextual information and show the layouts of the dwellings and communal areas within the settings. Hence, descriptions were developed, utilising all data sources, as follows:

- 1) Transcripts, photograph descriptions, documents, and demographic data were stored in an NVivo 12 Pro database.
- 2) The data were then reread, and the researcher familiarised themselves with the content.
- 3) Descriptive codes, relating to context, were assigned to sections of the text. For example, codes related to the setting's location, the size and structure of the setting, the support and care provided, additional services offered, and characteristics of the individuals involved in the case studies.
- 4) Detailed descriptions were assigned to each code within NVivo 12 Pro, including the researcher's interpretations of the coded data.
- 5) Descriptions of the settings and participants were then developed, to provide context for the reader.

Steps were taken to ensure that this process was rigorous. The central quality criterion in Stake's (1995) research relates to triangulation. As such, descriptions are supported by photographs to provide context, in addition to using content from interviews, documents, and demographic information to triangulate any interpretations. Further, the data used to provide contextual descriptions are, typically, incontestable (Stake, 1995). That is, the data relate to the building's size and structure, the length of time participants have lived or worked in the settings, the services provided, when the settings were built, and suchlike. Hence, the researcher's interpretations are less abstract and more concrete. Nonetheless, the summaries and contextual information were assessed for soundness by the researcher's supervisory team, through review of the case study reports and supervisory meetings.

5.5.2.2. Development of Themes

The remainder of the individual case study analyses utilised Stake's (1995) approach to categorical aggregation, to develop case study specific themes. As this study involves instrumental case studies, with the goal of understanding the overall aim and objectives of the study, with slightly less focus on the uniqueness or particularity of each case study, categorical aggregation is described as the most suitable approach (Stake, 1995). This stage of the analysis uses interview content, photograph descriptions, and documents.

Table 4: An overview of the initial codes developed from the conceptual framework outlined in Chapter Three. The codes and their related descriptions have been developed from theory, namely, environmental press - competence, the integrative framework of ageing well, personhood and person-centred care, and social citizenship.

Theory				
	Environmental Press-Competence	Integrative Framework of Ageing Well	Personhood and Person-Centred Care	Social Citizenship
Codes and Code Descriptions	<p><u>Press</u> Physical and social pressures or demands.</p>	<p><u>Behaviour Driven Agency</u> Goal-directed behaviour and having control over the physical environment, relating to the ability to change environments to meet needs, through adapting, retrofitting, and creating places.</p>	<p><u>Evidence of the Provision of Person-Centred Care</u> Description of the provision of person-centred care, emphasising the centrality of meeting an individual's personal needs and wants.</p>	<p><u>Attachment</u> An emotional bond to another person or place. Focus on psychological connectedness. Linked to place attachment, aspects of familiarity.</p> <p><u>Solidarity</u> Uniting with others to make a difference. The need for people to get together to create collective action. Focus on everyday experiences, local community influences, taking responsibility for others.</p>
	<p><u>Competence</u> An individual's abilities to meet these pressures or demands.</p>	<p><u>Experience Driven Belonging</u> Relates to place attachment, identity, the meaning of home, familiarity, and how these influence an individual's affective, cognitive, behavioural, and social bonds with their environment, which can develop over time.</p>	<p><u>Barriers to the Provision of Person-Centred Care</u> Barriers might relate to resources, dementia awareness, funding, etc.</p>	<p><u>Comfort</u> Feeling comfort in body and mind, experiencing human tenderness and warmth. Experiencing a sense of security in terms of feeling physically fine and free from harm or threat.</p> <p><u>Growth</u> Having opportunities to grow as human beings. To develop different aspects of oneself. Can be artistic, political, spiritual, or growth in relationships. Move away from loss and despair.</p>
		<p><u>Person-Environment Resources</u> Personal (e.g., cognitive functioning, affective functioning, personality traits) and environmental (e.g.,</p>		<p><u>Identity</u> Unique and co-constructed personal identity. Focussing on the maintenance of a sense of self. More emphasis on a fixed identity or set of characteristics.</p>

housing adaptations) resources
impact on belonging and
agency.

Social Positions

Acknowledges that individuals have multiple identities. Focus on social status, an individual's life course, and social structures. Different social positions hold different status in different contexts.

Inclusion

Focus on including those living with dementia in decisions, predominantly relating to care decisions.

Participation

Focus on agency and self-control - the right to participate in life in whatever way possible. Not only care decisions, but in wider sociopolitical issues and participation in civic life.

Love

Feeling cherished and respected.

Freedom from Discrimination

The right to being free from negative discrimination. I.e., denial of access to various benefits or services, interpersonal discrimination such as the assumption that an individual cannot think or speak for themselves.

Occupation

Occupation in meaningful activities, such as preparing meals or reminiscing. Focus on an individual's previous occupation and organise activities relating to this. Focus on psychological or therapeutic value. Often an emphasis on "doing".

Purpose

Focus on having a purpose or attributing meaning to life. Focus on what has purpose and meaning for the individual.

As stated in Chapter Three, this study utilises an inductive approach to analysis, informed by relevant theories that act as “lenses.” This aims to develop a deeper understanding of individual’s experiences, rather than testing theories for their soundness in explaining phenomena, in accordance with deductive analysis. In the first instance, a series of descriptive codes were developed based on the theories and conceptual framework outlined in Chapter Three. Specifically, these codes relate to personhood and person-centred care, social citizenship, environmental press – competence, and the integrative framework of ageing well. Table 4 provides an overview of how these codes were structured and described. The descriptions were developed based on how these concepts are described within the related literature.

As stated in Section 3.3, the descriptive codes that have been developed from the conceptual framework are used to enhance interpretations, and the development of a deeper understanding of living with dementia in supported housing. However, this conceptual framework is not fixed, and is open to change. As such, these theories can be thought of as “etic issues”, described by Stake (1995) as the issues and understandings brought in by the researcher prior to data collection. The inductive development of the codes and findings, that stem from these etic issues, led to the development of “emic issues.” These are interpretations of events and experiences that develop throughout the research process. Hence, the development of themes within the individual case studies has been conducted as follows in this research:

- 1) In accordance with Stake’s (1995) analytical approach, a list of “tentative”, descriptive codes was developed, as shown in Table 4.

- 2) Textual data from interview transcripts, photograph descriptions, and documents were first coded using these descriptive codes. These codes were not fixed, with existing codes being developed, and new codes being added, throughout the analytical process.

- 2.1) Though, it should be noted that case study three only involved analysis of interview data, as photographs and documents were not gathered.

- 3) After this initial process of coding, categorical aggregation followed, to restructure the codes into case study specific themes.

This process is heavily based on the researcher's interpretations. Therefore, it is important to demonstrate how rigour was upheld throughout this process. First, interpretations were supported with quotes or imagery, to allow the reader to evaluate the soundness or appropriateness of these interpretations. This is referred to as data source triangulation by Stake (1995). In this regard, if similar experiences are reported by individuals in different settings, or if similar conclusions can be drawn from the imagery gathered in different settings, then this would suggest a degree of triangulation regarding the interpretation of events and experiences.

This relates to methodological triangulation, as described by Stake (1995). This refers to the use of multiple methods of data collection in case study research. For example, this study uses interviews, photographs, and documents, gathered from different perspectives and settings. Hence, using multiple methods supports triangulation in case studies one and two.

Another form of triangulation, discussed by Stake (1995), is referred to as investigator triangulation. This involves having other researchers read interpretations, together with supporting data, to determine the soundness of these interpretations. As such, the case studies were read and evaluated by the researcher's supervisory team, to determine the soundness or appropriateness of any claims made.

Relatedly, a final form of triangulation is referred to as theory triangulation (Stake, 1995). This means that case study reports and interpretations are read by individuals from different research backgrounds, to determine whether the interpretations remain strong when considered by individuals with expertise stemming from different theoretical backgrounds. Members of the supervisory team come from nursing and psychology backgrounds. Therefore, research supervisors critiqued the thesis based on their unique backgrounds, further triangulating the interpretations made.

5.5.2.3. Summary of Case Study Findings

The final process of the analysis involved providing the reader with summary statements of findings outlined in each individual case study. These summaries are formed of short declarative statements and can be evaluated based on the data and interpretations outlined throughout the individual case reports. The summary statements are then used in elements of the cross-case analysis, to develop an understanding of

the similarities and differences that arose throughout the research. At the end of each individual case study, these summaries are presented, which filtered into the cross-case analysis.

5.5.3. Cross-Case Analysis

After the analysis and reporting of each individual case study, a cross-case analysis was conducted following the approach outlined by Stake (2006). Stake (2006, p. 40) states that a cross-case analysis is conducted to understand the quintain, or collective aim of the research, focussing both on "...its commonality and its differences across manifestations." There may be similarities across cases, however, each individual case study will have unique features (Stake, 2006, p. 40). Cross-case analysis, therefore, can further our understanding of the quintain in general, but also how the quintain occurs under different conditions and contexts (Stake, 2006). As discussed previously, Stake (1995; 2006) emphasises that the situationality and uniqueness of each case study is key to our understanding of the phenomenon, and how it manifests in different settings, which is first documented in the individual case study reports. The output of the cross-case analysis yields cross-case assertions, a series of declarative statements developed from the researcher's interpretations and claims (Stake, 1995; Stake, 2006). These cross-case assertions form the key findings of the empirical research and are explored further in the discussion in Chapter Seven. As the present study focusses on experiences of living with dementia in various models of supported housing, and on perspectives on supported housing as a future housing choice, Stake's cross-case analysis approach was deemed suitable to address the aim and objectives of the study.

Stake suggests that cross-case analysis is best completed by one individual, who understands the studied phenomenon, and understands each individual case study report in-depth (Stake, 2006). Throughout the analysis process, this individual receives input through discussion with "...team members and critical friends..." when required (Stake, 2006, p. 42), complimenting the PhD researcher and supervisory team relationship. As such, the cross-case analysis was conducted by the researcher, with findings discussed at supervisory team meetings, and through review of written documents. The process of Stake's (2006) cross-case analysis involves the completion of a series of worksheets, aimed at facilitating and clearly documenting

the stages of analysis. In accordance with Stake's (2006) approach, the steps that were followed are outlined, below.

5.5.3.1. Outlining the Aim and Objectives of the Multiple Case Study

Stake (2006) states that the aim and objectives of a multiple case study should reflect the primary information about the quintain that the researcher seeks. During the cross-case analysis, a copy of these objectives was kept on-hand, to refer to throughout the analysis process (Stake, 2006). These are outlined in Table 5, which is an adaptation of Stake's cross-case analysis Worksheet 2 (Stake, 2006, p. 43).

Table 5: Study aim and objectives. Adapted from Multiple Case Study Analysis, by Robert E. Stake (2006, p. 43). Copyright 2006 by The Guilford Press. Permission to use granted by purchase of the book, for professional use.

Overarching Aim (Quintain): To develop an in-depth understanding of the experience of living with dementia in supported housing in Scotland.

Objective 1: How support or care is delivered in supported housing settings to meet the needs of people living with dementia.

Objective 2: How living in supported housing impacts social relationships and community connections for people living with dementia.

Objective 3: How the physical environments of supported housing settings enable people living with dementia to maintain their independence.

Objective 4: Perspectives on supported housing as a future housing choice for people living with dementia.

The researcher then immersed themselves in the content of each individual case study report to refresh their thinking and develop further familiarity (Stake, 2006). During this process, a document for each individual case study was completed, containing the content outlined in Table 6. This is an adaptation of Stake's cross-case analysis Worksheet 3 (Stake, 2006, p. 45). Here, the summary findings developed from each individual case study were developed.

Table 6: Analyst's notes worksheet to be completed while reading each individual case study. Adapted from Multiple Case Study Analysis, by Robert E. Stake (2006, p. 45). Copyright 2006 by The Guilford Press. Permission to use granted by purchase of the book, for professional use.

Code Letters for This Case:

Case Study Report Title:

Analyst's Synopsis:

(Identifying the case, the site, key information sources, and context)

Uniqueness among Other Cases:

Prominence of Objective 1 in This Case:

Prominence of Objective 2 in This Case:

Prominence of Objective 3 in This Case:

Prominence of Objective 4 in This Case:

Expected Utility of This Case for Developing Objective 1:

Expected Utility of This Case for Developing Objective 2:

Expected Utility of This Case for Developing Objective 3:

Expected Utility of This Case for Developing Objective 4:

Findings:

Possible Excerpts for the Multiple Case Study Report:

(Noting case report page number)

Commentary:

(Sometimes noting case report page number)

Again, the cross-case analysis stemmed from the individual case study reports and analysis. While reading each case study report, systematic notes were made to highlight essential elements of the reports (Stake, 2006). This was conducted within NVivo 12 Pro (QSR International Pty Ltd, 2020). Throughout, the findings were expanded on and added to, to outline concepts that may have been missed or overlooked during the initial analysis and write-up for each case study. Shown in Table 6, sections on uniqueness were used to highlight findings and contexts that were unusual, atypical, or unique to that individual case study. Sections on prominence were used to document how often content relating to each specific objective appeared within the individual case studies, with prominence acting as an indicator of how relevant the case study is to develop an understanding of the objective. Utility was assessed by the overall depth and quality of discussion, and the collection of data from multiple perspectives. Again, the section on findings included a summary of

findings from each case study, with space for important quotations or excerpts and notes (commentary). This initial stage focussed on reading and understanding the individual case studies, in-depth, and the beginning of “...the highly reductive process...” of cross-case analysis, aimed at retaining the most important experiential knowledge from each case study to develop cross-case assertions (Stake, 2006, p. 44).

5.5.3.2. Expected Utility of Cases

The previous step involved noting the prominence of each objective in each case study, followed by an estimation of the expected utility of each case study for developing each objective. In the previous step, the uniqueness, or atypicality, of each case study was also documented. The researcher then considered how this prominence, estimated utility, and uniqueness might impact the cross-case assertions made at the end of the analysis, and how each case study expands understanding regarding the quintain, or the collective aim of the cross-case analysis (Stake, 2006). After reading all case study reports and completing Worksheet 3 (Table 6) for each, a more informed assessment of the expected utility of each case study for developing each objective was developed by completing the document outlined in Table 7, an adaptation of Stake’s cross-case analysis Worksheet 4 (Stake, 2006, p. 49).

At this stage, each objective was considered, together with the summary findings from each case, completed using Worksheet 3 (Table 6). Each case study was then subjectively rated in terms of its utility for developing each objective, based on interpretation, as high, middling, or low (Table 7). This stage enabled the visualisation of how relevant each case study was for developing each objective, revisited throughout the cross-case analysis. As stated previously, utility was informed by the quality and depth of the presented data, and the collection of data from multiple perspectives or sources.

Table 7: Ratings of expected utility of each case study for each objective. Adapted from Multiple Case Study Analysis, by Robert E. Stake (2006, p. 49). Copyright 2006 by The Guilford Press. Permission to use granted by purchase of the book, for professional use.

Utility of Cases	Case Study One	Case Study Two	Case Study Three
Objectives			
1			
2			
3			

Note: Each case study is ranked as having H = high utility, M = middling utility, L = low utility, for addressing each objective. High utility means that the case study appears to be one of the most useful for developing this objective.

5.5.3.3. The Grounds for Assertions

At this stage of the cross-case analysis, Stake (2006) states that there are three tracks that the researcher can follow to generate cross-case assertions:

Track I: Emphasises the importance of situationality, context, and the findings of each individual case study when completing the cross-case analysis.

Track II: Merges similar findings, paying little attention to situationality or context.

Track III: Converts findings into “factors” or variables that can be ranked or measured, most useful for quantitative research.

Had the original plan of conducting up to eight case studies been followed, Track I of Stake’s (2006) cross-case analysis approach would have been used. Stake (2006) states that this approach is followed when the multiple case study seeks to emphasise the importance of situationality, context, and the findings of each individual case study when completing the cross-case analysis. Track I is typically followed when the researcher has conducted four to ten case studies within different countries, cultures, or contexts. For example, Stake’s (2006) multiple case study analysis textbook focusses on the implementation of an educational programme within different countries, with these countries having different sociodemographic features and educational policies. As such, paying close attention to context was vitally important. Again, the original goal for this research at its inception was to conduct eight case studies emanating from an individual who lived within four different supported housing models, including shared housing, sheltered housing, very-sheltered or extra care housing, and dementia-specific supported housing. As such, situationality and context would have played a much more central role, given the dynamics of, for example, living in a room within a shared house (as opposed to a self-contained flat or bungalow), or living in an environment designed specifically for people living with dementia. Rather, the case studies in this research focussed on sheltered housing, very sheltered or extra care housing, and perspectives on supported housing as a future housing

choice. Resultantly, the contexts of these environments are, in many ways, similar, beyond the increase in support and care provision in very sheltered and extra care housing.

Hence, rather than following Track I of Stake's approach, the cross-case analysis followed Track II. Track II involves merging similar findings, paying less attention to situationality or context. Stake (2006) states that this track is typically more suitable for multiple case studies that involve fewer than four individual case studies, where in-depth comparisons of contexts may be challenging. The fundamental difference between Tracks I and II relates to a stage that involves the "merging" of findings from the individual case studies, which will be described more in this section. Following Track I, findings for each individual case study are kept separate, due to the focus on situationality and context when following this track. This is not to say that understanding context and situationality is not important in this study, as the study does aim to compare experiences of living with dementia in different models of supported housing.

Hence, the only difference here is the selection of which analytical track to follow, which alters one analytical step in Stake's (2006) approach. Track II aims to "merge" findings from all case studies to generate comparisons. Using Stake's (2006) terminology, to develop "generalisations" or an understanding of the transferability of findings to other contexts. Track III, not yet discussed in this section, is slightly more positivistic in orientation; in that it seeks to develop "factors" or variables from the data that are then used for analysis. To illustrate, in Stake's (2006) example, a factor named "Teacher Participation" was developed, with the researcher providing a categorical ranking for each teacher involved in the study, from "very low" to "very high", with these subjective rankings informed by the data. Other than this one analytical step, the other analytical processes remain the same, with the overall endpoint of the analysis being the generation of assertions, based on the researcher's interpretations. Hence, Track II was implemented as follows in this research.

First, following Worksheet 3 of Stake's methodology (Table 6), summary findings of each individual case report were considered. The second stage involved sorting or clustering summary findings into "merged findings", based on the researcher's interpretations. These merged findings were novel, cross-case findings that were developed based on review of the individual case study reports. This process was interpretive and

subjective in nature, remaining true to the relativist philosophical positioning of Stake (2006). These merged findings were then summarised into cross-case themes. Informed by a social constructionist philosophy, these cross-case themes can serve to challenge dominant narratives or stigmatising beliefs held in society and can influence practice and political change. To help the reader understand how these cross-case themes and interpretations were developed, illustrative quotes are provided.

5.5.3.4. Cross-Case Assertions

As stated previously, assertions are declarative statements that stem from the cross-case analysis. These assertions form the key findings of the overall thesis and are discussed in greater detail in Chapter Seven. The reader evaluates these assertions based on the data presented throughout the individual case studies and cross-case analysis.

5.6. Summary of Chapter Five

This chapter sought to present an overview of the case study methods used in this research. This study involves three instrumental case studies that focus on 1) living with dementia in sheltered housing, 2) living with dementia in very sheltered or extra care housing, and 3) perspectives on supported housing as a future housing choice for people living with dementia. Case studies one and two will involve three supported housing settings each, involving people living with dementia, family members or friends, and housing, health, or social care professionals. The data collection methods included interviews, documents, photographs, and outcome measures. Individual reports of the three case studies were developed, analysed through the presentation of description, direct interpretation, and categorical aggregation. This yielded case study specific themes. These themes were then summarised into statements, which were used in the cross-case analysis. Following Tack II of Stake's (2006) methodology, these statements were merged and cross-case themes were developed. This process yielded cross-case assertions, which are the key findings of the overall research.

To facilitate the collection of quality data, best practice guidelines regarding dementia research were followed when developing data collection processes and documents shared with potential participants. This sought to increase the likelihood that people with dementia could be meaningfully involved in the research.

Rigour has been upheld throughout the research process, focussing predominantly on Stake's (1995) descriptions of data source, methodological, theory, and investigator triangulation. Chapter Six will now present the findings of the individual case studies, followed by a cross-case analysis.

Chapter Six: Results

6.1 Introduction to Chapter Six

This chapter is split into four sections. The first three sections will present the findings of the individual case studies. These will be structured to provide 1) an overview of the case study and any changes to data collection procedures that occurred throughout the study, 2) contextual information for each case study, developed through description, direct interpretation, and categorical aggregation, 3) presentation of case study themes, developed through categorical aggregation, and 4) summary statements of findings from each case study. The final section will present the cross-case analysis, presented as cross-case themes. The chapter will culminate in the presentation of cross-case assertions.

6.2. Case Study One: Living with Dementia in Sheltered Housing

6.2.1 Context of Case Study One

An overview of case study one is presented in Figure 7. This case study involved three sheltered housing settings. Each setting was visited three times. Three people living with dementia, and three sheltered housing officers, were interviewed. All interviews were conducted in person. In total, seven interviews were conducted. Each interview lasted approximately one hour.

The first interview with a person living with dementia was conducted in Site A. Initially, this individual wanted to conduct interviews on separate days, as shorter interviews that focussed on specific topics. Hence, this individual was interviewed twice. However, during the second interview, the individual wished to discuss the remaining topics during that interview, as opposed to conducting interviews on separate days. The remaining individuals that were interviewed opted to conduct the interview in one session.

Further, the outcome measures were completed with the person with dementia who lived in Site A. After a conversation with this individual, it was noted that the outcome measures were unhelpful and added little to the overall understanding of the aim and objectives of the research. Administration of the outcome measures also disrupted the natural flow of the interview. Hence, the decision was made to not complete the outcome measures with any other individual who was interviewed, in all case studies.

Further, all individuals opted not to use a digital camera. Rather, they all offered tours of their homes, discussing personal items and their home environment in this way, with photographs taken throughout this process. In total, 180 individual photographs were gathered from the settings. Eleven documents were also gathered, including Care Inspectorate reports, business plans, and annual performance reviews (Figure 7).

Those involved declined to nominate family members or friends to be interviewed, stating that these individuals had busy schedules and would not be able to find the time to be interviewed. As such, no family members were involved in this case study. Further, although individuals with dementia lived in Site C, no individuals nominated themselves to be interviewed. Nonetheless, the sheltered housing officer for this setting was interviewed, and documents and photographs were gathered from the setting. To accommodate this, two people that were living with dementia were interviewed in Site B.

Figure 7: Overview of the settings and participants involved, and the sources of data collected, within case study one.

6.2.2. Case Study One Locations

Aligned with the methodology of Stake (Stake, 1995; Stake, 2006), this section provides context regarding the sheltered housing settings involved in this case study. To provide a brief overview, sheltered housing

developments for older people in Scotland have several defining features. For example, settings typically include handrails in communal areas and bathrooms, the use of community alarm systems, and the presence of a sheltered housing officer throughout the day (Scottish Government, 2022). Sheltered housing dwellings in Scotland are flats, bungalows, or individual rooms within shared houses, with residents classified as tenants or homeowners by law (Care Information Scotland, 2020). Direct care services are not offered by sheltered housing providers; however, home care services can be accessed in the same way as any individual living in the community. It is often stated that the overall aim or goal of sheltered housing is to support people to live independently, by enabling individuals to live in self-contained homes, with the added security of emergency alarm systems and staff presence (Care Information Scotland, 2020). Table 8, below, provides further information regarding the settings and individuals involved in this case study, with brief descriptions developed from the information included in the business plans, performance reviews, and Care Inspectorate reports gathered from the settings.

Table 8: Participant characteristics and brief descriptions of the involved sheltered housing settings.

Setting	Participant Characteristics	Description of Setting
Site A	<p>Elizabeth, Person with Dementia - Elizabeth was 78 years old and had been living with a diagnosis of dementia for three years. She had lived in the sheltered housing setting for nine months.</p> <p>Anne, Sheltered Housing Officer - Anne had worked in the setting for eleven-and-a-half years. She had worked as a carer within a care home prior to working as a sheltered housing officer. She was employed by the local council.</p>	<p>This setting was owned by a local council, built in the 1980s. The setting contained 39 flats, housed in a two-storey building. The setting was situated in a town, with a population of 17,000.</p>
Site B	<p>Rose, Person with Dementia – Rose was 88 years old. She had lived in the sheltered housing setting for 14 years. She did not disclose when she was diagnosed with dementia.</p> <p>James, Person with Dementia – James was 86 years old but did not disclose how long he had been living with a diagnosis of dementia. He had</p>	<p>This setting was owned by a housing association; however, the sheltered housing support services were provided by the local council. The building was built in the 1990s. The setting contained 31 flats, all of which were ground level. The setting was situated in a village, with a population of 6,000.</p>

	lived in the sheltered housing setting for eight months.	
	Susan, Sheltered Housing Officer – Susan had over 20 years of experience working for the local council, first as a home carer for 19 years, before taking the role of sheltered housing officer. She was employed by the local council.	
Site C	Kate, Sheltered Housing Officer –Kate had worked in the setting for seven years. Prior to working in the sheltered housing setting, Kate worked within a small dementia care setting as a carer. She was employed by a housing association.	This setting was owned by a housing association, built in the 1990s. The development contained 31 bungalows, all of which were ground level. The setting was situated in a town, with a population of 50,000.

To provide further context, based on interviews and from information included within study business plans, performance reviews, and Care Inspectorate reports, the sheltered housing developments in this case study were owned by local councils (Site A and B), and a housing association (Site C). The settings were built in the 1980s (Site A) and 1990s (Site B and C) and contained flats (Site A and B) or bungalows (Site C). Tenants rented properties from the local councils or housing association. The developments contained communal lounges, laundry rooms, drying areas, bathrooms, seating areas, gardens, and offices. Site A was a two-storey building, whereas the flats and bungalows in Sites B and C were ground level. Sites A and B were accessible by the front and rear of the building, through secure entry systems. As Site C contained bungalows, the setting had a communal building in which the communal lounge, office, and bathrooms were contained, again accessible through a secure entry system. The settings were situated in two local council areas, within suburban areas. The council areas had roughly the same populations. Site C was located within the largest town, with a population of 50,000. Site A was located within a town with a population of 17,000. Site B was located within a village with a population of 6,000. The developments were situated close to amenities, including bus stops, supermarkets, churches, leisure centres, and parks. The developments were also built near restaurants and pubs, general practice surgeries, and libraries. All amenities appeared to be within walking distance of the

developments, typically contained within a mile radius of the settings. The developments were also located within 20 miles of a Scottish city.

Each setting was staffed by one sheltered housing officer, either employed by the local councils (Site A and B) or housing association (Site C). The sheltered housing officers would provide general support through morning calls and health and safety checks, in addition to managing repairs and tenancies. They worked on-site between 8am and 3:30pm (Sites A and B), and 9am and 5pm (Site C), Monday-to-Friday. The settings operated with emergency pullcords, contained in flats and communal areas, and pendants, carried or worn by those living in the settings. If an emergency occurred during the sheltered housing officers' working hours, pullcords and pendants could be used to contact them. Outside of working hours, calls would be directed to a central call centre. The call centre staff would respond to the emergency, either by calling named emergency contacts or emergency services. Cleaners also worked in the properties within communal areas, again, employed by the local council or housing associations. The settings did not offer meal services. Some social activities, such as bingo, dominoes, or celebratory meals were arranged by the sheltered housing officers. The settings tended to only accept residents who were aged 60 and over (Site C) or retired and aged 66 and over (Sites A and B). Some exceptions were made, however, for younger people who were, for example, blind. All flats were decorated by tenants with their own furniture. The settings accepted people who were living with dementia, and it is noted in Care Inspectorate reports that the sheltered housing officers partook in dementia-oriented training. Within Site A, there was four people living with dementia, two in Site B, and two in Site C. These settings, therefore, were selected to be involved in this case study as they resembled typical Scottish sheltered housing developments and actively housed individuals living with dementia. Hence, the settings could support the development of an in-depth understanding of the experience of living with dementia in sheltered housing.

The next sections of this case study take the form of three themes, that aim to provide greater depth regarding the experience of living with dementia in sheltered housing. The first theme relates to the physical environments of sheltered housing, discussing the reasons why people living with dementia move into sheltered housing, and the extent to which the physical environments of these settings enable people with

dementia to live independently. The second theme relates to the provision of support and care in sheltered housing, with a focus on the challenges faced by those working in sheltered housing with regard to accessing and delivering support and care services to meet the needs of people living with dementia. The final theme relates to social relationships in sheltered housing, focussing on relationships with family members, friends, and other individuals living in the settings.

6.3. Theme One: The Physical Environment of Sheltered Housing Settings

To develop context, this theme first provides an overview of the purpose of sheltered housing, as a service, as discussed by those involved in the case study. The underlying aim of sheltered housing was described as the promotion or maintenance of independence. To illustrate, Anne, Susan, and Kate (sheltered housing officers) all referred to the sheltered housing services they provided as “independent living.” In this regard, independent living meant that those living in the settings were “expected”, or “encouraged”, to live independently, with “back up” provided by the sheltered housing officers, if required. There was no direct care delivered by the involved housing providers, and minimal support was delivered by the sheltered housing officers. In the documentation reviewed from the services, sheltered housing was described as the supporting of individuals to independently manage a tenancy, through the provision of housing support services.

To provide further context regarding these housing support services, Kate worked in the sheltered housing setting between 9am and 5pm, and Susan and Anne worked between 8am and 3:30pm, Monday to Friday. Their role, largely, involved supporting individuals with moves in and out of the settings, dealing with requests for repairs, checking in on residents, and responding to emergency calls. Additionally, some social activities were organised in the settings, such as bingo, dominoes, and day trips. Independent living, in theory, meant that those living in the settings could choose when and with whom to spend their time, engage with the local community, and manage or decorate their self-contained home with personal items and belongings. Anne, a sheltered housing officer, summarises her role in the setting in the following section:

My main job is just to make sure that the tenants in here are okay. It's independent living. They live independently. I'm only back up for them. I do a daily call. When I do the daily call, I can tell a lot from a voice. So, normally when someone new is coming in here, I really don't give them the choice. I just

tell them that this is the time of the call. Because, as I say, if someone is unwell or something like that, I can pick up on it. So, even if they tell me that they are okay, I know they're not okay. I can go and check on them. And the same when it comes to repairs or anything like that ... My main concern is my tenants and that they're all okay, and that their wellbeing is okay. If they need any doctors, ambulances, or anything like that, and if they're not able to do it for themselves, I'll do it for them. And then you also contact family members just to let them know what's happening as well. **(Anne, Site A, Sheltered Housing Officer).**

A comment to note here is the use of the term, "I don't give them the choice." In this regard, although having a morning call was deemed to be the choice of the resident, Anne, and Kate, both stated that they did not give residents this choice. This may appear minor upon first reading, but as this case study unfolds, it will become evident that individuals, particularly those living with dementia, do not always experience independence or autonomy.

However, turning to the experiences of those living with dementia in the settings, Elizabeth, Rose, and James all felt that they were living independently, and valued being able to come and go as they pleased from their property, not being "regimented", or "dictated" to, and conducting tasks to their own schedules. For example, Elizabeth, a person with dementia, provided her perspective on what it meant to live independently:

Living independently? Well, to be able to, obviously, live my life without being told what to do. Like a care home, you know? I mean, I know that they're there for a reason, care homes. But I can come and go as I please, and there's help there if I need it. There's help there if I require it, and that's the beauty of it. **(Elizabeth, Site A, Person with Dementia).**

These previous sections sought to begin unpacking the experience of living with dementia in sheltered housing. To summarise, the aim or purpose of sheltered housing is to support individuals to live independently in their self-contained homes, with the presence of a sheltered housing officer throughout the day. A limited amount of support is provided in these settings, hence, residents are "expected" or "encouraged" to live independently. Indeed, discussion around independence and autonomy permeated through much of the interviews in this case study. However, it was evident that people living with dementia

could experience different levels of independence and autonomy in these settings, often facing referral or management out of the settings as their needs increased. Having developed a fuller understanding of what sheltered housing is, and what it reportedly aims to provide as a service, the theme now begins to unpack the experience of living in such settings with a diagnosis of dementia.

To provide an overview of the reasons why those involved in the case study moved into sheltered housing. Elizabeth, Rose, and James (people with dementia) all discussed their reasoning for moving into sheltered housing throughout the interviews. This was mostly due to the large size of their previous homes, which became difficult to manage. For example, Elizabeth lived in a large bed and breakfast that was owned by her daughter and son-in-law, and James lived alone in a house with two levels. In this regard, moving to a smaller flat, with rooms contained on one level, was viewed as easier to manage, as discussed by James (person with dementia):

I was upstairs and downstairs. The bedrooms were upstairs. There were two bedrooms upstairs and then there was the living room and the kitchen, and it was just getting too much for me. My son managed to get this place here and I'm quite pleased with that, because it's all on one level. This is actually easier for me here, because I've got the kitchen, bathroom and everything is easy to reach.

(James, Site B, Person with Dementia).

All properties contained home adaptations and some assistive technologies. For example, handrails and emergency call systems. During their working hours, the emergency call systems could be used to contact the sheltered housing officers in the settings. Outside of working hours, calls would be directed to a central call centre. The call centre staff would respond to the emergency, either by calling named emergency contacts or services. Elizabeth (person with dementia) made use of the call system to contact the sheltered housing officer in the setting, when needed. However, Rose and James (people with dementia) had greater mobility needs, and valued the handrails and accessible shower rooms contained in their flats, as discussed by Rose:

The first thing I do when I get up is get in that shower, and if the carer's there by that time, then she helps me. But I've got grab rails and things, just everything that I really need, you know? Best move I ever made was coming in here. **(Rose, Site B, Person with Dementia).**

The images, below, are from James' (left) and Rose's (right) bathrooms. Various adaptations and assistive technologies are visible, including a pullcord (left), handrails, and walk-in showers.

When querying navigation of the flats and the communal areas of the buildings, Elizabeth, Rose, and James (people with dementia) all stated that they had no difficulties with wayfinding. Rose had lived in the setting for 14 years and was very familiar with her environment. During a visit to the setting, Rose provided an impromptu tour of the setting, showing communal areas, corridors, and directing the researcher to Susan's (sheltered housing officer) office. James' flat was situated directly next to the front entrance and communal lounge of the building, and they were visible from his front door. After the interview, James put on his cap, grabbed his walking stick, and went for a leisurely walk in the local community. Elizabeth also attested to being familiar with her environment, and walked the researcher to the front entrance, through looping corridors, to meet with Anne (sheltered housing officer) after the interview.

However, it was evident that people living with dementia in the settings could experience difficulties with wayfinding, and in some circumstances, this could lead to those living with dementia being moved out of the settings to receive a higher level of support elsewhere. This was discussed in detail by the sheltered housing

officers in the settings. For example, Anne (sheltered housing officer) provided an example of a person living with dementia, who was referred out of the setting due to difficulties using the entry systems of the building:

If you come in like Elizabeth, it's ideal. If you come in and you're all right, and then you take dementia, you know the environment anyway, you're okay. I did have one gentleman that came in and he was quite far gone with dementia. He didn't settle in because, as you've probably noticed, it's all touch buttons to get in and out, or it's fobs to get in. If you're outside, you've got to use a fob. This wee gentleman just couldn't get to grips with that. I would say he maybe lasted eight months to a year and he ended up in a care home, because this just wasn't the ideal place for him. **(Anne, Site A, Sheltered Housing Officer).**

In this regard, it was evident that there were individuals who were viewed as “ideal” for sheltered housing, and others who were not. The ideal individuals appeared to be those who could independently navigate the settings and live in their homes with minimal support. Elizabeth, Rose, and James (people with dementia) appeared to fit the criteria of being ideal. However, as the symptoms of dementia progress, sheltered housing settings appeared to lack the resources to support those living with dementia to live as independently as possible. As discussed previously, it seemed that living independently with minimal support was an expectation of living in sheltered housing, as opposed to individuals being supported to live independently with dementia as their condition progressed.

Further, when taking a deeper look into the physical environments of the developments, it can be argued that difficulties with navigation are created by design limitations. For example, during the interview, the researcher explained to Anne (sheltered housing officer) that they had difficulties locating Elizabeth’s flat. In this section of the conversation, Anne acknowledged the design limitations of the building:

Even at Elizabeth's side when you're going out, there's two push buttons, and it's trying to figure out which one's for which door, because you've got the two doors there, and everybody gets it wrong. **(Anne, Site A, Sheltered Housing Officer).**

This begs the question, if everybody gets it wrong, then why does this become a major issue and reason for those living with dementia being moved out of the settings? To reiterate, this was due to poor design, and the provision of an inadequate level of support, rather than being a product of having a dementia diagnosis. This is not to say that care or nursing homes are not appropriate settings for those living with dementia, but rather, individuals could face a premature move into a care or nursing home due to the disabling nature of their physical environment.

To provide further context, the images below, from two different settings, illustrate how the environments may be disorienting, with long, branching corridors that looked identical to other areas of the buildings. Doors to flats and bungalows tended to be the same in settings, and corridors were typically dimly lit due to limited natural light. Corridors had shadowy areas created by roof lights, and there was limited use of contrasting colour, with patterned carpets disorienting to the eye.

The implementation of dementia friendly design was negligible in all settings. In one setting, to aid with orientation, Susan (sheltered housing officer) had attended a training session about the implementation of dementia friendly design, regarding the use of signage and contrasting colour. This led to Susan placing signage on communal bathrooms, laundry rooms, the lounge, and office, as shown on the bathrooms on the image below. Beyond this, however, there was limited indication that dementia friendly design principles had been incorporated in the settings, outside of the use of adaptations like handrails and emergency pullcords. Indeed, all the sheltered housing officers stated that they had attended courses relating to dementia support and care, and the inspection reports for each setting noted that sheltered housing officers received such training. However, the content of this training was unclear, and largely involved short online courses. The images, below, also show that the signage was not placed at the correct height. Guidelines state that signs should be placed 4ft (1.2m) from ground level (The King's Fund, 2020), however, these signs were placed higher. Hence, although Susan (sheltered housing officer) had good intentions, it is unclear if these signs would have worked as intended.

This, therefore, points to a wider argument regarding dementia awareness in society. For example, the design and building of housing environments, access to and appropriateness of education provided to sheltered housing professionals, and the resources and funding available with regard to support and care provision. Although Elizabeth, Rose, and James (people with dementia) felt, and showed some evidence of being, independent, it appeared that they had adapted to the ideal requirements, or expectations, of living in sheltered housing, with limited evidence that the settings were built, equipped, or could be adapted, to meet the needs of people with dementia as their condition progresses.

Returning to discussion around what makes a person with dementia “ideal” for sheltered housing, this section focusses on the concept of familiarity. Elizabeth, Rose, and James (people with dementia) had all lived close to the sheltered housing developments, at some point in their lives, before their moves. As such, this created feelings of familiarity and belonging with the local community, with which they continued to engage. Elizabeth had lived in the local area for most of her life and returned to the area after a period of living with her daughter and son-in-law, to be closer to family and return to her roots. James had lived across the road from the sheltered housing development before moving in and was familiar with the local area. Rose had lived in the setting for 14 years and was diagnosed with dementia while living in sheltered housing, so had a high level of familiarity with the building, local area, and the individuals that lived or worked in the setting. Elizabeth (person with dementia) reflects on her returning to the area in which she had lived for most of her life:

Well, I do like it, obviously, because I'm familiar with the place to a degree. Albeit I've been away. My sister still stays in [local area]. It's changed a lot, obviously, over the years. I mean, she knows places, all of the nooks and crannies that I didn't know existed. But, no, I just wanted to come back, because the older I was getting, I was just wanting to come back to my roots, if you like. **(Elizabeth, Site A, Person with Dementia).**

Indeed, although Elizabeth had some familiarity, she could still face challenges when engaging with the local community, partly due to memory loss and the subsequent difficulties with navigation this could create. Nonetheless, Elizabeth had adopted strategies to support herself in the community, such as the use of a card that stated, "I Have Dementia", which she would show to shop workers if she became lost:

See if I go outwith my comfort zone? I feel a wee bit panicky. Because some shops have maybe got two doors and I maybe don't go out the door I came in. I stand going, "Dear God, where am I? Where am I here?" But what I do have is I have a card that says, "I Have Dementia", and I give it to, maybe, a shop assistant or something to help me. Anytime I use it, they're excellent with me. It's just because, sometimes, I need a wee bit of help, maybe for forms or things like that, you know? **(Elizabeth, Site A, Person with Dementia).**

Use of such a card is not necessarily the norm and was given to Elizabeth prior to moving into the setting. However, this quote affirms that Elizabeth was living with a neurodegenerative illness that impacted her memory. Although Elizabeth was viewed as being "ideal" at the time of interviewing, it was apparent that those living with dementia faced losing this label as their condition progressed. That is, Elizabeth, Rose, and James (people with dementia) might have been deemed ideal residents at that time, but they faced losing this identity as their condition progressed. The following quote from Anne (sheltered housing officer) describes Elizabeth as an "ideal candidate" for sheltered housing, linked in part to her familiarity with the setting and local area, and involvement of family in her life. However, there was an acknowledgement from Anne that Elizabeth's needs would likely change. Although Anne, likely, had Elizabeth's best intentions in mind, by paying attention to her safety, there was an indication that Anne was "watching" Elizabeth for signs that

her dementia was progressing. As discussed previously, with this comes the likelihood that Elizabeth could be moved from the setting as her needs increased:

To me, Elizabeth has just got a lot of memory loss just now. But, she can get in and out the house no problem. She knows her way in, she knows her way out. She's safe in the house. I've been in the house and I've watched her, and she's an ideal candidate for here. She needs a wee bit of background, a wee bit of safety here, but she's still able. I mean, she's out every day, she's got a sister that's local. She goes out walking a lot. I mean, she puts me to shame, so she does. But she is ideal for in here. She needs a wee bit of back up, but probably down the line I will have more to do with Elizabeth, but for the time being, I'm just in the background watching, just to make sure that she's okay. **(Anne, Site A, Sheltered Housing Officer).**

Therefore, the label of “independent living” can again be questioned here. For example, it is unlikely that a person who is living independently in their own home, outside of sheltered housing, would be watched in this way. It is also unclear what choice the residents had regarding this watching. Therefore, sheltered housing officers appeared to have a mediating role when deciding that a person with dementia is no longer ideal for the setting, with limited opportunities to increase support and care, or adapt environments to accommodate greater needs. Despite being an experienced carer and sheltered housing officer, Anne’s level of training and qualifications to make these decisions could also be questioned.

To provide a further example, Anne (sheltered housing officer) discussed another individual who was living with dementia in the setting. This individual was also being monitored for changes in her condition. Anne believed that they should be moved from the setting to receive a higher level of care elsewhere. This process of monitoring, or watching, appeared to lead to Anne attributing a fire alarm going off in the setting to this individual, without any definitive evidence:

I've got a wee lady just now. She was fine when she came in, but she's quite far gone with it now. But she's getting to the stage now where I don't think she should be here. But her son spends every day with her. A couple of weeks ago, the fire alarm went off and I'm sure it was her, because it's touch buttons, and she got lost and she touched one of the fire buttons instead and set the fire alarm off.

But, as I say, all in all she's fine as long as her son's here, but she's getting to the stage as well now where I just feel it's time for her to move on. She's needing a bit more care than what we can give her in here. **(Anne, Site A, Sheltered Housing Officer).**

Hence, it appeared that a disclosure of a dementia diagnosis led to those living with the condition facing an almost inevitable move from their home, at the point that they are too “far gone”, or no longer ideal. It also appeared that Elizabeth (person with dementia) was aware of this. Speaking of the woman that Anne (sheltered housing officer) discussed, above, Elizabeth acknowledged that this woman likely faced a move from her home. Elizabeth was also worried about her own condition progressing. It can be imagined that this would feel disconcerting; being comfortable, familiar, and independent at home, whilst also acknowledging that the length of time she could live in the setting was uncertain:

I've seen her a few times, out and down the stairs. Her son is usually always with her. She's still here, but I don't know for how long, because she's quite bad ... As I say, I won't get any better. The medication helps keep me at a level. But I get awfully sad when I see people who are really bad, you know? I do. I don't ever want to be like that. I really don't. I mean, I know about other people, my friend's friend, her mother, she was terrible. She was phoning during the night, and trying to get out, and whatever. That worries me, I must admit. **(Elizabeth, Site A, Person with Dementia).**

Nonetheless, Elizabeth, Rose, and James (people with dementia) discussed the importance of feeling comfortable, safe, and secure within the sheltered housing environments, which was outlined as a positive of living in the settings. For example, Elizabeth valued the use of secure entry systems in the setting, due to a previous home being burgled. James enjoyed being able to relax and do things in his own time. Rose valued feeling comfortable and safe in her home, whilst also having independence:

I like it here, because it's nice and clean and cosy, and I like my flat, you know? I like everything about it. And if you don't want to join in with people, you don't have to join in with people, so that's another thing I like. I like living here, I really do, because I feel safe and secure. **(Rose, Site B, Person with Dementia).**

Yeah. Is that a big thing, then, feeling safe and secure? **(Researcher)**.

Of course, it is, aye. Especially at my age and the way I am, you know? Because it's only recently that I've been unable to kind of walk quickly and do things that I used to do. So, I feel quite secure in here.

(Rose, Site B, Person with Dementia).

To provide further context, the image below shows one of the secure entries to a sheltered housing complex, with Anne's (sheltered housing officer) office window visible to the left side of the image. This added level of comfort and security provided by the setting was valued by those involved. Nonetheless, there appeared to be a fine line between feeling safe and secure, and being monitored or watched at home for changes to health that might lead to a move from the setting. Regardless, at the time, Elizabeth, Rose, and James (people with dementia) were happy in the sheltered housing developments, but the length of time they would be able to continue living in the settings was unclear, evidenced by the experiences of other people living with dementia in the settings.

6.4. Theme Two: Provision of Support and Care in Sheltered Housing

Having discussed elements of the physical environments of sheltered housing settings, and the experience of moving into and living with dementia in these settings, this theme turns to discussion surrounding the provision of support and care in sheltered housing. At the time of interviewing, Elizabeth (person with

dementia) did not receive any support or care, outside of safety check-ins and morning calls. Rose and James (people with dementia), however, were supported by home care workers, who took them to local shops, prepared meals for them, and helped with showering and provision of medication, as James discussed:

Well, there's three carers that come in daily. And one of them has got a car and she takes me down to the Co-Op. I get anything I want there and bring it back and put it in the fridge, and I can take it from there. I tell you, what I get here is first class service. And it makes all the difference, I can assure you. **(James, Site B, Person with Dementia).**

As discussed previously, the provision of support from sheltered housing officers involved organising home moves, repairs, providing morning calls, and responding to emergencies. In this regard, Kate (sheltered housing officer) described her involvement with residents as “the person bit.” However, as outlined in previous sections, it was evident that sheltered housing settings often lacked the resources to provide support and care to those living with dementia, particularly those with a higher level of need. Several reasons for this were discussed by the sheltered housing officers. First, Kate, Susan, and Anne (sheltered housing officers) all discussed changes to their job roles, that occurred throughout the years they were in employment. Most notably, this related to a shift from providing direct support to those living in the settings and organising social activities, to a focus on statistics and paperwork. Changes to the job role were discussed by Kate:

This job has changed. It's a lot more in relation, I would say, to the stats and the paperwork. There's less emphasis on people. But there's so much in the paperwork. I find that quite sad. You're spending so much time doing the paperwork, you can't even do the same amount of care that you're supposed to. I find that a bit tricky. As I say, that's me only been here seven years. There're people that have been here for 20 odd years, and they will say the job is nothing like it was when they started. But we are where we are. **(Kate, Site C, Sheltered Housing Officer).**

This felt unfair, as Kate, Susan, and Anne (sheltered housing officers) seemingly entered the job with caring personalities, with the supportive or caring aspects of their role slowly eroding. After all, they had worked in direct care roles before becoming sheltered housing officers. There was an acknowledgement that changes to the job role and the time pressures this created, with regard to supporting those living in the settings, were

caused by reduced funding. For Kate this created a feeling of insecurity and uncertainty with regard to her job role, who also stated the belief that "... the care has been taken out of social care." This job insecurity, and changes to her role, had led Kate to question if she wanted to remain working as a sheltered housing officer. Kate discussed changes to funding in the following excerpt:

We get funding from the council for care. Before, if you were called sheltered housing, they paid it automatically. As time went on, they wanted value for money. They want to see that you're doing things, and they want to see that what you're doing falls under the categories and the headings of what they consider to be care. If you're not ticking these boxes, then, potentially, you won't get the money. If we can't prove it, allegedly, they will remove the funding. There's a big issue with that as well, because what I have been told is, if they remove the funding, then basically, we won't be here.

(Kate, Site C, Sheltered Housing Officer).

Further, Kate, Susan, and Anne (sheltered housing officers) stated that time pressures meant they were taking on responsibilities that they were no longer supposed to, to meet the needs of those living in the settings. For example, Kate stated that she visited a person living with dementia, who was in hospital alone on Christmas day, with no close family members. Even the responsibility of organising social activities in the settings had been reduced for the sheltered housing officers, who were told that they should "encourage" residents to organise social activities themselves, rather than organise activities for them. Nonetheless, Kate, Susan, and Anne all continued to arrange activities, as discussed by Susan:

We're not supposed to do it. But if I've nothing to do on a Friday, and they're looking for a wee fish supper, I'll give up two hours. **(Susan, Site B, Sheltered Housing Officer).**

Yeah, why would they say you're not supposed to do it? **(Researcher).**

Just because it's outwith your working hours. Just outwith your working hours, so they'll not pay you overtime. They'll not. No interest. But, if you're dedicated to your job, what's two hours out of your life to see people happy? **(Susan, Site B, Sheltered Housing Officer).**

Anne and Kate (sheltered housing officers) had stated that arranged social activities were mainly for those that “need it”, referred to as those with more advanced dementia, those that were socially isolated from family, and those with high mobility needs. People like Elizabeth, Rose, and James (people with dementia), who were deemed to be independent and able to engage with the local community, were not as reliant on social activities arranged in the settings. In this regard, it may be assumed that those with the greatest need are impacted most by changes to the organisation of social activities, as they could become isolated or confined to their flats.

Funding limitations also had a wider impact with regard to accessing home carers, meaning that those living in the settings often did not see carers they were familiar with. This was largely due to changes in shift patterns, and the need to send carers as and when they were available, as opposed to having allocated care teams who attended the settings. This lack of familiarity and consistent care staff was linked to a loss of dignity by Anne (sheltered housing officer), who felt she could do nothing about the issue:

I was a carer for 18 years and I had the same service users daily. Every day without fail. But I was an old carer. We did housework and things like that. Now, what I find, is you could have about six carers a week. You maybe get two that are allocated to you, because I think they work three days, off two, they don't work a full week. I don't think it's right, but it's got nothing to do with me. I just think it's whoever's available that they send in now. And that's, no. Dignity is out the window with things like that, especially when it comes to showering and things like that. Because you've got to realise that they're individuals, but at the same time, if you need a carer, you need a carer. **(Anne, Site A, Sheltered Housing Officer).**

Although Elizabeth, James, and Rose (people with dementia) valued the support they received in the settings, and their relationships with the sheltered housing officers, the provision of support and care was stretched thin. Ultimately, these resource limitations meant that sheltered housing was viewed as “steppingstone” before a move into a setting that could provide a higher level of care. Resultantly, Kate, Anne, and Susan (sheltered housing officers) all stated that sheltered housing was suitable only for people living with the very early stages of dementia. Again, this reaffirms the idea that people living with dementia face an inevitable

move from their homes in sheltered housing, compounded by funding issues, a lack of resources, and challenges with accessing appropriate levels of support and care. This impacts the independence and autonomy of those living with dementia, who have limited choice with regard to the level of support or care that they receive, and should they wish, to continue living in sheltered housing.

6.5. Theme Three: Social Relationships in Sheltered Housing

Turning from a focus on the provision of support and care, this theme focusses on people with dementia's experiences of social relationships while living in sheltered housing. One of the apparent strengths of sheltered housing was the individuality and personalisation that was reflected in the homes of Elizabeth, Rose, and James (people with dementia). Their own unique identities shone through in the decoration of their homes, that were filled with personal belongings and photographs. For example, Rose had photographs of family and paintings of religious figures around her living room, in addition to vibrant, bright pink walls. Elizabeth's home contained novels, photographs of family, paintings, and souvenirs from travelling. James' home had photographs of family, and paintings relating to places he had visited or lived throughout his life. James provided an impromptu tour of his home, showing pictures of himself and his family, offering insights into his life. He was proud of his home and what he had achieved in his life:

That's the good lady and myself there. As I say, that there is the train station ... I helped to build the building. Because it burnt down and it was rebuilt, and I was employed on that to rebuild it. There was a big cinema there. And that there, the trams used to go around that. I mean, I've been around, as I say. I've seen an awful lot of things, actually. I know things. Been around. Life is a thing that, you either make it or you break it, you know? And I'm quite happy with what's here. I'm quite happy to show you what I've achieved, actually. And I have achieved quite a bit. **(James, Site B, Person with Dementia).**

The images, below, demonstrate the personalisation of the homes of Elizabeth (top), James (bottom left), and Rose (bottom right). Different decorations, personal items, and styles can be seen in each of the images, reflecting their identities.

This expression of identity and individuality made Elizabeth, Rose, and James (people with dementia) feel accepted in the settings, and James felt he was treated with civility. However, with the reluctance of turning positive experiences negative, it should be acknowledged that Elizabeth, Rose, and James were accepted in the settings as they met the “expectations” for living in sheltered housing and had the characteristics of being “ideal candidates.” Although James felt that there was “enough room for everybody” in the settings, it was evident that this was not the case. Those living with dementia, beyond the early stages, often lacked access to appropriate support and care to enable them to continue living in their homes. Nonetheless, at the time of interviewing, their experiences were positive:

I would say that I have been treated with civility in here ... I can't complain. And as far as I'm concerned, there's more than enough room for everybody. I mean, I'm not the only one in here, and I've been delighted because I've been accepted to be here. I'm quite happy in that. Everything has been working to my schedule, and I've got a lot of people that I know round about me, and they've been very, very helpful. **(James, Site B, Person with Dementia).**

Elizabeth, Rose, and James (people with dementia) all believed that living in sheltered housing supported them to maintain social relationships and connections with family, friends, and the local community, in addition to the development of new relationships with other individuals that lived in the settings. For example, Elizabeth had close relationships with her friends, sister, children, and grandchildren, who she visited frequently. James kept in contact with his son, daughter-in-law, and granddaughter. Rose kept in close contact with friends and others living in the setting, however, her son and daughter-in-law lived in England, and mainly kept in contact over the phone. To illustrate, Elizabeth spoke about her relationships with her sister, brother-in-law, and friend:

I go up to my sister's for my dinner, not every Saturday night, you know, because I don't want to put her right off. Her and her husband will go out for dinner and sometimes they'll take me, but it doesn't bother me. I'll go up maybe every fortnight for my dinner, and as I say, I'm out with my friend on a Sunday. Usually, I'll maybe even jump on the bus and I can go up to [nearby town] or wherever. As long as I'm up and out and about. As I say, I'm fine in here. I mean, obviously it's just a small place, but I'm perfectly happy and I feel secure, and that's the main thing. **(Elizabeth, Site A, Person with Dementia).**

Involvement of families in the lives of people with dementia was important, given the limited support and care provided in the settings. For example, family members would take on caring duties, check in frequently on their family members, or even stay with their family member to make sure they are well. This was discussed by Anne, a sheltered housing officer:

As I say, I'm only here for backup. We need the families to step up and make sure that their family members are okay, that they are looked after. I must admit, I've always been quite impressed with

the tenants I've had in here with dementia and their family. They know that I'm here, but they don't expect me to do everything for them. They're quite happy to do it themselves. **(Anne, Site A, Sheltered Housing Officer).**

However, the caveat here is that not all people with dementia will have strong relationships with family members, or their family members might live too far away to provide support. For example, Rose's (person with dementia) son and daughter-in-law lived in southern England, meaning they visited each other infrequently. Kate (sheltered housing officer) also spoke of a person living with dementia in the sheltered housing development in which she worked, whose family lived in America, hence, could not provide support. She described this person as being "lonely" and "isolated" from family. There is also the fact that Elizabeth, Rose, and James (people with dementia) lived locally to the sheltered housing developments before moving in, meaning that family members or friends were close by. Having the choice of where to move, or the opportunity to live in the same community, is not always possible, given the limited amount of sheltered housing dwellings in Scotland.

Regardless, Rose and James (people with dementia) spoke about the relationships they had developed with others living in sheltered housing and the local community. For example, James would attend a men's club in the local town, where he would meet others, listen to bands playing, and enjoyed dancing. Rose spoke of relationships with others living in the setting:

I've got a man in here that, every time he sees me, he'll come and take me by the arm and, oh, just make me laugh. He's away on holiday just now, so I'm going to strangle him when he gets back, because he didn't take me with him! He's lovely to me. Oh, aye, they're all nice in here. And the ones that are not nice, you don't need to have anything to do with, because you've got your own private place, you know? There's nobody like that in here, though. Everybody gets on. **(Rose, Site B, Person with Dementia).**

Further, communal lounges, where social activities took place, shown below, were spacious. Though, it appeared that these areas were mostly used when activities were organised by the sheltered housing officers,

such as bingo, dominoes, and celebratory meals. During visits to the settings, the communal areas were not being used.

Anne (sheltered housing officer) and Elizabeth (person with dementia) spoke about the importance of looking out for others who were living with dementia in the settings. For example, some residents would be aware that an individual was living with dementia and would provide support to them should they become lost. Despite issues with stigma and discrimination from other residents being discussed in other supported housing related research (Smith *et al.*, 2022), no one reported any incidences or experiences of stigma

throughout the interviews. During our interview, Elizabeth (person with dementia) shared her experience of helping another person with dementia, who lived in the setting, that was lost in the community:

It was frightening, she didn't know where she was going. That road can be really busy out there at times. I thought, "Dear God, she doesn't even know to cross at the lights." So, I was concerned about that. But we got her back here and she was fine ... If I see anybody that's struggling like that, especially if they're maybe in this kind of sheltered housing or whatever. Because you should never be afraid to ask for help. I need help myself, and I have had to ask for help myself at times, you know? **(Elizabeth, Site A, Person with Dementia).**

Although there was no direct, or obvious, instances of stigma, there was some indirect indications of poor dementia awareness shared during the interviews. For example, the sheltered housing officers believed that sheltered housing was not an appropriate setting for those living with dementia beyond the early stages. However, the idea that sheltered housing is not appropriate for people living with dementia is likely due to issues with environmental design, and limited access to appropriate support and care. Literature states that access to housing, health, and social care are fundamental human rights. However, even in settings that reportedly support individuals to live independently in their own homes through the provision of support, these fundamental human rights could be violated. Further, language used by the sheltered housing officers suggests othering of those living with dementia, who did not meet the criteria of being "ideal candidates" for the settings. For example, those who were deemed to be "too far gone", could become lost in the setting and in the community, or required a higher level of care. To illustrate, Kate's (sheltered housing officer) language, describing people with dementia as not being "normal", is outlined here:

If they're kept in an environment where it, it sounds terrible to say, but normal people, but people who don't have dementia, then it encourages them on to, you know, push themselves and become involved. They don't have the same opportunities to just drift, shall we say. Because they don't want people to notice, so they'll make that effort that they don't have to make if they were amongst everybody else with dementia, and potentially people who are worse off than them. **(Kate, Site C, Sheltered Housing Officer).**

There is evident stigma here, viewing dementia as a condition that should be hidden, to appear “normal.” Again, this points to poor dementia awareness and a lack of training or education, which can be detrimental to those living with dementia. In sum, although Elizabeth, Rose, and James (people with dementia) reported positive social experiences, and feelings of civility and acceptance, there remains a stigma and culture of othering in these settings. If an individual is not “normal”, not an “ideal candidate”, or if they are living with dementia, then it appears they are at risk of being watched, managed, and referred out of sheltered housing - with an individual’s involvement and choice regarding these decisions being unclear.

6.6. Summary of Case Study One

The underlying aim of sheltered housing is to support people to live independently in self-contained homes, through the provision of housing support services. For people with dementia, who can live independently with minimal support, living in sheltered housing can be a positive experience. For example, those involved in this case study were able to move to local sheltered housing developments, where they felt safe and comfortable, could decorate, and personalise their own homes with belongings, and could engage with friends and family in the local community. However, a prerequisite for living in sheltered housing was being an “ideal candidate.” That is, a person who can live independently, requires minimal or no support or care, and can navigate the setting and local community. For people living with dementia in the early stages, assuming the persona of an “ideal candidate” appeared achievable and was evidenced in this case study. However, the neurodegenerative nature of dementia means that those living with the condition will require a greater level of support or care as their condition progresses. Fundamentally, sheltered housing settings are not built or equipped to meet the needs of people with dementia as their condition progresses, meaning that individuals are watched or monitored until they face an inevitable move from their home. This risks a violation of human rights, regarding access to appropriate housing, health, and social care. Supporting those living with dementia in sheltered housing requires a greater number of resources and funding that is, at present, not available to sheltered housing professionals, who face time pressures and uncertainty regarding their job roles. There is also a fundamental lack of appropriate training and education for sheltered housing professionals relating to dementia, with stigma, discrimination, and othering evidenced in the settings.

Elizabeth, James, and Rose (people with dementia) are testament to the fact that people with dementia can, and should, be supported to live in sheltered housing. However, as things stand, sheltered housing will remain a mere steppingstone on the road to a move to a care or nursing home, with an individual's choice and needs coming second. Summary statements of the findings in this study, which will be used in the cross-case analysis, are shown in Table 9.

Table 9: Summary findings from case study one.

Case Study One: Summary of Findings	
I.	People with dementia move into sheltered housing due to the smaller size of the dwellings, increased safety and security, opportunities for social engagement and community involvement, and the emphasis on independence and autonomy.
II.	There is some indication that people with dementia can live independently in sheltered housing, by managing and personalising their self-contained homes, and continuing to engage with friends, family, and the local community.
III.	Sheltered housing settings provide a low level of housing support to individuals, such as check-ins from sheltered housing officers, and the organisation of repairs and social activities.
IV.	There are several factors that lead to people with dementia being referred or managed out of sheltered housing settings, like living with greater support and care needs, having difficulties with wayfinding, having little familiarity with the sheltered housing setting and local community, and limited involvement of family members or friends regarding support and care provision.
V.	These factors can be attributed to poor environmental design, poor dementia awareness and stigma, and limited access to resources and funding.

6.7. Case Study Two: Living with Dementia in Very Sheltered and Extra Care Housing

6.7.1. Context of Case Study Two

An overview of case study two is presented in Figure 8. This case study involved two extra care housing settings and one very sheltered housing setting. Each setting was visited three times. One person living with dementia, two family members, two service coordinators, and one support worker were interviewed. The interviews with the family members and support worker were conducted online. All other interviews were conducted in person. In total, six interviews were conducted. Each interview lasted approximately one hour.

The person with dementia that was interviewed in Site F opted to conduct the interview in one session, as opposed to multiple, shorter interviews. Further, this individual opted not to use a digital camera and offered a tour of their home, discussing personal items and their home environment in this way, with photographs taken throughout this process. In total, 120 individual photographs were gathered from the settings. Seven documents in total were also gathered, including Care Inspectorate reports and brochures for the settings (Figure 8).

The person with dementia that was interviewed in Site F offered to nominate a family member for interview. However, the person with dementia was hospitalised shortly after our interview, meaning that this interview was not conducted. No individuals with dementia were involved from Sites D and E. This was because all individuals that lived in the settings did not have capacity to provide informed consent. Nonetheless, family members of these individuals offered to be interviewed on their behalf.

6.7.2. Case Study Two Locations

As in case study one, this section provides context regarding the very sheltered and extra care housing settings involved in this case study. To provide a brief overview, very sheltered and extra care housing developments for older people in Scotland have several defining features. As with sheltered housing, these settings typically include handrails in communal areas and bathrooms, with bathrooms containing special adaptations, such as hoists, and the use of community alarm systems (Scottish Government, 2022).

Figure 8: Overview of the settings and participants involved, and the sources of data collected, within case study two.

In comparison to sheltered housing, a greater level of support and care is offered through the service of multiple housing officers or support workers, full-time care or domiciliary assistance, and the provision of meals (Scottish Government, 2022). Very sheltered and extra care housing dwellings in Scotland are typically flats, with residents classified as tenants or homeowners by law (Care Information Scotland, 2020). The overall aim or goal of very sheltered and extra care housing is to support people to live independently, by enabling individuals with a higher level of need to live in self-contained homes, with greater resources for support and care provision (Care Information Scotland, 2020). Table 10, below, introduces the settings and individuals involved in this case study, with brief descriptions developed from the information included in the brochures and Care Inspectorate reports for the sites.

Table 10: Participant characteristics and brief descriptions of the involved very sheltered and extra care housing settings.

Setting	Participant Characteristics	Description of Setting
Site D	Eve, Family Member - Eve was the daughter-in-law of a person living with dementia in extra care housing, who they had known for 50 years. The person with dementia was 91 years old, had lived with a diagnosis	This extra care housing setting was owned by a housing association, built in the 2000s. The support and care services were provided by the local council. The setting contained 26 flats, housed in a three-storey building. The

	<p>of dementia for 10 years, and lived in the setting for two years.</p> <p>Catherine, Service Coordinator - Catherine had worked in the setting for eight years. She had first worked in the setting for four-and-a-half years as a support worker, followed by three-and-a-half years as a senior support worker. She had recently taken up the position of service coordinator at the time of interviewing and was employed by the local council.</p>	<p>setting was situated in a town, with a population of 15,000.</p>
Site E	<p>Ailsa, Family Member - Ailsa was the daughter of a person living with dementia in extra care housing, who had lived in the setting for approximately one year. She was also a retired care manager and had experience working in a variety of care settings.</p> <p>Fiona, Support Worker - Fiona had worked in the setting for four-and-a-half years and was employed by the local council. She also had experience caring for her father, who was living with dementia and had lived within a sheltered housing setting.</p>	<p>This extra care housing setting was owned by a housing association, built in the 2000s. The support and care services were provided by the local council. The setting contained 20 flats, housed in a two-storey building. It was situated within a town, with a population of 15,000.</p>
Site F	<p>Martha, Service Coordinator - Martha had worked with the housing association that ran the development for several years. She had worked as a service coordinator in the involved very sheltered housing development for approximately one year. She had experience working in sheltered housing, very sheltered housing, and housing with care.</p> <p>Bella, Person living with Dementia - Bella had lived in the setting for 6 months. She was 68 years old, but did not disclose how long she had lived with dementia.</p>	<p>This very sheltered housing setting was owned by a housing association, built in the 2010s. The development contained 20 flats, housed in a two-storey building. It was situated within a town, with a population of 20,000.</p>

To provide further context, based on interviews and from information included within study brochures and Care Inspectorate reports, all the settings involved in this case study were owned by housing associations. The settings were built in the 2000s (Sites D and E) and 2010s (Site F) and contained flats. Tenants rented properties from the housing associations. The developments contained communal lounges, laundry rooms, drying areas, bathrooms, seating areas, gardens, and offices. The flats in the developments were housed in two-storey buildings. The developments were accessible by the front of the buildings, through secure entry systems. The settings were situated in two local council areas, within suburban areas. The council area in which Sites D and E were situated had roughly half the population of the council area in which Site F was located. Sites D and E were situated in the same town, with a population of 15,000. Site F was located within a slightly larger town, with a population of 20,000. The developments were situated close to amenities, including bus stops, supermarkets, churches, leisure centres, and parks. The developments were also built near restaurants and pubs, general practice surgeries, and libraries. All amenities appeared to be within walking distance of the developments, typically contained within a mile radius of the settings. The developments were located within 15 miles of a Scottish city.

Sites D and E were staffed by service coordinators, support workers, and chefs. The developments were owned by a housing association; however, the support and care services were provided by the local council. Site F was staffed by service coordinators, supported housing officers, and chefs. The staff working within the setting were provided by the housing association. The service coordinators within the settings would provide general support through morning calls and health and safety checks, in addition to managing repairs and tenancies, and coordinating staff and shift patterns in the settings. The support workers within Sites D and E would provide personal care and general housing support. The supported housing officers in Site F did not provide personal care, but provided general support and would help with the organisation of social activities. Staff were present 24/7 within Sites D and E, however, they were present within Site F between 8am and 10pm. The settings operated with emergency pullcords, contained in flats and communal areas, and pendants, carried or worn by those living in the settings. Pullcords and pendants could be used to contact the staff working within the settings. Outside of working hours in Site F, calls would be directed to a central call centre. The call centre staff would respond to the emergency, either by calling named emergency contacts or

emergency services. The settings offered meal services. Typically, tenants provided themselves breakfast, but were supported to prepare this within their flats. Lunches and dinners were provided each day during set mealtimes, within communal dining areas. Social activities, such as bingo, dominoes, reminiscence sessions and “men’s clubs”, were arranged by the staff working within the settings. The settings housed adults of all ages, with allocation to flats informed by needs assessments. All flats were decorated by tenants with their own furniture. The settings accepted people who were living with dementia, and it is noted in Care Inspectorate reports that the staff working in the settings partook in dementia-oriented training. The total number of individuals living with dementia in the settings was not disclosed, however, it was evident that there were more people living with dementia in these settings in comparison to the sites involved in case study one. These settings, therefore, were selected to be involved in this case study as they resembled typical Scottish very sheltered and extra care housing developments, and actively housed individuals living with dementia. Hence, the settings could support the development of an in-depth understanding of the experience of living with dementia in very sheltered and extra care housing.

The next sections of this case study take the form of two themes, that aim to provide greater depth regarding the experience of living with dementia in very sheltered and extra care housing. The first theme relates to comfort and growth in very sheltered and extra care housing. Comfort, because those living with dementia in the settings tended to move in due to the higher level of support and care that could be provided in the settings. Growth, because this added level of support and care, in addition to the organisation of social activities, supported those living with dementia in the settings to be more independent, safe, and sociable. As there was a greater emphasis on support and care provision in these settings, the second theme relates to the provision of support and care within very sheltered and extra care housing.

6.8. Theme One: Comfort and Growth in Very Sheltered and Extra Care Housing

This first theme centres on discussion around the benefits of moving into very sheltered or extra care housing for people living with dementia, focussing on the added safety and security that the settings can provide, and some of the personal growth experienced by people living with dementia and their family members. In this regard, this section focusses predominantly on comfort, safety, and security, in addition to socialising and

community engagement. The theme also aims to begin unpacking the underlying aim or goal of very sheltered and extra care housing, as discussed by those interviewed in the study.

To begin, Bella (person with dementia), Ailsa, and Eve (family members) discussed the reasons why they, or their family members, had moved into very sheltered or extra care housing. Predominantly, this was due to challenges with managing or maintaining their previous homes, and issues with safety and security that occurred due to living alone with a diagnosis of dementia. Living alone also contributed to feelings of loneliness or isolation, which was also a reason for moving into very sheltered or extra care housing. For Bella (person with dementia), the loneliness she experienced, in addition to her house being too large, contributed to poor mental health. She stated that she would rarely leave her house to engage with the local community, would rarely wash or dress herself, with limited contact with family and friends. For Ailsa and Eve (family members), whose family members were living with more advanced dementia, issues related more to safety due to risk of falling, with Ailsa's mother frequently becoming lost in the local community. To provide further context, Bella (person with dementia) discussed her reasoning for moving into very-sheltered housing, focussing on the loneliness she experienced and the challenges of managing a larger house:

I had nobody. I was staying in a two-bedroom house. Up and down stairs. And it was far too big for me, because me and my husband separated. So, it was too big. You were cleaning upstairs, and you're going, "That's fine, that's it." You go back down the stairs and it doesn't look right, you know? It's just – just – I just couldn't get on with it. So that was it. **(Bella, Site F, Person with Dementia).**

Yeah. Was that a big thing, then, it was too big to manage? **(Researcher).**

Oh, aye. It was far too big to manage. **(Bella, Site F, Person with Dementia).**

Interestingly, Ailsa's (family member) mother's previous home was located within a sheltered housing setting. Within this setting, she would receive check-ins from the sheltered housing officer, located on site, and had access to emergency call systems. However, the sheltered housing setting provided little support beyond this. Resultantly, due to increased risk of falls and becoming lost in the community, Ailsa and her family decided to investigate alternative housing settings. They visited extra care housing developments due to the extra level

of support and care they could provide, which, resultantly, led to a move into an extra care housing setting. Ailsa (family member) also provided some context regarding the overall aim or goal of extra care housing, linking this to the maintenance or promotion of independence. This was linked to individuals living in their own, self-contained homes, with support and care provided, provision of meals, and a greater emphasis on the organisation of social activities in the settings:

Extra care housing is before or pre-care home, where people can live in their own flats, and have pretty much their independence. They've got their own flat, they can go out and about. They're not, you know, they're not stopped from leaving. But they go down and they have lunch, and they go down and have dinner altogether, and they have activities ... So, she's got a nice little flat there. What was happening, she was already in supported housing, but was in a flat. And it was basically, like, she had the contact through the kind of radio thing. Someone you speak to every morning. But she had a few falls, and it was upstairs, and her dementia was getting worse. So, we went to [extra care housing setting] to have a look for a little extra support. When we went to it, we were really, really pleased with the setup there. And the staff have been absolutely fantastic with my mum. **(Ailsa, Site E, Family Member).**

A point to note here is the use of the description that those living in the settings "pretty much" have their independence. In this regard, there was an acknowledgement that individuals living in the settings, particularly those living in extra care housing, tended to have a higher level of need than individuals who live in sheltered or retirement housing. Hence, they had greater dependence on support or care. For example, as will be discussed throughout this case study, Ailsa and Eve's family members required frequent personal care, welfare checks throughout the night, and were largely confined to their flats due to mobility needs. In this regard, independence appeared to relate more to being able to remain living in a flat, as opposed to occupying a room in a care or nursing home. Hence, Ailsa described extra care housing as "pre-care home." Bella (person with dementia), however, continued to engage with the local community, and appeared to experience a higher level of independence than Ailsa and Eve's family members.

The added level of safety and security that very sheltered and extra care housing could provide was an apparent strength of the settings, from the viewpoints of Bella (person with dementia), Ailsa, and Eve (family members). To provide further context, Bella (person with dementia) utilised the assistive technology and home adaptations that were installed in her flat, such as pullcords, walk-in showers, and movement sensors. This ultimately gave her more independence and confidence with showering, which she would avoid doing in her previous home, as discussed in the following quote, when asked what helps her live independently in very sheltered housing:

Just going to the shop and going ... the only thing I can't do is go in for a shower. I must have somebody here. But I went in for one the other day without anybody here. My daughter's quite proud of me. She said, "See – I told you you could do it." I don't know what it is, sometimes I take a panic attack if I'm in myself. But I was quite all right. I think it's because I've got security. You know, like, security chains? I've got one right next to the shower as well, so maybe that's how. But in my old house, no. I wouldn't take any showers at all. I'd wash myself down and that was it. I've got to have somebody just to sit in. I know, my mind knows that there's somebody here. **(Bella, Site F, Person with Dementia).**

To provide further context, all properties in the settings contained home adaptations and assistive technologies. For example, emergency call systems, pullcords, and movement sensors. Emergency call systems could be used to contact support or care staff in the settings. The extra care housing settings in this case study operated with a lone night shift worker, meaning that at least one member of staff was present in the setting 24/7. The very sheltered housing setting operated with staff between 8am and 10pm, seven days a week. In this setting, outside of working hours, emergency calls would be directed to a central call centre.

The images, above, show the walk-in shower, pullcords (right of the shower), and emergency call system (right wall in the living room) installed in Bella's (person with dementia) flat.

Family members also valued the peace of mind that staff presence and assistive technologies provided. For example, Ailsa (family member) noted that night shift workers would check in on her mother as she slept. However, for Ailsa's mother, it was evident that this added level of security and safety could be associated with a loss of independence and privacy. For example, her mother's door was left unlocked throughout the night so that staff could enter her flat, to make sure she was sleeping and not in distress. However, it was unclear if this was the choice of the person with dementia, or if this constituted "living independently", with people free to come and go as they pleased from her home. Despite this, the presence of a night shift worker was a benefit, in that they could respond to emergencies that may have occurred in the evening. Ailsa (family member) discussed the use of assistive technologies and staff presence, below:

There's carers on throughout the night as well. There's also, strategically placed everywhere, is red pull cords, that if they do need any help, they're able to use them. So, it would alert the staff to come up if there was a problem. There's always somebody on call. They also do a check. They have a look

in, but they don't lock her door. We don't lock her outside door. So, the carers, if they wanted the door locked, they can have the door locked. But we just leave it open, and the carers will come in through the night and just have a wee look at her just to see that she's doing all right, she's sleeping and she's not in distress or anything. So, again, that gives us peace of mind that she is getting well looked after. **(Ailsa, Site E, Family Member).**

Other benefits of a move into very sheltered or extra care housing, for family members, were discussed. As Eve (family member) was actively involved in the provision of support to her mother-in-law, both before and after her move into extra care housing, she found it easier to clean her mother-in-law's flat due to its smaller size. She also valued the peace of mind of staff presence in the setting, who could respond to emergencies. This is outlined in the following quote, below:

She was in a three-bedroom house, it was obviously a much bigger house. So, even for us, my husband, he's 70 and I'm 67. It gets a wee bit easier for us just going into a one-bedroom flat and being able to give it a clean and Hoover and what have you. We do her washing still. The carers, if she has an accident in her bed, which she often does, she's quite incontinent. They'll change her bed. That's part of the service that they do. So, they will often change her bed clothes. But again, sometimes we do it as well, just kind of work it between us. But yeah, it's more down to, it's just easier for us. It gives us peace of mind knowing that there's always carers there, as well, so that, should she have a fall or just take unwell, the carers would notice quicker than possibly us going up to her old house to see her. **(Eve, Site D, Family Member).**

Hence, this added layer of safety and security enabled Bella (person with dementia) to develop independence with regard to washing and showering and made Eve and Ailsa (family members) feel content in the knowledge that their family member was being looked after. Ultimately, the overall aim or goal of very sheltered and extra care housing was described by Martha and Catherine (service coordinators) as the provision of an "independent living" service. However, it was evident that some people who were living in the settings, such as Ailsa and Eve's family members, had a high level of need. In this regard, their family members required personal care, a member of staff to check on them throughout the night, and they were

largely confined to their flat due to mobility needs. Hence, a positive of the settings discussed by those involved was the ability to provide a higher level of support and care, than, for example, settings like sheltered housing. This would suggest that very sheltered and extra care housing are well placed to provide a greater level of support and care to those living with dementia, if or when required. However, as will be discussed throughout this case study, it will become evident that this is not necessarily true, due to resource limitations.

Returning to the discussion around loneliness and isolation, in addition to safety and security, those involved in this case study valued the opportunities for socialising and community engagement that the settings fostered. Bella (person with dementia) discussed the relationships with others that she had developed since moving into the extra care housing setting. In particular, she had friends that she would have her lunch and dinner with, speaking fondly about her relationships with them. To reiterate, Bella (person with dementia) felt lonely in her previous home and would rarely interact with others and the local community. However, after moving into the very sheltered housing setting, she developed relationships with others, evidencing her growth as a person in this regard:

We get our lunch at twelve and we get our dinner at half past four. I got introduced to [name], and the new woman along there, and the woman next on this floor, I got introduced to them. We all sit together. I chap [name] at quarter to twelve and get her down for her dinner, because she's terrified of lifts. So, I take her down, I take her down every day. So, I'm really happy here. There's a wee man in here called [name]. Oh, what a man. He's had a stroke, and he comes and sits at the table across from me. I call him Double Trouble. The laugh we have in that dining hall, I tell you what. Oh, it's not real. **(Bella, Site F, Person with Dementia).**

The image below shows the dining room in the very sheltered housing setting in which Bella lived.

It was brightly lit, with an adjacent communal lounge, shown in the image, below.

It was early in the day during this visitation of the setting, and the communal areas were not in use. However, in discussions with Bella (person with dementia) and Martha (service coordinator), it was evident that these areas were used frequently by those living in the setting. Bella (person with dementia) also spoke about the excitement she had when waking up in the morning, washing, and getting dressed so that she could spend time in the communal foyer with her friend, “putting the world to rights” and chatting. The foyer is shown below, which was brightly lit, with chairs and views outside.

Through use of assistive technologies, staff presence, and opportunities for social engagement, Bella (person with dementia) stated that her daughter could see a positive change in her. Bella felt that moving into the setting had given her a new lease of life. She also stated that she would recommend the setting to anyone, that the setting improved her mental health and wellbeing, and that living in the setting supported her to engage with her local community. Again, there was clear evidence of growth experienced by Bella (person with dementia), as outlined in the quote, below:

Put it this way. I was up in my old house. I had nobody. I was – all day, I spoke to nobody if my daughter didn't come down. In here, I've got – oh, I've got everybody to talk to. Put it that way. It's been – it's really great. **(Bella, Site F, Person with Dementia).**

Do you think it's given you a new lease of life? **(Researcher).**

Yeah, it was a new lease of life. Brilliant lease of life, put it that way. Even my daughter knows the change in me ... I would recommend it to anybody – like myself – to come into one of these places. I'm telling you – you'll cheer yourself up. I was never dressed. I was going about in my housecoat and my pyjamas, and when I came in here, I'm dressed every day. Sometimes I go up and down to the shop. So, it's really helped me that way. I really love it. **(Bella, Site F, Person with Dementia).**

Eve (family member) also discussed the positive change in her mother-in-law due to the social aspects of living in extra care housing, and opportunities to spend time with other residents. However, as Eve's mother-in-law had high mobility needs and more advanced dementia, she required members of staff to take her on her wheelchair to the communal areas in the setting. In this regard, Eve (family member) believed that extra care housing was independent living for some people living in the setting, who had lesser support and care needs, but it is unclear if this applied to her mother-in-law. For example, a reliance on family members or staff to transfer her to other areas of the building might mean that her engagement with others in the setting or use of communal areas could be limited to mealtimes or organised social events. Nonetheless, such opportunities for social engagement were viewed positively, with such opportunities being limited in her previous home:

I think the social aspect has definitely made a difference to her. The fact that she can go down and mix with the other residents at lunch times and also after lunch. As I said, the staff will wheel her through to the TV room, along with all the other residents as well, the ones that want to. I mean, there's a lot of them that don't have dementia, and they're quite happy to just go back to their flat. It's independent living, if you like, for some of the residents who don't need an awful lot of help. But there is quite a number of them that are quite happy to socialise with each other. And the social aspect definitely, we feel, it's been really good for her. **(Eve, Site D, Family Member)**.

However, the challenges of coordinating activities and mealtimes, particularly within the extra care housing settings, were evident, due to the higher level of need of those living in the settings. For example, in the setting in which Catherine (service coordinator) worked, of the 26 flats, 17 individuals required the use of a wheelchair, hence, transferring from their flats to the dining room or communal areas. There was also an indication that care needs had increased over time, attributed in part to the COVID-19 pandemic and the subsequent frailty that individuals experienced due to their lack of movement. Hence, it is unclear how much independent or spontaneous activity took place in the settings, given the reliance on supporting individuals with mobility and the organisation of social activities and mealtimes:

What we're finding now is that some of our residents who come in, they come in and they've got quite high care needs. But, before, extra care didn't take people with equipment. So, what would happen would be, as your needs changed, and if you need equipment, that would be done and sorted. Now, in [extra care housing setting], they've got seventeen wheelchairs to bring down at lunch and dinner time. So, people are frailer as they've moved in. But, again, we don't know if that's just been because of COVID and restrictions, and people have become less mobile. But, before when people were moving in, they were very mobile, very independent. It was the meal thing for them. Whereas now, the care needs that are coming in are very high. As I say, the girls have got seventeen transfers over lunch and then the same at dinner time. It's very hard to fit wheelchairs into one space.

(Catherine, Site D, Service Coordinator).

In the images below, it is evident that the communal lounge in Site D, in which Catherine (service coordinator) worked, was small. Some cluttered areas, such as the table at the back right of the room, in the top image, were visible. Hence, it is unlikely that this room could accommodate more than a small gathering of people. Further, although more spacious, the challenge of accommodating 17 wheelchair users in the dining room, shown in the bottom image, below, can also be appreciated. Resultantly, throughout visits to both extra care housing sites, the dining and communal lounge areas were only occupied by staff members. For example, in one visit to an extra care housing setting, several staff members were occupying a communal lounge watching television, despite there being a dedicated staff room in the setting. In such instances, although anecdotal, the extra care housing developments felt more like places of work or care, due to the larger number of staff present, rather than housing settings. Another factor that may have influenced this interpretation was the uniforms worn by the extra care housing staff, with light blue tunics and navy trousers, resembling clinical or healthcare staff. In the very sheltered housing setting, staff wore regular clothing. This was likely due to the caring duties of the extra care housing staff, who were seen going door to door in the settings to provide care to those living in the flats.

Staff members involved in this case study discussed more of the challenges associated with providing support and care in the settings, organising social activities, and some of the negative aspects of living with dementia in extra care housing. For example, although Bella (person with dementia), Ailsa, and Eve (family members) discussed the benefits of socialising in the settings, Fiona (support worker) believed that social relationships between people living with dementia and other residents in the settings were not always positive. For example, she stated that people with dementia can be “easy targets” in the settings or in the community, and that some people were more “tolerant” or accepting of people with dementia than others:

People with dementia, people with any difference to anyone else in the world, you know, sometimes they can be an easy target. Sometimes it can be so obvious that there's a difference. Some people are accepting of that and are kind with that, and then others can be really, really harsh. I know one particular tenant, I was talking about earlier ... I feel for that person because that person is definitely in their own world, and I'm fairly confident that person lives in a really lovely world in their head. But then, some of the other tenants are more tolerant of that than some of the others. Is that because they can see the difference and they accept that that's just the way that person is, and that's all okay? Or is it they, the other tenants, might feel a bit frightened or intimidated, they don't know how to respond to a situation in that way? Or is it that they just maybe think, that tenant is a bit odd, different to themselves or their peer group at their table? **(Fiona, Site E, Support Worker).**

There was also an indication that family members had more positive outlooks regarding the experience of living with dementia in extra care housing, when compared to the interviewed staff members. For example, Ailsa believed that her mother was well looked after and valued the level of support, care, and opportunities for socialisation that she received, with the belief that she was safe and secure. However, when discussing Ailsa's mother, Catherine (support worker) believed that the setting was not suitable for her, due to the level of support and care she required. Giving some example scenarios, Catherine (support worker) stated that Ailsa's mother did not know, or would forget how, to use the pullcords and emergency call systems in her home. As a result, there were situations where Ailsa's mother had fallen or required support, waiting for hours for someone to check in on her. In another instance, Catherine (support worker) stated that Ailsa's mother ingested a denture cleaning tablet and required hospitalisation, discussed below:

I'm probably thinking of more advanced stages, but I do think to have places that are specific to dementia, I think, would be more beneficial. That's not to say that we don't love the ones that we've got, it's not that at all. I do think it's just not the right place for a lot of people with dementia, I would say. We did have a situation just a few weeks ago where the person took [denture cleaning] tablets, the tablets for steeping dentures. That person took them thinking they were mint sweeties. That was a sheer fluke. I was night shift that night, but it was a sheer fluke that I went in to do a welfare check

on that person, at that particular time, when it had just happened. And, also, that we managed to get an ambulance within an hour. **(Catherine, Site D, Service Coordinator)**.

In sum, there were clear benefits of living in very sheltered and extra care housing, like increased safety and security and opportunities for socialisation. These benefits promoted independence, particularly for Bella (person with dementia), and there were reports of positive changes experienced by those living with dementia in the settings from family members. However, several challenges or negatives were discussed, particularly by the interviewed staff members. These challenges related to those living with a higher level of care need, or more advanced dementia. It was evident that although staff presence was higher in these settings, those working in the settings still faced challenges due to the limited resources available. Although the underlying mantra of very sheltered and extra care housing was the provision of an independent living service, it was evident that independence often meant being able to live in a flat, as opposed to a care home, rather than independent or autonomous engagement within the setting and local community. Hence, staff faced clear challenges when organising mealtimes and coordinating social activities, meaning that Catherine (service coordinator) believed that extra care housing was not suitable for all people living with dementia, due to resource limitations. Hence, the next theme focusses more on practical aspects of support and care provision, given the greater emphasis on these services in very sheltered and extra care housing.

6.9. Theme Two: Provision of Support and Care in Very Sheltered and Extra Care Housing

This theme centres on discussion around the provision of support and care in very sheltered or extra care housing for people living with dementia. This is predominantly because there was a greater focus on support and care provision in discussions during interviews, given that very sheltered and extra care housing emphasise the provision of a higher level of support and care, when compared to other models of supported housing. Resultantly, the theme focusses on the higher level of support and care that these settings can provide, in comparison to sheltered or retirement housing, and the challenges faced by staff with regard to meeting the needs of people living with dementia.

To reiterate, the extra care housing settings involved in this case study aided with personal care, in addition to the provision of meals and the organisation of social activities within the settings. The settings supported

those living in the settings to prepare breakfast but provided lunch and dinner in dining rooms during set mealtimes. Extra care housing settings also had at least one member of staff present in the settings 24/7. The night shift worker would conduct welfare checks for those living in the settings, to check that they were not in any distress, and would respond to any emergency calls that would occur throughout the night. It should be noted that this was not an extensive staff team, but one staff member. Nonetheless, there were significantly more staff members present in the settings in comparison to sheltered housing settings, who operated with one sheltered housing officer throughout the day. Fiona (support worker) provides an overview of extra care housing, as a service:

It's sheltered accommodation, with extra care. Extra care being that staff are there 24/7. Albeit just a lone night shift worker. So, we are supposed to assist people, as required, with personal care, medication prompts. And they come down, it's all their own individual properties. They're all tenants, with their own tenancy agreements with a local housing authority. And we assist, prompt them, to come down to the main dining room at lunchtime and at evening mealtime, because they all eat together, that's part of the tenancy agreement. However, breakfast is taken in their own homes. They provide that, whatever they want, and staff can assist with the preparation and the serving up of that.

(Fiona, Site E, Support Worker).

In this regard, due to the higher level of support and care that was available, Catherine (service coordinator) stated that extra care housing settings were able to care for people until the end of life. For example, Catherine stated that extra care housing aims to support people, longer term, to remain at home until the end of their lives, without having to move to care or nursing homes. During their time living in the settings, people would move in with some level of need, with support or care increased incrementally as their needs progressed. At the same time, the individual would develop familiarity with the staff and the setting. In an ideal world, this would be true for all people living in the settings, and, in the research literature, being able to remain at home until the end of life is a goal for most individuals. However, this was not the case for all people, in particular, those living with advanced dementia, or those who were so ill they required full time nursing care. Although some individuals might require placement in a care or nursing home, should their

needs require, this likely points to a wider societal inequality with regard to access to healthcare. For example, advanced dementia is not only confined to end of life care. Hence, if appropriate and equal access to healthcare was available for those living with dementia, they might be better supported to continue living in their home, should they wish. However, as things stand, this does not appear to be a reality in very sheltered and extra care housing, despite the higher level of support and care provided. This is discussed by Catherine (service coordinator), below:

Usually, what you find with extra care housing, is tenants are long term tenants. We can meet their needs to end of life care. People don't tend to move on unless, perhaps, their dementia is really bad, or their health's generally declined and they need nursing care, you know? So, what you'll find is a lot of people move in, and they're a good five, six years, which is good. That's what extra care was always meant for. It was, you were at an age where you were quite able-bodied, but as you progressed, you knew the carers, you knew the staff. By the time your time comes to getting care, you were very familiar. **(Catherine, Site D, Service Coordinator).**

Within the very sheltered housing setting, Martha (service coordinator) stated that staff members working in the settings did not provide personal care. Rather, personal care was accessed externally. The supported housing staff working in the settings provided meals and organised social activities, and responded to any emergencies that arose in the settings. As had been stated previously by Catherine (service coordinator), this too appeared to be the original aim of extra care housing. However, due to the increased needs of those living in the settings, the focus of the involved extra care housing developments shifted more to the provision of support and care. Martha (service coordinator) provided an overview of very sheltered housing, as a service, in the quote, below:

Very sheltered, which we are, we've got supported housing workers, and we don't provide any, you know, care service. But we only provide meals and social activities. We arrange social activities like bingo nights. Men's club we've got upstairs. Sport memory we call it, yeah. So, that's the difference. Very sheltered provide meals and more, you know, the social side, but sheltered is just housing. **(Martha, Site F, Service Coordinator).**

From the perspective of family members, Ailsa reflected on the support and care that her mother received in extra care housing. Although it was evident that extra care housing settings could provide a higher level of care than settings like retirement or sheltered housing, it was again acknowledged that the provision of care was a finite resource, which often required staff members to go the extra mile to support those living with dementia. This can be interpreted as unfair on the staff members, in addition to Ailsa's mother. For staff, the unfairness might relate to an inability to meet the needs of those living in the setting, despite building a bond with these individuals and wanting to provide adequate support and care for them. For Ailsa's mother, the unfairness links to an unequal access to support and care to meet her progressing needs, despite being happy in her home, with the prospect of having to move into another care setting. Ailsa (family member) discussed staff members going the extra mile in the quote, below:

I think the girls in [extra care housing setting] go the extra mile for my mum, because [extra care housing] is designed, really, isn't really designed for severe dementia patients. It's, you know, it's clearly for people who are a little bit independent, or who still want to maintain that. But they've really enabled my mum to have as much independence. We've had to get a little bit extra care from her, regarding her personal care. So, they've just upped that as required. And if we've got any issues with them, we just go in and we'll just say "We've noticed she's not able to make a cup of tea now," or, "She can't stick her teeth in," or you know, so all the things that we, we just highlight it, and they just say, "Right, we'll put that in place. We'll make sure that that's done for her." So, I honestly believe they go the extra mile. **(Ailsa, Site E, Family Member).**

Following the notion that support and care in very sheltered and extra care housing is a finite resource, there was acknowledgement from Fiona (support worker), Catherine, and Martha (service coordinators) that very sheltered and extra care housing settings lacked the fundamental resources to provide a level of care that meets the needs of those living with dementia, beyond the earlier stages of the condition. As shown previously, Fiona (support worker) was vocal in her belief that extra care housing was not an appropriate setting for those living with dementia. Martha (service coordinator) also reiterated this view. Within the housing association that Martha worked for, the organisation operated with housing models that provided

varying levels of support and care. For example, sheltered housing provided a lower level of support, very sheltered housing provided a higher level of support and the provision of meals, and housing with care had care staff working in the setting 24 hours a day. Although acknowledging that some individuals with dementia may be able to live in very sheltered housing for up to ten years, it was again acknowledged that very sheltered housing lacked the resources to care for individuals with a high level of need. The quotations from Fiona (support worker) and Martha (service coordinator), below, were in response to the question, do you think the setting is a suitable setting for people living with dementia?

Out of the four complexes, I've worked in the four of them, and I would say, design wise and size wise, I think [extra care housing setting] is a perfect setup. However, with regard to dementia, I'm not convinced with that at all. Perhaps, maybe, in the early stages. The very early stages. **(Fiona, Site E, Support Worker).**

Depends on the level of dementia. If it's just, you know, onset dementia, like with the tenant you spoke to, it's fine, it's very good. But if the dementia is progressed, quite progressed – then it's a no, not at all. Not here. But if it's the housing with care development, yes. Because the carers are involved. Some developments, we've got twenty-four seven supports, so staff are always there. But not here, no. [Very sheltered housing] is either when someone has onset dementia, and they're quite independent until it progresses to the stage where they would need to move. But we don't know when that time will come, you know? Five years, ten years – nobody knows. So, until then it's okay for them to stay here. Otherwise, no. **(Martha, Site F, Service Coordinator).**

Providing further context as to why the settings were not suitable for those living with more advanced dementia, Fiona (support worker), Martha, and Catherine (service coordinators) all acknowledged that a challenging aspect of support and care provision, for those living with dementia, was supporting those who would “wander”, or walk with purpose. This was because the settings were described as independent living, with those living in the settings legally classed as tenants or homeowners by law. This meant that individuals were free to come and go as they pleased, which could result in those living with dementia becoming lost in the community. Catherine (service coordinator) discussed this further:

I think what we have to always be very aware of, if someone is prone to wandering – then we can't stop them leaving. When families come to look at [extra care housing setting], or any extra care, we will say, "If there's any risk of wandering, we would advise you to perhaps look at somewhere else." Because we're not a locked unit. Staff aren't always visible, or there's not always someone in the office that you would see them going out. So, we would always say, "We could meet your mum, dad's care needs to a certain extent. But if someone becomes a risk of wandering, we can't always manage that." **(Catherine, Site D, Service Coordinator).**

It can be argued that the design of the buildings did little to support wayfinding for those living with dementia, due to the long corridors that were contained in the buildings, that looked almost identical. There was also no evidence that dementia friendly design guidelines had been adhered to when building the settings. The images below, from both extra care housing settings, give some indication of how the setting might become disorienting, with sprawling, shadowy, and unnaturally lit corridors, and doors the same colour and style. It may be argued that with better design, and increased training regarding how to support people with dementia with wayfinding, that they could be supported to live in the settings for longer. After all, wayfinding is not necessarily a severe physical condition requiring full time healthcare, but rather, individuals' needs or distress can be eased by understanding where the individual wants to go, or spending time with them.

Regarding design of the built environment, Fiona (support worker) also had experience of caring for her father who had dementia. Her mother and father had lived in a sheltered housing development for several years. Due to the open nature of the setting, her father would often leave the property and become lost in the community. Resultantly, Fiona and her family sought different housing and care options. Her father subsequently moved into a setting that specialised in the provision of dementia care. In this discussion, Fiona spoke about one of the settings she had contacted when looking for an alternative setting for her father. This setting contained several "units", which could provide gradually higher levels of care as an individual's condition progressed. Each unit would contain rooms that looked the same as the other units. In theory, individuals would move into the unit which provides the lowest level of support and care and would progress

through the units as their needs changed. However, given that the units were similarly designed, this might support the individual to feel familiar in their environment:

They explained about their four units. But every single room was the same. And where that might be a negative for some people, you kind of think, right, okay, this makes sense, because, say for talking sake, say you move into the first unit and you're at early stage dementia, and then, and this was actually what was explained, was that someone who came in who had early dementia might progress through every unit in that building until the end stage. Now, hopefully that would be eased somewhat by the fact that they could be in the exact same room, you know, what they may think is the exact same room. By the time they start in there and within five years, ten years, they may have moved rooms four times, but, to them, it looks like the exact same room. And I thought, well, that's a fantastic idea. **(Fiona, Site E, Support Worker).**

Although at a smaller scale, there is evidence in the research literature that environments that can provide “continuing care”, for example, purpose-built retirement villages, can support people to live in the same community as their needs progress. For example, an individual might move into a sheltered housing bungalow, then move to an extra care housing flat, and into a nursing home if their needs required. However, all settings would be in the same development or grounds. In this regard, Catherine (service coordinator) spoke about the extra care housing development in which she worked. The housing association that ran the development also provided social housing, sheltered housing, and extra care housing, some of which containing specialist dementia care units, all within the local area. Catherine had spoken of individuals that lived in social housing, and subsequently moved across the road to an extra care housing development. This meant that individuals could continue living in the same community, whilst receiving a higher level of support and care when needed. However, the limited number of dwellings in the local area meant that the progression of individuals, from low level support settings, through to higher level dementia care settings, did not always occur. Catherine (service coordinator) discussed this in the following quotes:

Because over at [extra care housing location] we do have a locked unit, I don’t know if you’re aware of that? **(Catherine, Site E, Service Coordinator).**

Okay. No, I didn’t know that, no. **(Researcher).**

So [extra care housing setting] has a locked unit. And that is like the hospital doors, so it’s a fob to get in and out. It’s a square. The flats are all based round a square, and that’s right out onto the garden, but the garden’s all secure. So, the tenants that are in there who have dementia, or high levels of dementia, have a lot of freedom because they’re safe. They can’t go anywhere. But in that unit the now, because... I think we’ve got three tenants on that site that don’t have any dementia. They’re able to get in and out with their fob. But in an ideal world they would be in mainstream. But it all depends on what flats become available at the time. **(Catherine, Site E, Service Coordinator).**

Hence, although very sheltered and extra care housing settings had access to greater resources in comparison to settings like sheltered or retirement housing, these settings still faced challenges with regard to meeting a

higher level of needs. There was also limited choice regarding where to live, because of the low number of supported housing settings in local areas.

A further challenge discussed by those involved related to issues with accessing an appropriate number of staff. For example, Martha (service coordinator) described challenges when accessing staff cover, caused in part due to changes in policies that meant she could no longer offer overtime to staff who worked in the settings. Ultimately, this created challenges with developing a staff team that was familiar with the setting. Challenges with accessing staff could also impact the services offered in the setting, such as the provision of cooked meals, or having staff present until 10pm. Furthermore, covering shifts required using an agency service, who often did not have enough staff members to provide support. Additionally, all the involved family members and staff in this case study discussed the importance of the development of familiarity between staff members and people living with dementia. Challenges with accessing appropriate staff are discussed by Martha (service coordinator), below:

The biggest challenge is to cover the development. That's the biggest challenge, at the moment, and for the past three years from COVID. Because, when you don't have a cook, it's a big impact on the service. That means we need to go to the contingency plan, and that's frozen meals, which I don't want to serve my tenants. I want them to have good meals. Home-made meals. Or, if the supported housing workers are not covered, then that means the bingo night is cancelled. Or locking up and closing everything at six o'clock, or five o'clock, you know? And it's a big impact on them, and I don't feel happy about it. That's a huge challenge at the moment. And the policies always change. We had a policy that if you have to cover sick or annual leave, I could offer it to my staff members, and they were always happy to cover. But the new law we have, it all needs to go through agencies. So, we contact them, we inform them, "Right, today, I don't have this" or, you know? And I have no right to ask my staff. That's a big challenge, and I don't like that. And I'm not the only one. All coordinators, all managers, we hate this system. Hopefully they will change this soon. **(Martha, Site F, Service Coordinator).**

Other challenges discussed in the interviews related to communication and coordination between staff members who worked in the settings. Ailsa (family member) had worked as a care manager before retiring and had extensive experience with regard to providing training to care staff and coordinating services. The interview was conducted to gather her perspective on her mother's experience of living with dementia in extra care housing, but she also reflected on her previous job roles. She felt that communication between staff members was the greatest issue for social care to overcome, as this could create problems for those living in the settings. Fundamentally, she believed that this was an issue created by the training received by social care professionals, which often focusses more on interactions with "service users", as opposed to interactions and communication with other professionals. She believed that this could contribute to a loss of dignity for people with dementia living in the settings, whose needs may not be met because of poor communication and relaying information to other individuals working in the settings. This is outlined in the following excerpt:

For me, one of the biggest issues in these kind of settings is what people are writing in the book. Because if a family member says, "Oh, her teeth keep falling down. Would you be able to put more glue in it?" It would be a good idea to write it in the book. Because then whoever comes in next will see that. I have actually seen it being really disruptive in other care settings. I've seen it actually causing chaos, because people aren't communicating ... from being a trainer, I think that that's a training issue. And to me, that's one thing in the whole of social care that would improve, if there was some kind of training programme done around staff dealing with staff. Not staff dealing with service users, but staff dealing with staff, and that's not really addressed, because everything's about your service user. Are you communicating with them, do you look at them? Is your body language good? And actually, when I think about it now, the key is, if one member of staff knows something about, for example, my mum, everybody needs to know. And it might seem minor, but I guess it's not, for somebody's dignity and respect, isn't it? **(Ailsa, Site E, Family Member).**

In addition to challenges created with regard to accessing staff, and the difficulties created because of poor communication between staff members, Catherine (service coordinator) also acknowledged that staff often

lacked the resources, training, and time to better support those living with dementia. She also acknowledged the importance of family involvement in the support or care for people with dementia. Catherine discussed the need for greater resources to support those living with dementia in the quote, below:

I think we could have more resources. I think we could be doing with more staff training. And just resources to ... you know, whether it just be, right, I've seen this memory game, or whether... you know, I think we need a wee bit more time to spend with people with dementia as well, you know? I think just in general to make their life a wee bit more pleasant. Especially if somebody doesn't want to talk or they're quite isolated. I do feel that we need more resources with, with dementia. But sometimes - because obviously you need a lot of family participation with that, sometimes you'll find that some families aren't willing to help. I think as well, a family can tell us loads of information, or they can give us basics. And I think sometimes we need more help from the families as well, to give us that wee bit of wealth of knowledge, so that ... I mean, if it was my family moving in here, I think I would be telling them everything, whether that's because I've worked in this situation, but sometimes – it takes a long time to get to know somebody. You know, their likes, their dislikes, their quirks. Again, I think it is just about communicating with one another, you know? **(Catherine, Site D, Service Coordinator).**

In this regard, Bella (person with dementia) had frequent contact with family and friends, and Eve and Ailsa were involved in providing support and care to their family members. However, as discussed by Catherine (service coordinator), this was not always the norm. This added greater pressure with regard to meeting the needs of those living with dementia in the settings.

6.10. Summary of Case Study Two

This case study first discussed some of the positives of living with dementia in very sheltered and extra care housing. Most notably, Bella (person with dementia) described her experience of developing independence and relationships in the setting, after a period of being lonely at home, facing challenges with housework, and managing her personal care. Further, Bella (person with dementia), Eve, and Ailsa (family members) valued the added safety, security, and peace of mind that the settings offered, due to staff presence and

access to assistive technologies and home adaptations. Indeed, very sheltered, and extra care housing, had greater resources to provide support and care, when compared to sheltered or retirement housing, including personal care and the provision of meals. However, Fiona (support worker), Catherine, and Martha (service coordinators) all believed that the settings were poorly equipped to provide support and care to those living with advanced dementia. Further, the settings were also challenged to accommodate individuals who were prone to “wandering” or walking with purpose, and becoming lost in the community, due to the open nature of these settings and their emphasis on independent living. Accessing familiar staff members was described as a challenge, and poor communication between staff members could lead to a loss of dignity and create unnecessary problems for those living with dementia in the settings. It was suggested that training could improve the support and care provided to those living with dementia. Further, suggestions were made regarding changes to the models of care provided in the settings. These included offering staged or tiered levels of care that could be accessed as and when needed, and the provision of more extra care housing developments that would enable individuals to continue living in their local community. Summary statements of findings that will be used in the cross-case analysis are shown in Table 11.

Table 11: Summary of findings from case study two.

Case Study Two: Summary of Findings

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|------|--|
| I. | People with dementia move into very sheltered and extra care housing for comfort and security, the increased provision of support and care, and opportunities for social engagement. |
| II. | There is an indication that very sheltered and extra care housing can support people with dementia to live with some independence, though to a lesser extent, due to the increased mobility and care needs of the individuals living in the settings. |
| III. | Very sheltered and extra care housing settings can provide a higher level of support and care, through increased staff numbers, the presence of support workers or home care staff, and the provision of meals. |
| IV. | There are several factors that lead to people with dementia being referred or managed out of these settings, like living with advanced dementia, having difficulties with wayfinding, and the limited involvement of family members or friends regarding support and care provision. |
| V. | These factors can be attributed to poor environmental design, poor dementia awareness and stigma, and limited access to resources and funding. |
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6.11. Case Study Three: Perspectives on Supported Housing as a Future Housing Choice

6.11.1. Context of Case Study Three

This case study has a different format to previous case studies because it aims to explore the experiences and perceptions of people with dementia who are contemplating moving into supported housing. Although case studies one and two included interviews, photographs, and documents, this case study only involved interviews. The interviews sought to gather some perspectives on supported housing as a future housing choice, from the viewpoints of people living with dementia. Those involved in the case study were considering, or had considered, a move into supported housing. This viewpoint was important to capture, given that individuals can often face challenges when accessing supported housing, due to long waiting lists. Further, there are also limitations regarding choice and types of supported housing in Scotland, with many dwellings provided by social landlords or local councils. This means that individuals who do not qualify for social housing, or wish to stay in a private residence, have little choice. The case study sought to involve three people living with dementia. 1) An individual who had firmly decided that supported housing was not right for them; 2) an individual who was actively looking for a residence in supported housing, had viewed multiple properties, but could not find the right fit; and 3) an individual who had been on a waiting list for a place in supported housing for several years. Due to the third individual being hospitalised, they were no longer able to be involved in this case study. Therefore, Table 12, below, introduces the two people living with dementia that were involved in the study, including participant characteristics and information about their living arrangements. These interviews lasted one hour each.

Table 12: Participant characteristics and descriptions of living arrangements.

Participant	Participant Characteristics	Description of Living Arrangements
David, person with dementia.	David was 58 years old and was living with young-onset dementia. He was diagnosed with dementia at age 50. He also lived with epilepsy and had a history of cardiovascular health conditions.	David lived in a cottage with his partner. He had lived in his house for 20 years. In addition to receiving support from his partner, David was visited by an independent carer, or personal assistant, who would support him throughout the day.
John, person with dementia.	John was 69 years old and had been living with Alzheimer's disease for	John lived in a house with his son-in-law and had lived in the house for

one year. He had a history of cardiovascular health conditions.

approximately one year. He was living with his son-in-law while he looked for a more permanent residence, and had been viewing supported housing settings with the prospect of moving into one.

The next section of this case study is formed of one theme, relating to accessing housing, health, and social care. This relates to choosing where to live, and finding an appropriate setting that meets an individual's needs and wants. The theme also focusses on choice with regard to accessing appropriate levels of support and care to meet an individual's needs and wants, to support people with dementia to live independently at home in the community.

6.12. Theme One: Accessing Housing, Health, and Social Care

Those involved in this case study had negative views towards supported housing, with both individuals expressing that supported housing settings would likely not satisfy their needs and wants. To provide some context here, David lived with his partner, and was visited regularly by an independent carer, or personal assistant, accessed through self-directed support. The Scottish Parliament passed the Social Care (Self-directed Support) (Scotland) Act 2013, to give eligible recipients of social care and support greater choice and control over how they receive such services. Individuals receive a care assessment and are allocated a budget that can be used to access personalised support and care services. For example, David used this self-directed support budget to employ a personal assistant, who would support him with day-to-day activities when needed. As such, David felt supported and independent at home due to the level of support he received from social care services and family. However, he also acknowledged that accessing such supports was challenging, and ultimately required input from a local councillor to fight for the supports on his behalf. In this regard, it should be noted that not all people with dementia will have the knowledge of, or experience of accessing, such supports. Other individuals may live alone, again limiting the amount of support or care available. Further, John did not receive any support or care services at the time of interviewing, likely because he had only recently been diagnosed. He lived with his son-in-law, who had provided some support to him as he recovered from major surgery. John was still able to drive and lived independently. Nonetheless, to provide

some context with regard to accessing support and care for people with dementia, David discussed the challenges with accessing self-directed support in the quote, below:

We had a lot of problems accessing self-directed support for myself. And it was only because I knew about it from my previous experience, so I knew what I was entitled to. And my local councillor was happy to fight on my behalf. But social work weren't, so they wanted to provide all of the support, which was essentially what they decided I needed. **(David, Person with Dementia).**

Although David and John felt supported at home and did not feel a move to supported housing was necessary, John was aware of the challenges of accessing appropriate supports in the community for people with dementia. He acknowledged the inconsistency and limited access to care professionals, and the unequal access to healthcare that people with dementia face. Further, although feeling satisfied and supported at the time of our interview, David acknowledged that there may come a time when he would require a move from his present home. This was because his partner was 68 years old and kept in ill health, meaning that he may face challenges when meeting greater mobility or care needs. For example, the bathroom in their cottage was contained downstairs, but the bedrooms were on the second level, meaning the bathroom could become difficult to access. Resultantly, David spoke of the prospect of selling his house to move to a home that was "future-proof." In theory, this future-proofed home could meet his, his partner's, and his mother's needs, as they grew older and their needs increased. However, it was also acknowledged that this setting should not resemble long-term care:

I was able to pay the mortgage off, which we're starting to wonder if that was a good thing to do or not. Because if things get worse, I mean, I'm... what I would term it, high performing? I'm not bad. I have good days and bad days, but I don't require the assistance that some others require because of this condition. If I did, then we would have to look at options, which would include selling the house. When we lost my father, my mother owns her own house, we looked at the option of selling both houses and buying something which was future-proof for my mother and myself, and my partner, who's ten years older than me and doesn't keep in the best of health. But I'm not keen on long-term care. My mother is not keen on long-term care. **(David, Person with Dementia).**

David included supported housing in his description of long-term care. He did not want to move into long-term care, or supported housing, as he believed his partner may not be able to live with him. He had also developed routines and familiarity within his present home, where he had lived for 20 years. He also worried about the prospect of becoming socially isolated, as he continued to engage with his local community, through attending church and playing in a flute band. There was a worry that a move to supported housing could remove him from this community. In the following quote, David discussed his connections to his local community and the independence he experienced:

I am very independent, and the band I play in ... I'm forty-six years a member ... I can still play, I can still read, and I can still meet and I can still arrange music on the computer. I've got a programme that allows me to arrange ... As a person, I'm independent. Church is a strong part of my life. I'm a regular churchgoer. **(David, Person with Dementia).**

John lived with his son-in-law who helped him with his recovery from major heart surgery, which he had received the previous year. He now felt that he could move into his own home, and had been looking at supported housing settings, in addition to standard flats. However, John was displeased with the supported housing settings that he visited. He felt that the settings were institutional. For example, describing one of his visits to a supported housing setting, he stated that the environment felt like a "prison for older people", or an "oldie's ghetto." This is outlined in the quote, below:

We walked in, and there were lifts up to the, I think it was the third floor we had to go to. But then the lift door opened, and there was an enormous, long corridor with a sort of beige carpet and doors. And it just felt like a... it felt a bit like a sort of prison for older people. That was all I could think of. If I'd have found a sheltered housing scheme that I'd have liked, I might think differently. But, but the one I went to didn't grab me at all. Yeah, but it's more the idea of being in an oldie's ghetto that fills me with horror. **(John, Person with Dementia).**

John wanted to live in a setting that was close to shops and pubs, and despite liking the location in which the above flat was located, the environment did not appeal to him. Instead, John stated that he wished to move to a setting that was intergenerational, rather than designed specifically for people of older age. For example,

he stated that he would like to live with students or toddlers, as opposed to only living with older people. John also discussed cultural issues that might have impacted the design and building of supported housing developments in the United Kingdom, with an overemphasis on living independently, and grouping individuals in settings with similar ages. Ultimately, John had decided that he wanted to move to a flat on his own, as opposed to a supported housing setting. This was because he could not find the right housing choice for him. The following excerpt is large, but John highlights several issues with regard to; choice and access to housing; an overemphasis in the United Kingdom on independence, as opposed to community; and, the segregation of older people from others in society.

The more I thought about the idea of living in a retirement community, the less happy I was about that. I don't want to be just around old people. I actually like being around people of different ages. But we just don't seem to have that pattern in Britain. I know of various sort of experiments where students have lived with older people and things. And I would be really interested in taking part in something like that. It just isn't there, or that I can find. So, in the end I've decided to buy my own flat, which I'm doing. But slightly reluctantly, because I'm still thinking, "Well, what about this lovely community I'd really like to be part of?" **(John, Person with Dementia).**

6.13. Summary of Case Study Three

To summarise, it was evident that David and John had negative views towards supported housing as a future housing choice for people living with dementia. At the time of interviewing, they both felt supported at home. For David, this involved the receiving of support and care from a personal assistant and his partner. John did not require support or care, but lived with his son-in-law, who had supported him through his recovery from surgery. Living in their own properties meant that David and John could still independently engage with their local community, going to church, band practice, and visiting shops and pubs. Nonetheless, David acknowledged the prospect of moving from his present home as his condition and health needs progressed. However, David and John acknowledged the limitations with regard to accessing housing, health, and social care in Scotland, and there was an acknowledgment that supported housing might not meet their needs or wants. This was because supported housing settings were deemed to be institutional, resembling long-term

care settings, or were somewhat exclusionary of younger individuals. Although it is evident that this case study is informed by only two people with dementia's viewpoints, they nonetheless raise important societal issues that impact those living with dementia in Scotland. For example, challenges with accessing appropriate housing environments due to limited choice and housing types, challenges with accessing appropriate levels of support and care due to bureaucratic processes and a stretched social care workforce, and an overemphasis on segregating older people and people with dementia from other age groups in society. An interesting point raised by John is the emphasis on living independently in Scotland, and the wider United Kingdom, which may hinder the development of communities that support one another. After all, the previous case studies had emphasised the centrality of "independent living" within supported housing settings, with an inability to live independently contributing to people living with dementia being moved from the settings. Hence, this case study provides important insights into, not only, the experience of living with dementia in supported housing, but the experience of accessing supported housing and attitudes towards living in such environments from the perspectives of people living with dementia. Summary statements of findings that will be used in the cross-case analysis are shown in Table 13.

Table 13: Summary of findings from case study three.

Case Study Three: Summary of Findings	
I.	People with dementia have limited choice regarding housing options, particularly for people who do not wish to live in supported housing for older people, for individuals who want to remain living with family, or for individuals who would not qualify for social housing.
II.	Negative perceptions of supported housing exist from the viewpoints of people living with dementia, who viewed supported housing as institutional.

6.14. Cross-Case Analysis

As stated in Chapter Five, Section 5.5.3., the cross-case analysis utilises the summary findings developed throughout the case studies. These statements have been compiled and are shown in Table 14. The cross-case analysis resulted in the development of three cross-case themes. These themes resembled the changing labels assigned to people living with dementia and supported housing, as an individual's condition and living circumstances change.

The first theme is titled "Views of Supported Housing" that is, people with dementia's perspectives on moving into supported housing, drawing from the viewpoints of people with dementia who had considered, or had moved, into supported housing.

The second is titled "The Ideal Candidate"; the labelling of a person with dementia who is viewed as being "ideal" for life in supported housing.

The final cross-case theme is titled "Too Far Gone"; the point at which a person with dementia is deemed to no longer be ideal for the settings, facing a move from their home. It is important to note that there were multiple iterations of this final stage of analysis. For example, an initial analysis led to the construction of cross-case themes that resembled transitions through housing settings, from living in standard housing in the community, to sheltered housing, very sheltered or extra care housing, culminating in a move into a care or nursing home. However, this did not reflect the "bigger picture" of living with dementia in supported housing, as many individuals do not experience smooth transitions through housing settings.

Rather, through supervisory meetings and redrafting elements of the analysis, the three cross-case themes, presented below, provide a sound interpretation of the experience of living with dementia in supported housing. The presentation of the three case study reports, and the following cross-case analysis, serve to enhance the vicarious experiences of the reader (Stake, 1995). This aims to help the reader understand how the findings were developed, and the applicability of these findings to their own subjective experiences and contexts.

Table 14: Summary of findings from the individual case studies.

Case Study One: Summary of Findings

- I. People with dementia move into sheltered housing due to the smaller size of the dwellings, increased safety and security, opportunities for social engagement and community involvement, and the emphasis on independence and autonomy.
- II. There is some indication that people with dementia can live independently in sheltered housing, by managing and personalising their self-contained homes, and continuing to engage with friends, family, and the local community.
- III. Sheltered housing settings provide a low level of housing support to individuals, such as check-ins from sheltered housing officers, and the organisation of repairs and social activities.
- IV. There are several factors that lead to people with dementia being referred or managed out of sheltered housing settings, like living with greater support and care needs, having difficulties with wayfinding, having little familiarity with the sheltered housing setting and local community, and limited involvement of family members or friends regarding support and care provision.
- V. These factors can be attributed to poor environmental design, poor dementia awareness and stigma, and limited access to resources and funding.

Case Study Two: Summary of Findings

- I. People with dementia move into very sheltered and extra care housing for comfort and security, the increased provision of support and care, and opportunities for social engagement.
 - II. There is an indication that very sheltered and extra care housing can support people with dementia to live with some independence, though to a lesser extent, due to the increased mobility and care needs of the individuals living in the settings.
 - III. Very sheltered and extra care housing settings can provide a higher level of support and care, through increased staff numbers, the presence of support workers or home care staff, and the provision of meals.
 - IV. There are several factors that lead to people with dementia being referred or managed out of these settings, like living with advanced dementia, having difficulties with wayfinding, and the limited involvement of family members or friends regarding support and care provision.
 - V. These factors can be attributed to poor environmental design, poor dementia awareness and stigma, and limited access to resources and funding.
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Case Study Three: Summary of Findings

I. People with dementia have limited choice regarding housing options, particularly for people who do not wish to live in supported housing for older people, for individuals who want to remain living with family, or for individuals who would not qualify for social housing.

II. Negative perceptions of supported housing exist from the viewpoints of people living with dementia, who viewed supported housing as institutional.

6.15. Cross-Case Themes

To aid the reader regarding how these cross-case themes were developed, Figure 10 has been created. This Figure aims to document the pathway from developing the themes within the individual case studies, the development of summary findings from each case study, the formation of cross-case themes based on these summary findings, and the resulting cross-case assertions. The cross-case themes are now presented.

6.15.1. Cross-Case Theme One: Views of Supported Housing

For each cross-case theme, figures have been developed to show the summary findings that formed the cross-case theme. For example, Figure 9 provides an illustration of the summary findings that informed the development of the cross-case theme "Views of Supported Housing." The cross-case theme is then presented, together with the researcher's interpretations and illustrative quotes, to demonstrate how this theme was formed. This first cross-case theme draws on data from all three case studies.

Figure 9: Summary findings that were merged to inform the development of the cross-case theme "Views of Supported Housing."

Figure 10: The process of reaching cross-case assertions, starting from the development of themes in the individual case studies, the summary findings based on these themes, and the development of cross-case themes.

Two opposing worldviews of moving into supported housing were shared by 1) those living with dementia in supported housing in case studies one and two, and 2) those that had considered a move into the settings in case study three. First, the outlook of those living with dementia in supported housing was overwhelmingly positive. For example, living in the settings was described as “the best move I ever made”, with the settings providing a new “lease of life.” In this regard, those living with dementia had made informed choices to move into supported housing, and all individuals had lived in the local communities before moving into the settings. For these individuals, the settings provided comfort and security, increased opportunities for socialisation, and supported these individuals to live in homes that were more manageable. To illustrate, James describes sheltered housing as perfect:

But you know, on the whole I’m very, very happy here. I couldn’t ask for anything better. And as I say, that everybody round here is very, very friendly. And I – I’ve found that that’s – makes the difference. I wouldn’t change anything. Because it’s perfect as far as I’m concerned. **(Case Study One, James, Person with Dementia).**

Oppositely, those involved in case study three viewed supported housing as being institutional prisons, with even the prospect of moving into sheltered housing creating feelings of “horror” for John, as he discusses below:

And we walked in, and there was lifts up to the, I think it was the third floor we had to go to. But then the lift door opened, and there was an enormous, long corridor with sort of beige carpets and doors. And it just felt like a ... it felt a bit like a sort of prison for older people ... If I’d have found a sheltered housing scheme that I’d have liked, I might think differently. But, but the one I went to didn’t grab me at all. Yeah, but it’s more the idea of being in an oldie’s ghetto that fills me with horror. **(Case Study Three, John, Person with Dementia).**

These quotes evidence the totally opposing viewpoints of James and John; a place of horror for one, and perfect for the other. Importantly, there were some defining characteristics of the individuals involved in the case studies that may have informed these judgements. For example, the individuals that lived in the supported housing settings had previously lived alone or faced the prospect of living alone. Hence, these

individuals tended to be isolated or lonely, and lived in houses that were too large to manage by themselves. Those involved in case study three lived with family members and received ample support and care from family and external care organisations. Hence, for the individuals that were living in supported housing, who had tended to live alone with limited support, their experiences were wholly positive. Further, it felt apparent that these individuals were not imprisoned or institutionalised. Their homes were personalised, and they engaged with family, other residents, and their local communities. In other words, they appeared to be living independently and autonomously.

Nonetheless, there remains an overwhelming lack of choice regarding housing options. For example, if an individual does not want to move into a block of flats or bungalows that are solely populated by older people, or for individuals that are not living alone and wish to remain living with their partners. There were also challenges for those who would not qualify for social housing, or who would wish to move into a private setting, as the supported housing model in Scotland does not appear to accommodate this subgroup of individuals. To illustrate, John discusses the lack of housing options that were available to him, and his idyllic housing setting, below. This, ultimately, reflected a social construction of being an older person, or living with dementia, as being othered, segregated, or locked away from other age groups in society:

People keep saying, "Oh, you've got lots of options." Then you actually look at it, and your options narrow, because, actually, as somebody who's sold a house, my chances of getting social housing are pretty low. Even though I might have special needs, I've got quite a lot of money in the bank ... The ideal would be, I think everybody does need their own space, you know? You ultimately want somewhere that you can retire to and read a book. But my ideal would be a community which meant that you could also dip in and out of activity and relationships with other people of other ages. Where it wasn't that everybody in the same place was old, but that maybe some were young. Where maybe there were kids at school needing help with homework, that I could help with homework. That maybe there were kids at school or students who could help me with housework. Where there are children running around the place. **(Case Study Three, John, Person with Dementia).**

Further, it is also important to acknowledge that a move into supported housing is accompanied by a loss of some independence. For example, those working in the settings are in the position to inform social services of an individual's health condition. They can also organise moves out of supported housing, if they deem that the setting is not appropriate for the individual. This is not necessarily a negative for all individuals, as those involved in the study opted to move into supported housing due to the added security, safety, and comfort that the settings could provide. The individuals involved in the study had utilised the support, care, and home adaptations that were available to them. Again, these individuals tended to live alone and struggled with the management of their homes before their move. Nonetheless, it appeared that there could be a fine line between being safe and secure and being monitored for an inevitable move out of the settings, to receive support and care elsewhere. For example, it was proclaimed that supported housing was not suitable for people living beyond the earlier stages of the condition.

Additionally, although not "imprisoned", those living in the extra care housing settings were largely confined to their own homes. This was linked to mobility needs and the experience of living with more advanced dementia. Further, those who might become lost when leaving the settings, due to wayfinding needs, were actively encouraged not to leave the settings, and were resultantly referred or managed out of the settings. This was because of their open nature. Hence, for such individuals, the settings might be reflective of "institutions", despite being labelled as independent living. Fundamentally, this was due to resource limitations, limited dementia awareness and education, and poor environmental design. To illustrate, Eve discussed her mother-in-law's engagement with the local community. Due to her mobility needs, she rarely left the setting, as she required the use of a wheelchair and the support of family or housing staff. Resultantly, the extent of her community engagement often involved looking out of her window:

I mean, her view from her window, she's quite happy to, I mean she kind of looks onto the car park, but she's quite happy to see people coming and going. You know, coming in and out their cars. The school kids from the local school, they kind of cross over as well at lunch time when they're going to the shops and stuff for their lunch, so, there's always something to see for her, which is quite

important to have, as well, you know, that she doesn't feel that she's just isolated, if you like, you know? **(Eve, Case Study Two, Family Member).**

For John, it appeared that Eve's mother-in-law's situation was the very thing he wished to avoid, being somewhat secluded or isolated from community and social engagement. This is not to deny that those living with dementia often require a high-level of support and care, or that all individuals can live as wholly independent social citizens. I also do not want to simply shift stigma towards care or nursing homes as being "prisons" or "institutions." For individuals with a high level of need in Scotland, care and nursing home settings are, presently, better equipped to meet these needs. This was abundantly clear throughout the case studies, given the limited funding and resources available in supported housing settings. Hence, this first cross-case theme begins to highlight two major issues. First, that there is a significant lack of choice regarding where to live for many people living with dementia. Particularly, for individuals who do not want to move into typical models of supported housing, or for individuals who do not meet the requirements for social housing. Second, that resources are stretched thin in supported housing settings. Resultantly, people with dementia, that can live independently and can engage with their local communities – living with minimal care needs or being "ideal" – valued their move into supported housing. However, individuals with greater care needs, requiring support throughout the night, or who were living with more advanced dementia – were deemed as being "too far gone" to live in the settings. Therefore, two further cross-case themes relating to living with dementia in supported housing were developed, Being Ideal Candidates and being Too Far Gone. The remaining sections aim to unpack these themes.

6.15.2. Cross-Case Theme Two: The Ideal Candidate

Figure 11 provides an illustration of the key findings that informed the development of the cross-case theme "The Ideal Candidate." The theme is then presented, together with the researcher's interpretations and illustrative quotes, to demonstrate how it was formed. This theme draws on data from case studies one and two. It should be noted that case study three did not inform the development of this cross-case theme, due to the case study's focus on understanding perspectives on supported housing as a future housing choice, rather than the experience of actively living in supported housing.

Figure 11: Summary findings that were merged to inform the development of the cross-case theme: "The Ideal Candidate."

As stated previously, the individuals that were living with dementia in supported housing throughout this research appeared to fit the mould of being "ideal candidates" for the settings. Fundamentally, these individuals were able to live independently with minimal support, could engage with their local community, and were supported by family members or friends. To illustrate this, the following quotations are provided, discussed by Anne and Martha, taken from separate interviews from case studies one and two:

Because, to me, Elizabeth has just got a lot of memory loss just now. But, she can get in and out the house no problem. She knows her way in, she knows her way out. She's safe in the house. I've been in the house and I've watched her, and she's an ideal candidate for here. She needs a wee bit of background, a wee bit of safety here, but she's still able. **(Case Study One, Anne, Sheltered Housing Officer).**

She is, she's absolutely ideal for this place, she's a perfect candidate to live here. Her family when, when they moved her here, they're very happy. They say that they know that she's safe, and we're always in contact with them. We work along with them. If there's anything, you know, any concerns, we raise the concerns to them, and then they take it further on what can be done. But so far she's brilliant. **(Case Study Two, Martha, Service Coordinator).**

It could be argued, therefore, that such ideal candidates were categorised by having few dementia symptoms, other than some memory loss. Hence, these individuals were referred to as being “normal.” For the housing and social care professionals involved in this study, it was apparent that being “normal” meant sharing characteristics with individuals who were not living with neurodegenerative brain diseases. Ultimately, being “ideal” meant living with the early stages of dementia, as discussed by Susan, below:

Early dementia, yep, absolutely fine. They get used to the environment, they get used to their own wee house. Walk them round the corridors a few times, just to familiarise them, and get that they know exactly where they are, and their own house number, things like that. **(Case Study One, Susan, Sheltered Housing Officer).**

For individuals who met the criteria for being “ideal” or “normal”, their experiences of living in supported housing were very positive. It was evident that their homes had been decorated and personalised, with each home being unique and reflective of the characteristics of the individuals. There were no negative experiences shared by those living with dementia in the settings that were interviewed. Therefore, for individuals that were living with dementia who had these characteristics, the settings seemed to be a good fit for them.

A further key characteristic about these individuals was that they had lived within the local communities in which the supported housing settings were situated, before moving. In some circumstances, this meant that individuals had moved within a few minutes of their previous homes. This, in turn, meant that these individuals either had family members or friends who lived nearby, were familiar with the setting, and would continue to engage in community-based activities. Importantly, this is not reflective of the norm regarding supported housing in Scotland. There exists significantly higher demand than can be met for individuals who are waiting for a move into supported housing. For example, focussing on one of the local authority housing providers who were involved in this study, the authority rented 2,200 homes in 2022, of which, 160 dwellings were classed as supported housing. However, in the same calendar year, this local authority received over 17,000 applications for these properties, with over 16,000 individuals remaining on waiting lists. Therefore, it can be extrapolated that the demand for supported housing in Scotland far outreaches the available housing stock. It appears that being allocated a place in these settings relies on luck and circumstance,

meaning that most individuals would need to find housing options outside of their local communities. Resultantly, there was some evidence throughout the case studies that a lack of familiarity with the environment and local community meant that people with dementia were at risk of being managed out or moved from the settings. This will be expanded upon further in the next theme; however, this again points to the severe lack of choice regarding housing options in Scotland and their lack of resources to accommodate support and care needs.

Therefore, there are certain characteristics attributed to individuals living with dementia that means they are “ideal candidates” for supported housing. For example, being “ideal” reflected an ability to live independently with minimal support; being familiar with the environment and local community; and, being supported by family members or friends. However, it was evident that obtaining this label was somewhat exclusive of having a diagnosis of dementia. That is, developing greater care needs or symptoms of dementia meant that individuals were no longer classed as being ideal. This, invariably, points to the stigma and inequalities that exist for people living with dementia in supported housing, particularly for those who are living with more advanced dementia. Indeed, this sentiment was shared by all the housing and social care professionals involved in the research. Even in settings that could provide a higher level of support and care, such as very sheltered or extra care housing, it was evident that their resources could not meet the needs of all individuals living with dementia. Hence, it was apparent that at the point an individual is no longer “ideal”, they are then identified as being “too far gone”, living in “another world”, unsuitable, and ultimately, excluded from living in supported housing. Therefore, the next theme relates to being an individual living with dementia in supported housing that is “Too Far Gone.”

6.15.3. Cross-Case Theme Three: Too Far Gone

Figure 12 provides an illustration of the key findings that informed the development of the cross-case theme “Too Far Gone.” The theme is then presented, together with the researcher’s interpretations and illustrative quotes, to demonstrate how it was formed. This theme draws on data from case studies one and two. It should be noted that case study three did not inform the development of this theme due to the case study’s

focus on understanding perspectives on supported housing as a future housing choice, rather than the experience of actively living in supported housing.

Figure 12: Summary findings that were merged to inform the development of the cross-case theme: "Too Far Gone."

Within sheltered housing developments, it appeared that being “too far gone” related to living with dementia, requiring some level of support or care, whilst being unable to independently navigate the development and local community. In very sheltered and extra care housing settings, this appeared to be much the same. However, extra care housing developments were equipped to provide a higher level of personal care. Nonetheless, if a person with dementia had wayfinding needs, those working in extra care housing were adamant that the settings could not accommodate these. To illustrate, the following quotes from Kate, Fiona, and Martha, extracted from separate interviews in case studies one and two, are provided, below. These quotes show that in every involved model of supported housing, the settings were deemed to only be suitable for people living with the early stages of dementia:

I think certainly at the start. Because I think it's good for them not to have it thrust in their face constantly. **(Case Study One, Kate, Sheltered Housing Officer).**

With regard to dementia, I'm not convinced with that at all. Perhaps, maybe, in the early stages. The very early stages. **(Case Study Two, Fiona, Support Worker).**

It depends on the level. If it's just, you know, onset dementia, like with the tenant you spoke to, it's fine, it's very good. But if the dementia is progressed, quite progressed – then it's a no, not at all.

(Case Study Three, Martha, Service Coordinator).

However, particularly in sheltered housing, the classification of being “too far gone” appeared to have a weak tipping point. For example, simply having challenges using secure entry systems resulted in people with dementia being moved from sheltered housing environments into care homes. However, as outlined in case studies one and two, it was evident that wayfinding challenges were exacerbated by poor environmental design, that was ultimately disabling for people living with dementia. Further, the settings were not equipped to provide adequate support or care to those living with dementia beyond the earlier stages of the condition. Hence, the argument here is that people living with dementia are not “too far gone.” Rather, it is that housing, support, and care services are not equipped or structured to meet the needs of these individuals. This notion of being “too far gone” is deep-rooted and embedded within a societal perspective that those living with dementia are, metaphorically, alien. That is, they inhabit “another world”, or are no longer human. Hence, this labelling raises several societal issues in Scotland that should be challenged and will be expanded upon in the discussion section of this thesis.

6.16. Cross-Case Assertions

The endpoint of Stake's (2006) multiple-case study analysis involves the formation of cross-case assertions. The strength and soundness of these assertions are evaluated by the reader, based on the researcher's interpretations, and supporting evidence. Hence, there are several assertions that can be made, which are outlined below.

- I. Supported housing settings are often not equipped to provide support and care to people living with dementia beyond the early stages of the condition, due to limited resources, funding, education, and poor environmental design.
- II. Being able to live with dementia in supported housing requires the individual to possess a series of ideal characteristics, such as living independently with minimal support; being familiar with the

supported housing setting and the local community; and being supported by family members and friends.

- III. In Scotland, there exists limited choice for people living with dementia regarding housing options, particularly for those who would not qualify for social housing, or those who do not want to live in housing for older people.

6.17 Summary of Chapter Six

This chapter began with the presentation of three individual case study reports, relating to living with dementia in 1) sheltered housing, 2) very sheltered or extra care housing, and 3) perspectives on supported housing as a future housing choice for people living with dementia. In total, the study involved six supported housing settings, six people living with dementia, six professionals, and two family members. Subsequently, several case-specific and cross-case themes were developed, culminating in the presentation of cross-case assertions.

Although positive experiences were shared by people with dementia and family members throughout the case studies, findings also uncovered challenges associated with delivering adequate support and care for people living with dementia in supported housing. They occurred due to resource constraints, insufficient funding, educational gaps, and suboptimal environmental design. It appeared that living with dementia in supported housing requires the individual to possess a series of “ideal” characteristics, focussing on the ability to live independently with minimal support, familiarity with the setting and local community, and close relationships with family and friends. While assuming the persona of an “ideal candidate” is feasible in earlier stages of dementia, the progressive nature of the condition leads to an increased need for support and care, which supported housing settings often fail to accommodate. Resultantly, people with dementia can be labelled as being “too far gone” for life in supported housing and are often moved from their homes. The research also illuminates the restricted housing options available to individuals with dementia in Scotland, particularly for those who are ineligible for social housing or are hesitant to reside in housing for older adults.

Chapter Seven: Discussion

7.1. Introduction to Chapter Seven

This chapter begins with a discussion of the findings of the study, with reference to theoretical and conceptual literature, and the wider research and policy landscape. Implications of these findings are also provided. The chapter then outlines the strengths and limitations of the research. First, drawing on rigour developed through the systematic review and empirical research study, followed by limitations associated with the COVID-19 pandemic disruptions, in addition to methodological limitations of the research. A critique of Stake's case study methodology is then presented, together with a discussion on how methodological integrity is demonstrated through the study design and the resultant findings. Recommendations for future research, practice, education, and policy are offered. Finally, the conclusion brings the thesis to a close.

7.2. Interpretation of Findings and Implications

7.2.1. Objective One: To understand how support or care is delivered in supported housing settings to meet the needs of people living with dementia.

The underlying aim of supported housing is to help individuals live independently in their own homes, through the provision of housing, support, or care. Within the policy-oriented literature, it is stated that the underlying goal of supported housing is to help people live independently in the community, through the provision of support, care, or supervision (Department for Work and Pensions and Department for Communities and Local Government, 2016). A central goal of Scotland's current housing policy (not only relating to supported housing) is to ensure that "... everyone who can and who wants to..." can access housing that enables them to live independently, facilitated through access to health and social care, in addition to home adaptations (Scottish Government, 2021, p.11). Therefore, it is unsurprising that many of the findings related to this objective. At the practical level, sheltered housing settings provided a low level of housing support. For example, a sheltered housing officer worked on-site throughout the day in each of the settings. These individuals would conduct morning calls, organise tenancies and repairs, and respond to emergencies throughout the day. Similarly, in very sheltered and extra care housing, those working in the settings would

provide housing support services. However, these settings also operated with greater staff numbers, including support workers and professional caregivers. Staff would work into the evening, and a care worker was present in the extra care housing settings throughout the night. Those living in all settings were entitled to free personal care, in accordance with the Community Care and Health (Scotland) Act 2002, much the same as any individual living in the community. In the case studies, this resembled visitations throughout the day from home care workers, who would support people with washing and dressing, meal preparation, visiting the shops, and general household cleaning.

The people living with dementia in the case studies were satisfied with the provision of support and care they received at the time of interviewing. However, supported housing settings lack the resources to provide a high level of support and care as a person's condition progresses. These resource limitations meant that people with dementia were often relocated to receive a higher level of care elsewhere. As such, settings often emphasised the need for people to live independently to remain living in the settings, rather than increasing support and care provision to meet the needs of these individuals. Challenges relating to support and care provision were raised by the housing and social care professionals involved in the study. For example, funding limitations, challenges with accessing social care staff, and a need for dementia training. This is at odds with the goals of Scotland's housing and social care policies, which state that everyone should have equal access to health and social care to meet their needs (Scottish Government, 2019).

Ultimately, the results relating to objective one informed the cross-case assertions of this thesis. Most notably, that supported housing settings lack the resources to meet the needs of people living with dementia, unless they possess the ideal characteristics of being able to live independently with minimal support; being familiar with the supported housing setting and the local community; and being supported by family members and friends. These findings are corroborated by theoretical literature, policy documents, and in published research, uncovered in the systematic review in Chapter Two, together with research published since the review's completion. This will now be discussed.

Chapter Two acknowledged that supported housing settings are appropriate for people living with dementia *to a degree*. However, increasing care needs, limited resources and funding, and poor dementia awareness

meant that many people were referred or moved from their homes. Since the conducting of this review, five articles have been identified that are of relevance to this thesis, focussing on English, Northern Irish, and Scottish contexts. As with the findings reported in Chapter Two, and throughout the remainder of this thesis, the articles report that people with dementia value the promotion of independence, autonomy, and safety in the settings (Atkinson and Oatley, 2023; Atkinson, Oatley and Evans, 2023; Daly-Lynn *et al.*, 2022; Daly-Lynn *et al.*, 2023). However, they also note that supported housing fails to meet the needs of people with dementia, due to staff availability, challenges with providing flexible, person-centred care, limited funding, and an inability to meet the needs of people living with advanced dementia (Atkinson and Oatley, 2023; Atkinson, Oatley and Evans, 2023; Daly-Lynn *et al.*, 2022; Daly-Lynn *et al.*, 2023; Tolson *et al.*, 2023). Hence, these issues have continued to be raised in supported housing-oriented literature published over the last 20 years, and, again, in this thesis.

Relatedly, the conceptual framework that was presented in Figure 5, Section 3.5 of this thesis, acknowledged these issues in the context of dementia care delivery. For example, Kitwood's (1997) work relating to personhood and person-centred care was first conceptualised in the 1980s (Fazio *et al.*, 2018), with person-centred care models in dementia continuing to evolve (Fazio *et al.*, 2018; Kitwood and Brooker, 2019; McCormack and McCance, 2017). Person-centred dementia care is often described as the gold standard in dementia care guidelines, such as those produced by the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence and the Scottish Intercollegiate Guidelines Network, regarding assessment, diagnosis, care and support for people with dementia and their carers (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, 2018; Scottish Intercollegiate Guidelines Network, 2023). Such person-centred care models and guidelines describe the importance of developing individualised care plans, respect and dignity, empowerment, flexible care, involvement of family members, staff training, and the importance of the design of the physical environment (Fazio *et al.*, 2018; Kitwood and Brooker, 2019; National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, 2018; Scottish Intercollegiate Guidelines Network, 2023).

However, despite writings relating to personhood and person-centred care existing for over 30 years and outlined as the gold standard of dementia care in theoretical, research, policy, and practice-oriented

literature, it is disheartening to see that many barriers still exist regarding its implementation. This was demonstrated in the present research, with limited evidence of the provision of person-centred care. For example, supported housing settings appear to lack the resources to implement personalised care plans; the extent to which staff are trained regarding dementia support and care is unclear; and the design of the physical environments of these settings are often disabling. Although the particulars of person-centred care are important, the reality of its implementation in supported housing can be questioned. Indeed, it is often stated in supported housing, and wider dementia related literature, that person-centred care should be implemented, without describing the fundamentals of what this would look like in practice (Atkinson, Oatley and Evans, 2023; Smith *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, it could be argued that the term risks losing its meaning, and the potential for it to become tokenistic or hollow. For person-centred care to be actively provided in supported housing settings for people living with dementia, it appears that the distribution and delivery of care resources in these settings needs reform.

Throughout this discussion, it is apparent that many of the issues pertaining to support and care delivery in supported housing relate to access to resources and funding. Drawing on a recent independent review of adult social care in Scotland (Feeley, 2021), Tolson *et al.* (2023) discuss the need for different thinking in this regard. Focussing on support and care provision, Feeley (2021) recommends the introduction of a national care service in Scotland. This is in acknowledgment of the challenges that social care services, and those who try to access such services, currently face. The development of the national care service is still in the consultation phase. However, some goals of the service are to integrate housing, health, and social care services, improve quality of care, embed a human-rights based approach, and provide person-centred health and social care. Feeley (2021) acknowledges that government bodies often think of social care provision as a financial burden. That is, social care is typically provided in response to crises, or to meet some level of immediate need, rather than being preventative and anticipatory. The belief is that this current way of thinking means that social care provision is unsustainable, unmanageable, and costly, given that crises could be prevented or anticipated. The belief is that social care should be thought of as a vehicle that enhances human rights and capabilities, promotes collaboration and relationships, and supports people to live

independent lives (Feeley, 2021; Tolson *et al.*, 2023). It is evident that the current social care system, in many instances, fails to achieve these goals.

Indeed, these issues are documented in the present thesis, and the level of anticipatory or preventative social care, provided in supported housing, is unclear. This means that people with dementia are often moved from their homes in supported housing, despite it being known that people with dementia will develop increased support and care needs. In many instances, housing providers are aware that an individual has a diagnosis of dementia before their move into supported housing. Supported housing places emphasis on the ability to live independently with minimal support, rather than anticipating and increasing support and care as an individual's condition progresses. The national care service aims to address these issues, by providing early intervention, and increasing this support, consistently and fairly, when needed. Again, at this higher, conceptual level, it is important to acknowledge the importance of integrating services and delivering human-rights and person-centred care. However, it is important that the national care service provides evidence that these ideals are implemented in practice. It is not enough to continually redefine, reconceptualise, or repackage the central components of person-centred care, without actively delivering such care in practice.

This also raises an important discussion point surrounding independence and autonomy in supported housing, regarding support and care provision. As noted in Chapter Two, the research literature states that supported housing helps people with dementia to maintain their independence and autonomy. It is often stated that the underlying goal of supported housing is to promote independence and increase autonomy through the choice and control that an individual has within their home environment. However, it is apparent that the concept of independence holds more weight in the context of supported housing. In this regard, independence appears to be defined in terms of being functionally able to conduct activities of daily living at home in the community, as outlined in the conceptual framework in Figure 5. It was shown in this thesis that people with dementia are supported or "encouraged" to live independently in supported housing, through the provision of varying levels of support and care. However, being able to live independently with minimal support is a central criterion that is considered when deciding if an individual can continue living in supported housing, as contended within the conceptual framework. Within supported housing settings, this creates a

circular argument regarding whether supported housing is a suitable housing environment for people with dementia. For a person living with dementia to access the support and care that enables them to live independently in supported housing, they must already be living independently with minimal support. However, if the individual requires a high level of support and care to live independently, they cannot access the support and care needed to live independently. It can be argued that supported housing settings should refrain from stating that they “enable people to live independently”, or that they “promote” or “maintain” independence, as this is not evidenced in this thesis. At present, it should be stated that supported housing is suited to people who can live independently with minimal support, as there is little evidence to suggest that independence is “enabled”, “promoted”, or “maintained” for people with dementia as their conditions progress and support or care needs increase. As acknowledged in the cross-case themes developed within this thesis in Sections 6.15.1. – 6.15.3., this way of thinking risks infringing an individual’s human rights regarding the autonomy to choose where to live and having access to appropriate levels of support and care to make this a reality, for as long as they wish.

Hence, this is not reflective of autonomy, that embodies self-determination, choice, and control. People with dementia often have little choice when deciding if they would like to continue living in supported housing as their conditions progress and care needs change. This decision is predominantly made by those who work within the settings, compounded by the limited access to appropriate support and care in the community. There also appears to be no anticipatory care planning within the settings, that enables a person with dementia to make informed future care decisions, and the choice to continue living in supported housing, should they wish. It could be argued that autonomy is not maintained within supported housing, as is often suggested in research, policy, and practice-based literature. At present, the emphasis is on the ability to live independently. Although a key area of the conceptual framework, displayed in Figure 5, the concept of autonomy warrants further exploration in relation to living with dementia in supported housing, to determine if this is truly maintained. It appears that a lack of autonomy regarding support and care decisions can contribute to people with dementia being moved from supported housing settings, as suggested by the conceptual framework.

Although theoretical, policy, and research-oriented literature acknowledge the need to embed human-rights, and person-centred approaches to support and care provision for people living with dementia, discussion of this was limited in the present study. Rather, through the presentation of cross-case themes, relating to “The Ideal Candidate” and being “Too Far Gone,” it was apparent that there not only exist resource limitations, but poor dementia awareness and training. This could have a negative impact on the experience of living with dementia in supported housing, with many people living with dementia facing an inevitable move from their homes into residential or nursing care as their condition progresses. The necessity of such moves can be questioned, given that some individuals were moved from their homes due to wayfinding needs, or challenges when using secure entry systems. It may be argued that with better training and improved dementia awareness, that these unnecessary moves could be limited. Indeed, this is highlighted within recent publications relating to supported housing and dementia (Atkinson and Oatley, 2023; Atkinson, Oatley and Evans, 2023). This adds rigour to the findings outlined in the present study, given that they are triangulated within different contexts and literature. Although it is important to acknowledge the practical challenges facing supported housing settings, it is also important to acknowledge wider societal perspectives of dementia and supported housing, that should be challenged and incorporated within policy and practice guidelines.

7.2.2. Objective Two: To understand how living in supported housing impacts social relationships and community connections for people living with dementia.

Throughout the case studies, it was stated that supported housing settings aim to limit loneliness and social isolation through the organisation of social activities. During the interviews, examples of organised social activities included bingo, dominoes, and celebratory lunches and dinners. Within very sheltered and extra care housing settings, meals were provided, which further increased opportunities for social interaction.

People living with dementia engaged with family members and friends, and in some cases, had made friends with others who lived in the settings. They also continued to engage with their local communities, visiting towns, shops, community-based clubs, and more. Opportunities for social engagement appeared to be lessened for those living with more advanced dementia or mobility needs. Nonetheless, family members of

these individuals stated that those living with dementia benefitted from the social aspects of living in supported housing, as they were otherwise isolated or lonely in their previous homes.

However, the sheltered housing officers involved in the study stated that changes to funding meant that organising social activities was challenging. Sheltered housing officers were being encouraged *not* to organise social activities, and to shift their focus towards paperwork and the administrative aspects of their roles. Despite this, the sheltered housing officers continued to organise activities, often outside of work times, whilst acknowledging that they were “not supposed to” do this. Although the organisation of social activities was still embedded into the services provided in very sheltered and extra care housing, those working in the settings still faced challenges with the organisation of activities. This was related to limited access to staff, and the increased care and mobility needs of the individuals living in these settings. Drawing from wider research, this was raised within the literature reviewed in Chapter Two, and in research published since (Atkinson and Oatley, 2023; Atkinson, Oatley and Evans, 2023). These published articles document the challenges with accessing appropriate staff numbers for organising social activities. Again, this feeds into one of the cross-case assertions from this thesis, that supported housing settings lack the resources to meet the needs of people living with dementia. Continuing discussions in the previous sections, these changes to job roles are reflective of changes to funding for supported housing (Scottish Government, 2011a). Reductions to funding mean that settings operate with fewer staff members, with staff working less hours, and job roles prioritising administrative duties and maintenance over social care provision, including the organisation of social activities (Scottish Government, 2011a). These funding limitations, therefore, directly impact the extent to which social activities are arranged in the settings, which may limit opportunities for social engagement.

Additionally, it was stated that those living with dementia in extra care housing could face stigma or prejudice from others living in the settings, due to poor dementia awareness. Such viewpoints appeared to go hand-in-hand with views shared by the housing and social care professionals involved in the study, who described people with dementia as not being “normal” or living in “another world.” Ultimately, this led to all professionals stating that supported housing is not suitable for many people living with dementia, possibly pointing to a wider, societal stigma, othering, and exclusion of people with dementia in these settings. Stigma

and prejudice were discussed in Chapter Two, and it was acknowledged in more recently published literature that those living with dementia continue to face stigma and prejudice from other residents living in the supported housing settings (Atkinson and Oatley, 2023; Atkinson, Oatley and Evans, 2023). Scotland's National Dementia Strategies (Scottish Government, 2023) have emphasised the need to tackle stigma and discrimination relating to dementia, to support individuals to live a life that is free from discrimination. Within Chapter Two, and throughout the findings of this thesis, it was apparent that stigma and lack of dementia awareness could contribute to people with dementia being moved from supported housing. This is a key component within social citizenship theory, which contends that discrimination can impact a person with dementia's right to engage in life as an active social citizen. The conceptual framework (Figure 5) suggests that discrimination, through stigma and poor dementia awareness, can contribute to people with dementia being moved from their homes. The thesis supports this contention, as demonstrated within the cross-case themes of "The Ideal Candidate" and "Too Far Gone." That is, people living with dementia in supported housing are often required to possess a series of "ideal" characteristics to remain living in supported housing, rather than increasing support and care provision, or adapting home environments, to enable people to continue living in such settings, should they wish. Rather, people with dementia are often described as being "Too Far Gone" as their conditions progress, stigmatised as not being "normal" or living in "another world", and subsequently moved from their homes in supported housing. It is unclear how much choice people with dementia have regarding these decisions. This thesis argues that people with dementia are not "ideal" or "too far gone." It is that supported housing settings are not equipped to meet the changing needs of people with dementia, with stigma and poor dementia awareness evident in the settings, contributing to people with dementia being moved from their homes.

The systematic review in Chapter Two developed a subtheme relating to social relationships. This subtheme emphasised the importance of facilitating relationships between people with dementia and their family members or friends, other residents and health and social care staff working within the settings. Facilitating relationships, providing opportunities for social interaction, and promoting choice regarding who people with dementia spend their time with, was linked to maintaining independence and autonomy. Within the reviewed literature, it was apparent that the organisation of social activities was a central feature of the services offered

in supported housing. For example, those living with dementia discussed taking part in bingo, dominoes, tapestry making, and other activities. It was also highlighted that the open nature of supported housing meant that relationships with family members and friends were well maintained, as the settings were not restricted by visiting hours.

However, it was acknowledged that “considerable stigma and prejudice” existed in extra care housing. Again, this was linked to views shared by other people living in the settings, who did not have dementia, in keeping with the findings of this thesis. Within the research literature published after the conducting of the systematic review, discussion of social interaction features prominently. For example, in the studies relating to extra care housing and technology-enriched supported accommodation (Atkinson and Oatley, 2023; Atkinson, Oatley and Evans, 2023; Daly-Lynn *et al.*, 2022), it was stated that those living with dementia valued the organisation of social activities in these settings, and reportedly experienced less social isolation and greater opportunities for community engagement. However, the studies conducted within extra care housing also noted that people living with dementia experienced social exclusion, loneliness, and stigma (Atkinson and Oatley, 2023; Atkinson, Oatley and Evans, 2023). This, again, supports the findings outlined in this thesis, and demonstrates rigour regarding the interpretations presented throughout.

The cross-case themes, presented in Chapter Six, provide further insights into social relationships and stigma in supported housing. For example, the individuals who were interviewed in the research appeared to fit the characteristics of being “ideal candidates.” In terms of social engagement and community connections, this meant that these individuals continued to engage with family members, friends, and their local communities, living independently with minimal support. However, individuals deemed to be “too far gone” tended to be less able to independently engage in social activities within the settings or local community and received less support from family members and friends. The tension point here is that to continue living in supported housing, there often appeared to be an expectation that a person would continue to live as “normal,” referred to as a person *not* living with dementia. As an individual’s condition progressed, there was a risk of being labelled as living in “another world,” being unfit for the settings, and being “too far gone.”

Although the people with dementia involved in this thesis were socially active, the findings suggest that they would likely be excluded from the settings, or moved from their homes, as their conditions progressed. Further learnings can be drawn from the conceptual framework in Chapter Three (Figure 5), such as personhood and social citizenship (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010; Kitwood, 1997; Kitwood and Brooker, 2019). Namely, the risk that people with dementia are labelled by their condition, and not by their values and characteristics as social citizens. This is not to deny that people with dementia live with complex care needs, but rather, that housing, health, and social care resources should be made available to this population to support participation in society in any way possible, and the leading of a life that is free from discrimination. Again, it is disconcerting to see that in the decades since the publication of Kitwood's seminal work on personhood and dementia, that such discrimination still exists. This is particularly damning when considering the Scottish Government's position on tackling stigma and discrimination, emphasised within the Scottish National Dementia Strategies (Scottish Government, 2023). Despite this being raised within Scotland's First National Dementia Strategy, published 14 years ago (Scottish Government, 2010), stigma and poor dementia awareness are still evident in society, even in settings that reportedly aim to improve the independence and autonomy of their residents.

This raises an important discussion point regarding the disclosure of a dementia diagnosis. For example, those living in supported housing in Scotland are tenants or homeowners, by law. These individuals do not need to disclose a diagnosis of dementia to those working within the settings, prior to moving or during their stay. This is a human right, and individuals may wish not to disclose a diagnosis due to the risk of being labelled or stigmatised, or the likelihood that they would be moved from their home in supported housing, as has been shown throughout this thesis. However, there is the need to acknowledge that people with dementia are vulnerable and have progressively complex needs, and to continue living safely and as independently as possible, these must be recognised and met (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2007; Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010).

Social citizenship theory does not state that people with dementia can simply live as independent social citizens, but rather, that supports should be put in place to enable such individuals to enact their rights to live as social citizens as far as possible. Any future decisions regarding living arrangements or care should be

reflective of the person's wishes as their condition progresses. Therefore, this tension point must be addressed. For example, people with dementia should have the right not to disclose their diagnosis, if they wish. However, this may impact the support or care available to the individual. If the sheltered housing officers or service coordinators in these settings are aware of an individual's condition, they may be best placed to inform services of the individual's needs. However, as shown throughout this thesis, it is unclear if sheltered housing officers and service coordinators have the expertise to make such decisions, which may lead to people being prematurely moved from their homes. Again, this relates to discussion raised by Feeley (2021) in the independent review of adult social care, which suggests that care decisions are often made in the event of a crisis, with care provision not being preventative or anticipatory, or delivered in a way that enhances an individual's human rights and capabilities.

This points to the importance of dementia awareness and education, and the need for the integration of housing, health, and social care services (Feeley, 2021). Access to integrated services, at the point of diagnosis, might mitigate the need to disclose a diagnosis to others, as individuals would be known to services. In theory, these services could increase support and care when needed. However, the reality of this occurring in practice can be questioned, due to funding constraints, and the evident lack of synergy between services. In sum, to ensure that people with dementia can continue to live as active social citizens in supported housing, greater practical supports should be provided through the provision of health and social care, and the labels of "being ideal" and "being too far gone" need to be challenged. This may be achieved through the provision of training and education regarding dementia care and awareness, and the integration of housing, health, and social care services, as stated in other literature (Atkinson and Oatley, 2023; Atkinson, Oatley and Evans, 2023; Tolson *et al.*, 2023).

7.2.3. Objective Three: To understand how the physical environments of supported housing settings enable people living with dementia to maintain their independence.

One of the greatest strengths, relating to the physical environments of supported housing, was the personalisation of the homes of the individuals involved in the study. Dwellings were decorated with personal furnishings, photographs, and items. Although the properties tended to be similar in size and layout, each

person's home felt unique and personal. People with dementia valued the self-contained nature of their homes, and the fact they could come and go as they pleased. They also valued the comfort, safety, and security that supported housing could provide.

However, for individuals with wayfinding needs, the physical environments of the supported housing settings could become disabling. For example, study participants shared examples of previous residents with dementia being moved out of their settings due to difficulties with wayfinding. Even in settings that provided a higher level of care, such as extra care housing, a prerequisite for moving into the settings was the ability to independently navigate the building and local environment. As shown in the imagery presented in Chapter Six, the study sites did not incorporate dementia-friendly design principles, and tended to be formed of long, similarly designed corridors. It is unsurprising that people developed difficulties with wayfinding. The same issues are also discussed in Chapter Two and noted in literature published since (Atkinson and Oatley, 2023; Atkinson, Oatley and Evans, 2023).

In the reviewed literature in Chapter Two, challenges with wayfinding, referred to as "wandering" or "walking with purpose", were discussed. It appeared that the two main reasons for people with dementia being moved from supported housing settings were the lack of resources to meet personal care needs, and the development of wayfinding needs. Again, this was linked to deficiencies in the design of the settings and suboptimal geographic locations. In the literature published since conducting the systematic review, a central finding was the disabling nature of the physical environments of supported housing settings (Atkinson, Oatley and Evans, 2023). This related to building size, similarity of corridors, poor lighting, use of patterns, and fob-door entry systems. Disabling environments, therefore, led to people being isolated in their homes due to challenges when independently navigating the settings, and engaging in autonomous activity, contributing to feelings of "institutional living" (Atkinson, Oatley and Evans, 2023).

The present study documented the same design flaws, which were evident in all the involved developments. This demonstrates further rigour regarding the interpretations presented throughout the results, given that the same issues are continually raised within different contexts. In the present thesis, particularly in extra care housing, it appeared that people living with more advanced dementia could largely be confined to their

own homes. Such individuals had limited interaction with the outside world, beyond looking out of their windows. Indeed, this is reflective of “institutional living,” with these individuals seemingly cut off from the rest of society or occupying “another world.” The loss of self and identity, associated with institutional living, has been documented for decades (Goffman, 1961), and is a central discussion point in personhood and social citizenship theory (Kitwood, 1997; Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010).

Fundamentally, the experience of institutional living is at odds with the suggestion that supported housing promotes independence, autonomy, and community engagement for people with dementia. More widely, this is contrary to the aspirations shared in Scottish dementia strategies and care guidelines. For example, the current Scottish dementia strategy states that housing, health, and social care should be integrated to support people with dementia to live independently in the community, for as long as they wish (Scottish Government, 2023a). Dementia care guidelines state that people with dementia, who live in the community, should be enabled to lead a “normal life”, through the provision of appropriate support and care (Scottish Intercollegiate Guidelines Network, 2023). This thesis shows that this is only experienced by those who possess the “ideal” characteristics necessary to engage in life in supported housing, and that the settings are often not equipped to support individuals to live independently and engage with their communities. The choice of a person with dementia to continue living in supported housing, should they wish, is unclear, with this experience influenced by deficiencies in support and care provision, and in the design of the built environment.

Scotland’s most recent housing policy has acknowledged that housing environments in Scotland can be disabling (Scottish Government, 2021). For example, the document acknowledges that over 10,000 people with disabling conditions in Scotland remain on waiting lists for appropriate housing, with thousands more on waiting lists for home adaptations (Scottish Government, 2021). The document acknowledges that the challenge of meeting this housing need will only increase, with reference to the fact that Scotland’s population is ageing, meaning that by 2040, 730,000 people in Scotland will be aged 75 or over (Scottish Government, 2021). As such, the only options for many older people and people with disabilities, including dementia, are care homes – but it is acknowledged that this is not preferred option for such individuals (Scottish Government, 2021). Although one proposed solution is increasing choice by developing more

housing options, such as supported housing, it is acknowledged that more needs to be done to meet this demand (Scottish Government, 2021). Therefore, it is proposed that all newly built homes in Scotland should be future proof, to ensure that "... those with long-term conditions and disabilities and everyone who can and wants to is enabled to live independently in a home of their own" (Scottish Government, 2021, p. 55). The document states that achieving this requires changes to building standards to make homes easily adaptable, and to integrate adaptation, social care, health, and housing services within public and private sectors (Scottish Government, 2021). The document also acknowledges the challenges faced by social care services, referring to the independent review of adult social care (Feeley, 2021). Hence, to make these goals a reality, it is suggested that housing, health, and social care services should develop a joint accountability and outcomes framework to ensure that people have access to the services that they need (Scottish Government, 2021). This is a positive step, as the present thesis has shown that supported housing does not meet the needs of people with dementia, particularly for those who are "Too Far Gone." There is some way to go to make this policy goal a reality, but learnings from the present thesis can highlight areas for improvement.

Returning to the cross-case theme of being "Too Far Gone," it should be stated that many challenges with wayfinding cannot simply be attributed to living with a diagnosis of dementia. Rather, supported housing settings have fundamental design flaws that are avoidable and disabling to the individual. Regarding the conceptual framework, presented in Chapter Three (Figure 5), Lawton and colleagues were making this very point throughout the 1960s and beyond (Lawton and Brody, 1969; Lawton and Nahemow, 1973; Lawton and Simon, 1968). That is, an individual with low competence, occupying an environment with strong physical and social demands, may experience negative affect and maladaptive behaviour. In contrast, an individual with high competence, occupying an environment with weak physical and social demands, can also experience negative affect and maladaptive behaviour (Lawton and Nahemow, 1973). In other words, the environment must be the right fit for the individual. The integrative framework of ageing well as person-environment interchange also suggested that social and environmental resources can impact an individual's agency and feelings of belonging within such environments, which can impact autonomy, wellbeing, and identity (Wahl, Iwarsson, and Oswald, 2012). Incorporating this, the conceptual framework suggested that such concepts can influence the likelihood that a person with dementia can continue living in supported housing (Figure 5).

The thesis has shown that this is apparent within supported housing settings, as limited access to environmental resources, limited familiarity (belonging), and a lack of agency often results in people with dementia being moved from their homes.

The case studies showed that aspects of the supported housing developments were disabling, contributing to people with dementia being moved from the settings. It could be argued that these design flaws, inadvertently, fed into the labelling of “being ideal” and “being too far gone.” For example, “being ideal” meant that people with dementia were labelled with a series of characteristics that meant they were the right fit for the environment, including being able to independently navigate the setting and local community. Developing greater care or wayfinding needs, or becoming “too far gone,” meant that individuals were deemed to no longer be the right fit for the environment and were moved from the settings. However, these wayfinding needs were exacerbated by the disabling environments of the supported housing developments. Therefore, settings should be designed and adapted to meet the needs of people with dementia, to support them as their conditions progress. Instead, it appeared that people with dementia were expected to retain these ideal characteristics, with limited opportunities to increase support and care or adapt their homes to meet their needs. Despite guidelines existing regarding dementia-friendly design (The King's Fund, 2014; The King's Fund, 2020), there was no indication that dementia-friendly design principles had been incorporated in the settings, beyond the use of some signage in case study one. However, the signage was incorrectly placed and it is unclear if it would have worked as intended. There is a need for training and education regarding dementia, and the design of the built environment, for housing developers and planners. There also appears to be a greater need for dementia-oriented training for housing and social care professionals, with steps taken to ensure the learning outcomes of this training are applied correctly in practice.

7.2.4. Objective Four: To understand perspectives on supported housing as a future housing choice for people living with dementia.

Drawing from case study three, it was noted that there is limited choice regarding housing options for people living with dementia in Scotland. For example, those who were interviewed in case study three had considered a move into supported housing but had opted not to for various reasons. Namely, the challenges

with finding a supported housing residence as a couple, accessing supported housing that was not only housed by older people, and the limited supported housing options available for people who would not qualify for social housing. Ultimately, those interviewed in this case study felt that supported housing settings were institutional. Contrastingly, those who lived with dementia in supported housing, interviewed in case studies one and two, spoke positively about their living experiences. These individuals valued the comfort, safety, and security the settings provided, and enjoyed having opportunities to socialise with others. Nonetheless, if a person wishes to move into an alternative form of supported housing, that not only houses older people, or is not a form of social housing, there is limited choice.

The systematic review in Chapter Two did not aim to uncover research on supported housing as a future housing choice for people living with dementia. Nonetheless, a research article was uncovered that sought to gather perspectives on living with dementia in extra care housing in England, from the perspectives of couples (Poyner, Innes and Dekker, 2017). Although the involved couples believed that extra care housing could remove some of the stress regarding caregiving, they were reluctant to move. This was because they did not want to downsize their homes and move into a flat, the stress a home move would cause, and a reluctance to move away from their local community. The central finding was that couples with dementia preferred to remain living in their current home, accessing home care and support in the community. This resonates with much of the findings discussed in case study three, and the cross-case theme “Views of Supported Housing.” For those who had opted not to move into supported housing in case study three, such settings were viewed as institutional and undesirable. Again, this points to the limited supported housing options that exist in Scotland. This fed into the development of a cross-case assertion in this thesis, namely, in Scotland, there exists limited choice for people living with dementia regarding housing options, particularly for those who would not qualify for social housing, or those who do not want to live in housing for older people.

Within current Scottish housing policy, limitations with housing choice, availability, and demand are acknowledged. To address this, housing policy states the goal of building 100,000 affordable homes by 2032, with the majority of these homes made available for social rent (Scottish Government, 2021). There are

problems with this policy for two main reasons. First, provision of supported housing in Scotland does not meet demand (Tolson *et al.*, 2023). Accounting for population ageing and housing demand, projections suggest that to meet demand for supported housing in Scotland by 2030, the country will need 48,000 supported housing dwellings for older people (Wittenberg and Hu, 2017). However, the most recent Scottish housing strategy states that roughly 1% of Scotland's total housing stock is classified as supported housing, equating to 27,000 dwellings (Scottish Government, 2021). Hence, it is unlikely that over 20,000 supported housing dwellings will be built in Scotland by 2030, given that the total number of supported housing dwellings in Scotland has reduced substantially over the last two decades (Scottish Government, 2022). Second, building 100,000 affordable homes, with the majority being available for social rent, does not address the limited choice and availability of supported housing, particularly for people who would not qualify for social housing.

Again, the previous section outlined that a proposed solution for meeting this demand is to ensure that all new housing in Scotland is future proof, meaning that those living with long-term health conditions can easily adapt these homes to meet their needs (Scottish Government, 2021). It is also suggested that housing, health, and social care services should develop a joint accountability and outcomes framework to ensure that people have access to the services that they need, in acknowledgement of the challenges faced when accessing health and social care in the community (Scottish Government, 2021). These are positive steps that suggest that the Scottish Government is aware of the challenges faced within housing, health, and social care services, and the need for accountability to address these challenges. This thesis has shown that supported housing is a microcosm of larger issues relating to housing, health, social care, and dementia in Scotland. In particular, the lack of access to social care services to meet needs, limited resources and funding, poor dementia awareness and stigma, and limited autonomy and choice regarding where to live. As such, the findings of this thesis can be used to highlight the benefits and challenges of living with dementia in supported housing, in addition to housing, health, and social care more widely. These are reflected in the recommendations made in Section 7.4. of this chapter.

7.3. Strengths and Limitations

A strength of the present study is the robust systematic review of qualitative literature, discussing how living in supported housing influences the lives of people with dementia. The purpose of this review was to develop an understanding of what was known about the experience of living with dementia in supported housing, to highlight research gaps, and to support the development of the empirical study. The rigour and value of the review is evidenced in its subsequent publication in the peer-reviewed *Journal of Health and Social Care in the Community*. At the time of writing, the review, which was first published in October 2021, has been cited ten times in literature relating to supported housing and dementia, further evidencing its value within the research evidence base. The systematic review provided the platform for the development of the empirical research study and ensured that it would be an original contribution to research.

The published research included and reviewed within the systematic review did, however, have methodological weaknesses. Most notably, 1) poorly developed or unclear methodologies and methods, and 2) limited application or learning from theoretical perspectives regarding housing and dementia. Hence, a goal of this thesis was to enhance its rigour and methodological integrity by adhering to an appropriate methodology, with the study informed by conceptual and theoretical underpinnings. Case study research was identified as the most appropriate approach to address the aim and objectives of the thesis. This was because of its focus on gathering multiple perspectives, conducting research in real-life contexts, use of multiple methods, and its emphasis on generating knowledge to inform policy development, professional practice and civil or community action (Simons, 2009). Initial visits to supported housing settings, prior to the conducting of the research, and the systematic review, highlighted that the experience of living with dementia in supported housing has many influences. For example, housing and dementia policy, the physical environment, organisational practices, and social relationships. Hence, case study research was deemed to be most appropriate for this thesis, as it allows for these concepts to be understood from different perspectives, drawing from multiple data sources to develop an understanding of the experience of living with dementia in supported housing.

As discussed in Chapter Four, texts from three of the main case study methodologists were reviewed. Namely, those published by Stake, Merriam, and Yin. The philosophical perspective that reflected the researcher's worldview was social constructionism, given its focus on the importance of social interaction on knowledge construction, and the development of social constructions of knowledge that can be used to challenge political and wider societal perspectives (Andrews, 2012; Denzin and Lincoln, 2018; Jacobs and Manzi, 2000; Jacobs, Kemeny and Manzi, 2004). Accordingly, Stake's (1995; 2006) work was deemed to be best suited to social constructionist research, given his discussion of the importance of social interaction on knowledge generation, and his relativist ontological positioning. As such, steps outlined by Stake were adhered to, to improve the rigour of the research. For example, Stake (1995) discusses the importance of triangulating data sources in case study research. Resultantly, the research involved interviews with multiple participant groups, and the use of other data sources, like photographs and documents, to support the triangulation of findings. Additionally, Stake (1995) states that data collection procedures can be supported using a detailed study protocol, which was developed and reviewed prior to the commencement of this research study. In this regard, triangulation of data sources, and adhering to the study protocol, increased the credibility of any interpretations made throughout the research.

Challenges with conducting the research were encountered because of the COVID-19 pandemic. Most notably, it was envisaged that more people with dementia would be recruited. However, accessing individuals who were living with dementia in supported housing was particularly challenging during lockdown. This may have been due to the known escalations in dementia related symptoms that occurred with reduced social stimulation and contact. Notwithstanding the impact of lockdown, some gatekeepers within the study sites admitted that they had reservations in approaching residents with dementia. It was not clear if this was due to a known loss of capacity, concerns about capacity, or another factor that made staff feel that a resident should not be considered as a potential participant in research. This is still an important finding in this thesis, in relation to involving people with dementia in supported housing-oriented research, which may explain why this group are underrepresented in supported housing research literature. Although a small number of people with dementia were involved, important findings were still raised throughout the thesis.

Nonetheless, the pandemic contributed to recruitment challenges for several reasons. First, prior to the pandemic, many housing organisations noted that they supported people living with dementia. During meetings with professionals working in these settings, before commencing the research study, it was stated that each setting supported several people living with dementia. However, as restrictions eased towards the end of the pandemic, disease progression was apparent in individuals living with dementia in supported housing. As discussed by service coordinators and managers, this appeared to be caused by extended periods of lockdown, which led to people with dementia moving into care homes, individuals dying, or being assessed as no longer having capacity. Second, funding pressures were exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic, leading to the restructuring of some housing organisations, meaning that housing providers operated with fewer settings due to closures, or provided less support due to the challenges associated with accessing staff. Third, sheltered housing officers, service coordinators, and individuals in management positions continued to work from home until early 2022, which limited the distribution of study information within sites. Finally, housing organisations did not accept new tenants until late Summer 2021, due to COVID-19 guidelines. This may have impacted the number of people living with dementia in the settings, or the number of individuals meeting the inclusion criteria for the study.

The flexible nature of case study research meant that the empirical study could be completed. Although the depth of data and associated rigour of the researcher's interpretations are discussed throughout this thesis, the findings in case studies one and two are informed by the viewpoints of four individuals living with dementia. Discussed in Chapter Six, these individuals possessed the characteristics of being "ideal" for supported housing. These viewpoints are, likely, not reflective of the experiences of other individuals living with dementia in supported housing, such as those who are isolated from family, rely on a high level of support and care, or do not have capacity to provide informed consent. Although the research did not involve such individuals, the thesis can serve to highlight further gaps in the research and inform directions for future studies.

It may also be argued that the small number of people with dementia in the study impacts the "generalisability" of the findings presented throughout the thesis (Hellström, 2008; Hyett, Kenny and Dickson-

Swift, 2014). In qualitative research, however, it is important to consider terms like transferability and naturalistic generalisation (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018; Miles, Huberman and Saldaña, 2018; Stake, 1995; Stake, 2010). That is, whether the findings can be transferred to other contexts or settings, or, regarding naturalistic generalisations, that findings are presented and described in such a way that enable the reader to apply the findings to their own experiences and contexts (Mills, Durepos and Wiebe, 2010; Stake, 1995). Efforts were made to enhance rigour of any interpretations made by, first, systematically reviewing the evidence base to identify research gaps, second, adhering to a study protocol, and third, presenting findings in such a way that analytical steps, from presenting individual case reports to developing cross-case assertions, can be followed. The findings in Chapter Two, and the discussion of findings in this chapter, have shown that similar experiences have been documented in other research studies. The findings have been situated in relation to relevant research literature and theory and demonstrate that the findings can be transferred to other supported housing contexts. In this regard, the thesis can serve to challenge the proposition that supported housing is suitable for people living with dementia, as many issues have been raised in wider research literature, and in this thesis, in relation to supporting people with dementia as their conditions progress.

The subjective and interpretive nature of qualitative case study research may also raise questions regarding the soundness of any interpretations made (Bumbuc, 2016). In this thesis, such a critique may be warranted, given that no member checking activities were conducted, and the interpretations presented are entirely those of the researcher (Birt *et al.*, 2016). Indeed, this could have an impact on the trustworthiness or authenticity of the research (Lincoln, Lynham and Guba, 2018). Despite this, steps were taken to enhance the trustworthiness and authenticity of the research, first, by ensuring that the voices (viewpoints) of all individuals involved in the research were heard. This can be demonstrated in the presentation of illustrative quotes throughout Chapter Six, with the viewpoints of all individuals shared. A second criteria relating to trustworthiness and authenticity is the likelihood that the research could evoke social change or empower individuals to act. Informed by a social constructionist philosophy, the cross-case themes are reflective of wider societal influences, and the thesis has discussed these in relation to theoretical, research, policy, and practice-oriented literature. A final criterion is that the research generates sufficient knowledge about the experiences of those involved. It can be contended that the rigour and quality of data collection processes

are demonstrated in the rich data excerpts that are presented in Chapter Six, together with the triangulation of data sources like photographs and documentation. Further, documentation and interview processes were designed in accordance with the Scottish Dementia Working Group, the Dementia Empowerment and Engagement Project, and Alzheimer Europe guidelines for involving people with dementia in research (Alzheimer Europe, 2019; The Dementia Empowerment and Engagement Project, 2020; The Scottish Dementia Working Group Research Sub-Group, 2014). The goal of this was to ensure that those involved could be supported to share their experiences and engage meaningfully with the research. As such, although member checking activities were not conducted, steps were taken to ensure that interpretations were trustworthy and authentic. Any interpretations were discussed and critiqued through supervision sessions, and such interpretations are supported through the presentation of interview data, photographs, and the content of gathered documents.

Reflecting a wider critique of case study research, and Stakian case study methodology, it can be argued that the flexible, and, at times, vague nature of case study research poses a threat to methodological integrity and credibility (Hyett, Kenny and Dickson-Swift, 2014). As such, some argue whether case study research is a methodology or method (Hyett, Kenny and Dickson-Swift, 2014). That is, whether a case study research project is underpinned by a clear rationale, informed by a particular philosophical worldview, with research methods selected based on this rationale or worldview; or, if the term “case study” is simply used when multiple methods of data collection are used.

On reflection, Stake’s (1995; 2006) methodology is, at times, vague, in relation to its application. Particularly, regarding data collection methods and analysis. Indeed, to address this, more recent publications on case study research, such as work by Yin (2017), have turned their attention to the active design and application of case study research, as opposed to focussing only on research methods. As stated in these texts, this has been done in order to establish case study research as a fully-fledged methodology (Yin, 2017). Although Stake’s work would benefit from clearer presentations of data collection procedures and analytical steps, it can be argued that Stake’s approach situates itself as a distinct methodology. Appreciating the methodology and its application requires a deeper understanding of his philosophical worldview – the subjective and

interpretive nature of his approach, and its relativist ontological positioning. Reflecting this worldview, Stake's methodology is underpinned by several defining features, which have been adhered to throughout the research process. For example, the social elements of his constructivist epistemology, and his relativist ontology, support the gathering of multiple perspectives in his research. Hearing these perspectives provides greater insights in the research, as interpretations of experiences are informed by multiple viewpoints which enhances the rigour of any claims made. In recognition of the reader's role in interpretation, again, reflecting his relativist ontology, Stake (1995; 2006) states that research should be conducted within the real-life environments in which phenomena occur. This enables the researcher to provide description, or present other supporting information such as photographs or documents, to situate the findings in context for the reader, which evoke vicarious experiences, and allow the reader to evaluate interpretations based on what is presented. As such, these steps were adhered to, and it is hoped that this demonstrates the methodological integrity of the research study.

7.4. Recommendations

7.4.1. Recommendations for Future Research

The first recommendation for future research is to conduct a study that involves people living with dementia in alternative models of housing in Scotland, such as shared housing, retirement villages, or dementia-specific settings. This study focussed only on sheltered, very sheltered, and extra care housing. However, there is suggestion that other housing models might benefit people living with dementia. Drawing from wider research literature, small-scale care environments, where people with dementia occupy a room within a shared house, have been described as an optimal model of care for many people living with dementia (Ausserhofer *et al.*, 2016; de Boer *et al.*, 2019; de Rooij *et al.*, 2011; de Rooij *et al.*, 2012; Marshall, 1993; van Hoof *et al.*, 2013; Verbeek *et al.*, 2009b; Verbeek *et al.*, 2009a; Verbeek *et al.*, 2010; Verbeek *et al.*, 2012; Zwakhalen *et al.*, 2018). However, these settings are described as small-scale, homelike residential care settings, and not "housing." That is, the individuals that reside within these settings are not classified as tenants or homeowners by law, but as care home residents. The settings, aesthetically, and often, structurally, resemble houses, but it is the model of care that is different. That is, health or social care staff are always

present in the settings, including nurses. Nonetheless, the individuals who live in the settings prepare meals together, clean, and conduct other domestic activities, though are supported to do so by staff members. Within Scotland, there are shared models of supported housing, whereby individuals occupy a room within a shared occupancy larger house. Individuals that live in such settings are classified as tenants or homeowners by law. The settings are also staffed by support workers rather than caregivers or nurses. It would be valuable to understand the benefits of living with dementia in these settings, given that small-scale, shared care environments have been described as successful.

Relatedly, retirement communities and villages have also been described as beneficial housing models for people with dementia (Ayalon and Yahav, 2019; Campbell, 2016; Cutchin, Marshall and Aldrich, 2010; Jenkins and Smythe, 2013; Kelsey, Laditka and Laditka, 2008; Kelsey, Laditka and Laditka, 2010). For example, these may be referred to as continuing care retirement communities in the United States and Australia, where people live in settings akin to sheltered housing (referred to as independent living), then move into settings akin to extra care housing (referred to as assisted living) as their needs progress, and finally, into a care or nursing home, if they require (Campbell, 2016; National Seniors Australia, 2023). Further examples are referred to as dementia villages, where dedicated villages have been built, including shops, libraries, cafes, and other amenities, that house people with dementia (Jenkins and Smythe, 2013). Benefits of retirement villages or communities are linked to the fact that various housing models, and care or nursing homes, are located within the same site, meaning that people with dementia do not have to relocate from their local community. There are only a handful of retirement communities in Scotland, however, the benefits of living with dementia in these settings have not been studied within the Scottish context. This is particularly important, as literature has suggested that the United Kingdom learn from such housing models (Beach, 2018).

However, although these housing models have shown benefits, they reportedly experience many of the same issues highlighted by the findings of the present study. For example, shown in Chapter Two, challenges with access to housing, and the provision of support and care for people with dementia, were reported in assisted living settings, contained within continuing care retirement communities in the United States. Drawing from

wider literature, from the United States and Australia, there is a suggestion that these countries face their own senior housing “crises” (National Seniors Australia, 2023; Zimmerman *et al.*, 2022). For example, a recent article states that issues with access to funding, health and social care, together with the increasing needs of residents, means that continuing care housing provision needs reform in the United States (Zimmerman *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, a recent article published in Australia noted that older people face challenges when accessing senior housing and community-based care, and the rising costs of housing and care (National Seniors Australia, 2023). As stated, it has been suggested that the United Kingdom should learn from these countries regarding housing provision for older people (Beach, 2018). However, the findings in this study, and in the wider research literature, suggest that these housing models may not solve the issues relating to supported housing and dementia. Hence, further research would be beneficial, drawing from the Scottish context, and from the perspectives of people living with dementia in these settings.

There is also a suggestion that dementia-specific models of supported housing are appropriate for people living with dementia (Henderson and Sharp, 2019). This is due to the provision of support and care, in addition to end of life and palliative care that these settings can provide, due to the successful integration of housing, health, and social care. Within Scotland, there is only one supported housing setting that has been specifically designed to house people living with dementia (Henderson and Sharp, 2019). If this model can successfully support people living with dementia, then it would be beneficial to understand this through research, with the goal of informing policy regarding the development of more models of this kind. Returning to the discussion around continuing care retirement communities, these settings often incorporate small-scale dementia “units,” designed to meet the needs of people living with dementia (Caspi, 2013; Caspi, 2014a; Caspi, 2014b; Caspi, 2015). In this context, these settings are not models of housing as such, but are nonetheless contained within retirement communities. Again, despite the reported success of these arguably more progressive models, those living in the settings still face challenges with wayfinding, distress, neglect, and access to appropriate levels of support and care (Caspi, 2013; Caspi, 2014a; Caspi, 2014b; Caspi, 2015). Again, it would be beneficial to conduct research within the Scottish housing context, to determine if these models are a realistic solution.

A second recommendation for future research is to conduct studies that involve people living with dementia, who do not have capacity to provide informed consent, but nonetheless live in supported housing. As shown throughout this thesis, it appears that many of the challenges associated with living with dementia in supported housing stem from living with advanced dementia, as supported housing settings are not equipped to meet these individual's needs. Although such experiences were shared, they were not gathered from the perspectives of people living with dementia. There has been no research study, conducted in supported housing, that includes people with dementia who have been assessed as not having capacity. Research has shown that people with dementia, and incapacity, can, and should be, supported to be involved in research as far as possible (Brooks, Savitch and Gridley, 2017; McKeown *et al.*, 2010). Such a research study would allow the experiences of this population to be understood, in addition to understanding the practicalities of supporting people living with more advanced dementia in supported housing.

7.4.2. Recommendations for Practice and Education

Housing providers should recognise that it is not enough to tackle housing issues, facing those living with dementia, by increasing housing stock. Rather, addressing issues of access to appropriate health and social care, organising home repairs and adaptations, and targeting societal stigma must also be priorities in practice. In this regard, policies and guidelines relating to dementia, housing, health, and social care need to be implemented in practice, and solutions for the integration of housing, health, and social care must be developed by housing providers. For example, the Standards of Care for Dementia in Scotland, and dementia care guidelines developed by the Scottish Intercollegiate Guidelines Network, present practical solutions for providing support and care to people with dementia who live in their own homes, in addition to recommendations for relationship building to develop integrated housing, health, and social care models (Scottish Government, 2011d; Scottish Intercollegiate Guidelines Network, 2023). Support and care guidelines relate to the delivery of practical help, support at home, personal care, specialist dementia day care services, respite, telecare, and assistive technology, for people with dementia and their families. However, it is apparent that such guidelines are not implemented, at scale, within supported housing settings, despite the proposition that such models are appropriate for people with dementia. Not all responsibilities should be placed with housing providers regarding such implementation of good clinical practice in supported housing

settings, acknowledging that these settings are challenged with funding, access to staff, and resources. Nonetheless, they do hold a central responsibility here, given that they house people living with dementia and are registered with the Scottish Social Services Council as registered social care providers, with such services evaluated by the Care Inspectorate, under the remit that they provide appropriate housing and social care services to meet individual's needs (Care Inspectorate, 2015; Scottish Social Services Council, 2023).

Relatedly, housing providers need to be educated regarding dementia-friendly design and dementia awareness, in addition to developing practical solutions for implementation of these design principles within supported housing settings. Further, housing providers have a duty to educate individuals who live in supported housing, without dementia, and those working in such settings, regarding dementia awareness and the experience of living with dementia in supported housing. The goal here should be to reduce the disabling nature of supported housing developments, improve the delivery of dementia-oriented support and care, and tackle the inherent stigma, that is still present in these settings.

7.4.3. Recommendations for Policy

At the widest level, the Scottish Government must recognise their role regarding integration between supported housing, health, and social care services (e.g., Scottish Government, 2021). Evidence-based guidelines for the delivery of support and care for people living with dementia, specific to supported housing, need to be developed, in addition to the development of housing models that are dementia-friendly and not disabling. Further, any guidelines relating to health and social care delivery, or dementia-friendly design principles, require detailed instructions for implementation. It is not enough to simply state that these services should be integrated, without actively developing strategies that can be applied in practice. Evidently, the gap between policy and strategy development, and implementation in practice, needs to be addressed.

Literature relating to Scottish policy has proposed some solutions for the integration of housing, health, and social care. For example, there has been some discussion surrounding the need to develop a national care service and the reforming of housing policy (Feeley, 2021; Scottish Government, 2023b; Tolson *et al.*, 2023). Suggestions relate to improving workforce education, providing human-rights and person-centred care, diversifying housing options, and evaluating quality improvement initiatives (Scottish Government, 2023b).

The key point here is that the Scottish Government acknowledges the need for reform regarding housing and care provision for older people and people with dementia, but what this might look like, in practice, remains conceptual.

It should be noted that these problems are not new and have been acknowledged for over a decade in Scottish policy documents. For example, Scotland's housing policy and strategy, Age, Home, and Community (Scottish Government, 2011a), implemented between 2012 – 2021, stated the need to improve quality of care, increase access to person-centred care, and provide more housing options. The same issues were again acknowledged in Scotland's most recent policy document, Housing to 2040 (Scottish Government, 2021), with a greater focus on increasing housing stock. Other policies and strategies focussing specifically on dementia, such as the most recent Scottish dementia strategy, have acknowledged the importance of housing with regard to support and care provision for people with dementia (Scottish Government, 2023a). However, Housing to 2040 (Scottish Government, 2021) makes no reference to dementia, signifying that policies are disjointed.

Having established that these challenges are not new, it is important to reiterate that these proposed solutions and suggestions for change do not simply remain as political rhetoric but are actively implemented in practice. The findings of this study show that some people with dementia can live independently in supported housing in Scotland. However, due to resource limitations, poor dementia awareness, and a lack of housing options, people with dementia face moves into care or nursing homes, or into housing that may not meet their needs and wants. The Scottish Government's current housing and dementia strategies acknowledge these issues. Potential solutions have been documented. For example, relating to housing, it has been suggested that all new houses built in Scotland should be future proof. That is, housing should be easily adaptable to meet an individual's needs, through retrofitting and the use of assistive technologies (Scottish Government, 2021). It is suggested this goal would be met by developing new planning and building standards in Scotland by 2026, to ensure that housing developers build homes that are future proof (Scottish Government, 2021). Indeed, this would be a positive first step. However, it is also necessary to address issues relating to health and social care delivery, as this thesis has shown that the physical environment is only part

of the issue. Indeed, the development of a National Care Service is a positive solution, that aims to ensure that social care delivery is preventative, anticipatory, collaborative, reflective of human rights, and is person-centred (Feeley, 2021). This is in acknowledgement that social care delivery is often reactionary and provided in times of crises. Although these solutions might address many issues experienced by people living with dementia in the community, there is a need for joint working and accountability to ensure that these policy goals are implemented. To avoid perpetuating the issues outlined in this thesis, there needs to be greater discussion, integration, and active working between individuals within housing research, policy, provision, planning, construction, and care backgrounds. The cross-case themes and assertions presented in this study can be used to demonstrate the experience of living with dementia in supported housing in Scotland to these stakeholders. They highlight the challenges associated with living with dementia in these settings, which should be tackled through joint working and proactive solutions.

7.5. Conclusion

This thesis makes an original contribution to research through the conducting of a theory informed study with a robust methodology. Chapter Two presents the first systematic review to be conducted in the research area, with the goal of synthesising research relating to the experience of living with dementia in supported housing. The review showed that previous studies have significant quality issues, including poorly described methodologies and methods, with limited application of theory, which can impact our understanding regarding the experience of living with dementia in supported housing. As such, this thesis can act as a template for conducting high quality case study research within such settings and provides the basis for developing theory in the area.

This positions the thesis to make strong claims regarding the provision of supported housing for people with dementia in Scotland. Fundamentally, this thesis contests the proposition that supported housing is an appropriate housing option for people with dementia in Scotland. Although there is some evidence to suggest that people living with the earlier stages of dementia can live independently in supported housing, the settings lack the resources to adequately care for these individuals as their conditions progress. There is a mismatch between the services offered in supported housing, and the complexity of healthcare needs that

people with dementia develop over time. The issue here is that there is a finite window, where people living with dementia are classified as “ideal candidates” for supported housing. However, the progression of dementia varies substantially for everyone, and the length of time a person can remain as “ideal” is uncertain. The findings in this thesis have shown that people with dementia can live in the settings for as little as eight months before being labelled as “too far gone” and requiring a move into a care home.

This serves to question the underlying goal or ethos of supported housing in Scotland, stated as the “promotion” or “maintenance” of independence and autonomy, to enable people to continue living in the community. This thesis shows that this is not inherently true for people with dementia, and that the ability to live independently is often a prerequisite to continue living within the settings. That is, people with dementia are expected to live independently with minimal support, rather than being enabled to live independently through support and care provision. This does not reflect the “promotion” or “maintenance” of independence, facilitated through increased support, care, or home adaptations. Nor is this reflective of “autonomy,” as the amount of choice or control over the level of support and care received is unclear, and decisions referring people with dementia out of supported housing settings are often made on their behalf. In this regard, supported housing providers should refrain from stating that they support people to live independently and autonomously. Rather, it should be stated that the ability to live independently with minimal support is a requirement for life in the settings, rather than independence being “enabled”, “promoted”, or “maintained” through the provision of support and care.

These issues are not new and have been reported in research literature relating to supported housing and dementia over the last 20 years. This is problematic, as within policy-oriented literature, models of supported housing, such as extra care housing, are still described as alternatives to care homes for people with dementia – with the suggestion that more of these settings should be built. However, this thesis has shown that this proposition is ill informed. For supported housing settings to be true long-term care alternatives for people with dementia, there is a requirement to meet complex health needs, including the provision of palliative and end-of-life care, in addition to the provision of social care to support people to continue living in their homes.

As things stand, supported housing should not be labelled as a care home alternative, or indeed, an appropriate housing option for people with dementia.

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REVIEW ARTICLE

WILEY

Living with dementia in supported housing: A systematic review and thematic synthesis of qualitative research

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Abstract

Supported housing has been highlighted as a potential way to facilitate independent living for people with dementia by integrating housing with support or care services. However, the benefits and challenges of living with dementia in supported housing are not fully understood. This systematic review and thematic synthesis sought to understand how living in supported housing influences the lives of people with dementia, from the perspectives of people with dementia, their supporters, health and social care professionals. Seven databases were searched for qualitative research, date range: 1 January 2000–31 July 2021. Eleven published articles were included in the thematic synthesis. One core theme was generated, Maintaining Independence and Autonomy, divided into three subthemes – Support and Care, Social Relationships and the Physical Environment. Factors like person-centred care, social interaction and good environmental design contributed to the maintenance of independence and autonomy. Barriers like low staff ratios, stigma and limited access to the community led to a loss of independence and autonomy – often leading to people with dementia being referred or managed out of the settings. Although the articles acknowledged the importance of maintaining independence and autonomy for people with dementia, it appeared that supported housing settings often lacked the resources and facilities to make this a reality. More high-quality research is needed, particularly from the perspectives of people with dementia and their supporters, to understand if supported housing can delay care home admission, promote independence and autonomy and facilitate social networks and community connections for this population.

KEYWORDS

dementia, environment design, housing for the elderly, independent living, qualitative research, social interaction, social support

1 | INTRODUCTION

Most people with dementia live in their own homes in the community, with figures ranging from 60% in the United Kingdom, 70% in Australia, 80% in the United States and 93% in Canada (Osborne, 2020). Living at home is linked to feelings of connection, permanency, familiarity, expression and autonomy for people with dementia, amidst the uncertainty posed by the condition (Aminzadeh et al., 2010). A recent systematic review found that living independently, remaining at home and delaying entry into residential care was the preferred option for people with dementia (Tochel et al., 2019).

The United Nations has emphasised that access to housing, health and social care are human rights for people with dementia and their family carers (United Nations, 2006; World Health Organization, 2015). Internationally, dementia policy reflects this by highlighting the importance of enabling people with dementia to live independently at home or in a homely setting for as long as they wish (Alzheimer Europe, 2018; World Health Organization, 2017), though achieving this '...requires appropriate housing options in the community, in combination with home and social care...' (Fleming et al., 2020, p. 15). However, research suggests that many community-dwelling people with dementia experience unmet health and social care needs (Morrisby et al., 2018), while others question if enough appropriate housing options exist for this population (Brown et al., 2017; Harding et al., 2018). There is a need for research to assess all housing options for people with dementia and their ability to facilitate independent living, reflecting the rights-based approaches espoused in dementia policy.

One housing option, supported housing, has been described as a potential way to facilitate independent living for people with dementia, by integrating housing with additional support or care services (Dutton, 2009; Twyford, 2016). In the United Kingdom, supported housing is defined as '...any housing scheme where housing is provided alongside care, support, or supervision to help people live as independently as possible in the community' (Department for Communities and Local Government Department for Work and Pensions, 2016, p. 9). In terms of housing for older people, this covers settings in which a low level of support is provided, e.g. sheltered or retirement housing, through to housing offering a higher level of support and sometimes care, e.g. very-sheltered or extra-care housing (Beach, 2018; Howe et al., 2013). Similar housing options exist internationally, such as independent or assisted living settings in the United States, supportive seniors' housing in Canada and supported independent accommodation in New Zealand (Howe et al., 2013). Supply of this form of housing varies by country, with 0.7% of people aged 65+ in the United Kingdom living in supported housing and similar settings, compared to 5.2% in New Zealand, 5.4% in Australia and 6.1% in the United States (Beach, 2018). Some evidence suggests that these housing models can improve quality of life, increase independence and autonomy, combat social isolation, reduce hospitalisations and defer entry into residential care for people with dementia (Brooker et al., 2011; Holland et al., 2015; Twyford, 2016).

What is known about the topic?

- Many community-dwelling people with dementia experience unmet housing, health and social care needs.
- Supported housing has been identified as an appropriate housing choice for people with dementia.

What this paper adds

- The review shows that although the ethos of supported housing is to promote independence and autonomy, in practice, this is not always achieved.
- Maintaining the independence and autonomy of people living with dementia in supported housing requires flexible, person-centred support and care, organisation of social activities, specialist dementia training and a suitably designed building that facilitates engagement within the local community.

However, research also suggests that these outcomes are not universally experienced (Dutton, 2010; Verbeek et al., 2019). There is a need to understand the experience of living with dementia in supported housing, to surface the benefits and challenges of living within these settings.

Research stresses the importance of synthesising personal stories and lived experiences to gain a comprehensive and multifaceted understanding of living with dementia (Górska et al., 2018; O'Rourke et al., 2015). However, scoping searches of PROSPERO, the Cochrane Library and the Joanna Briggs Institute review repositories indicate that there has yet to be a rigorous systematic review focussing on the experience of living with dementia in supported housing. Considering the international policy imperative on access to housing for people with dementia, the importance of enabling independent living for this population and the potential of supported housing to facilitate this, this review can enhance our understanding of this housing option. By thematically synthesising an international body of qualitative research, this review aimed to answer the question:

How does living in supported housing influence the lives of people with dementia, from the perspectives of people living with dementia, their supporters, health and social care professionals?

2 | METHODS

The systematic review protocol was registered on PROSPERO (ID CRD42020176816). The reviewers adhered to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA; Moher et al., 2009) and the Centre for Reviews and Dissemination (CRD) guidance for undertaking reviews in healthcare (Tacconelli, 2010).

2.1 | Search strategy

All search strategies are provided in Appendix S1 of the supplementary material for this article. This systematic review thematically synthesised findings from peer-reviewed qualitative research, including mixed methods research with a qualitative component. The search strategy was first developed for MEDLINE (EBSCOhost), then adapted for CINAHL Complete (EBSCOhost), Health Source: Nursing/Academic Edition (EBSCOhost), APA PsycArticles (EBSCOhost), Psychology and Behavioural Sciences Collection (EBSCOhost), SocINDEX (EBSCOhost) and Social Care Institute for Excellence: Social Care Online (<https://www.scie-socialcareonline.org.uk>).

Each search in EBSCOhost was conducted individually to account for differences in search functions for each database. Search terms related to supported housing and comparative housing models, study methodologies and methods, dementia and its major subtypes and a range of symptoms, experiences and outcomes of dementia. The search strategy was informed by previous housing reviews (Croucher et al., 2006; Dutton, 2009; Howe et al., 2013; O'Malley & Croucher, 2005), core or priority dementia-related outcomes lists (Janssen et al., 2020; Reilly et al., 2020; Webster et al., 2017) and elements of the lived experience of dementia (Górska et al., 2018). The search was balanced for sensitivity and specificity and incorporated subject headings/indexing terms specific to each database (e.g. Medical Subject Headings, CINAHL Subject Headings, APA Thesaurus of Psychological Index Terms), synonyms and differences in spellings in accordance with CRD guidelines (Tacconelli, 2010). Articles written in English from all countries were included.

The date range of the searches was limited to 1 January 2000–31 July 2021, including articles that were available as preprints or were forthcoming at the time of the search. Although published and unpublished articles have reviewed literature relating to housing and dementia prior to the year 2009 (e.g. Dutton, 2009; O'Malley & Croucher, 2005), we were aware of qualitative research, published in 2000–2009, not discussed in these reviews. This may be due to the omission of search terms like 'assisted living', 'independent living' or 'extra care' (O'Malley & Croucher, 2005), or the specified inclusion criteria of the review (Dutton, 2009). It is also unclear how search strategies were input into each database, or if subject headings and indexing terms were used in accordance with CRD guidelines, which may have impacted the number of references uncovered (Tacconelli, 2010). As such, the specified date range was selected to provide an overview of the most up-to-date qualitative research, while documenting a replicable search strategy and robust critical appraisal of relevant research.

The authors of any relevant, unpublished research were contacted to determine if their findings had been published in a peer-reviewed journal. The reference lists of any relevant articles were also hand-searched, to uncover literature not identified in the databases.

2.2 | Selection criteria and screening

Drawing on comparative reviews of international housing models for older people and previous literature reviews on supported housing (e.g. Croucher et al., 2006; Dutton, 2009; O'Malley & Croucher, 2005), a broad definition of supported housing was used. In this review, supported housing was defined as any form of housing for older people, where housing is provided alongside support or care to promote independent living. This included settings offering a low level of support (e.g. sheltered housing, retirement housing, independent living), and settings offering a higher level of support and care (e.g. very-sheltered housing, extra-care housing, housing with care, assisted living). Settings described as 'care homes', 'nursing homes', 'locked', 'secure' or 'institutional' were not included. This was to ensure that the included settings operationally focussed on the provision of housing rather than the provision of healthcare. Further inclusion and exclusion criteria (Table 1) were developed in accordance with the Study, Participants, Phenomenon of Interest, Outcomes (SPIO) framework (Richardson et al., 1995).

All peer-reviewed articles meeting the review criteria were included. This meant that if a subsection of the research related to dementia, it would be included, provided the findings could be extracted from the article and differentiated from other participant groups. EndNote X8 (Clarivate Analytics, 2018) was used for reference management. Covidence software (Veritas Health Innovation LTD, 2019) facilitated screening. All titles/abstracts/full texts were screened by the lead author and a second reviewer.

2.3 | Quality appraisal

For each article, methodological quality was assessed using the 10 items of the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) Qualitative Checklist (Critical Appraisal Skills Programme, 2018). Each article was given a score ranging from 0 to 10 based on the satisfaction of each criterion. A score of 0 (denoting 'No') was given if the article did not meet the criterion. A score of 0.5 was given if the article provided evidence of relevance to the criterion, though not in sufficient detail to determine if the criterion was satisfied (denoting 'Can't Tell'). A score of 1 was given if the article satisfied the criterion (denoting 'Yes'). In line with the thematic synthesis process, no articles were excluded based on quality, but rather, quality issues were outlined as part of the overall synthesis (Thomas & Harden, 2008). A sensitivity analysis was conducted, in line with the thematic synthesis approach, to determine the contribution of each article to the overall synthesis and the potential impact of methodological quality on the review findings (Thomas & Harden, 2008). The lead author conducted all appraisals, with content agreed at research team meetings.

2.4 | Data extraction and synthesis

A data extraction form was developed, available in Appendix S2 of the supplementary material for this article. Data extraction was

TABLE 1 Outline of inclusion and exclusion criteria, following the SPIO framework (Richardson et al., 1995)

Inclusion	Exclusion
Study design Qualitative research. Mixed methods research with an extractable qualitative component	Quantitative research. Commentaries, discussion or opinion pieces. Literature reviews. Intervention studies
Population People with dementia: all subtypes, living in supported housing Supporters: family members, friends (including other residents) and unpaid caregivers of people living with dementia in supported housing Health and social care professionals: paid caregivers, support workers, managers, primary care nurses, community mental health nurses, allied health professionals, general practitioners and other health and social care professionals who provide support or care to people living with dementia in supported housing	People living in care or nursing homes (including small-scale, homelike dementia care settings and nursing homes) or those living in 'ordinary' housing People with learning disabilities or severe mental health problems and dementia People with mild cognitive impairment Building planners/architects/policy makers or individuals with no direct role in the everyday functioning of a supported housing setting
Phenomenon of Interest How living in supported housing influences the lives of people with dementia, from the perspectives of the populations of interest	Views regarding the prospect of moving into a supported housing setting
Outcomes (Findings) Experiential accounts, related specifically to living in supported housing with a diagnosis of dementia	Quantitative analysis. Commentaries, opinion or discussion pieces. Evidence syntheses in literature reviews

conducted by the lead author, with content agreed at research team meetings.

Data synthesis utilised the thematic synthesis approach (Thomas & Harden, 2008). Thematic synthesis enables researchers '...to stay "close" to the results of the primary studies, synthesising them in a transparent way, and facilitating the explicit production of new concepts...' and can be used to inform policy, practice and directions for future research (Thomas & Harden, 2008). It draws from elements of meta-ethnography and grounded theory and is philosophically underpinned by critical realism (Barnett-Page & Thomas, 2009). It is characterised by three analytical processes: coding text, development of descriptive themes and generating analytical themes, conducted as follows in the present review.

Coding Text: The qualitative data and the authors' second-level interpretations were extracted from the results section of each article and stored in an NVivo 12 Pro database (QSR International Pty Ltd, 2020). In some instances, unique findings were reported in the discussion sections of the articles, which were extracted. Free coding of the findings was conducted line-by-line. Articles with the highest methodological quality and the largest amount of relevant data were coded first, followed by the remaining articles. New and existing codes were developed throughout the analytical process. Coding was conducted by the lead author, with the coding framework refined at subsequent meetings with the research team.

Development of Descriptive Themes: All codes were then arranged and visualised hierarchically using NVivo 12 Pro software, forming the basis of the descriptive themes. Visualising codes promoted rigorous synthesis and enabled the research team to group codes into meaningful themes, capturing the content of the included articles.

Generating Analytical Themes: The descriptive themes were then expanded into analytical themes. The previous steps were

rooted in the original findings of the included articles. This step aimed to transcend the content of the individual articles, generating new concepts and understandings from the evidence base. This process was cyclical and conducted within the research team until all descriptive themes were synthesised. These analytical themes, together with illustrative participant quotes and authors' interpretations, are reported in Results section.

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | Searches

Figure 1 shows the output of the database searches and screening phases. Based on title/abstract screening of the 3,914 unique records identified in the searches, there was 95% agreement with regards to inclusion and exclusion decisions, meaning that conflicts arose for 198 articles. This corresponded to Cohen's kappa statistic of 0.52, denoting a moderate level of inter-rater reliability (Cohen, 1960). Conflicts were resolved within the research team. Of the 153 full texts screened, 11 articles were included in the thematic synthesis.

3.2 | Study characteristics

Characteristics of the 11 included articles are shown in Table 2. The articles were based on eight research studies. Two articles were based on a research study conducted in assisted living settings in Missouri, USA (Aud, 2002, 2004). Two articles were based on the Provision of Social Care in Extra Care Housing study (ECHO)

FIGURE 1 PRISMA Flow Diagram (Moher et al., 2009) showing citation numbers in each stage of the screening process

conducted in England, UK (Cameron et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2020). Two articles were based on the Technology-Enriched Supported Accommodation study conducted in Northern Ireland, UK (Rondon-Sulbaran, Daly-Lynn, McCormack, Ryan, & Martin, 2020, 2021). The five remaining studies were conducted in England in retirement housing (O'Malley et al., 2018), extra-care housing (Evans et al., 2019; Evans & Means, 2006), a mixture of supported housing settings (Barrett et al., 2020) and supportive seniors' housing in Western Canada (Stewart-Archer et al., 2016). Studies were described as exploratory, longitudinal or mixed methods. Articles that reported details of analysis using thematic analysis or presented their findings as themes. From articles that explicitly reported participant numbers, views were gathered from 21 people with dementia, 28 supporters and 77 health and social care professionals.

3.3 | Quality appraisal and sensitivity analysis

CASP Qualitative Checklist (Critical Appraisal Skills Programme, 2018) scores are shown in Table 2, with a more detailed breakdown provided in Appendix S3 of the supplementary material for this article. The most common quality issues were not discussing the relationship between the researcher(s) and the research participants and providing limited information on data collection methods. Other common issues related to limited descriptions of recruitment, ethical considerations and data analysis. The least common quality issues related to providing clear study aims, the appropriateness of qualitative research to address these aims and discussion of how valuable the research is – with all articles providing a clear statement of findings. Similar trends have been reported in systematic reviews

TABLE 2 Summary of study characteristics

Article; Location	Study Aim(s)	Research Design, Data Collection, Analysis	Relevant Participants	Relevant Setting(s)	CASP Score
Aud (2002); Missouri, USA ¹	To understand the reasons why people with dementia are discharged from assisted living settings to skilled nursing facilities, focussing on behaviour–environment interactions	Exploratory qualitative. Ethnographic-style interviews: 45–90 min Open coding with findings reported as themes	14 assisted living administrators	14 assisted living sites, housing between 24 and 136 people, 7 not for profit, 7 for profit.	5.5
Aud (2004); Missouri, USA ¹	To understand the reasons why people with dementia are discharged from assisted living settings to skilled nursing facilities, focussing on behaviour	Exploratory qualitative. Ethnographic-style interviews: 45–90 min Open coding with findings reported as themes	14 assisted living administrators	14 assisted living sites, housing between 24 and 136 people, 7 not for profit, 7 for profit.	6.5
Barrett et al. (2020); England, UK	To explore the causes, implications, impact and outcomes of walking with purpose on the lives of people with dementia	Mixed methods with qualitative case study component Structured interviews Thematic analysis	Three family members, eight housing managers	Three extra-care housing and three retirement housing sites	6
Cameron et al. (2020); England, UK ²	To explore tenants' perceptions and experiences of living in extra-care housing and to consider the advantages and disadvantages of this model	Longitudinal qualitative interviews conducted four times over a 20-month period Thematic analysis	Study included 51 people living in extra-care housing, seven housing managers, 20 formal caregivers; total number of people with dementia not reported	Four extra-care housing sites, one of which dementia-specific	6.5
Evans et al. (2020); England, UK ²	To explore how extra-care housing can respond to the changing social care needs of people with dementia	Longitudinal qualitative interviews conducted four times over a 20-month period Thematic analysis	Study included 51 people living in extra-care housing, seven housing managers, 20 formal caregivers; total number of people with dementia not reported.	Four extra-care housing sites, one of which dementia-specific	7.5
Evans et al. (2019); England, UK	To explore opportunities, benefits, barriers and enablers to interaction with nature for people with dementia	Mixed methods Qualitative case study component Interviews Thematic analysis	Seven people with dementia, three housing managers, four other staff members including care assistants and activity co-ordinators	Three extra-care housing sites	5.5
Evans and Means (2006); England, UK	To understand professional perceptions and practices regarding risk and the desire of people with dementia to remain independent in extra care housing	Longitudinal, mixed methods with qualitative case study component. Study was conducted over 3–5 years, during which periodic interviews were conducted at six case study sites	The study involved people with dementia, other residents, relatives and health/housing/social care managers; Participant numbers not reported	Six extra-care housing sites	6
O'Malley et al. (2018); England, UK	To explore wayfinding experiences of older adults with memory difficulties living in a communal retirement development and explore their design preferences	No information on analysis Exploratory qualitative Semi-structured interviews. Thematic analysis	Two people with dementia, article included 13 people living with memory difficulties, but only two had a dementia diagnosis	One retirement housing site, 42 apartments	10

TABLE 2 (Continued)

Article; Location	Study Aim(s)	Research Design, Data Collection, Analysis	Relevant Participants	Relevant Setting(s)	CASP Score
Rondon-Sulbaran et al. (2020); Northern Ireland, UK ³	To explore the extent to which person-centred care practices are evident in technology-enriched supported accommodation and how this can be facilitated using assistive technology	Exploratory qualitative Semi-structured interviews, 40–60 min Thematic analysis	Twenty-one staff members, including 13 support workers, two senior support workers, three managers, two activity co-ordinators and one team leader	Nine technology-enriched supported accommodation sites, housing between 12 and 61 people	10
Rondon-Sulbaran et al. (2021); Northern Ireland, UK ³	To explore informal caregivers' perceptions of technology-enriched supported accommodation for people with dementia and their perceptions of their relatives' experience of the move and of life in the scheme	Exploratory qualitative Semi-structured interviews, 40–60 min Thematic analysis	Twenty-five family members, including 11 daughters, six sons, three wives, one friend, one granddaughter, one niece, one sister, one sister-in-law.	Nine technology-enriched supported accommodation sites, housing between 12 and 61 people	10
Stewart-Archer et al. (2016); Western Canada	To define quality of life as characterised by people with dementia	Mixed methods with qualitative interview component Semi-structured interviews Thematic content analysis	Twelve people with dementia	Nine supportive seniors' housing sites	10

Note: Superscript numbers indicate that articles were based on the same study.

of qualitative dementia research; however, authors suggest that a clear statement of findings is the most important quality indicator for qualitative data synthesis (e.g. O'Rourke et al., 2015).

A sensitivity analysis was conducted to determine the contribution of each article to the overall synthesis, considering issues of methodological quality (Thomas & Harden, 2008). Contribution to the synthesis appeared to be determined by a trade-off between the following two factors: (1) high methodological quality and (2) the amount of data and themes reported of relevance to the review question. Articles with high methodological quality that reported a large amount of data contributed the most to the synthesis (Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020, 2021). Articles with lower methodological quality that reported a large amount of data also contributed meaningfully to the synthesis, though to a lesser extent (Aud, 2002, 2004; Barrett et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2019, 2020; Evans & Means, 2006). This was largely because the data analysis and reported themes were less developed, a phenomenon consistent with previous thematic syntheses (Thomas & Harden, 2008). Articles reporting a small amount of data (e.g. where people with dementia were a subgroup of the total sample) contributed least to the synthesis, regardless of methodological quality (Cameron et al., 2020; O'Malley et al., 2018; Stewart-Archer et al., 2016). These articles still contributed meaningfully to the synthesis, as their participants included people with dementia (O'Malley et al., 2018; Stewart-Archer et al., 2016) and their supporters (Cameron et al., 2020), with a limited amount of data available for these participant groups in the included articles.

3.4 | Thematic synthesis

The thematic synthesis generated one overarching theme, Maintaining Independence and Autonomy. This was divided into three subthemes – Support and Care, Social Relationships and the Physical Environment. To illustrate how the overarching theme and subthemes were developed and to provide further context to the findings, Table 3 shows example codes, data extracts, codes assigned to each extract and the articles contributing to each theme.

3.5 | Overarching theme: Maintaining independence and autonomy

All articles, and participant groups, discussed the importance of 'independence', 'control', 'freedom', 'choice', 'autonomy' or 'self-determination' for people with dementia in supported housing. 'Promoting', 'maximising' or 'supporting' independence and autonomy was highlighted as a central goal of supported housing (Aud, 2002, 2004; Evans et al., 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020), described as the underlying 'philosophy', 'ethos' or 'ideal' of the settings (Aud, 2002; Evans et al., 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020). In the context of the included articles, independence focussed more on supporting people with dementia

TABLE 3 Illustrating the thematic synthesis process, showing the theme/subthemes, example codes, example data extracts and codes assigned to these and a breakdown of contributing articles/participant groups

Overarching Theme	Example Codes	Example Data Extracts/Codes(s) Assigned	Articles/Participant Groups Contributing to Theme
Maintaining Independence and Autonomy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Independence Autonomy <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Choice Control Self-determination As an ethos/philosophy/ideal of supported housing Loss of independence/autonomy 	<p>'I ran a good household, raised 8 kids well. What did I do to let them think I can't look after myself? I didn't even get to choose 1 photo, or hang 1 picture here now. I don't need help with anything, but everything is done for you. Everything' (Person with dementia, supportive seniors' housing; Stewart-Archer et al., 2016, p. 1724) – choice, loss of independence/autonomy</p> <p>'They've got a bit of their own independence you know their own room, they can make their breakfast and their tea and their cups of tea when they want it and they can come down to the lounge for stimulation or they can go upstairs and just be themselves'. (Family member; extra-care housing; Evans & Means, 2006, p. 79) – independence, autonomy</p> <p>'...our ethos is more basically trying to promote as much independence with them as possible. So, being more, us standing back and giving them by that to promote, for them to be able to do the things for themselves, to try and keep their minds stimulated' (Formal caregiver, technology-enriched supported accommodation; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020, p. 2.297) – as an ethos/philosophy/ideal of supported housing, independence</p>	<p>People with dementia: (Evans et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2019; Evans & Means, 2006; O'Malley et al., 2018; Stewart-Archer et al., 2016)</p> <p>Supporters: (Cameron et al., 2020; Evans & Means, 2006; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2021)</p> <p>Health and Social Care Professionals: (Aud, 2002, 2004; Barrett et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2019, 2020; Evans & Means, 2006; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020)</p>
Subtheme 1 Support and Care	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitators of independence and autonomy Person-centred support/care Staff training Good staff ratios Good dementia understanding/awareness Barriers to independence and autonomy Lack of funding Cost of care Inadequate staff ratios Lack of dementia understanding and awareness Support/care need versus limited availability Risk averse support/care approaches 	<p>'Well for (a) start off you're still yourself and that's what I like, you know, they're not coming round and saying you've gotta... they don't, but if you ask them anything you want them to do they'll do it' (Person with dementia, extra-care housing; Evans et al., 2020, p. 1.496) – person-centred support/care</p> <p>'I don't think there could be a business formula with dementia... [To] care successfully for people that are suffering from dementia requires a slightly different cost approach from the containment that you have in a nursing home facility where people are confined in rooms or beds and there's a ratio of one to ten or one to 15. Here you've got maybe somebody that is in need to go downtown to get to do a message and that stimulus is very important to them and that opportunity for them to get out and engage with the community and have that independence...'. (Family member, technology-enriched supported accommodation; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2021, p. 19) – person-centred support/care, good staff ratios</p> <p>'If you've got someone with dementia yeah, we will promote independence and I think that's what we need to focus to promote it, but it's not that "Oh if she's here let's expect her to be independent" because that's not how it works. They sometimes can do only small things – let them do those small things, if they cannot do the big ones help them and let's see how we go' – (Formal caregiver, extra-care housing; Evans et al., 2020, p. 1.497) – person-centred support/care</p>	<p>People with dementia: (Evans et al., 2020; Evans & Means, 2006; Stewart-Archer et al., 2016)</p> <p>Supporters: (Cameron et al., 2020; Evans & Means, 2006; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2021)</p> <p>Health and Social Care Professionals: (Aud, 2002, 2004; Barrett et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2019, 2020; Evans & Means, 2006; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020)</p>

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TABLE 3 (Continued)

Overarching Theme	Example Codes	Example Data Extracts/Code(s) Assigned	Articles/Participant Groups Contributing to Theme
Subtheme 2			
Social Relationships	<p>Facilitators of independence and autonomy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relationships with: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Family/friends Other residents Staff Involvement in social activities <p>Barriers to independence and autonomy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social isolation/loneliness Stigma/prejudice from other residents Lack of funding/staff to organise activities Deteriorating health 	<p>'I used to go and meet up with four friends of a Wednesday and have a coffee and hour in town when I was capable, and I used to have – that's with four of my friends – and then another couple of my neighbours we used to have a taxi once or twice a week and go into town regularly and do our shopping. And I miss that' (Person with dementia, extra-care housing; Evans et al., 2020, p. 1,500) – relationships with family/friends, social isolation/loneliness, deteriorating health</p> <p>Equally, the social aspect of the facility in terms of activities and encouragement of social life (outside and within the facility) and relationships was also praised by the participants:</p> <p>'But then she's made friends here, too. Which is good, because if she was at home accommodation; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2021, p. 21) – relationships with other family/friends/other residents, involvement in social activities</p> <p>Pressures on staff time were identified by several interviewees as a barrier to supporting connections with nature... one extra care housing manager had no dedicated activity staff and a lack of time and funding for care staff to support nature-based activities. (Housing manager, extra-care housing; Evans et al., 2019, p. 148) – lack of funding/staff to organise activities</p>	<p>People with dementia: (Evans et al., 2019, 2020)</p> <p>Supporters: (Cameron et al., 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2021)</p> <p>Health and Social Care Professionals: (Aud, 2002, 2004; Barrett et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2019, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020)</p>
Subtheme 3			
The Physical Environment	<p>Facilitators of independence and autonomy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dementia friendly design <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Signage Colour contrast Space Good location within the community <p>Barriers to independence and autonomy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assistive technology <p>Large buildings</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Navigation difficulties Small communal or dining areas Small flats/apartments Poor location within the community Lack of access to amenities Lack of funding/training regarding assistive technology 	<p>The location of a scheme, for example, can restrict opportunities for autonomous activity:</p> <p>'Yes, and try to walk up to the local Co-Op or something like that, but I don't know how far it is. Well, it's not far up the road. I've been in the car and seen it but I don't just know quite how long it would take me so I'm a bit nervous about risking going up there' (Person with dementia, extra-care housing; Evans et al., 2020, p. 1,498) – poor location within the community, lack of access to amenities</p> <p>'...the apartments are well spaced out, they are not cramped and there are good grounds outside... it's within a housing estate... it's just like a wee oasis in the middle of it all' (Family member, technology-enriched supported accommodation; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2021, p. 19) – space, good location within the community</p> <p>'You know, even their push buttons in bathrooms and stuff, they're right beside the toilet and they know to press that so I think it gives them confidence as well to live independently as much as they can, that they can go in and use the toilet by themselves... We don't have to be there all the time... it's about them being able to do the things without us constantly following them' – (Formal caregiver, technology-enriched supported accommodation; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020, p. 2,302) – assistive technology</p>	<p>People with dementia: (Evans et al., 2020; O'Malley et al., 2018)</p> <p>Supporters: (Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2021)</p> <p>Health and Social Care Professionals: (Aud, 2002, 2004; Barrett et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2019; Evans & Means, 2006; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020)</p>

to 'do things' for themselves, related to activities of daily living like self-care, shopping and household management (Aud, 2002, 2004; Evans et al., 2020; Evans & Means, 2006; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020, 2021; Stewart-Archer et al., 2016). Terms like autonomy, control, choice and self-determination focussed on the freedom of choosing how, where and who people with dementia spent their time – in addition to choosing the level of support required to live independently (Barrett et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2020; Evans & Means, 2006; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020, 2021; Stewart-Archer et al., 2016).

Despite this, articles frequently described barriers to maintaining independence and autonomy, suggesting that these 'ideals' are not always evident in practice (Evans et al., 2019, 2020; Stewart-Archer et al., 2016). The three subthemes of Support and Care, Social Relationships and The Physical Environment highlight barriers and facilitators to maintaining the independence and autonomy of people with dementia living in supported housing and form the remainder of the thematic synthesis.

3.6 | Subtheme 1: Support and care

With regards to providing support or care for people with dementia, adopting a person-centred approach was outlined as key to ensuring that the individual can remain in the supported housing setting for as long as possible (Cameron et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2020; Evans & Means, 2006; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020, 2021). A flexible, person-centred approach was described as essential for enabling people with dementia to maintain their independence and autonomy, discussed by the following care manager working in extra-care housing:

Extra care for people living with dementia is a great concept. It's a great way to keep people living independently for that little bit longer, if possible. However, it really does come with its challenges to be able to be flexible like we need to be to support people with dementia. I will say that the team, the care and support workers, are really good in that they know their clients so well. If they do go to somebody who that particular day doesn't want to go to bed, they're very good at working together to say, 'Gertrude is looking like she wants to go to bed in the communal room. Let's swap this with Gertrude. Let's move Isabella to her time' (Evans et al., 2020, p. 1501).

However, articles highlighted the need for specific staff training to support person-centred care (Cameron et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2020; Evans & Means, 2006; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020). In situations where training was provided, health and social care staff reported attending training sessions on person-centred dementia care approaches and learning from senior staff and other colleagues (Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020).

Although there was evidence that person-centred care could facilitate the maintenance of independence and autonomy for people with dementia, articles highlighted barriers to delivering adequate and meaningful person-centred care. These included low staff ratios, lack of appropriate funding, a lack of training or understanding of dementia and costs of delivering care (Aud, 2002, 2004; Cameron et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2019, 2020; Evans & Means, 2006; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020). Issues with staff ratios were discussed by a family member of a person with dementia living in technology-enriched supported accommodation:

I know there are times where they're short staffed and they don't have the time, really, and stuff like that. I think there have been problems when they don't have the full squad in. (Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2021, p. 20).

Lack of understanding and training, negative attitudes towards people with dementia and funding pressures also lead to people with dementia being managed or referred out of supporting housing settings according to the literature (Aud, 2002, 2004; Evans et al., 2020; Evans & Means, 2006). In the article by Aud (2002), an administrator spoke of managing the support people with dementia received by charging people for additional support with activities of daily living:

So mainly for the dependent people sometimes like we'll do eye drops or we'll do dressings for them for a limited period of time and you know there's a time factor there. And sometimes we don't charge and sometimes we do charge them. The main thing, main reason we charge is to try to limit. Not that we want to make money, but to try to limit (Aud, 2002, p. 74).

In many instances, it appeared that an over-emphasis on being able to live independently with minimal support, rather than meeting the increasing needs of people with dementia to maximise their independence and autonomy, led to many reports of people with dementia moving into residential care or nursing home settings (Aud, 2002, 2004; Cameron et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2020; Evans & Means, 2006).

The literature suggests that barriers to person-centred care often result in a risk-averse approach to supporting people with dementia, which is in contrast with the rights-based approaches to housing, support and care emphasised in policy (Aud, 2002, 2004; Barrett et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2020; Evans & Means, 2006). This is often related to finding a 'balance' between safety and independence, with safety issues relating to falls, misuse of household items or becoming lost when leaving the settings (Aud, 2002, 2004; Barrett et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2020; Evans & Means, 2006). Articles acknowledged the importance of independence and autonomy, yet an over-emphasis on ensuring the safety of people with dementia and minimising risk often led to restrictions on independence and autonomy (Barrett et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2020; Evans & Means, 2006; Stewart-Archer et al., 2016), as

discussed by the following person living with dementia in supportive seniors' housing:

I want to do more. Not allowed to do much by neither staff nor family. They do it all for you... right down to doing your laundry and putting my photos where they want them. I did this all for years and years (Stewart-Archer et al., 2016, p. 1722).

It was suggested that instances of 'risky' or 'unsafe' behaviours were often rare occurrences (Barrett et al., 2020; Evans & Means, 2006), with risk-averse approaches informed by 'anxiety' experienced by health and social care professionals (Evans & Means, 2006). A person-centred approach to managing risk was emphasised as a facilitator of independence and autonomy (Evans & Means, 2006; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020), though settings often lacked appropriate policies or training to implement this in practice (Barrett et al., 2020; Evans & Means, 2006).

There was some evidence to suggest that people with dementia could defer entry into residential care in supported housing settings that utilised a flexible, person-centred approach with a good staffing ratio and dementia-specific training. However, the literature highlights that where person-centred care was not facilitated in the settings, the ideals of maintaining independence and autonomy could not be delivered.

3.7 | Subtheme 2: Social relationships

The literature emphasised the importance of facilitating relationships between people with dementia and their family members or friends, other residents and health and social care staff working within the settings. Facilitating relationships, providing opportunities for social interaction and promoting choice regarding who people with dementia spend their time with, was linked to maintaining independence and autonomy.

Family members and health and social care professionals believed that the supported housing model had advantages over residential care settings, by facilitating familial relationships and enabling family members to adopt caregiving responsibilities (Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020, 2021). Adopting caregiving responsibilities was valued by health and social care staff, as this alleviated pressure caused by low staffing ratios and helped ensure the needs of the person with dementia were met (Aud, 2002, 2004; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020).

In some instances, supported housing was viewed as having fewer restrictions on independence and autonomy, e.g. not operating with highly structured mealtimes or care plans, which might be evident in residential care (Evans et al., 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020, 2021). In this context, supported housing was described as a facilitator of family involvement and inclusivity (Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020, 2021). However, apparent barriers to maintaining family relationships related to the small size of some flats, meaning that

family members could not stay overnight in the setting, contributing to feelings of loneliness and isolation (Evans et al., 2020).

Relationships between people with dementia and other residents focussed mainly on engagement in social activities, which provided opportunities for social interaction (Cameron et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2019, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020, 2021). Activities involved walking, outdoor fayres, tapestry, dominoes, bingo and mindfulness, art and music groups (Evans et al., 2019, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020, 2021). The development of positive relationships with other residents was discussed by people with dementia (Evans et al., 2020), and supporters and health and social care professionals believed that providing opportunities for independent and autonomous engagement in social activities limited social isolation (Evans et al., 2019, 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2021). A person with dementia living in extra-care housing discusses their involvement in social activities:

Yes, we play dominoes and bingo and [pause] I'm doing some tapestry at the moment and knitting squares for a blanket. Yes, yeah. And that was one of the things I really wanted to come for, to join in with the activities (Evans et al., 2020, p. 1499).

One article reported that in settings with 'good dementia awareness', other residents would take an active role in supporting people with dementia, e.g. helping them return to their flat if they become lost (Barrett et al., 2020). Though in other instances, residents who did not have dementia held stigmatising or prejudiced views towards those living with dementia, linked to poor understanding or awareness of the condition (Cameron et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2020), outlined in the following authors' interpretation.

Our findings also suggest that despite increasing awareness of dementia, there is still considerable stigma and prejudice amongst other residents. There was some evidence of a lack of understanding about dementia on the part of residents across all four schemes that took part in the study (Evans et al., 2020, pp. 1498-1499).

This meant that, in some instances, residents without dementia reported not interacting with or speaking to people with dementia, which contributed to social isolation and fewer opportunities for social interaction (Cameron et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2020). Other barriers to forming social relationships with other residents related to people with dementia becoming isolated in their flat due to poor physical health or limited staff capacity to run activity groups (Evans et al., 2019, 2020). This contributed to limited opportunities for independent and autonomous engagement in the settings (Evans et al., 2020).

Relationships between people with dementia and health and social care staff were often functionally driven, focussed on the provision of support or care and meeting the needs of people

with dementia (Aud, 2002; Barrett et al., 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020, 2021). However, health and social care staff reported engaging in informal chatting and spending time with people with dementia, in more socially driven interactions, outlined in the following quote from a formal caregiver:

...there's the support and the girls, the staff go in and out for a short space of time and do what they need to do. And then if they want to have a chat or sit down, they'll sit and have a chat with you, but if they don't, then just go out again. (Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020, p. 2297).

This was linked to the flexible, person-centred approach to care that some supported housing settings offered, meaning that social relationships could be developed rather than always focussing on the functional aspects of support or care provision (Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020). However, barriers to forming these relationships related to an over-emphasis on 'task-oriented' duties and low staff ratios, which limited opportunities for social interaction (Evans et al., 2020; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020).

3.8 | Subtheme 3: The physical environment

The internal and external physical environments of the supported housing settings and their location within the local community were described as either barriers or facilitators to maintaining the independence and autonomy of people with dementia.

Throughout, the design of the interior of the supported housing settings was discussed (Barrett et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2019, 2020; O'Malley et al., 2018; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020, 2021). An evident barrier to independence and autonomy was the overall size of the supported housing settings, with larger settings having similar corridors on all floors requiring the use of lifts or stairs to reach higher levels, which created navigation difficulties (O'Malley et al., 2018), outlined in the following quote from a person living with dementia:

I really think that was badly designed because they do have a long way to come, you know two lifts to have to use. Or two flights of stairs or whatever but not for me because as I say I'm well placed (O'Malley et al., 2018, p. 1803).

Strategies to aid independent navigation included hanging familiar photographs at the end of corridors, use of signage, colour contrast, spacious flats and corridors, with frequent seating areas throughout communal areas (Barrett et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2020; O'Malley et al., 2018; Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2021). These features are indicative of dementia-friendly design guidelines, however, possible barriers to their implementation related to the prospect of making the setting look 'institutional' or

unappealing to potential residents and funding limitations (Evans et al., 2020).

Additionally, small communal and dining areas were an evident barrier to social interaction and engagement in social activities (Evans et al., 2019, 2020). In one dementia-specific setting, small dining areas meant that mealtimes had to be staggered due to a lack of seating, meaning that many residents could not eat together (Evans et al., 2020). The dementia-specific setting also had no access to a café, hairdresser or shop on-site, whereas the non-dementia-specific settings did – again, linked to reduced opportunities for social interaction and independent or autonomous engagement in activities (Evans et al., 2020).

As supported housing aims to promote an open, independent environment, the immediate external environment of the settings (gardens, patios, outdoor communal areas) and the physical location of the settings within the wider community (links to shops, closeness to roads, connections to nature) were frequently discussed (Aud, 2002, 2004; Barrett et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2019, 2020). A good location enabled people with dementia to engage independently with their local community, discussed in the following quote from a formal caregiver:

Some of the tenants just go out shopping, they go to church, they do everything that they would've done in their own home; but they're assessed to see how safe they're on the road. That's an important assessment because you don't want to, this is not, you know, this is just supported housing, so we want them to enjoy life and not to be feeling enclosed (Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020, p. 2298).

In other instances, the physical location of the setting was a barrier to engaging with the local community. This was largely due to limited access to amenities and the proximity to busy roads, leading to a loss of independence and autonomy (Aud, 2004; Barrett et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2020).

Assistive technologies, when used in a non-restrictive, unobtrusive way, could also facilitate independence and privacy (Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020), potentially combating the 'risk-averse' approaches to support and care discussed previously. Assistive technologies included alarm systems, sensors, lifestyle monitoring devices, CCTV, mobile phones and telecare (Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020). When used positively, the assistive technology alerted staff to falls or accidents within the home, while enabling the resident to live otherwise independently, highlighted in the following authors' interpretation:

...assistive technology enabled formal carers to monitor the execution of simple tasks like making cups of tea or cooking snacks, so that accidents could be prevented while still allowing the person to do things for themselves when they wanted (Rondon-Sulbaran et al., 2020, p. 2301).

The use of assistive technology varied throughout the literature, with low uptake and ineffectual use linked to lack of staff knowledge and funding (Barrett et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2020; Evans & Means, 2006).

4 | DISCUSSION

Drawing from an international evidence base, the present systematic review and thematic synthesis aimed to understand how living in supported housing influences the lives of people with dementia, from the perspectives of people with dementia, their supporters, health and social care professionals. One overarching theme was generated, Maintaining Independence and Autonomy, divided into three subthemes – Support and Care, Social Relationships and the Physical Environment.

The reviewed literature included multiple supported housing types, including extra-care housing, assisted living, supported accommodation, etc. However, the common aim of these settings was to promote the independence and autonomy of the residents. In previous literatures, supported housing has been described as a potential way to support people with dementia to live independently in the community for longer (Brooker et al., 2011; Brown et al., 2017; Dutton, 2009; Fleming et al., 2020; Twyford, 2016). However, the evidence presented in this systematic review shows that a diagnosis of dementia may become a barrier to living independently and autonomously in supported housing, with people referred out of the settings as their condition progressed and care needs increased. A lack of resources, including low staff numbers, limited/no staff training in dementia and dementia care and limitations in the physical environment appeared to be the main reasons for this. Similar findings have been reported in previous reviews (e.g. Brown et al., 2017; Dutton, 2009), discussion papers (Dutton, 2010), and in quantitative research conducted in supported housing settings (e.g. Brooker et al., 2009; Twyford, 2016; Verbeek et al., 2019). These studies questioned if supported housing settings have the resources to support or care for people with dementia beyond the milder stages of the condition.

The international dementia policy imperative emphasises that people with dementia should be enabled to live independently at home or in a homely setting for as long they wish (Alzheimer Europe, 2018), with access to appropriate housing, health and social care defined as a human right for people with dementia (United Nations, 2006; World Health Organization, 2015, 2017). This review suggests that even in housing settings offering integrated support and care, these policy ideals may not reflect the experience of supported housing residents living with dementia. To meet these policy ideals, it is imperative that housing organisations are provided with adequate funding and resources so that support and care can be configured in a way that meets the complex and changing needs of people with dementia.

4.1 | Limitations in the evidence base

An aim of this review was to explore the experience of living in supported housing from the perspectives of people with dementia and their supporters. However, the research reviewed does not adequately present the voice of these groups, with most articles presenting the views of health and social care staff. People with dementia and their supporters were often a subsample of the participants in the included articles, meaning that the amount of relevant data extracted was often limited. Of note, there was limited evidence regarding what independence and autonomy meant from the perspectives of people with dementia and their supporters, with most data on these concepts collected from health and social care professionals. There was also limited evidence from people with dementia on the care or support received within the settings, their engagement in the social aspects of the settings and their perspectives on the environmental design. There was limited evidence on the perspectives of people with dementia living in dementia-specific supported housing and settings offering a low level of support, such as sheltered or retirement housing. Future research should explore ways to involve people with dementia and their supporters to express their views.

A further limitation in the evidence base was the overall sparsity of research in the area. Only eleven articles were identified for inclusion in the systematic review. The included articles were conducted in the United Kingdom and North America, meaning that the findings are reflective of those living in these regions. Additionally, segmented publication was evident in articles based on the ECHO study, with five articles uncovered in the systematic search based on the same data (Cameron et al., 2019; Cameron, Johnson & Evans, 2020; Cameron, Johnson, Evans, Lloyd et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2020; Johnson et al., 2020). This could potentially distort the findings of the review (Šupak Smolčić, 2013), but an effort was made to include the articles of greatest relevance to dementia.

4.2 | Methodological limitations

Initially, the review aimed to include unpublished literature. Throughout the review process, it was evident that unpublished reports did not document formal research processes and lacked sufficient detail regarding methodology, recruitment, data collection and analysis. Given the limited volume and quality of some of the included peer-reviewed articles, the reviewers opted to exclude unpublished research from the thematic synthesis to limit any additional bias. Instead, authors of the unpublished articles were contacted to determine if their findings had been published in a peer-reviewed journal. The review only included articles written in English, meaning that some articles of relevance to the review may have been missed.

4.3 | Implications and conclusions

As dementia progresses, it is inevitable that the individual's care and support needs will change (Brown et al., 2020). In terms of housing and support, there is a need to respond to these changes to prevent unnecessary moves out of settings deemed appropriate. Although the literature suggests that supported housing can be a suitable housing option for people with dementia (e.g. Fleming et al., 2020), the findings of this review suggest that we are failing to meet the needs of many people living with dementia in supported housing settings.

Future research on supported housing should strive to include the perspectives of people with dementia and their supporters, to better understand how supported housing can facilitate access to health and social care, promote social relationships and community connections and provide dementia-friendly environments that promote the independence, autonomy and well-being of those living with dementia.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

MS created the search strategy and protocol, reviewed by MB, LR, CP and DT. MS conducted all searches and reference management. MS, MB, LR and CP conducted all screening. MS conducted critical appraisals and data extraction, reviewed by MB, LR, DT and CP. MS conducted initial thematic synthesis, refined by LR, MB, DT and CP. Write-up and revisions completed by MS, LR, MB, DT and CP.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data are available on request from authors.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information may be found in the online version of the article at the publisher's website.

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Appendix 2: Systematic Review Search Strategies

MEDLINE Search Strategy (Developed in EBSCOhost) – Conducted 31 July 2021.

Limiters - Scholarly (Peer Reviewed) Journals; Date of Publication: 1st January 2000 – 31st July 2021; English

Language; Human; Age Related: 45 + years.

Search modes - Boolean/Phrase.

Abbreviations: MH = Exact Subject Heading (MeSH 2020), AB = Abstract, TI = Title, TX = All Text.

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
Supported housing	1	(MH "Assisted Living Facilities") OR (MH "Housing for the Elderly") OR (MH "Independent Living")	8,378
	2	AB ("supported hous*" OR "supportive hous*" OR "supported living" OR "supportive living" OR "supported accommodation" OR "supportive accommodation" OR "extra care" OR "extra-care" OR ExtraCare OR sheltered OR "medium dependency" OR "congregate hous*" OR "adult foster" OR "assisted living" OR "assisted-living" OR "retirement hous*" OR "retirement home" OR "retirement village" OR "retirement accommodation" OR "retirement communit*" OR "clustered hous*" OR "close care" OR "close-care" OR "continuing care" OR "easy care" OR "easy-care" OR "inclusive hous*" OR "shared hous*" OR "shared-hous*" OR cohousing OR "co-housing" OR "cooperative hous*" OR "co-operative hous*" OR "small scale" OR "small-scale" OR "independent living" OR "independent hous*" OR "independent accommodation" OR "domiciliary care" OR "specialist hous*" OR "housing with care" OR "senior hous*" OR "enhanced care" OR "communal hous*" OR "communal living" OR "intermediate care" OR "intermediate-care" OR "collaborative hous*" OR "collaborative living" OR "collaborative accommodation" OR "grouped hous*" OR "group home" OR "group hous*" OR "group living" OR "group-living" OR "housing association*" OR "enriched hous*" OR "housing and support" OR "green hous*" OR "alternative care" OR "community-dwelling" OR "community dwelling" OR "community hous*" OR "housing support" OR "aging in place" OR "ageing in place") OR TI ("supported hous*" OR "supportive hous*" OR "supported living" OR "supportive living" OR "supported accommodation" OR "supportive accommodation" OR "extra care" OR "extra-care" OR ExtraCare OR sheltered OR "medium dependency" OR "congregate hous*" OR "adult foster" OR "assisted living" OR "assisted-living" OR "retirement hous*" OR "retirement home" OR "retirement village" OR "retirement accommodation" OR "retirement	25,816

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
		communit*" OR "clustered hous*" OR "close care" OR "close-care" OR "continuing care" OR "easy care" OR "easy-care" OR "inclusive hous*" OR "shared hous*" OR "shared-hous*" OR cohousing OR "co-housing" OR "cooperative hous*" OR "co-operative hous*" OR "small scale" OR "small-scale" OR "independent living" OR "independent hous*" OR "independent accommodation" OR "domiciliary care" OR "specialist hous*" OR "housing with care" OR "senior hous*" OR "enhanced care" OR "communal hous*" OR "communal living" OR "intermediate care" OR "intermediate-care" OR "collaborative hous*" OR "collaborative living" OR "collaborative accommodation" OR "grouped hous*" OR "group home" OR "group hous*" OR "group living" OR "group-living" OR "housing association*" OR "enriched hous*" OR "housing and support" OR "green hous*" OR "alternative care" OR "community-dwelling" OR "community dwelling" OR "community hous*" OR "housing support" OR "aging in place" OR "ageing in place")	
	3	1 OR 2	28,173
Study methodology	4	(MH "Qualitative Research+") OR (MH "Interviews as Topic") OR (MH "Focus Groups")	52,474
	5	AB (qualitative OR delphi OR "mixed method*" OR "mixed-method*" OR "multi method*" OR "multi-method*" OR IPA OR "thematic analysis" OR "grounded theory" OR "content analysis" OR discours* OR phenomeno* OR "conjoint analysis" OR interview OR "focus group" OR "semi structured" OR "semi-structured" OR unstructured OR informal OR "in depth" OR "in-depth" OR fieldwork OR "field-work" OR observation* OR narrative OR "case stud*" OR "case-stud*" OR intervention* OR "nominal group" OR consensus OR poll OR conversation OR ethno* OR framework OR constructivis* OR constructionis* OR positivis* OR realism OR realist OR relativis* OR discussion OR interpersonal OR attitud* OR explor*) OR TI (qualitative OR delphi OR "mixed method*" OR "mixed-method*" OR "multi method*" OR "multi-method*" OR IPA OR "thematic analysis" OR "grounded theory" OR "content analysis" OR discours* OR phenomeno* OR "conjoint analysis" OR interview OR "focus group" OR "semi structured" OR "semi-structured" OR unstructured OR informal OR "in depth" OR "in-depth" OR fieldwork OR "field-work" OR observation* OR narrative OR "case stud*" OR "case-stud*" OR intervention* OR "nominal group" OR consensus OR poll OR conversation OR ethno* OR framework OR constructivis* OR constructionis* OR positivis* OR realism OR realist OR relativis* OR discussion OR interpersonal OR attitud* OR explor*)	606,818
	6	4 OR 5	613,031

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
Dementia	7	(MH "Dementia+") OR (MH "Frontotemporal Dementia+") OR (MH "Dementia, Vascular+") OR (MH "Alzheimer Disease") OR (MH "Lewy Body Disease") OR (MH "Mental Status and Dementia Tests+")	60,103
	8	TX (dement* OR alzheimer* OR "mild cognitive impairment" OR MCI OR FTD OR DLB OR LBD OR "Lewy bod*")	89,865
	9	7 OR 8	93,933
Symptoms, experiences, and outcomes	10	(MH "Cognition+") OR (MH "Memory+") OR (MH "Executive Function") OR (MH "Orientation+") OR (MH "Thinking+")	95,075
	11	TX (cognit* OR memor* OR language OR communicat* OR judgment OR judgement OR insight OR neuro* OR orientation OR sight OR spatial OR navigat* OR aphasia OR ataxia OR visual)	734,834
	12	(MH "Activities of Daily Living+")	50,685
	13	TX (activit* OR ADL OR BADL OR IADL OR hobb* OR function* OR depend* OR independ* OR autonomy OR "self efficacy" OR "self-efficacy" OR confiden* OR esteem OR driv* OR mobility OR work OR shopp* OR cooking OR financ* OR transport* OR washing OR dressing OR employ* OR abilit* OR motor OR incontinen* OR wander* OR frail* OR exerci* OR lifestyl* OR physical)	1,478,939
	14	(MH "Social Isolation+") OR (MH "Social Support+")	27,433
	15	TX (social OR isolat* OR carer OR caregiv* OR famil* OR relationship* OR suppor* OR stigma OR engag* OR contact OR belong* OR connect* OR network* OR lone* OR alone OR stereotyp* OR comfort* OR safe* OR neglect* OR burden)	1,277,702
	16	(MH "Built Environment") OR (MH "Environment Design+") OR (MH "Social Environment+")	31,070
	17	TX (environment* OR nature)	160,289
	18	(MH "Psychology+") OR (MH "Behavior+") OR (MH "Neurology+") OR (MH "Psychiatry+")	369,910
	19	TX (behavio* OR "mental health" OR identity OR personality OR apathy OR sleep OR psych* OR mood OR emotion* OR distress* OR anxi* OR delir* OR depress* OR attach* OR hallucinat* OR stress OR coping OR dysphoria OR delusion* OR dysfunction* OR aggressi* OR confus*)	833,544
	20	(MH "Quality of Life") OR (MH "Quality-Adjusted Life Years")	103,624
	21	TX ("quality of life" OR qol OR wellbeing OR "well-being" OR "quality-adjusted life year*" OR qaly* OR hrqol)	137,441
22	(MH "Delivery of Health Care+")	250,958	

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
	23	TX (treatment OR servic* OR healthcare OR "health care" OR "social care" OR outcom* OR assess* OR treat* OR comorbid* OR symptom*)	2,087,675
	24	TX (experienc* OR belief* OR perspective* OR meaning OR influence OR impact)	663,958
	25	10 OR 11 OR 12 OR 13 OR 14 OR 15 OR 16 OR 17 OR 18 OR 19 OR 20 OR 21 OR 22 OR 23 OR 24	2,774,531
Final search	26	3 AND 6 AND 9 AND 25	2,005

CINAHL Search Strategy (Developed in EBSCOhost) – Conducted 31 July 2021.

Limiters - Published Date: 1st January 2000 – 31st July 2021; English Language; Peer Reviewed; Exclude

MEDLINE records; Human; Language: English; Age Groups: All Adult.

Search modes - Boolean/Phrase.

Abbreviations: MH = Exact Subject Heading, AB = Abstract, TI = Title, TX = All Text.

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
Supported housing	1	(MH "Assisted Living") OR (MH "Housing for the Elderly") OR (MH "Community Living+")	6,941
	2	AB ("supported hous*" OR "supportive hous*" OR "supported living" OR "supportive living" OR "supported accommodation" OR "supportive accommodation" OR "extra care" OR "extra-care" OR ExtraCare OR sheltered OR "medium dependency" OR "congregate hous*" OR "adult foster" OR "assisted living" OR "assisted-living" OR "retirement hous*" OR "retirement home" OR "retirement village" OR "retirement accommodation" OR "retirement communit*" OR "clustered hous*" OR "close care" OR "close-care" OR "continuing care" OR "easy care" OR "easy-care" OR "inclusive hous*" OR "shared hous*" OR "shared-hous*" OR cohousing OR "co-housing" OR "cooperative hous*" OR "co-operative hous*" OR "small scale" OR "small-scale" OR "independent living" OR "independent hous*" OR "independent accommodation" OR "domiciliary care" OR "specialist hous*" OR "housing with care" OR "senior hous*" OR "enhanced care" OR "communal hous*" OR "communal living" OR "intermediate care" OR "intermediate-care" OR "collaborative hous*" OR "collaborative living" OR "collaborative accommodation" OR "grouped hous*" OR "group home" OR "group hous*" OR "group living" OR "group-living" OR "housing association*" OR "enriched hous*" OR "housing and support" OR "green hous*" OR "alternative care" OR "community-dwelling" OR "community dwelling" OR "community hous*" OR "housing support" OR "aging in place" OR "ageing in place") OR TI ("supported hous*" OR "supportive hous*" OR "supported living" OR "supportive living" OR "supported accommodation" OR "supportive accommodation" OR "extra care" OR "extra-care" OR ExtraCare OR sheltered OR "medium dependency" OR "congregate hous*" OR "adult foster" OR "assisted living" OR "assisted-living" OR "retirement hous*" OR "retirement home" OR "retirement village" OR "retirement accommodation" OR "retirement communit*" OR "clustered hous*" OR "close care" OR "close-care" OR "continuing care" OR "easy care" OR "easy-care" OR "inclusive hous*" OR "shared hous*" OR "shared-hous*" OR	7,246

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
		cohousing OR "co-housing" OR "cooperative hous*" OR "co-operative hous*" OR "small scale" OR "small-scale" OR "independent living" OR "independent hous*" OR "independent accommodation" OR "domiciliary care" OR "specialist hous*" OR "housing with care" OR "senior hous*" OR "enhanced care" OR "communal hous*" OR "communal living" OR "intermediate care" OR "intermediate-care" OR "collaborative hous*" OR "collaborative living" OR "collaborative accommodation" OR "grouped hous*" OR "group home" OR "group hous*" OR "group living" OR "group-living" OR "housing association*" OR "enriched hous*" OR "housing and support" OR "green hous*" OR "alternative care" OR "community-dwelling" OR "community dwelling" OR "community hous*" OR "housing support" OR "aging in place" OR "ageing in place")	
	3	1 OR 2	9,901
	4	(MH "Qualitative Studies+") OR (MH "Interviews+") OR (MH "Focus Groups")	57,930
	5	AB (qualitative OR delphi OR "mixed method*" OR "mixed-method*" OR "multi method*" OR "multi-method*" OR IPA OR "thematic analysis" OR "grounded theory" OR "content analysis" OR discours* OR phenomeno* OR "conjoint analysis" OR interview OR "focus group" OR "semi structured" OR "semi-structured" OR unstructured OR informal OR "in depth" OR "in-depth" OR fieldwork OR "field-work" OR observation* OR narrative OR "case stud*" OR "case-stud*" OR intervention* OR "nominal group" OR consensus OR poll OR conversation OR ethno* OR framework OR constructivis* OR constructionis* OR positivis* OR realism OR realist OR relativis* OR discussion OR interpersonal OR attitud* OR explor*) OR TI (qualitative OR delphi OR "mixed method*" OR "mixed-method*" OR "multi method*" OR "multi-method*" OR IPA OR "thematic analysis" OR "grounded theory" OR "content analysis" OR discours* OR phenomeno* OR "conjoint analysis" OR interview OR "focus group" OR "semi structured" OR "semi-structured" OR unstructured OR informal OR "in depth" OR "in-depth" OR fieldwork OR "field-work" OR observation* OR narrative OR "case stud*" OR "case-stud*" OR intervention* OR "nominal group" OR consensus OR poll OR conversation OR ethno* OR framework OR constructivis* OR constructionis* OR positivis* OR realism OR realist OR relativis* OR discussion OR interpersonal OR attitud* OR explor*)	121,948
	6	4 OR 5	136,611
Dementia	7	(MH "Dementia+") OR (MH "Parkinsonian Disorders+") OR (MH "Alzheimer's Disease") OR (MH "Dementia, Vascular+")	6,800

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
	8	TX (dement* OR alzheimer* OR "mild cognitive impairment" OR MCI OR FTD OR DLB OR LBD OR "Lewy bod*")	13,221
	9	7 OR 8	14,402
Symptoms, experiences, and outcomes	10	(MH "Cognition+") OR (MH "Memory+") OR (MH "Executive Function") OR (MH "Orientation+") OR (MH "Thinking+")	20,691
	11	TX (cognit* OR memor* OR language OR communicat* OR judgment OR judgement OR insight OR neuro* OR orientation OR sight OR spatial OR navigat* OR aphasia OR ataxia OR visual)	81,758
	12	(MH "Activities of Daily Living+")	8,398
	13	TX (activit* OR ADL OR BADL OR IADL OR hobb* OR function* OR depend* OR independ* OR autonomy OR "self efficacy" OR "self-efficacy" OR confiden* OR esteem OR driv* OR mobility OR work OR shopp* OR cooking OR financ* OR transport* OR washing OR dressing OR employ* OR abilit* OR motor OR incontinen* OR wander* OR frail* OR exerci* OR lifestyl* OR physical)	188,104
	14	(MH "Social Isolation+") OR (MH "Support, Psychosocial+")	15,055
	15	TX (social OR isolat* OR carer OR caregiv* OR famil* OR relationship* OR suppor* OR stigma OR engag* OR contact OR belong* OR connect* OR network* OR lone* OR alone OR stereotyp* OR comfort* OR safe* OR neglect* OR burden)	164,788
	16	(MH "Built Environment") OR (MH "Social Environment+")	5,819
	17	TX (environment* OR nature)	50,568
	18	(MH "Psychology+") OR (MH "Behavior+") OR (MH "Neurology") OR (MH "Psychiatry+") OR (MH "Geriatrics")	97,469
	19	TX (behavio* OR "mental health" OR identity OR personality OR apathy OR sleep OR psych* OR mood OR emotion* OR distress* OR anxi* OR delir* OR depress* OR attach* OR hallucinat* OR stress OR coping OR dysphoria OR delusion* OR dysfunction* OR aggressi* OR confus*)	144,894
	20	(MH "Quality of Life+") OR (MH "Quality-Adjusted Life Years")	14,891
21	TX ("quality of life" OR qol OR wellbeing OR "well-being" OR "quality-adjusted life year*" OR qaly* OR hrqol)	41,767	
22	(MH "Health Care Delivery+")	19,323	
23	TX (treatment OR servic* OR healthcare OR "health care" OR "social care" OR outcom* OR assess* OR treat* OR comorbid* OR symptom*)	203,445	

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
	24	TX (experienc* OR belief* OR perspective* OR meaning OR influence OR impact)	125,901
	25	10 OR 11 OR 12 OR 13 OR 14 OR 15 OR 16 OR 17 OR 18 OR 19 OR 20 OR 21 OR 22 OR 23 OR 24	271,787
Final search	26	3 AND 6 AND 9 AND 25	953

Health Source: Nursing Search Strategy (Developed in EBSCOhost) – Conducted 31 July 2021.

Limiters - Scholarly (Peer Reviewed) Journals; Published Date: 1st January 2000 – 31st July 2021.

Search modes - Boolean/Phrase.

Abbreviations: DE = Heading or Keyword (Phrase Indexed), AB = Abstract, TI = Title, TX = All Text.

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
Supported housing	1	(DE "CONGREGATE housing") OR (DE "INDEPENDENT living")	3,490
	2	AB ("supported hous*" OR "supportive hous*" OR "supported living" OR "supportive living" OR "supported accommodation" OR "supportive accommodation" OR "extra care" OR "extra-care" OR ExtraCare OR sheltered OR "medium dependency" OR "congregate hous*" OR "adult foster" OR "assisted living" OR "assisted-living" OR "retirement hous*" OR "retirement home" OR "retirement village" OR "retirement accommodation" OR "retirement communit*" OR "clustered hous*" OR "close care" OR "close-care" OR "continuing care" OR "easy care" OR "easy-care" OR "inclusive hous*" OR "shared hous*" OR "shared-hous*" OR cohousing OR "co-housing" OR "cooperative hous*" OR "co-operative hous*" OR "small scale" OR "small-scale" OR "independent living" OR "independent hous*" OR "independent accommodation" OR "domiciliary care" OR "specialist hous*" OR "housing with care" OR "senior hous*" OR "enhanced care" OR "communal hous*" OR "communal living" OR "intermediate care" OR "intermediate-care" OR "collaborative hous*" OR "collaborative living" OR "collaborative accommodation" OR "grouped hous*" OR "group home" OR "group hous*" OR "group living" OR "group-living" OR "housing association*" OR "enriched hous*" OR "housing and support" OR "green hous*" OR "alternative care" OR "community-dwelling" OR "community dwelling" OR "community hous*" OR "housing support" OR "aging in place" OR "ageing in place") OR TI ("supported hous*" OR "supportive hous*" OR "supported living" OR "supportive living" OR "supported accommodation" OR "supportive accommodation" OR "extra care" OR "extra-care" OR ExtraCare OR sheltered OR "medium dependency" OR "congregate hous*" OR "adult foster" OR "assisted living" OR "assisted-living" OR "retirement hous*" OR "retirement home" OR "retirement village" OR "retirement accommodation" OR "retirement communit*" OR "clustered hous*" OR "close care" OR "close-care" OR "continuing care" OR "easy care" OR "easy-care" OR "inclusive hous*" OR "shared hous*" OR "shared-hous*" OR cohousing OR "co-housing" OR "cooperative hous*" OR "co-operative hous*" OR "small scale" OR "small-scale" OR "independent living" OR "independent hous*" OR "independent	10,817

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
		accommodation" OR "domiciliary care" OR "specialist hous*" OR "housing with care" OR "senior hous*" OR "enhanced care" OR "communal hous*" OR "communal living" OR "intermediate care" OR "intermediate-care" OR "collaborative hous*" OR "collaborative living" OR "collaborative accommodation" OR "grouped hous*" OR "group home" OR "group hous*" OR "group living" OR "group-living" OR "housing association*" OR "enriched hous*" OR "housing and support" OR "green hous*" OR "alternative care" OR "community-dwelling" OR "community dwelling" OR "community hous*" OR "housing support" OR "aging in place" OR "ageing in place")	
	3	1 OR 2	12,242
Dementia Study methodology	4	(DE "QUALITATIVE research") OR (DE "CONVERSATION analysis") OR (DE "FOCUS groups") OR (DE "PARTICIPANT observation") OR (DE "PHENOMENOGRAPHY") OR (DE "QUALITATIVE research methodology") OR (DE "CONTENT analysis") OR (DE "MIXED methods research")	34,936
	5	AB (qualitative OR delphi OR "mixed method*" OR "mixed-method*" OR "multi method*" OR "multi-method*" OR IPA OR "thematic analysis" OR "grounded theory" OR "content analysis" OR discours* OR phenomeno* OR "conjoint analysis" OR interview OR "focus group" OR "semi structured" OR "semi-structured" OR unstructured OR informal OR "in depth" OR "in-depth" OR fieldwork OR "field-work" OR observation* OR narrative OR "case stud*" OR "case-stud*" OR intervention* OR "nominal group" OR consensus OR poll OR conversation OR ethno* OR framework OR constructivis* OR constructionis* OR positivis* OR realism OR realist OR relativis* OR discussion OR interpersonal OR attitud* OR explor*) OR TI (qualitative OR delphi OR "mixed method*" OR "mixed-method*" OR "multi method*" OR "multi-method*" OR IPA OR "thematic analysis" OR "grounded theory" OR "content analysis" OR discours* OR phenomeno* OR "conjoint analysis" OR interview OR "focus group" OR "semi structured" OR "semi-structured" OR unstructured OR informal OR "in depth" OR "in-depth" OR fieldwork OR "field-work" OR observation* OR narrative OR "case stud*" OR "case-stud*" OR intervention* OR "nominal group" OR consensus OR poll OR conversation OR ethno* OR framework OR constructivis* OR constructionis* OR positivis* OR realism OR realist OR relativis* OR discussion OR interpersonal OR attitud* OR explor*)	480,216
	6	4 OR 5	482,626
Dementia	7	(DE "DEMENTIA") OR (DE "LEWY body dementia") OR (DE "VASCULAR dementia") OR (DE "ALZHEIMER'S disease")	12,398

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
	8	TX (dement* OR alzheimer* OR "mild cognitive impairment" OR MCI OR FTD OR DLB OR LBD OR "Lewy bod*")	35,899
	9	7 OR 8	35,899
Symptoms, experiences, and outcomes	10	(DE "COGNITION") OR (DE "MEMORY") OR (DE "EXECUTIVE function (Neuropsychology)") OR (DE "ORIENTATION") OR (DE "THOUGHT and thinking")	14,446
	11	TX (cognit* OR memor* OR language OR communicat* OR judgment OR judgement OR insight OR neuro* OR orientation OR sight OR spatial OR navigat* OR aphasia OR ataxia OR visual)	579,961
	12	(DE "ACTIVITIES of daily living")	4,876
	13	TX (activit* OR ADL OR BADL OR IADL OR hobb* OR function* OR depend* OR independ* OR autonomy OR "self efficacy" OR "self-efficacy" OR confiden* OR esteem OR driv* OR mobility OR work OR shopp* OR cooking OR financ* OR transport* OR washing OR dressing OR employ* OR abilit* OR motor OR incontinen* OR wander* OR frail* OR exerci* OR lifestyl* OR physical)	1,120,940
	14	(DE "SOCIAL isolation") OR (DE "SOCIAL support")	17,165
	15	TX (social OR isolat* OR carer OR caregiv* OR famil* OR relationship* OR suppor* OR stigma OR engag* OR contact OR belong* OR connect* OR network* OR lone* OR alone OR stereotyp* OR comfort* OR safe* OR neglect* OR burden)	996,717
	16	(DE "BUILT environment")	367
	17	TX (environment* OR nature)	409,718
	18	(DE "PSYCHOLOGY") OR (DE "BEHAVIOR") OR (DE "NEUROLOGY") OR (DE "PSYCHIATRY") OR (DE "GERONTOLOGY")	36,576
	19	TX (behavio* OR "mental health" OR identity OR personality OR apathy OR sleep OR psych* OR mood OR emotion* OR distress* OR anxi* OR delir* OR depress* OR attach* OR hallucinat* OR stress OR coping OR dysphoria OR delusion* OR dysfunction* OR aggressi* OR confus*)	751,071
	20	(DE "QUALITY of life") OR (DE "QUALITY-adjusted life years")	22,599
21	TX ("quality of life" OR qol OR wellbeing OR "well-being" OR "quality-adjusted life year*" OR qaly* OR hrqol)	123,096	
22	(DE "MEDICAL care")	53,448	
23	TX (treatment OR servic* OR healthcare OR "health care" OR "social care" OR outcom* OR assess* OR treat* OR comorbid* OR symptom*)	1,220,914	

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
	24	TX (experienc* OR belief* OR perspective* OR meaning OR influence OR impact)	622,924
	25	10 OR 11 OR 12 OR 13 OR 14 OR 15 OR 16 OR 17 OR 18 OR 19 OR 20 OR 21 OR 22 OR 23 OR 24	1,784,673
Final search	26	3 AND 6 AND 9 AND 25	818

PsycArticles Search Strategy (Developed in EBSCOhost) – Conducted 31 July 2021.

Limiters - Published Date: 1st January 2000 – 31st July 2021; Scholarly (Peer Reviewed) Journals; Age Groups:

Adulthood (18 yrs and older); Population Group: Human.

Search modes - Boolean/Phrase.

Abbreviations: DE = Heading or Keyword (Phrase Indexed), AB = Abstract, TI = Title, TX = All Text.

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
Supported housing	1	(DE "Assisted Living") OR (DE "Independent Living Programs")	11
	2	AB ("supported hous*" OR "supportive hous*" OR "supported living" OR "supportive living" OR "supported accommodation" OR "supportive accommodation" OR "extra care" OR "extra-care" OR ExtraCare OR sheltered OR "medium dependency" OR "congregate hous*" OR "adult foster" OR "assisted living" OR "assisted-living" OR "retirement hous*" OR "retirement home" OR "retirement village" OR "retirement accommodation" OR "retirement communit*" OR "clustered hous*" OR "close care" OR "close-care" OR "continuing care" OR "easy care" OR "easy-care" OR "inclusive hous*" OR "shared hous*" OR "shared-hous*" OR cohousing OR "co-housing" OR "cooperative hous*" OR "co-operative hous*" OR "small scale" OR "small-scale" OR "independent living" OR "independent hous*" OR "independent accommodation" OR "domiciliary care" OR "specialist hous*" OR "housing with care" OR "senior hous*" OR "enhanced care" OR "communal hous*" OR "communal living" OR "intermediate care" OR "intermediate-care" OR "collaborative hous*" OR "collaborative living" OR "collaborative accommodation" OR "grouped hous*" OR "group home" OR "group hous*" OR "group living" OR "group-living" OR "housing association*" OR "enriched hous*" OR "housing and support" OR "green hous*" OR "alternative care" OR "community-dwelling" OR "community dwelling" OR "community hous*" OR "housing support" OR "aging in place" OR "ageing in place") OR TI ("supported hous*" OR "supportive hous*" OR "supported living" OR "supportive living" OR "supported accommodation" OR "supportive accommodation" OR "extra care" OR "extra-care" OR ExtraCare OR sheltered OR "medium dependency" OR "congregate hous*" OR "adult foster" OR "assisted living" OR "assisted-living" OR "retirement hous*" OR "retirement home" OR "retirement village" OR "retirement accommodation" OR "retirement communit*" OR "clustered hous*" OR "close care" OR "close-care" OR "continuing care" OR "easy care" OR "easy-care" OR "inclusive hous*" OR "shared hous*" OR "shared-hous*" OR cohousing OR "co-housing" OR "cooperative hous*" OR "co-operative hous*" OR "small scale" OR "small-scale" OR	378

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
		"independent living" OR "independent hous*" OR "independent accommodation" OR "domiciliary care" OR "specialist hous*" OR "housing with care" OR "senior hous*" OR "enhanced care" OR "communal hous*" OR "communal living" OR "intermediate care" OR "intermediate-care" OR "collaborative hous*" OR "collaborative living" OR "collaborative accommodation" OR "grouped hous*" OR "group home" OR "group hous*" OR "group living" OR "group-living" OR "housing association*" OR "enriched hous*" OR "housing and support" OR "green hous*" OR "alternative care" OR "community-dwelling" OR "community dwelling" OR "community hous*" OR "housing support" OR "aging in place" OR "ageing in place")	
	3	1 OR 2	382
	4	(DE "Qualitative Methods") OR (DE "Mixed Methods Research") OR (DE "Focus Group") OR (DE "Data Collection") OR (DE "Randomized Controlled Trials")	470
	5	AB (qualitative OR delphi OR "mixed method*" OR "mixed-method*" OR "multi method*" OR "multi-method*" OR IPA OR "thematic analysis" OR "grounded theory" OR "content analysis" OR discours* OR phenomeno* OR "conjoint analysis" OR interview OR "focus group" OR "semi structured" OR "semi-structured" OR unstructured OR informal OR "in depth" OR "in-depth" OR fieldwork OR "field-work" OR observation* OR narrative OR "case stud*" OR "case-stud*" OR intervention* OR "nominal group" OR consensus OR poll OR conversation OR ethno* OR framework OR constructivis* OR constructionis* OR positivis* OR realism OR realist OR relativis* OR discussion OR interpersonal OR attitud* OR explor*) OR TI (qualitative OR delphi OR "mixed method*" OR "mixed-method*" OR "multi method*" OR "multi-method*" OR IPA OR "thematic analysis" OR "grounded theory" OR "content analysis" OR discours* OR phenomeno* OR "conjoint analysis" OR interview OR "focus group" OR "semi structured" OR "semi-structured" OR unstructured OR informal OR "in depth" OR "in-depth" OR fieldwork OR "field-work" OR observation* OR narrative OR "case stud*" OR "case-stud*" OR intervention* OR "nominal group" OR consensus OR poll OR conversation OR ethno* OR framework OR constructivis* OR constructionis* OR positivis* OR realism OR realist OR relativis* OR discussion OR interpersonal OR attitud* OR explor*)	24,860
	6	4 OR 5	25,031
	7	(DE "Dementia") OR (DE "Alzheimer's Disease")	517
	8	TX (dement* OR alzheimer* OR "mild cognitive impairment" OR MCI OR FTD OR DLB OR LBD OR "Lewy bod*")	3,900
Study methodology			
Dementia			

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
	9	7 OR 8	3,900
Symptoms, experiences, and outcomes	10	(DE "Cognition") OR (DE "Memory") OR (DE "Executive Function") OR (DE "Spatial Orientation (Perception)") OR (DE "Thinking")	5,973
	11	TX (cognit* OR memor* OR language OR communicat* OR judgment OR judgement OR insight OR neuro* OR orientation OR sight OR spatial OR navigat* OR aphasia OR ataxia OR visual)	49,205
	12	(DE "Activities of Daily Living")	378
	13	TX (activit* OR ADL OR BADL OR IADL OR hobb* OR function* OR depend* OR independ* OR autonomy OR "self efficacy" OR "self-efficacy" OR confiden* OR esteem OR driv* OR mobility OR work OR shopp* OR cooking OR financ* OR transport* OR washing OR dressing OR employ* OR abilit* OR motor OR incontinen* OR wander* OR frail* OR exerci* OR lifestyl* OR physical)	45,280
	14	(DE "Social Isolation") OR (DE "Social Support")	2,033
	15	TX (social OR isolat* OR carer OR caregiv* OR famil* OR relationship* OR suppor* OR stigma OR engag* OR contact OR belong* OR connect* OR network* OR lone* OR alone OR stereotyp* OR comfort* OR safe* OR neglect* OR burden)	51,920
	16	(DE "Built Environment") OR (DE "Environmental Planning")	16
	17	TX (environment* OR nature)	32,496
	18	(DE "Psychology") OR (DE "Behavior") OR (DE "Neurology") OR (DE "Psychiatry")	1,212
	19	TX (behavio* OR "mental health" OR identity OR personality OR apathy OR sleep OR psych* OR mood OR emotion* OR distress* OR anxi* OR delir* OR depress* OR attach* OR hallucinat* OR stress OR coping OR dysphoria OR delusion* OR dysfunction* OR aggressi* OR confus*)	57,261
	20	(DE "Quality of Life") OR (DE "Health Related Quality of Life")	859
	21	TX ("quality of life" OR qol OR wellbeing OR "well-being" OR "quality-adjusted life year*" OR qaly* OR hrqol)	8,804
	22	(DE "Health Care Delivery")	179
	23	TX (treatment OR servic* OR healthcare OR "health care" OR "social care" OR outcom* OR assess* OR treat* OR comorbid* OR symptom*)	38,988
24	TX (experienc* OR belief* OR perspective* OR meaning OR influence OR impact)	50,672	

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
	25	10 OR 11 OR 12 OR 13 OR 14 OR 15 OR 16 OR 17 OR 18 OR 19 OR 20 OR 21 OR 22 OR 23 OR 24	57,324
Final search	26	3 AND 6 AND 9 AND 25	38

Psychology and Behavioral Sciences Search Strategy (Developed in EBSCOhost) – Conducted

31 July 2021.

Limiters - Peer Reviewed; Published Date: 1st January 2000 – 31st July 2021.

Search modes - Boolean/Phrase.

Abbreviations: DE = Heading or Keyword (Phrase Indexed), AB = Abstract, TI = Title, TX = All Text.

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
Supported housing	1	(DE "CONGREGATE housing") OR (DE "INDEPENDENT living")	1,512
	2	AB ("supported hous*" OR "supportive hous*" OR "supported living" OR "supportive living" OR "supported accommodation" OR "supportive accommodation" OR "extra care" OR "extra-care" OR ExtraCare OR sheltered OR "medium dependency" OR "congregate hous*" OR "adult foster" OR "assisted living" OR "assisted-living" OR "retirement hous*" OR "retirement home" OR "retirement village" OR "retirement accommodation" OR "retirement communit*" OR "clustered hous*" OR "close care" OR "close-care" OR "continuing care" OR "easy care" OR "easy-care" OR "inclusive hous*" OR "shared hous*" OR "shared-hous*" OR cohousing OR "co-housing" OR "cooperative hous*" OR "co-operative hous*" OR "small scale" OR "small-scale" OR "independent living" OR "independent hous*" OR "independent accommodation" OR "domiciliary care" OR "specialist hous*" OR "housing with care" OR "senior hous*" OR "enhanced care" OR "communal hous*" OR "communal living" OR "intermediate care" OR "intermediate-care" OR "collaborative hous*" OR "collaborative living" OR "collaborative accommodation" OR "grouped hous*" OR "group home" OR "group hous*" OR "group living" OR "group-living" OR "housing association*" OR "enriched hous*" OR "housing and support" OR "green hous*" OR "alternative care" OR "community-dwelling" OR "community dwelling" OR "community hous*" OR "housing support" OR "aging in place" OR "ageing in place") OR TI ("supported hous*" OR "supportive hous*" OR "supported living" OR "supportive living" OR "supported accommodation" OR "supportive accommodation" OR "extra care" OR "extra-care" OR ExtraCare OR sheltered OR "medium dependency" OR "congregate hous*" OR "adult foster" OR "assisted living" OR "assisted-living" OR "retirement hous*" OR "retirement home" OR "retirement village" OR "retirement accommodation" OR "retirement communit*" OR "clustered hous*" OR "close care" OR "close-care" OR "continuing care" OR "easy care" OR "easy-care" OR "inclusive hous*" OR "shared hous*" OR "shared-hous*" OR	5,631

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
		cohousing OR "co-housing" OR "cooperative hous*" OR "co-operative hous*" OR "small scale" OR "small-scale" OR "independent living" OR "independent hous*" OR "independent accommodation" OR "domiciliary care" OR "specialist hous*" OR "housing with care" OR "senior hous*" OR "enhanced care" OR "communal hous*" OR "communal living" OR "intermediate care" OR "intermediate-care" OR "collaborative hous*" OR "collaborative living" OR "collaborative accommodation" OR "grouped hous*" OR "group home" OR "group hous*" OR "group living" OR "group-living" OR "housing association*" OR "enriched hous*" OR "housing and support" OR "green hous*" OR "alternative care" OR "community-dwelling" OR "community dwelling" OR "community hous*" OR "housing support" OR "aging in place" OR "ageing in place")	
	3	1 OR 2	6,265
Study methodology	4	(DE "QUALITATIVE research") OR (DE "CONVERSATION analysis") OR (DE "FOCUS groups") OR (DE "PARTICIPANT observation") OR (DE "PHENOMENOGRAPHY") OR (DE "QUALITATIVE research methodology") OR (DE "CONTENT analysis") OR (DE "MIXED methods research")	14,497
	5	TI (qualitative OR delphi OR "mixed method*" OR "mixed-method*" OR "multi method*" OR "multi-method*" OR IPA OR "thematic analysis" OR "grounded theory" OR "content analysis" OR discours* OR phenomeno* OR "conjoint analysis" OR interview OR "focus group" OR "semi structured" OR "semi-structured" OR unstructured OR informal OR "in depth" OR "in-depth" OR fieldwork OR "field-work" OR observation* OR narrative OR "case stud*" OR "case-stud*" OR intervention* OR "nominal group" OR consensus OR poll OR conversation OR ethno* OR framework OR constructivis* OR constructionis* OR positivis* OR realism OR realist OR relativis* OR discussion OR interpersonal OR attitud* OR exploratory) OR AB (qualitative OR delphi OR "mixed method*" OR "mixed-method*" OR "multi method*" OR "multi-method*" OR IPA OR "thematic analysis" OR "grounded theory" OR "content analysis" OR discours* OR phenomeno* OR "conjoint analysis" OR interview OR "focus group" OR "semi structured" OR "semi-structured" OR unstructured OR informal OR "in depth" OR "in-depth" OR fieldwork OR "field-work" OR observation* OR narrative OR "case stud*" OR "case-stud*" OR intervention* OR "nominal group" OR consensus OR poll OR conversation OR ethno* OR framework OR constructivis* OR constructionis* OR positivis* OR realism OR realist OR relativis* OR discussion OR interpersonal OR attitud* OR exploratory)	232,253
	6	4 OR 5	233,534

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
Dementia	7	(DE "DEMENTIA") OR (DE "LEWY body dementia") OR (DE "VASCULAR dementia") OR (DE "ALZHEIMER'S disease")	7,190
	8	TX (dement* OR alzheimer* OR "mild cognitive impairment" OR MCI OR FTD OR DLB OR LBD OR "Lewy bod*")	35,371
	9	7 OR 8	35,371
Symptoms, experiences, and outcomes	10	(DE "COGNITION") OR (DE "MEMORY") OR (DE "EXECUTIVE function (Neuropsychology)") OR (DE "ORIENTATION") OR (DE "THOUGHT and thinking")	22,951
	11	TX (cognit* OR memor* OR language OR communicat* OR judgment OR judgement OR insight OR neuro* OR orientation OR sight OR spatial OR navigat* OR aphasia OR ataxia OR visual)	557,414
	12	(DE "ACTIVITIES of daily living")	2,025
	13	TX (activit* OR ADL OR BADL OR IADL OR hobb* OR function* OR depend* OR independ* OR autonomy OR "self efficacy" OR "self-efficacy" OR confiden* OR esteem OR driv* OR mobility OR work OR shopp* OR cooking OR financ* OR transport* OR washing OR dressing OR employ* OR abilit* OR motor OR incontinen* OR wander* OR frail* OR exerci* OR lifestyle* OR physical)	664,662
	14	(DE "SOCIAL isolation") OR (DE "SOCIAL support")	10,042
	15	TX (social OR isolat* OR carer OR caregiv* OR famil* OR relationship* OR suppor* OR stigma OR engag* OR contact OR belong* OR connect* OR network* OR lone* OR alone OR stereotyp* OR comfort* OR safe* OR neglect* OR burden)	648,720
	16	(DE "BUILT environment")	83
	17	TX (environment* OR nature)	421,187
	18	(DE "PSYCHOLOGY") OR (DE "BEHAVIOR") OR (DE "NEUROLOGY") OR (DE "PSYCHIATRY") OR (DE "GERONTOLOGY")	44,726
	19	TX (behavio* OR "mental health" OR identity OR personality OR apathy OR sleep OR psych* OR mood OR emotion* OR distress* OR anxi* OR delir* OR depress* OR attach* OR hallucinat* OR stress OR coping OR dysphoria OR delusion* OR dysfunction* OR aggressi* OR confus*)	569,078
	20	(DE "QUALITY of life") OR (DE "QUALITY-adjusted life years")	12,480
	21	TX ("quality of life" OR qol OR wellbeing OR "well-being" OR "quality-adjusted life year*" OR qaly* OR hrqol)	133,474
22	TX (treatment OR servic* OR healthcare OR "health care" OR "social care" OR outcom* OR assess* OR treat* OR comorbid* OR symptom*)	631,814	

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
	23	TX (experienc* OR belief* OR perspective* OR meaning OR influence OR impact)	429,289
	24	10 OR 11 OR 12 OR 13 OR 14 OR 15 OR 16 OR 17 OR 18 OR 19 OR 20 OR 21 OR 22 OR 23	841,611
Final search	25	3 AND 6 AND 9 AND 24	573

SocINDEX Search Strategy (Developed in EBSCOhost) – Conducted 31 July 2021.

Limiters - Scholarly (Peer Reviewed) Journals; Date of Publication: 1st January 2000 – 31st July 2021;

Language: English.

Search modes - Boolean/Phrase.

Abbreviations: DE = Heading or Keyword (Phrase Indexed), AB = Abstract, TI = Title, TX = All Text.

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
Supported housing	1	(DE "CONGREGATE housing") OR (DE "INDEPENDENT living")	2,089
	2	AB ("supported hous*" OR "supportive hous*" OR "supported living" OR "supportive living" OR "supported accommodation" OR "supportive accommodation" OR "extra care" OR "extra-care" OR ExtraCare OR sheltered OR "medium dependency" OR "congregate hous*" OR "adult foster" OR "assisted living" OR "assisted-living" OR "retirement hous*" OR "retirement home" OR "retirement village" OR "retirement accommodation" OR "retirement communit*" OR "clustered hous*" OR "close care" OR "close-care" OR "continuing care" OR "easy care" OR "easy-care" OR "inclusive hous*" OR "shared hous*" OR "shared-hous*" OR cohousing OR "co-housing" OR "cooperative hous*" OR "co-operative hous*" OR "small scale" OR "small-scale" OR "independent living" OR "independent hous*" OR "independent accommodation" OR "domiciliary care" OR "specialist hous*" OR "housing with care" OR "senior hous*" OR "enhanced care" OR "communal hous*" OR "communal living" OR "intermediate care" OR "intermediate-care" OR "collaborative hous*" OR "collaborative living" OR "collaborative accommodation" OR "grouped hous*" OR "group home" OR "group hous*" OR "group living" OR "group-living" OR "housing association*" OR "enriched hous*" OR "housing and support" OR "green hous*" OR "alternative care" OR "community-dwelling" OR "community dwelling" OR "community hous*" OR "housing support" OR "aging in place" OR "ageing in place") OR TI ("supported hous*" OR "supportive hous*" OR "supported living" OR "supportive living" OR "supported accommodation" OR "supportive accommodation" OR "extra care" OR "extra-care" OR ExtraCare OR sheltered OR "medium dependency" OR "congregate hous*" OR "adult foster" OR "assisted living" OR "assisted-living" OR "retirement hous*" OR "retirement home" OR "retirement village" OR "retirement accommodation" OR "retirement communit*" OR "clustered hous*" OR "close care" OR "close-care" OR "continuing care" OR "easy care" OR "easy-care" OR "inclusive hous*" OR "shared hous*" OR "shared-hous*" OR cohousing OR "co-housing" OR "cooperative hous*" OR "co-operative hous*" OR "small scale" OR "small-scale" OR	6,881

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
		"independent living" OR "independent hous*" OR "independent accommodation" OR "domiciliary care" OR "specialist hous*" OR "housing with care" OR "senior hous*" OR "enhanced care" OR "communal hous*" OR "communal living" OR "intermediate care" OR "intermediate-care" OR "collaborative hous*" OR "collaborative living" OR "collaborative accommodation" OR "grouped hous*" OR "group home" OR "group hous*" OR "group living" OR "group-living" OR "housing association*" OR "enriched hous*" OR "housing and support" OR "green hous*" OR "alternative care" OR "community-dwelling" OR "community dwelling" OR "community hous*" OR "housing support" OR "aging in place" OR "ageing in place")	
	3	1 OR 2	7,694
Study methodology	4	(DE "QUALITATIVE research") OR (DE "CONVERSATION analysis") OR (DE "FOCUS groups") OR (DE "PARTICIPANT observation") OR (DE "PHENOMENOGRAPHY") OR (DE "QUALITATIVE research methodology") OR (DE "CONTENT analysis") OR (DE "MIXED methods research")	21,442
	5	AB (qualitative OR delphi OR "mixed method*" OR "mixed-method*" OR "multi method*" OR "multi-method*" OR IPA OR "thematic analysis" OR "grounded theory" OR "content analysis" OR discours* OR phenomeno* OR "conjoint analysis" OR interview OR "focus group" OR "semi structured" OR "semi-structured" OR unstructured OR informal OR "in depth" OR "in-depth" OR fieldwork OR "field-work" OR observation* OR narrative OR "case stud*" OR "case-stud*" OR intervention* OR "nominal group" OR consensus OR poll OR conversation OR ethno* OR framework OR constructivis* OR constructionis* OR positivis* OR realism OR realist OR relativis* OR discussion OR interpersonal OR attitud* OR explor*) OR TI (qualitative OR delphi OR "mixed method*" OR "mixed-method*" OR "multi method*" OR "multi-method*" OR IPA OR "thematic analysis" OR "grounded theory" OR "content analysis" OR discours* OR phenomeno* OR "conjoint analysis" OR interview OR "focus group" OR "semi structured" OR "semi-structured" OR unstructured OR informal OR "in depth" OR "in-depth" OR fieldwork OR "field-work" OR observation* OR narrative OR "case stud*" OR "case-stud*" OR intervention* OR "nominal group" OR consensus OR poll OR conversation OR ethno* OR framework OR constructivis* OR constructionis* OR positivis* OR realism OR realist OR relativis* OR discussion OR interpersonal OR attitud* OR explor*)	337,335
	6	4 OR 5	338,996

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
Dementia	7	(DE "DEMENTIA") OR (DE "LEWY body dementia") OR (DE "VASCULAR dementia") OR (DE "ALZHEIMER'S disease")	3,895
	8	TX (dement* OR alzheimer* OR "mild cognitive impairment" OR MCI OR FTD OR DLB OR LBD OR "Lewy bod*")	13,646
	9	7 OR 8	13,646
Symptoms, experiences, and outcomes	10	(DE "COGNITION") OR (DE "MEMORY") OR (DE "EXECUTIVE function (Neuropsychology)") OR (DE "ORIENTATION") OR (DE "THOUGHT and thinking")	8,461
	11	TX (cognit* OR memor* OR language OR communicat* OR judgment OR judgement OR insight OR neuro* OR orientation OR sight OR spatial OR navigat* OR aphasia OR ataxia OR visual)	244,356
	12	(DE "ACTIVITIES of daily living")	1,454
	13	TX (activit* OR ADL OR BADL OR IADL OR hobb* OR function* OR depend* OR independ* OR autonomy OR "self efficacy" OR "self-efficacy" OR confiden* OR esteem OR driv* OR mobility OR work OR shopp* OR cooking OR financ* OR transport* OR washing OR dressing OR employ* OR abilit* OR motor OR incontinen* OR wander* OR frail* OR exerci* OR lifestyle* OR physical)	505,456
	14	(DE "SOCIAL isolation") OR (DE "SOCIAL support")	12,853
	15	TX (social OR isolat* OR carer OR caregiv* OR famil* OR relationship* OR suppor* OR stigma OR engag* OR contact OR belong* OR connect* OR network* OR lone* OR alone OR stereotyp* OR comfort* OR safe* OR neglect* OR burden)	675,507
	16	(DE "BUILT environment")	492
	17	TX (environment* OR nature)	339,034
	18	(DE "PSYCHOLOGY") OR (DE "BEHAVIOR") OR (DE "NEUROLOGY") OR (DE "PSYCHIATRY") OR (DE "GERONTOLOGY")	27,147
	19	TX (behavio* OR "mental health" OR identity OR personality OR apathy OR sleep OR psych* OR mood OR emotion* OR distress* OR anxi* OR delir* OR depress* OR attach* OR hallucinat* OR stress OR coping OR dysphoria OR delusion* OR dysfunction* OR aggressi* OR confus*)	453,243
	20	(DE "QUALITY of life") OR (DE "QUALITY-adjusted life years")	7,226
	21	TX ("quality of life" OR qol OR wellbeing OR "well-being" OR "quality-adjusted life year*" OR qaly* OR hrqol)	58,641
22	(DE "MEDICAL care")	12,536	

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
	23	TX (treatment OR servic* OR healthcare OR "health care" OR "social care" OR outcom* OR assess* OR treat* OR comorbid* OR symptom*)	386,694
	24	TX (experienc* OR belief* OR perspective* OR meaning OR influence OR impact)	451,194
	25	10 OR 11 OR 12 OR 13 OR 14 OR 15 OR 16 OR 17 OR 18 OR 19 OR 20 OR 21 OR 22 OR 23 OR 24	794,176
Final search	26	3 AND 6 AND 9 AND 25	621

Social Care Online Search Strategy – Conducted 31 July 2021.

Limiters: Publication Year: 2000 – 2021.

Note: This search was simplified as the database does not recognise truncations.

Theme	Search	Terms	Results
Supported Housing	1	All Fields ("supported housing" OR "supportive housing" OR "supported living" OR "supportive living" OR "supported accommodation" OR "supportive accommodation" OR "extra care" OR "extra-care" OR "ExtraCare" OR sheltered OR "medium dependency" OR "congregate housing" OR "adult foster" OR "assisted living" OR "assisted-living" OR "retirement housing" OR "retirement home" OR "retirement village" OR "retirement accommodation" OR "retirement community" OR "clustered housing" OR "close care" OR "close-care" OR "continuing care" OR "easy care" OR "easy-care" OR "inclusive housing" OR "shared housing" OR "shared-housing" OR "cohousing" OR "co-housing" OR "cooperative housing" OR "co-operative housing" OR "small scale housing" OR "small-scale housing" OR "independent living" OR "independent housing" OR "independent accommodation" OR "domiciliary care" OR "specialist housing" OR "housing with care" OR "senior housing" OR "housing and care" OR "enhanced care" OR "communal housing" OR "communal living" OR "intermediate care" OR "intermediate-care" OR "collaborative housing" OR "collaborative living" OR "collaborative accommodation" OR "grouped housing" OR "group housing" OR "group home" OR "group living" OR "housing association" OR "continuing care" OR "enriched housing" OR "green housing" OR "green home" OR "alternative care" OR "community housing" OR "community dwelling" OR "community-dwelling" OR "housing support" OR "aging in place" OR "ageing in place")	3,868
Dementia	2	All Fields (dementia OR Alzheimer OR Alzheimer's OR "mild cognitive impairment" OR DLB OR MCI OR FTD OR LBD OR Lewy)	7,480
Final search	3	1 AND 2	351

Appendix 3: Systematic Review Data Extraction Sheet

Article Screening and Population	
Article relates to research question?	
Includes people with dementia?	
Includes supporters of people with dementia?	
Includes health or social care professionals?	
Citation Details	
Covidence ID Number	
Citation	
Year study was conducted if different to date published	
Geographic region	
Aims, Methods, and Sample Characteristics	
Study aim(s) and research question(s)	
Study setting e.g. details of supported housing environment(s)	
Study design and methodology	
Data collection methods used, e.g. interview, focus group	
Details of data collection e.g. number of interviews, interview length, approach, led by researcher or clinician, number of hours of field observations	
Details of analytical approach e.g. thematic analysis, framework analysis, content analysis	
Details of theoretical framework if provided, or theoretical underpinnings outlined in literature review	
Sample size and characteristics, e.g. age, gender, socioeconomic status, details of dementia diagnosis, details of dementia subtype, education level, ethnicity, etc.	
Details of recruitment, if provided e.g. who identified the participants? Where did the	

interviews take place? Follow up conducted with debriefing?	
Findings	
Details of themes / categories outlined in the study, relating to experiences of living with a diagnosis of dementia in supported housing: Note, themes should relate explicitly to dementia. If this cannot be discerned, the theme should not be included	
Findings of relevance to the review question, e.g. relevant quotes and interpretations outlined in the results section of the study	
Implications and Additional Comments	
Implications for current practice / policy, if provided	
Any limitations discussed by the authors?	
Any limitations identified by you, the reviewer?	
Additional comments e.g. rigour, reliability, transferability	

Appendix 4: Systematic Review Critical Appraisal Results – CASP Qualitative Checklist

Article	Score	Clear aims	Qualitative methods appropriate	Design appropriate	Recruitment appropriate	Data collection appropriate	Researcher influence considered	Ethical	Analysis rigorous	Clear findings	Valuable
Aud (2002)	5.5	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Can't Tell	No	No	No	Yes	No
Aud (2004)	6.5	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Can't Tell	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
Barrett <i>et al.</i> (2020)	6	Yes	Yes	Yes	Can't Tell	Can't Tell	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
Cameron <i>et al.</i> (2020)	6.5	Yes	Yes	Can't Tell	Can't Tell	Can't Tell	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Evans <i>et al.</i> (2020)	7.5	Yes	Yes	Can't Tell	Can't Tell	Can't Tell	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Evans <i>et al.</i> (2019)	5.5	Yes	Yes	Can't Tell	Can't Tell	Can't Tell	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
Evans and Means (2006)	6	Yes	Yes	Yes	Can't Tell	Can't Tell	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
O'Malley <i>et al.</i> (2018)	10	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Rondon – Sulbaran <i>et al.</i> (2020)	10	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Rondon – Sulbaran <i>et al.</i> (2021)	10	Yes									
Stewart – Archer <i>et al.</i> (2016)	10	Yes									
Total No / Can't Tell	-	0	0	3	5	7	7	5	6	0	1

Appendix 5: Inclusion Criteria Document Provided to Gatekeepers

AN EXPLORATION OF LIVING WITH DEMENTIA IN SUPPORTED HOUSING Study Inclusion Criteria for People Living with Dementia

The inclusion criteria for people living with dementia are:

- Living with a diagnosis of dementia, and aware of this diagnosis.
- Ability to provide informed consent to participate.
 - In accordance with the Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act 2000, the definition of an adult with incapacity is anyone over the age of 16, who is deemed incapable of:
 - Acting; or
 - Making decisions; or
 - Communicating decisions; or
 - Understanding decisions; or
 - Retaining the memory of decisions.
- Living in a supported housing setting for a minimum of six months prior to the start of the study.
- Willing to nominate family members or friends and staff members working within the supported housing setting to be interviewed as part of the case study (would be desirable, but not essential if the person has no family / friend / staff contacts).
- Comfortable conducting interviews by video call or telephone – or in-person, should COVID-19 guidelines allow.

Appendix 6: Study Flyer Provided to People Living with Dementia

AN EXPLORATION OF LIVING WITH DEMENTIA IN SUPPORTED HOUSING **Research Study Flyer for People Living with Dementia**

To whom it may concern,

My name is Michael Smith and I am a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland. I am carrying out a research study about living with dementia in supported housing.

I am seeking people who are living with dementia to take part in my research. I want to know how you feel about living in your home in supported housing.

I would like to hear from...

People living with dementia who have lived in supported housing for at least 6 months.

The study will involve...

Four short interviews to discuss your home environment, your social relationships and community connections, and the support or care you receive.

If possible, I would also like to carry out interviews with a family member or friend and a member of staff who provides support to you.

How do I get involved?

If you would like to be involved in the research, I would be pleased to discuss this with you and can be contacted at:

Michael Smith

████████████████████
██

Thank you for reading.

Yours sincerely,
Michael Smith

Appendix 7: Study Flyers Shared on Social Media

Living with Dementia in Supported Housing in Scotland

PhD Student: Michael Smith

Supervisors: Dr Louise Ritchie, Dr Margaret Brown, Professor Debbie Tolson

UWS

THE Abbeyfield
RESEARCH
FOUNDATION

To whom it may concern,

My name is Michael Smith and I am a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland.

I am carrying out a research study on the experience of living with dementia in supported housing in Scotland.

I would like to hear from...

People living with dementia in supported housing in Scotland.

Organisations or individuals who support people living with dementia in supported housing in Scotland, who would be willing to help with recruitment to the study.

The study will involve...

Interviews with people living with dementia, their family members or friends, and members of staff who work within supported housing settings.

How do I get involved?

If you would like to hear more, get involved, or help with recruitment for my research, I would be pleased to discuss this with you and can be contacted at:

Michael Smith

Telephone or Text: Removed

Email: [REDACTED]

Living with Dementia in Supported Housing in Scotland

PhD Student: Michael Smith

Supervisors: Dr Louise Ritchie, Dr Margaret Brown, Professor Debbie Tolson

UWS

THE Abbeyfield
RESEARCH
FOUNDATION

To whom it may concern,

My name is Michael Smith and I am a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland.

I am carrying out a research study on the experience of living with dementia in supported housing in Scotland, including perspectives on supported housing as a future housing choice.

I would like to hear from...

People living with dementia in their own homes in the community in Scotland, who would like to discuss their experience of living independently at home, and their perspectives on supported housing as a future housing choice.

The study will involve...

One interview, lasting approximately one hour. This can be conducted in-person, over the phone, or online.

How do I get involved?

If you would like to hear more, I would be pleased to discuss this with you and can be contacted at:

Michael Smith

Telephone or Text: Removed

Email: [REDACTED]

Appendix 8: Ethical Approval Letter

23/09/2021 (Dr Gordon Mackay, ethics co-chair)

Dear Michael Smith,

Your application 16527: An Exploration of Living with Dementia in Supported Housing using Multiple-Case Studies., submission reference 14057, has been approved, with conditions, by the Health and Life Sciences SEC. **You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined below;**

Title	Comment
Where will the proposed research take place?	Please ensure that a fieldwork risk assessment is in place before the research begins.
Where will the proposed research take place?	Please ensure that all access permission are in place before the research begins.

If you wish to make any significant changes to your study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Gary Boyd

Appendix 9: Participant Information Sheets

People Living with Dementia

AN EXPLORATION OF LIVING WITH DEMENTIA IN SUPPORTED HOUSING **Participant Information Sheet for People Living with Dementia**

I would like to invite you to take part in a research study. This information sheet provides information about the study and what would be involved if you decide to take part. Before you decide, I would like you to understand why the study is being carried out and what it would involve for you. Take time to think it over and discuss it with your family, friends, or supporters. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. My contact details are included at the end of this document, and I would be happy to discuss the study with you.

Who is doing the research study?

I am a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland. My study has been funded by the Abbeyfield Research Foundation.

What is the research study about?

I am interested in the experience of living with dementia in supported housing. I would like to hear from people living with dementia in supported housing, their family members or friends, and members of staff who provide support to them.

The study aims to develop an understanding of how people living with dementia experience their home environment, how living in supported housing influences their social relationships and community connections, and how support or care is provided within supported housing to meet their needs.

Why have I been invited to take part in the research study?

You have been invited to take part in this study because you are a person living with dementia in supported housing. You have previously contacted me and have expressed interest about taking part.

What would taking part in the research study involve?

The study will involve four interviews lasting 30 minutes each. They will be scheduled across a period of one month. They will be arranged for dates and times that are convenient for you. With your permission, the interviews will be recorded. The interviews can be carried out by video call over the internet, by telephone, or face to face (if COVID-19 guidelines permit), depending on your preference.

During the first interview, we will complete three surveys together. They will relate to social engagement and independence, psychological wellbeing, and quality of life. We can also discuss the study in more detail, and I can answer any questions you have.

For interviews two to four, you will be provided with a digital camera. You will be asked to take three photographs relating to three interview topics. We can then talk about your photographs during the interviews. The three interview topics are as follows:

For the interview relating to **Your Home Environment**, the photographs might relate to your favourite space, where you like to eat, where you like to relax, or other things you like about your home.

For the interview relating to **Social Relationships and Community Connections**, the photographs might relate to your hobbies, any social activities you like to do, where you like to socialise, or the places you like to visit in your local community.

For the interview relating to **Support and Care**, the photographs might relate to things that support you in your home, emergency pull-chords, handrails, or signs and reminders that help you in your home environment.

I would also like to take some photographs of the supported housing setting you live in. I would like to take photographs of the outside of the building and its interior, including communal and dining areas. With your permission and if COVID-19 guidelines permit, I would also like to take some photographs of the inside of your home.

Finally, I will ask you to provide some contact information for one family member or friend and one member of staff who provides support to you. With your permission, I will then contact these individuals to ask if they would like to be interviewed as part of the study.

What are the benefits or disadvantages of taking part?

There would be no direct benefit to you from taking part in the study. However, this study will help develop a deeper understanding of living with dementia in supported housing. The findings will be used to inform future housing research and policies. You

can also keep the digital camera if you wish, and I will provide you with a written report of your contributions to the research at the end of the study.

Do I have to take part?

No, you do not have to participate. Participation is entirely voluntary, and you would be free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form.

What will happen to information collected in the research study?

All information collected during the study will be kept strictly confidential. You, your family members or friends, and any staff members involved will not be identifiable in any publication, conference presentation, or report produced for this study.

The findings will be presented at conferences and in written publications and reports.

Further information about this research study:

I will be pleased to answer any question you may have and can be contacted at:

Michael Smith

[Redacted]
[Redacted]

If preferred, you can also contact my academic supervisor (Dr Louise Ritchie), or a researcher from the University of the West of Scotland who has no affiliation with the project (Dr Rhoda MacRae):

Name	Email
Dr Louise Ritchie	[Redacted]
Dr Rhoda MacRae	[Redacted]

THANK YOU FOR READING THIS INFORMATION SHEET

AN EXPLORATION OF LIVING WITH DEMENTIA IN SUPPORTED HOUSING

Participant Information Sheet for Family Members, Friends, or Staff

I would like to invite you to take part in a research study. This information sheet provides information about the study and what would be involved if you decide to take part. Before you decide, I would like you to understand why the study is being carried out and what it would involve for you. Please take time to think it over and ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. My contact details are included at the end of this document, and I would be happy to discuss the study with you.

Who is doing the research study?

I am a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland. My study has been funded by the Abbeyfield Research Foundation.

What is the research study about?

I am interested in the experience of living with dementia in supported housing. I would like to hear from people living with dementia in supported housing, their family members or friends, and members of staff who provide support to them.

The study aims to develop an understanding of how people living with dementia experience their home environment, how living in supported housing influences their social relationships and community connections, and how support or care is provided within supported housing to meet their needs.

Why have I been invited to take part in the research study?

You have been invited to take part in this study because you are a family member or friend of a person living with dementia in supported housing or are a member of staff working in the supported housing setting. A person living with dementia has nominated you to be interviewed as part of the study.

What would taking part in the research study involve?

The study will involve one interview lasting approximately one hour. It will be scheduled for a date and time that is suitable for you. With your permission, the

interview will be recorded. The interview can be carried out by video call, by telephone, or face to face (if COVID-19 restrictions permit), depending on what you prefer.

The interview will focus on three topics of discussion, relating to the person living with dementia who nominated you to take part:

What are the benefits or disadvantages of taking part?

There would be no direct benefit to you from taking part in the study. However, this study will help develop a deeper understanding of living with dementia in supported housing. The findings will be used to inform future housing research and policies.

Do I have to take part?

No, you do not have to participate. Participation is entirely voluntary, and you would be free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form.

What will happen to information collected in the research study?

All information collected during the study will be kept strictly confidential. You, and any other person involved in the study, will not be identifiable in any publication, conference presentation, or report produced for this study.

The findings will be presented at conferences and in written publications and reports.

Further information about this research study:

I will be pleased to answer any question you may have and can be contacted at:

Michael Smith

██████████

If preferred, you can also contact my academic supervisor (Professor Debbie Tolson), or a researcher from the University of the West of Scotland who has no affiliation with the project (Dr Rhoda MacRae):

Name	Email
Professor Debbie Tolson	[REDACTED]
Dr Rhoda MacRae	[REDACTED]

THANK YOU FOR READING THIS INFORMATION SHEET

**LIVING WITH DEMENTIA AT HOME
AND PERCEPTIONS OF SUPPORTED HOUSING AS A FUTURE HOUSING CHOICE
Participant Information Sheet for People Living with Dementia**

I would like to invite you to take part in a research study. This information sheet provides information about the study and what would be involved if you decide to take part. Before you decide, I would like you to understand why the study is being carried out and what it would involve for you. Take time to think it over, or discuss it with your family, friends, or supporters. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. My contact details are included at the end of this document, and I would be happy to discuss the study with you.

Who is doing the research study?

I am a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland. My study has been funded by the Abbeyfield Research Foundation.

What is the research study about?

I am interested in the experience of living with dementia in supported housing, and in perceptions of supported housing in terms of future housing choices. I would like to hear from people living with dementia.

I would like to hear your perceptions on living independently at home, and to hear your thoughts on supported housing as a future housing choice.

Why have I been invited to take part in the research study?

You have been invited to take part in this study because you are a person living with dementia at home and are interested in sharing your views on supported housing as a future housing choice.

You have previously contacted me and have expressed your interest about taking part.

What would taking part in the research study involve?

The study will involve an interview lasting approximately one hour. It will be arranged for a date and time that is convenient for you. With your permission, the interview will be recorded. The interview can be carried out by video call over the internet, by telephone, or face to face (if COVID-19 guidelines permit), depending on your preference.

What are the benefits or disadvantages of taking part?

There would be no direct benefit to you for taking part in the study. However, this study will help develop a deeper understanding of perceptions of supported housing

as a future housing choice. The findings will be used to inform future housing research and policies.

Do I have to take part?

No, you do not have to participate. Participation is entirely voluntary, and you would be free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form.

What will happen to information collected in the research study?

All information collected during the study will be kept strictly confidential. You will not be identifiable in any publication, conference presentation, or report produced for this study.

The findings will be presented at conferences and in written publications and reports.

Further information about this research study:

I will be pleased to answer any question you may have and can be contacted at:

Michael Smith

██████████
████████████████████

If preferred, you can also contact my academic supervisor (Professor Debbie Tolson), or a researcher from the University of the West of Scotland who has no affiliation with the project (Dr Rhoda MacRae):

Name	Email
Professor Debbie Tolson	████████████████████
Dr Rhoda MacRae	████████████████████

Appendix 10: Consent Forms

People Living with Dementia

AN EXPLORATION OF LIVING WITH DEMENTIA IN SUPPORTED HOUSING Consent Form for People Living with Dementia

Participant ID:

Date:

Researcher:

Please Initial

1.	I confirm that I have read and understand the participant information sheet (Version 1, 28/06/21) for the above research study.	
2.	I have had the opportunity to think about the information, ask questions, and have them answered satisfactorily.	
3.	I understand that my participation is voluntary and I am free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason.	
4.	I agree to the interviews being recorded.	
5.	I agree to taking photographs relating to the interviews and sharing these with the researcher.	
6.	I agree to the researcher taking photographs of my home and other areas of the supported housing development in which I live.	
7.	I agree that the researcher can inform a member of staff if they observe a situation that may impact my own, another resident's, or a member of staff's safety.	
8.	I understand that the data I provide will be used for a PhD thesis, in conference presentations, and in research publications, and that the data will be anonymised.	
9.	I agree that my (anonymised) data can be quoted / shared in research outputs.	
10.	I understand that any personal information that can identify me will be kept confidential and not shared with anyone beyond the researcher and their supervisors.	
11.	I agree to take part in the above study.	

Name of Participant

Date

Signature

Name of Person taking consent

Date

Signature

AN EXPLORATION OF LIVING WITH DEMENTIA IN SUPPORTED HOUSING
Consent Form for Family Members, Friends, or Staff

Participant ID:

Date:

Researcher:

Please Initial

1.	I confirm that I have read and understand the participant information sheet (Version 1, 28/06/21) for the above research study.	
2.	I have had the opportunity to think about the information, ask questions, and have them answered satisfactorily.	
3.	I understand that my participation is voluntary and I am free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason.	
4.	I agree to the interview being recorded.	
5.	I understand that the information I provide will be used for a PhD thesis, conference presentations, and research publications, and that the information will be anonymised.	
6.	I agree that my (anonymised) information can be quoted in research outputs.	
7.	I understand that any personal information that can identify me – such as my name, address, will be kept confidential and not shared with anyone beyond the researcher and their supervisors.	
8.	I agree to take part in the above study.	

Name of Participant

Date

Signature

Name of Person taking consent

Date

Signature

**AN EXPLORATION OF LIVING WITH DEMENTIA IN SUPPORTED HOUSING
Consent Form for People Living with Dementia**

Participant ID:

Date of Interview:

Researcher:

Please Initial

1.	I confirm that I have read and understand the participant information sheet (Version 2, 16/06/22) for the above research study.	
2.	I have had the opportunity to think about the information, ask questions, and have them answered satisfactorily.	
3.	I understand that my participation is voluntary and I am free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason.	
4.	I agree to the interview being recorded.	
5.	I understand that the data I provide will be used for a PhD thesis, in conference presentations, and in research publications, and that the data will be anonymised.	
6.	I agree that my (anonymised) data can be quoted / shared in research outputs.	
7.	I understand that any personal information that can identify me will be kept confidential and not shared with anyone beyond the researcher and their supervisors.	
8.	I agree to take part in the above study.	
Name of Participant:		Date:
Signature:		
Name of Person Taking Consent:		Date:
Signature:		

Appendix 11: Interview Schedules

People Living with Dementia

AN EXPLORATION OF LIVING WITH DEMENTIA IN SUPPORTED HOUSING

Interview Schedules for People Living with Dementia

Interview 1: Introduction to Study & Completion of Outcome Measures.

Researcher

I am interested in your experiences of living with dementia in supported housing. This project aims to develop an understanding of how you experience your home environment, how living in supported housing influences your social relationships and community connections, and how support or care is provided to meet your needs. For this first interview, I would like to answer any questions you have about the study and complete three surveys together. They relate to social engagement and independence, your psychological wellbeing, and your quality of life.

Topics to cover include:

1. Provide further details about the study, answer any questions.
2. Provide any guidelines on the use of the digital camera, if needed.
3. Complete the three outcome measures: EID-Q, PPOM, and QoL-AD.
4. Collate contact details for nominated family members, friends, and staff.
5. Provide photograph prompts for the next interview on **The Home Environment**. The prompts provided in the participant information sheet for this interview state:
 - a. For the interview relating to Your Home Environment, the photographs might relate to your favourite space, where you like to eat, where you like to relax, or other things you like about your home.
6. Arrange a date and time for the next interview.

Interview 2: The Home Environment – relating to the individual’s experience of the physical environment of the supported housing setting.

The content of the interviews will vary depending on the photographs shared by the individual.

Researcher

Today, I would like to hear more about your experience of living in your home in supported housing. When we last met, we spoke about taking some photographs relating to your home environment, such as your favourite space, where you like to eat, where you like to relax, or other things you like about your home. Did you manage to take any photographs? Would you like to tell me a bit more about these?

Additional topics to cover include:

1. Things the individual might change about their home environment.
2. Navigating and finding their way around their home and the supported housing setting.
3. Their move to supported housing and how their current living situation compares to previous.
4. Feeling independent within their home environment.
5. Provide photograph prompts for the next interview on **Social Relationships and Community Connections**. The prompts provided in the participant information sheet for this interview state:
 - a. For the interview relating to Social Relationships and Community Connections, the photographs might relate to your hobbies, any social activities you like to do, where you like to socialise, or the places you like to visit in your local community.
6. Arrange a date and time for next interview.

Interview 3: Social Relationships and Community Connections – relating to the individual’s social relationships, community connections, and engagement in hobbies or social activities.

The content of the interviews will vary depending on the photographs shared by the individual.

Researcher

Today, I would like to hear more about your social relationships and community connections. When we last met, we spoke about taking some photographs relating to this topic, such as your hobbies, any social activities you like to do, where you like to socialise, or the places you like to visit in your local community. Did you manage to take any photographs? Would you like to tell me a bit more about these?

Additional topics to cover include:

1. Relationships with family members or friends.
2. Relationships with other individuals living in the supported housing setting.
3. Relationships with staff members.
4. Provide photograph prompts for the next interview on **Support and Care**. The prompts provided in the participant information sheet for this interview state:
 - a. For the interview relating to Support and Care, the photographs might relate to things that support you in your home, emergency pull-chords, handrails, or signs and reminders that help you in your home environment.
5. Arrange a date and time for the next interview.

Interview 4: Support and Care – relating to the support or care provided to the individual.

The content of the interviews will vary depending on the photographs shared by the individual.

Researcher

Today, I would like to hear more about the how you are supported in your home or the care you receive. When we last met, we spoke about taking some photographs relating to this topic, such as emergency pull-chords, handrails, or signs and reminders that help you in your home environment. Did you manage to take any photographs? Would you like to tell me a bit more about these?

Additional topics to cover include:

1. The kinds of support or care the individual receives.
2. If the support or care provided helps the individual maintain their independence.
3. If they would change the support or care they receive, and if they feel the support or care offered meets their needs.

Family Members or Friends

AN EXPLORATION OF LIVING WITH DEMENTIA IN SUPPORTED HOUSING

Interview Schedule for Family Members and Friends

Interview content will vary depending on the experiences/knowledge of each participant based on their relationship with the person with dementia.

Researcher

As we discussed previously, you are being interviewed today as you were nominated by an individual who is living with dementia in supported housing. I would like to hear a bit more about your relationship with the person living with dementia, and your views about their experience of living in the setting. I would like to know a bit more about how the individual experiences their home environment, how living in supported housing influences their social relationships and community connections, and how support or care is provided to meet their needs, from your perspective.

Topics to cover include:

Perspectives on the Home Environment

4. Their perceptions on the person with dementia's home environment.
5. The person with dementia's move into the setting.
6. How the setting differs to the person with dementia's previous living arrangements.

Perspectives on Social Relationships and Community Connections

7. Their relationship with the person with dementia, and how the relationship is maintained.
8. Social activities or hobbies involving the person with dementia.
9. The person with dementia's relationships with other family members or friends, other residents in the setting, and staff.
10. Community connections.

Perspectives on Support and Care

11. The support or care provided to the person with dementia, and if this meets their needs.
12. How living in the setting impacts the person with dementia's wellbeing.
13. If the supported housing environment promotes the independence of the individual living with dementia.

AN EXPLORATION OF LIVING WITH DEMENTIA IN SUPPORTED HOUSING

Interview Schedule for Staff

Interview content will vary depending on the experiences/knowledge of each participant based on their relationship with the person with dementia.

Researcher

As we discussed previously, you are being interviewed today as you were nominated by an individual who is living with dementia in the supported housing setting you work in. I would like to hear a bit more about your relationship with the person living with dementia, and your views about their experience of living in the setting. I would like to know a bit more about how the individual experiences their home environment, how living in supported housing influences their social relationships and community connections, and how support or care is provided to meet their needs, from your perspective.

Topics to cover include:

Perspectives on the Home Environment

14. The person with dementia's home environment.
15. The person with dementia's move into the setting.
16. How the setting differs to the person with dementia's previous living arrangements.
17. Suitability of the setting for the person with dementia.

Perspectives on Social Relationships and Community Connections

18. Their relationship with the person with dementia.
19. Social activities or hobbies involving the person with dementia.
20. The person with dementia's relationships with family members or friends, other residents in the setting, and staff.
21. Community connections.

Perspectives on Support and Care

22. The support or care provided to the person with dementia.
23. How living in the setting impacts the person with dementia's wellbeing.
24. If the supported housing environment promotes the independence of the individual living with dementia.
25. The benefits and challenges of living with dementia in the setting.

Contemplating Case Study

LIVING WITH DEMENTIA AT HOME AND PERCEPTIONS OF SUPPORTED HOUSING AS A FUTURE HOUSING CHOICE

Interview Schedule for People Living with Dementia

Interview Topic: Living with dementia at home and perceptions of supported housing as a future housing choice

Researcher

I am interested in your experiences of living with dementia at home, and your perceptions of supported housing as a future housing choice. This project aims to develop an understanding of how you experience your home environment, how living at home influences your social relationships and community connections, and how support or care is provided to meet your needs. Additionally, I am interested in your perceptions of supported housing as a future housing choice.

Topics to cover include:

1. Their experience of living at home
2. Their experience of social relationships and community connections
3. The support or care provided to them to meet their needs
4. Perceptions of supported housing as a future housing choice
 - a. Example questions for this topic include:
 - i. At a future point, do you think you might consider moving home?
 - ii. Have you ever heard of supported housing? What are your thoughts on it?
 - iii. What would make supported housing a positive housing choice?
 - iv. Why would you reject a move to supported housing?

